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LIST OF ACRONYMS

BREEAM: Building Research Establishment Environmental Assessment Method

COICOP: Classification of Individual Consumption According to Purpose

GDP: Gross Domestic Product

GUMTOB: South Marmara Association of Touristic Hoteliers and Operators

HRI: Hotels, Restaurants, Institutional

IMF: International Monetary Fund

KOSGEB: Small and Medium Scaled Industry Development and Support Directorate

LEED: Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design

NUTS: The Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics

OECD: Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development

PESTEL: Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental and Legal

POYD: Professional Hotel Managers Association

TAFED: Turkish Culinary Federation

TASPAKON: Cooks and Pastry Culinary Confederation

TGA: Türkiye Tourism Promotion and Development Agency

TOBB: Union of Chambers and Commodity Exchanges of Türkiye

TTYD: Turkish Tourism Investors Association

TUADER: Tourism Academics Association

TURCEV: Foundation for Environmental Education in Türkiye

TUREB: Association of Tourist Guides

TURES: Restaurants and Tourism Association

TURKSTAT: Turkish Statistical Institute

TUROB: Hotel Association of Türkiye

TUROFED: Turkish Hoteliers Federation

TUROYD: Tourism Hotel Managers Association

TURSAB: Association of Turkish Travel Agencies

WTO: World Tourism Organization

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Analysis of the Hospitality Sector in Türkiye is one of the deliverables of the REMODEL project funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101079203. It is the first task of Work Package 4 Research on Innovative Business Models Leveraging the BMI Lab. This document is based on the conditions set out in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement. This document is a guiding reference for other deliverables to be produced during the REMODEL project under the Work Package of 4.

Increasing the competitiveness of Turkish SME's in the hospitality sector is the main aim of the REMODEL Project. Thus, it is very important to analyse the hospitality industry firstly. This report includes the detailed analysis of the hospitality sector of Türkiye. The hospitality sector is analysed under two main sectors that are accommodation and food&beverage sectors. The analysis methods are both secondary and primary. Statistics, reports, academic literature, primary consumer data and etc. are used for this report.

The report is composed of six parts which are introduction, hospitality industry analysis, impact of COVID-19 on hospitality industry, hospitality industry segmentation, hospitality industry insights and primary data collection by means of customer journey grid respectively. The hospitality sector in Türkiye is analysed from a tourism marketing perspective. Thus, the size and growth of industry, leading cities of hospitality industry, leading companies of industry, macro and micro environment analysis topics are explained in detail. This report totally provides a current perspective for hospitality industry in Türkiye.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Purpose of the Report

This report includes the detailed analysis of the hospitality sector of Türkiye. It is one of the tasks of WP4 Research on Innovative Business Models Leveraging the BMI Lab. This task is named as T4.1. Analysis of the Hospitality Sector in Türkiye. The purpose of the report is to analyse the hospitality sector under accommodation and food&beverage sectors with the help of statistics and literature. The report includes two types data that are primary and secondary for analyzing the hospitality sector in Türkiye. First five sections are written based on secondary data which is about hospitality sector's actors (such as companies, destinations, organizations and etc.). Thus, the perspective of this analysis is mostly based macro variables except customers. The last section is written based on primary data collected from the customers of the hospitality sector in order to include customers and their perspective into the analysis.

1.2. Research Methodology

The research methodology consists of the analysis of both secondary data and primary data. Secondary data is collected from reports, literature, statistics and data bases. Primary data is collected from both hotel customers and restaurant customers. This research is conducted within the scope of the European Union project REMODEL being focused on the consumers' experience at hotels and restaurants. In this study, which focuses on the experiences of tourists in hotels and restaurants, the survey method was used to measure the experiences. Two questionnaires were prepared. The first questionnaire was developed to assess the last experience of tourists while staying in a hotel in Türkiye. The second questionnaire was developed to assess the last experience of tourists while having lunch/dinner in a restaurant in Türkiye. The study collected data from four different samples using two questionnaires. First, tourists were divided into two groups, international and domestic. Then, hotel and restaurant questionnaires were administered to international and domestic tourists. In the hotel survey, 300 international tourists and 300 domestic tourists were reached. The data collected were from 4-star and 5-star hotels. The survey conducted in restaurants reached 200 international tourists and 200 domestic tourists.

2. HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY ANALYSIS

2.1. Industry Overview

In order to understand the report, it will be useful to define some basic concepts that are sometimes confused or used interchangeably. The first concept is tourism. Tourism refers to the sum of the relationships arising out of the activities of persons travelling to and staying in places outside their usual environment for not more than one consecutive year for leisure, business and other purposes. Tourist destinations, transportation and tickets for travelling, and tourism activities such as mountain climbing, trekking, rock climbing, canoeing, mountain biking, jungle safari, sights seeing are some of the areas of the tourism industry.

The second concept is hospitality concept. Hospitality is a sector that focuses on providing accommodations to visitors at hospitality-related industries, such as hotels, motels, restaurants, cruise ships, country clubs, casinos, and convention centers, while tourism is focused on providing quality attractions and events in order to entice tourists to come. The major function of tourism is to encourage people to travel in order for people to spend money on hospitality. Thus, hospitality is a component of the tourism industry, as it provides services and amenities to tourists. However, tourism is a broader industry encompassing various sectors, including transportation, accommodation, and attractions.

Because travelers need a place to stay, grab a bite to eat, and transportation to the local activities, tourists purchase services provided by the hospitality industry. This relationship is important because the more tourists visit, the more services the hospitality industry sells.

For each of these fields to be successful, hospitality businesses focus on specific ways to keep people satisfied, so they will return. Hospitality businesses must build strong relationships with their guests not only to prevent them from going to a competitor, but to keep them coming back. Many tourism businesses are classified as hospitality businesses as they must also have meaningful relationships, but they are more focused on travelling activities that may include heavy planning and marketing.

As mentioned before, hotels, restaurants, and event centers tend to fall in the hospitality industry category. Hotel managers, event managers, hotel clerks, bar managers, and chefs are just a few job examples in this industry.

A hotel manager makes sure that guests are comfortable during their stay in a hotel or a resort. They may have to arrange for blankets or other amenities to be taken to hotel rooms, oversee the employees of the hotel, and ensure that supplies, like soap and shampoo, are ordered in a timely manner. On a resort property, the hotel manager may also be in charge of entertainment. The exact setting or location will dictate exact duties and responsibilities for this role. Overall, it is the manager's job to handle customer service needs that pop up during a guest's stay.

An event manager or event planner helps planning large events to ensure all attendees enjoy the experience. These individuals, like others in the hospitality industry, need to be highly organized. Event managers will plan all of the details, gather bids from venues and vendors, coordinate transportation for attendees, arrange for food, and even connect with local hotels to ensure people have a place to stay. They help their clients manage and maximize their budgets and ensure that everything is ready when the special event starts.

A concierge is employed by a resort or an event center to help guests to book entertainment and enjoy their stay more fully. These professionals need to know their local area well so they can connect guests to the entertainment options that best fit their tastes and desires for their trip. Concierge professionals tend to be employed by high-end resorts and luxury hotels. Distinguished guests expect to have someone to help them book their services and are willing to tip well for this service.

The hospitality industry is also the industry that covers restaurants and catering services. While those interested in opening a restaurant or catering business will also need to explore foodservice training, training in hospitality will help them understand the customer service side of this industry. These professionals can work anywhere where food and beverage are prepared and served, including hotels, resorts, and restaurants.

It can be said that tourism is tasked with managing a destination's details and resources, while hospitality manages and facilitates the provisions of food,

accommodation, and socialization for tourists. To say it in another way, tourism and hospitality complement each other. For example, a tourist needs tickets for travelling (tourism) and a place like hotel to stay in and perhaps a restaurant to eat in (hospitality).

Tourism not only creates jobs in the tertiary sector, it also stimulates growth in the primary and secondary sectors of the economy. This is known as the multiplier effect, which in its simplest form is how many times money spent by a tourist circulates through a country's economy.

There are different types of businesses within the hospitality industry and these businesses usually fall under four broad categories i.e. accommodation, food and beverage, travel and entertainment. In spite of this, most academic articles include accommodation sector when they refer to hospitality concept. Besides, accommodation and food&beverage are two important categories of the hospitality sector in Türkiye. That's why, the hospitality sector analysis of Türkiye is planned and written under these two categories¹.

2.1.1. Accommodation

2.1.1.1. Size and Growth of Industry

The size and growth of the accommodation industry of Türkiye has been compiled with the information obtained from the statistical data and reports published by national and international organizations. The national institutions used to determine the size of the accommodation industry were the Republic of Türkiye Ministry of Culture and Tourism and the Turkish Statistical Institute (TURKSTAT). Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) and The World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) were used as international organizations.

By compiling the data and reports of national and international organizations, a lot of information about the Turkish accommodation industry, similar to the one summarized

¹ Ottenbacher, M., Harrington, R., & Parsa, H. G. (2009). Defining the hospitality discipline: a discussion of pedagogical and research implications. *Journal of hospitality & tourism research*, 33(3), 265-268; Pizam, A., & Shani, A. (2009). The nature of the hospitality industry: Present and future managers' perspectives. *Anatolia*, 20(1), 134-150; Khatter, A. (2023). Challenges and Solutions for Environmental Sustainability in the Hospitality Sector. *Sustainability*, 15(15), 11491.

below, is presented: Number of facilities, rooms and beds affiliated to the Ministry of Culture and Tourism and municipalities; number of facilities, rooms and beds according to facility types; According to NUTS², the number of facilities, rooms and beds in the regions; the number of employees in tourism and its sub-sectors; number of tourists, tourism revenues, average expenditure; the number of same-day visits and overnight stays; regions and countries with the highest number of arrivals.

Information on the size of the Turkish hospitality industry is presented in the order of the Republic of Türkiye Ministry of Culture and Tourism, TURKSTAT, OECD and UNWTO.

Tourism facilities in Türkiye are classified according to the criteria determined by the legal regulation. The Ministry of Culture and Tourism classifies tourism facilities according to the "Regulation on the Qualifications of Tourism Facilities" published in 2019. The distinction between "Tourism Investment License" and "Tourism Establishment License" in this regulation is used by the Ministry of Culture and Tourism for the classification of businesses in Türkiye and for keeping statistical data. According to this regulation, "Tourism Investment License" means the document given at the investment stage for touristic facilities and "Tourism Establishment License" means the document given after the completion of the investment related to the touristic facility and the opening of the business.³

Tourism facilities in Türkiye are divided according to the public institutions they are affiliated with, as well as the "Tourism Investment License" and "Tourism Establishment License" distinction. While the touristic facilities affiliated to the Ministry of Culture and Tourism are divided into "Tourism Investment Licenced Accommodation Establishments" and "Tourism Establishment Licenced Accommodation Establishments", the facilities affiliated to the municipalities are in the "Tourism Establishment Licenced Accommodation Establishments" class.

Statistical data of both the facilities affiliated to the Ministry of Culture and Tourism and the facilities affiliated to municipalities are published by the Ministry of Culture and

² The Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics.

³ Regulation on the Qualifications of Tourism Facilities, (01.06.2019), Official Gazette of the Republic of Türkiye (No: 30791), <https://www.resmigazete.gov.tr/eskiler/2019/06/20190601.pdf>.

Tourism. Tourism facility statistics of the Ministry of Culture and Tourism and municipalities are presented below, respectively.

Figure 1: Number of Tourism Licenced Accommodation Establishments Affiliated to Culture and Tourism Ministry by Years (2002-2021)

Source: Ministry of Culture and Tourism, Establishment Statistics, <https://yigm.ktb.gov.tr/TR-201131/tesis-istatistikleri.html>.

According to the data of the Ministry of Culture and Tourism, it is seen that the total number of Tourism Licenced Accommodation Establishments was 3262 in 2002 and increased to 5386 in 2021. It has been determined that the number of Accommodation Facilities with Tourism Operation Certificate, which was 2124 in 2002, increased to 4801 in 2021. It was determined that the number of Accommodation Facilities with Tourism Investment Certificate, which was 1138 in 2002, decreased to 585 in 2021.

It is thought that the reason for this decrease is that the investment stages of the Tourism Investment Licenced Accommodation Establishments have been completed and they have passed to the status of Tourism Establishment Licenced Accommodation Establishments.

Figure 2: Number of Beds of Tourism Licenced Accommodation Establishments Affiliated to Culture and Tourism Ministry by Years (2002-2021)

Source: Ministry of Culture and Tourism, Establishment Statistics, <https://yigm.ktb.gov.tr/TR-201131/tesis-istatistikleri.html>.

Similar to the Number of Tourism Licenced Accommodation Establishments, it is seen that the number of beds in these establishments increased from 2002 to 2021. It has been determined that the total number of beds, which was 619024 in 2002 in the facilities affiliated to the Ministry of Culture and Tourism, increased to 1205240 in 2021. It is observed that the number of beds in Tourism Establishment Licenced

Accommodation Establishments increased in parallel with the increase in the number of facilities between 2002-2021. Similarly, it is seen that the decrease in the number of facilities experienced between 2002-2021 in Tourism Investment Licenced Accommodation Establishments is also seen in the number of beds.

Figure 3: Number of Tourism Licenced Accommodation Establishments Affiliated to Culture and Tourism Ministry by Type (2021)

Source: Ministry of Culture and Tourism, Establishment Statistics, <https://yigm.ktb.gov.tr/TR-201131/tesis-istatistikleri.html>.

The Ministry of Culture and Tourism classifies its affiliated facilities as hotel, motel, holiday village, thermal hotel, private facility, thermal holiday village, thermal apart hotel, hostel, camping area and others. According to this classification, the total number of hotels affiliated to the Ministry of Culture and Tourism is 3641. The most crowded type, excluding hotels, is the facilities in the 'others' type with 1353.

Considering the distinction between Tourism Establishment Licence and Tourism Investment Licence it is seen that the number of Tourism Establishment Licenced Establishments is by far more in almost all types.

Figure 4: Number of Beds of Tourism Licenced Accommodation Establishments Affiliated to Culture and Tourism Ministry by Type (2021)

Source: Ministry of Culture and Tourism, Establishment Statistics, <https://yigm.ktb.gov.tr/TR-201131/tesis-istatistikleri.html>.

In the classification made by the Ministry of Culture and Tourism regarding the facilities, it was determined that the most crowded type was hotels with 994223 beds. The 'Others' type appears to be the second most populated type with 92517 beds. Holiday villages with 71535 beds and thermal hotels with 39334 beds also have significant numbers.

Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics (NUTS) has been developed by the European Union (EU) Bureau of Statistics (Eurostat) to create a certain structure in the regional statistics to be produced in the EU.

NUTS was created to meet the needs of regional statistics in various dimensions in order to develop policies for economic and social problems at the regional level. Türkiye has started to use NUTS with the regulation it published in 2003.⁴

According to NUTS, Türkiye consists of the following regions: TR1 İstanbul, TR2 West Marmara, TR3 Aegean, TR4 East Marmara, TR5 West Anatolia, TR6 Mediterranean, TR7 Central Anatolia, TR8 West Black Sea, TR9 East Black Sea, TRA Northeast Anatolia, TRB Centraleast Anatolia, TRC Southeast Anatolia.

Figure 5: Number of Tourism Licenced Accommodation Establishments Affiliated to Culture and Tourism Ministry According to NUTS (2021)

Source: Ministry of Culture and Tourism, Establishment Statistics, <https://yigm.ktb.gov.tr/TR-201131/tesis-istatistikleri.html>.

⁴ Şengül Ü., S. Eslmian, M. Eren, 2013, Türkiye’de İstatistikî Bölge Birimleri Sınıflamasına Göre Düzey 2 Bölgelerinin Ekonomik Etkinliklerinin VZA Yöntemi ile Belirlenmesi ve Tobit Model Uygulaması, Yönetim Bilimleri Dergisi, Cilt: 11, Sayı: 21, ss: 75-99.

The TR6 Mediterranean region, led by Antalya, one of Türkiye's most important tourism cities, is the region with the highest number of accommodation facilities with 1293. There are 1220 accommodation facilities in the TR3 Aegean region, led by Muğla, İzmir and Aydın. Although it is a city, TR1 İstanbul, which is defined as a region on its own due to its crowded population, has 754 accommodation facilities.

Figure 6: Number of Beds of Tourism Licenced Accommodation Establishments Affiliated to Culture and Tourism Ministry According to NUTS (2021)

Source: Ministry of Culture and Tourism, Establishment Statistics, <https://yigm.ktb.gov.tr/TR-201131/tesis-istatistikleri.html>.

Considering the number of beds in accommodation facilities, it is seen that the TR6 Mediterranean region is by far ahead with a total number of 559,934 beds. It has been determined that the TR3 Aegean region has significant numbers with the total number of beds 245,117 and the TR1 İstanbul region with the total number of beds 149,099.

Figure 7: Number of Establishments of Tourism Licenced Hotels Affiliated to Culture and Tourism Ministry by Classes (2021)

Source: Ministry of Culture and Tourism, Establishment Statistics, <https://yigm.ktb.gov.tr/TR-201131/tesis-istatistikleri.html>.

According to the star classification for hotels, the highest number of hotels in Türkiye are in the 3-star category with 1285 hotels. While there are 1041 hotels in the 4-star class, there are 854 hotels in the 5-star class.

Figure 8: Number of Beds of Establishments of Tourism Licenced Hotels Affiliated to Culture and Tourism Ministry by Classes (2021)

Source: Ministry of Culture and Tourism, Establishment Statistics, <https://yigm.ktb.gov.tr/TR-201131/tesis-istatistikleri.html>.

Although the number of hotels is higher in the 3-star class, 5-star hotels are ahead in the number of beds. While there are a total of 556416 beds in 5-star hotels, there are 268442 beds in 4-star hotels and 139425 beds in 3-star hotels. Although the number of 5-star and 4-star hotels is less than the number of 3-star hotels, there are more beds in 5-star and 4-star hotels due to the large size of the hotels.

Table 1: Number of Tourism Licenced Accommodation Establishments Affiliated to Culture and Tourism Ministry by Years (2002-2021)

Years	Tourism Investment Licenced Accommodation Establishments			Tourism Establishment Licenced Accommodation Establishments		
	Establishments	Rooms	Beds	Establishments	Rooms	Beds
2002	1138	102972	222876	2124	190327	396148
2003	1130	111894	242603	2240	202339	420697
2004	1151	118883	259424	2357	217664	454290
2005	1039	128005	278255	2412	231123	483330
2006	869	123326	274687	2475	241702	508632
2007	776	112541	254191	2514	251987	532262
2008	772	113487	258287	2566	268633	567470
2009	754	103119	231456	2625	289383	608765
2010	877	114771	252984	2647	299621	629465
2011	922	122364	267900	2783	319319	668829
2012	960	126592	273877	2870	336447	706019
2013	1056	139928	301862	2982	357440	749299
2014	1117	145648	309556	3131	384454	807316
2015	1125	146162	314194	3309	404462	850089
2016	1135	144616	312912	3641	426981	899881
2017	1051	122228	263033	3771	446228	935286
2018	981	104910	225421	3925	464927	974574
2019	723	84172	180852	4038	473609	992341
2020	649	77587	167673	4218	487386	1020985
2021	585	64002	139703	4801	508511	1065537

Source: Ministry of Culture and Tourism, Establishment Statistics, <https://yigm.ktb.gov.tr/TR-201131/tesis-istatistikleri.html>.

Tourism Investment Licenced Accommodation Establishments and Tourism Establishment Licenced Accommodation Establishments were previously evaluated and compared in terms of the number of facilities and the number of beds. It is seen that the number of rooms, as well as the number of facilities and beds, changed from 2002 to 2021. While the number of rooms in Tourism Investment Licenced Accommodation Establishments was 102972 in 2002, it decreased to 64002 in 2021. In Tourism Establishment Licenced Accommodation Establishments, the number of rooms increased from 190327 in 2002 to 508511 in 2021.

Table 2: Number of Tourism Licenced Accommodation Establishments Affiliated to Culture and Tourism Ministry According to NUTS (31.12.2021)

NUTS	Tourism Investment Licenced Accommodation Establishments						Tourism Establishment Licenced Accommodation Establishments					
	Establishments		Rooms		Beds		Establishments		Rooms		Beds	
	Number	% Percent	Number	% Percent	Number	% Percent	Number	% Percent	Number	% Percent	Number	% Percent
TR1 İstanbul	72	12.31	7856	12.27	16308	11.67	682	14.21	65845	12.95	132791	12.46
TR2 West Marmara	38	6.5	2532	3.96	5637	4.03	248	5.17	12996	2.56	26299	2.47
TR3 Aegean	128	21.88	14865	23.23	33571	24.03	1092	22.75	100585	19.78	211546	19.85
TR4 East Marmara	42	7.18	3883	6.07	8012	5.74	330	6.87	21340	4.2	43486	4.08
TR5 West Anatolia	17	2.91	1766	2.76	3681	2.63	232	4.83	18847	3.71	37780	3.55
TR6 Mediterranean	137	23.42	22731	35.52	51281	36.71	1156	24.08	237134	46.63	508653	47.74
TR7 Central Anatolia	33	5.64	2281	3.56	4684	3.35	235	4.89	11890	2.34	24572	2.31
TR8 West Black Sea	23	3.93	1333	2.08	2682	1.92	233	4.85	8504	1.67	17163	1.61
TR9 East Black Sea	29	4.96	1892	2.96	3762	2.69	206	4.29	9585	1.88	19601	1.84
TRA Northeast Anatolia	20	3.42	1717	2.68	3638	2.6	113	2.35	4947	0.97	9824	0.92
TRB Centraleast Anatolia	14	2.39	739	1.15	1454	1.04	111	2.31	5313	1.04	10815	1.01
TRC Southeast Anatolia	32	5.47	2407	3.76	4993	3.57	163	3.4	11525	2.27	23007	2.16
Total	585	100	64002	100	139703	100	4801	100	508511	100	1065537	100

Source: Ministry of Culture and Tourism, Establishment Statistics, <https://yigm.ktb.gov.tr/TR-201131/tesis-istatistikleri.html>.

Tourism facilities divided into regions according to the NUTS classification were evaluated in terms of the ratio of the number of facilities, rooms and beds. Considering the Tourism Investment Licenced Accommodation Establishments, it is seen that the total number of facilities in TR6 Mediterranean, TR3 Aegean and TR1 İstanbul regions constitute 57.61% of the number of facilities in Türkiye. It has been determined that the number of rooms in these three regions constitutes 71.02% of the number of rooms in Türkiye, and the number of beds constitutes 72.41% of the number of beds in Türkiye.

Considering the Tourism Establishment Licenced Accommodation Establishments, it has been determined that the number of facilities in TR6 Mediterranean, TR3 Aegean and TR1 İstanbul regions constitute 61.04% of the number of facilities in Türkiye. number of beds in Türkiye.

Table 3: Number of Tourism Licenced Accommodation Establishments Affiliated to Culture and Tourism Ministry According to NUTS on City Basis (2021)

NUTS	City	Tourism Investment Licenced Accommodation Establishments			Tourism Establishment Licenced Accommodation Establishments		
		Establishments	Rooms	Beds	Establishments	Rooms	Beds
TR Türkiye	Country Total	585	64002	139703	4801	508511	1065537
TR1 İstanbul	Region Total	72	7856	16308	682	65845	132791
	İstanbul	72	7856	16308	682	65845	132791
TR2 West Marmara	Region Total	38	2532	5637	248	12996	26299
	Balıkesir	14	768	1486	97	5705	11636
	Edirne	5	725	1582	26	1216	2411
	Kırklareli	3	160	467	11	690	1377
	Tekirdağ	6	442	944	28	1738	3461
	Çanakkale	10	437	1158	86	3647	7414
TR3 Aegean	Region Total	128	14865	33571	1092	100585	211546
	Afyonkarahisar	5	1370	2988	36	3915	8189
	Aydın	13	2585	5863	129	15321	32227
	Denizli	7	685	1359	39	3516	7045
	Kütahya	4	257	636	12	586	1179
	Manisa	2	339	553	30	1667	3353
	Muğla	59	6297	14630	425	51964	110951
	Uşak	1	50	100	15	576	1144
	İzmir	37	3282	7442	406	23040	47458
TR4 East Marmara	Region Total	42	3883	8012	330	21340	43486
	Bilecik	1	11	22	7	344	655
	Bolu	4	471	942	28	2070	4323
	Bursa	20	1750	3626	100	6937	14139
	Düzce	2	46	96	17	707	1421
	Eskişehir				39	2439	4845
	Kocaeli	2	243	447	92	4835	9935
	Sakarya	7	686	1513	24	2402	4845
	Yalova	6	676	1366	23	1606	3323
TR5 West Anatolia	Region Total	17	1766	3681	232	18847	37780
	Ankara	12	1218	2551	186	14816	29688
	Karaman	1	180	392	8	564	1124
	Konya	4	368	738	38	3467	6968
TR6 Mediterranean	Region Total	137	22731	51281	1156	237134	508653
	Adana	4	494	1051	45	3725	7513
	Antalya	87	15494	33327	875	221780	477476
	Burdur				26	704	1333

	Hatay	12	1474	3066	56	2734	5518
	Isparta				30	1308	2640
	Kahramanmaraş	6	315	3346	54	2106	4201
	Mersin	26	4757	10097	66	4514	9449
	Osmaniye	2	197	394	4	263	523
TR7 Central Anatolia	Region Total	33	2281	4684	235	11890	24572
	Aksaray	1	99	164	18	819	1650
	Kayseri	8	684	1421	27	2131	4324
	Kırıkkale	1	25	50	3	164	332
	Kırşehir				5	478	989
	Nevşehir	17	888	1813	124	6038	12682
	Niğde	2	139	284	30	851	1703
	Sivas	2	54	132	16	718	1448
	Yozgat	2	392	820	12	691	1444
TR8 West Black Sea		23	1333	2682	233	8504	17163
	Amasya	1	20	40	23	740	1497
	Bartın				35	738	1478
	Karabük	5	429	864	27	631	1257
	Kastamonu	4	175	334	24	962	1919
	Samsun	5	240	482	32	2047	4113
	Sinop	1	30	45	39	797	1771
	Tokat	3	140	280	19	843	1663
	Zonguldak	3	202	440	16	883	1784
	Çankırı	1	97	197	9	336	663
	Çorum				9	527	1018
TR9 East Black Sea	Region Total	29	1892	3762	206	9585	19601
	Artvin	2	76	152	12	638	1268
	Giresun	2	146	292	31	864	1710
	Gümüşhane	1	34	68	6	267	526
	Ordu	7	321	601	40	1784	3608
	Rize	6	314	618	17	1015	2094
	Trabzon	11	1001	2031	100	5017	10395
TRA Northeast Anatolia	Region Total	20	1717	3638	113	4947	9824
	Ardahan				12	310	536
	Ağrı	2	130	260	23	882	1715
	Bayburt	1	90	180	2	138	271
	Erzincan				15	632	1220
	Erzurum	7	920	1958	21	1381	2784
	Iğdır				2	109	215

	Kars	10	577	1240	38	1495	3083
TRB Centraleast Anatolia	Region Total	14	739	1454	111	5313	10815
	Bingöl				3	177	374
	Bitlis	1	45	90	10	462	933
	Elazığ	2	166	332	22	1082	2190
	Hakkari	1	165	334	5	198	396
	Malatya				16	1229	2447
	Muş	5	124	197	25	714	1525
	Tunceli	2	45	114	6	161	322
	Van	3	194	387	24	1290	2628
TRC Southeast Anatolia	Region Total	32	2407	4993	163	11525	23007
	Adıyaman	4	300	584	15	891	1777
	Batman	2	176	372	9	599	1202
	Diyarbakır	5	333	625	33	2358	4674
	Gaziantep	6	524	1105	52	4283	8557
	Kilis				1	46	86
	Mardin	8	577	1214	28	1432	2859
	Siirt				2	187	374
	Şanlıurfa	6	457	983	17	1082	2182
	Şırnak	1	40	110	6	647	1296

Source: Ministry of Culture and Tourism, Establishment Statistics, <https://yigm.ktb.gov.tr/TR-201131/tesis-istatistikleri.html>.

When the regions included in NUTS are considered on a city basis, it is seen that some cities stand out in terms of tourism.

İstanbul, which constitutes a region on its own, is the second city with the largest facilities, with a total of 754 facilities, 73701 rooms and 149099 beds, affiliated to the Ministry of Culture and Tourism.

In the TR2 West Marmara region, Balıkesir with a total of 111 facilities, 6473 rooms and 13122 beds, and Çanakkale with a total of 96 facilities, 4084 rooms and 8572 beds are prominent cities in terms of tourism.

In the TR3 Aegean region, Muğla, İzmir and Aydın, where Sea-Sand-Sun Tourism is dominant, stand out with the number of establishments. There are a total of 484 facilities, 58261 rooms and 125581 beds in Muğla, which are affiliated to the Ministry of Culture and Tourism. İzmir has 443 facilities, 26322 rooms and 54900 beds, while Aydın has 142 facilities, 17906 rooms and 38090 beds.

17765 beds, while Kocaeli has a total of 94 facilities, 5078 rooms and 10382 beds.

In the TR5 West Anatolia region, Ankara, the capital of Türkiye, has 198 facilities, 16034 rooms and 32239 beds in total.

Located in the TR6 Mediterranean region, Antalya is the most important city in Türkiye in terms of tourism facilities. With a total of 962 facilities, 237274 rooms and 510803 beds, Antalya is far ahead of all other cities in Türkiye, including İstanbul.

Nevşehir, which is located in the TR7 Central Anatolia region and covers Kapadokya, is the leader of the region in tourism with a total of 141 facilities, 6926 rooms and 14495 beds.

Samsun is the leader of the region with 37 facilities, 2287 rooms and 4995 beds in total in the TR8 West Black Sea region, which has less facilities in terms of tourism.

In the TR9 East Black Sea region, which stands out with its nature tourism, Trabzon is the tourism leader of the region with a total of 111 facilities, 6018 rooms and 12426 beds.

Kars, which has a total of 48 facilities, 2072 rooms and 4323 beds, is the pioneer of the region in tourism in the TRA Northeast Anatolia region, which has the second lowest number of facilities in Türkiye in terms of tourism facilities.

Van, which has 27 facilities, 1484 rooms and 3015 beds in total in TRB Middle East Anatolia region, which has the lowest number of facilities in Türkiye, is ahead of other cities in the region in terms of facilities.

Standing out with its gastronomic tourism, Gaziantep is the leading city in tourism in the TRC Southeast Anatolia region with a total of 58 facilities, 4807 rooms and 9662 beds.

Table 4: Number of Tourism Licenced Accommodation Establishments Affiliated to Culture and Tourism Ministry According to Types and Classes (31.12.2021)

Types	Classes	Tourism Investment Licenced Accommodation Establishments			Tourism Establishment Licenced Accommodation Establishments		
		Establishments	Rooms	Beds	Rooms	Establishments	Beds
Total		585	64002	139703	4801	508511	1065537
Hotel	Total	454	52153	109433	3187	424562	884790
	5 Star	115	27608	58439	739	234525	497977
	4 Star	133	14876	31376	908	115199	237066
	3 Star	173	8676	17665	1112	60538	121760
	2 Star	11	414	842	374	12870	25202
	1 Star	22	579	1111	54	1430	2785
Motel	Total	2	109	218	6	230	473
	2. Class				1	65	134
	Motel	2	109	218	5	165	339
Holiday Village	Total	25	5440	13464	77	26390	58071
	1. Class	11	2645	5934	67	24854	54847
	2. Class	14	2795	7530	10	1536	3224
Private Facility	Total	29	661	1362	459	13826	28421
	(No Class)	29	661	1362	459	13826	28421
Thermal Hotel	Total	19	3366	7171	94	15241	32163
	5 Star	8	2089	4409	44	10625	22554
	4 Star	5	775	1597	30	3510	7319
	3 Star	6	502	1165	19	1081	2240
	1 Star				1	25	50
Thermal Holiday Village	Total	1	129	310			
	5 Star	1	129	310			
Thermal Detached Apart Hotel	Total				3	93	189
	(No Class)				3	93	189
Pension	Total				153	1785	3572
	(No Class)				153	1785	3572
Camping	Total	4	684	1644	7	417	1203
	(No Class)	4	684	1644	7	417	1203
Obergı	Total				3	454	957
	(No Class)				3	454	957
Apart Hotel	Total				217	7947	18289
	(No Class)				217	7947	18289
Detached Apart Hotel	Total				21	738	1792
					21	738	1792
Golf Resort	Total				3	531	1348

	(No Class)				3	531	1348
Tourism Complex	Total				4	3043	6442
	(No Class)				4	3043	6442
Boutique Hotel	Total	37	1117	2526	111	4242	8746
	(No Class)	37	1117	2526	111	4242	8746
Type B Holiday Site	Total				2	42	236
	(No Class)				2	42	236
Boutique Holiday Villa	Total	1	40	144	1	70	140
	(No Class)	1	40	144	1	70	140
Mountain House	Total	1	20	60	4	140	363
	(No Class)	1	20	60	4	140	363
Farm House / Village House	Total				12	112	225
	(No Class)				12	112	225
Mountain House (Highland)	Total				2	30	90
	(No Class)				2	30	90
Other	Total	2	126	257	1	5	10
	(No Class)	2	126	257	1	5	10
Rural Tourism Facility	Total	10	157	3114	9	118	240
	(No Class)	10	157	3114	9	118	240
Boutique Thermal Hotel	Total				2	65	124
	(No Class)				2	65	124
Simple Accommodation Facility	Total				423	8430	17653
	Motel				3	35	70
	Camping				1	10	20
	Otel				190	4996	10195
	Pension				229	3389	7368

Source: Ministry of Culture and Tourism, Establishment Statistics, <https://yigm.ktb.gov.tr/TR-201131/tesis-istatistikleri.html>.

Hotel, holiday village and thermal hotel types come to the fore in the tourism licensed facility classification made according to types and classes. Apart from these three types of facilities, there are also various types of tourism facilities such as apart hotels, golf resorts and mountain hotels.

While there are 3641 facilities in the hotel type, there are 476715 rooms and 994223 beds in these facilities. As the number of stars in the hotel type decreases, the size of the facility also decreases. As a natural consequence of this, the number of rooms and beds is also decreasing.

There are 102 facilities, 31830 rooms and 71535 beds in total in the type of holiday village. An important part of the holiday village type consists of 1. class facilities.

In the thermal hotel type, there are 113 facilities, 18607 rooms and 39334 beds in total. Most of the thermal hotel type consists of 5-star and 4-star thermal hotels.

Figure 9: Number of Municipality Licenced Accommodation Establishments by Years (2002-2021)

Source: Ministry of Culture and Tourism, Establishment Statistics, <https://yigm.ktb.gov.tr/TR-201131/tesis-istatistikleri.html>.

Considering the tourism facilities affiliated to the municipalities, it is seen that the number of facilities, which was 7772 in 2002, increased to 9445 in 2021. The number of facilities, which continued around 7000 until 2010, increased this year and reached 9185. The number of facilities, which continued around 9000 from 2010 to 2016, decreased to 5206 in 2016 and increased to 9000 again in 2021.

Figure 10: Number of Beds of Municipality Licenced Accommodation Establishments by Years (2002-2021)

Source: Ministry of Culture and Tourism, Establishment Statistics, <https://yigm.ktb.gov.tr/TR-201131/tesis-istatistikleri.html>.

It is seen that the increases and decreases in the number of tourism facilities affiliated to municipalities are similar in the number of beds. The number of beds, which was 408005 in 2002, increased to 620349 in 2021. The number of beds, which continued to be around 400000 until 2010, increased and reached 527712. The number of ongoing beds, which was around 500000 from 2010 to 2016, decreased to 345267 in 2016 and increased to 620349 in 2021.

Figure 11: Number of Municipality Licenced Accommodation Establishments by Types (2021)

Source: Ministry of Culture and Tourism, Establishment Statistics, <https://yigm.ktb.gov.tr/TR-201131/tesis-istatistikleri.html>.

When considered in terms of the types of touristic facilities affiliated to municipalities, it is seen that hotels, pensions and government guesthouses come to the fore. The number of hotels affiliated to municipalities is 5300, the number of pensions 2964 and the number of government guesthouses is 753. Apart from these three types, it is seen that there are also facilities such as motels, holiday villages, camping areas and thermal springs.

Figure 12: Number of Beds of Municipality Licenced Accommodation Establishments by Types (2021)

Source: Ministry of Culture and Tourism, Establishment Statistics, <https://yigm.ktb.gov.tr/TR-201131/tesis-istatistikleri.html>.

When the touristic facilities affiliated to the municipalities are considered in terms of types, it has been determined that hotels, pensions and government guesthouses stand out in the number of beds in parallel with the number of facilities. While there are 430080 beds in hotels affiliated to municipalities, there are 97877 beds in pensions and 42642 beds in government guesthouses. Apart from these three types, there are 49750 beds in total in facilities such as motels, holiday villages, camping areas and thermal springs.

Figure 13: Number of Municipality Licenced Accommodation Establishments According to NUTS (2021)

Source: Ministry of Culture and Tourism, Establishment Statistics, <https://yigm.ktb.gov.tr/TR-201131/tesis-istatistikleri.html>.

When tourism facilities affiliated to municipalities are considered in terms of NUTS, it is seen that TR6 Mediterranean, TR1 İstanbul, TR3 Aegean and TR2 West Marmara regions stand out. There are 1862 facilities affiliated to municipalities in the TR6 Mediterranean region. It is seen that there are 1666 facilities in TR1 İstanbul region, 1629 facilities in TR3 Aegean region and 1085 facilities in TR2 West Marmara region. In the other eight regions, there are a total of 3203 touristic facilities affiliated to municipalities.

Figure 14: Number of Beds of Municipality Licenced Accommodation Establishments According to NUTS (2021)

Source: Ministry of Culture and Tourism, Establishment Statistics, <https://yigm.ktb.gov.tr/TR-201131/tesis-istatistikleri.html>.

In parallel with the number of touristic facilities affiliated to municipalities, TR6 Mediterranean, TR1 İstanbul, TR3 Aegean and TR2 West Marmara regions stand out in the number of beds. The TR6 Mediterranean region is well ahead with 185552 beds. This region is followed by TR3 Aegean with 117555 beds, TR1 İstanbul with 96614 beds and West Marmara with 58526 beds. In the other eight regions, there are a total of 162102 beds in touristic facilities affiliated to municipalities.

Table 5: Number of Municipality Licenced Accommodation Establishments by Years (2002-2021)

Years	Municipality Licenced Accommodation Establishments		
	Establishments	Rooms	Beds
2002	7772	178660	408005
2003	7637	174991	399369
2004	7514	171906	392582
2005	7494	171888	392338
2006	7033	174632	395671
2007	7073	175261	399110
2008	7064	174859	397684
2009	7115	176637	402289
2010	9185	232658	527712
2011	8893	223025	504877
2012	8988	226954	497728
2013	9196	224469	497728
2014	9188	224191	496697
2015	9187	224157	496574
2016	5206	159159	345267
2017	7607	230219	506934
2018	7671	231001	511076
2019	8104	237516	545669
2020	8609	253444	575682
2021	9445	276150	620349

Source: Ministry of Culture and Tourism, Establishment Statistics, <https://yigm.ktb.gov.tr/TR-201131/tesis-istatistikleri.html>.

The increase and decrease in the number of facilities and beds in touristic facilities affiliated to municipalities show parallelism in the number of rooms, as well. It is seen that the number of rooms, which was 178660 in 2002, suddenly increased to 232658 in 2010. The number of rooms, which continued around 225000 until 2016, decreased to 159159 this year, then increased again and reached 276150 rooms in 2021.

Table 6: Number of Municipality Licenced Accommodation Establishments According to NUTS (2021)

NUTS	Municipality Licenced Accommodation Establishments					
	Establishments		Rooms		Beds	
	Number	% Percent	Number	% Percent	Number	% Percent
TR1 İstanbul	1666	17.64	51294	18.57	96614	15.57
TR2 West Marmara	1085	11.49	24500	8.87	58526	9.43
TR3 Aegean	1629	17.25	51814	18.76	117555	18.95
TR4 East Marmara	712	7.54	18227	6.6	40401	6.51
TR5 West Anatolia	191	2.02	5633	2.04	11222	1.81
TR6 Mediterranean	1862	19.71	74008	26.8	185552	29.91
TR7 Central Anatolia	511	5.41	11960	4.33	26973	4.35
TR8 West Black Sea	797	8.44	12843	4.65	29495	4.75
TR9 East Black Sea	354	3.75	7912	2.87	17027	2.74
TRA Northeast Anatolia	215	2.28	5567	2.02	10990	1.77
TRB Centraleast Anatolia	185	1.96	5572	2.02	11418	1.84
TRC Southeast Anatolia	238	2.52	6820	2.47	14576	2.35
Total	9445	100	276150	100	620349	100

Source: Ministry of Culture and Tourism, Establishment Statistics, <https://yigm.ktb.gov.tr/TR-201131/tesis-istatistikleri.html>.

Tourism facilities divided into regions according to the NUTS classification were evaluated in terms of the ratio of the number of facilities, rooms and beds. Considering the Municipality Licenced Accommodation Establishments, it is seen that the total number of facilities in TR6 Mediterranean, TR1 İstanbul, TR3 Aegean and TR2 West Marmara regions constitute 66.09% of the number of facilities in Türkiye. It has been determined that the number of rooms in these four regions constitutes 73% of the number of rooms in Türkiye, and the number of beds constitutes 73.86% of the number of beds in Türkiye.

Table 7: Number of Municipality Licenced Accommodation Establishments According to NUTS on City Basis (2021)

NUTS	City	Municipality Licenced Accommodation Establishments		
		Establishments	Rooms	Beds
TR Türkiye	Country Total	9445	276150	620349
TR1 İstanbul	Region Total	1666	51294	96614
	İstanbul	1666	51294	96614
TR2 West Marmara	Region Total	1085	24500	58526
	Balıkesir	538	12734	31687
	Edirne	98	2725	6252
	Kırklareli	25	664	1307
	Tekirdağ	59	1357	2738
	Çanakkale	365	7020	16542
TR3 Aegean	Region Total	1629	51814	117555
	Afyonkarahisar	101	4456	11376
	Aydın	168	6373	13959
	Denizli	13	391	806
	Kütahya	37	1464	4235
	Manisa	89	2187	4860
	Muğla	988	31574	71080
	Uşak	11	243	433
	İzmir	222	5126	10806
TR4 East Marmara	Region Total	712	18227	40401
	Bilecik	18	379	797
	Bolu	101	2021	4077
	Bursa	207	6581	14534
	Düzce	69	1682	3777
	Eskişehir	27	987	2144
	Kocaeli	103	2551	5688
	Sakarya	94	1628	3498
	Yalova	93	2398	5886
TR5 West Anatolia	Region Total	191	5633	11222
	Ankara	63	2420	4769
	Karaman	4	125	202

	Konya	124	3088	6251
TR6 Mediterranean	Region Total	1862	74008	185552
	Adana	73	1967	3582
	Antalya	1018	54393	140110
	Burdur	69	939	1962
	Hatay	155	3803	8818
	Isparta	47	1107	2376
	Kahramanmaraş	22	476	924
	Mersin	464	10966	27088
	Osmaniye	14	357	692
TR7 Central Anatolia	Region Total	511	11960	26973
	Aksaray	16	556	1198
	Kayseri	34	1169	2365
	Kırıkkale	12	316	574
	Kırşehir	8	253	523
	Nevşehir	322	5803	13688
	Niğde	19	773	1877
	Sivas	54	2018	4647
	Yozgat	46	1072	2101
TR8 West Black Sea	Region Total	797	12843	29495
	Amasya	66	918	2030
	Bartın	249	1901	4652
	Karabük	111	1271	2942
	Kastamonu	88	1828	4214
	Samsun	24	410	862
	Sinop	62	1115	3040
	Tokat	104	3060	6966
	Zonguldak	35	981	1975
	Çankırı	17	362	851
TR9 East Black Sea	Çorum	41	997	1963
	Region Total	354	7912	17027
	Artvin	87	1807	3657
	Giresun	47	793	1745
	Gümüşhane	14	266	554

	Ordu	32	610	1323
	Rize	53	1450	3142
	Trabzon	121	2986	6606
TRA Northeast Anatolia	Region Total	215	5567	10990
	Ardahan	20	393	742
	Ağrı	10	378	663
	Bayburt	4	73	122
	Erzincan	44	989	1992
	Erzurum	98	2588	5298
	Iğdır	14	491	872
	Kars	25	655	1301
TRB Centraleast Anatolia	Region Total	185	5572	11418
	Bingöl	8	230	392
	Bitlis	17	583	1161
	Elazığ	18	453	896
	Hakkari	17	467	976
	Malatya	38	1175	2235
	Muş	22	497	947
	Tunceli	6	100	233
	Van	59	2067	4578
TRC Southeast Anatolia	Region Total	238	6820	14576
	Adıyaman	22	639	1193
	Batman	15	500	1022
	Diyarbakır	21	560	1078
	Gaziantep	17	611	1184
	Kilis	6	213	446
	Mardin	56	1564	3440
	Siirt	7	298	570
	Şanlıurfa	83	2101	4739
	Şırnak	11	334	904

Source: Ministry of Culture and Tourism, Establishment Statistics, <https://yigm.ktb.gov.tr/TR-201131/tesis-istatistikleri.html>.

When the regions included in NUTS are considered on a city basis, it is seen that some cities stand out in terms of tourism.

İstanbul, which constitutes a region on its own, is the city with the most facilities in Türkiye in terms of municipal touristic facilities. İstanbul ranks second after Antalya in the number of rooms and beds. There are 1666 facilities, 51294 rooms and 96614 beds in İstanbul, which are affiliated to municipalities.

In the TR2 West Marmara region, the cities of Balıkesir and Çanakkale stand out among the touristic facilities affiliated to the municipalities. While Balıkesir has 538 facilities, 12734 rooms and 31687 beds, Çanakkale has 365 facilities, 7020 rooms and 16542 beds.

In the TR3 Aegean region, Muğla is far ahead of other cities in the region in terms of touristic facilities affiliated to municipalities. There are 988 facilities, 31574 rooms and 71080 beds in Muğla.

In the TR4 West Marmara region, Bursa is the leader of the region in terms of tourist facilities affiliated to municipalities. There are 207 facilities, 6581 rooms and 14534 beds in Bursa.

In the TR5 Western Anatolia region, Konya is the leader of the region in terms of touristic facilities affiliated to municipalities, having more facilities than Ankara, the capital of Türkiye. There are 124 facilities, 3088 rooms and 6251 beds in Konya.

Antalya, the leader of Türkiye in the number of rooms and beds in touristic facilities affiliated to municipalities, is far ahead of all other cities in the TR6 Mediterranean region. There are 1018 facilities, 54393 rooms and 140110 beds in Antalya, which are affiliated with municipalities.

In the TR7 Central Anatolia region, Nevşehir is the leader of the region in terms of touristic facilities affiliated to municipalities. There are 322 facilities, 5803 rooms and 13688 beds in Nevşehir affiliated to municipalities.

In the TR8 West Black Sea region, Bartın is the leader in the number of facilities and Tokat is the leader in the number of rooms and beds. Bartın is the leader of the region in the number of facilities with 249. Tokat is the leader in the number of rooms and beds with 3060 rooms and 6966 beds.

In the TR9 East Black Sea region, Trabzon is the leader of the region in terms of touristic facilities affiliated to municipalities. There are 121 facilities, 2986 rooms and 6606 beds in Trabzon affiliated to municipalities.

The number of facilities located in the cities of TRA Northeast Anatolia, TRB Central East Anatolia and TRC Southeast Anatolia regions lag behind the cities in other regions. In the TRA Northeast Anatolia region, Erzurum is the leader of the region with 98 facilities, 2588 rooms and 5298 beds. While Van stands out with 59 facilities, 2067 rooms and 4578 beds in the TRB Central East Anatolia region, Şanlıurfa is the leader of the region with 83 facilities, 2101 rooms and 4739 beds in the TRC Southeast Anatolia region.

Table 8: Number of Municipality Licenced Accommodation Establishments by Types and Classes (31.12.2021)

Type	Class	Municipality Licenced Accommodation Establishments		
		Establishments	Rooms	Beds
Total		9445	276150	620349
Hotel	Total	5300	195189	430080
	(No Class)	5300	195189	430080
Motel	Total	204	3620	8305
	(No Class)	204	3620	8305
Pension	Total	2964	43325	97877
	(No Class)	2964	43325	97877
Holiday Village	Total	54	6354	17254
	(No Class)	54	6354	17254
Camping	Total	77	2380	6182
	(No Class)	77	2380	6182
Thermal Spring	Total	93	6362	18009
	(No Class)	93	6362	18009
Government Guesthouse	Total	753	18920	42642
	(No Class)	753	18920	42642

Source: Ministry of Culture and Tourism, Establishment Statistics, <https://yigm.ktb.gov.tr/TR-201131/tesis-istatistikleri.html>.

It has been previously stated that hotels, pensions and government guesthouses are ahead in the number of facilities and beds in the classification of touristic facilities affiliated to municipalities in terms of types. It is seen that hotels, pensions and government guesthouses are ahead in the number of rooms. There are 195189 rooms in hotels, 43325 rooms in pensions and 18920 rooms in government guesthouses.

Table 9: Amount of Tourism Income, Expense and Average Expenditure by Years (2004-2023/9 Months)

Years	Total					Turkish Citizen ¹	
	Number of Arrivals	Number of Departures	Tourism Income (1000 \$)	Average Expenditure (\$)	Tourism ² Expense (1000 \$)	Tourism Income (1000 \$)	Average Expenditure (\$)
2004	20753734	20262640	17076607	843	2954459	3862552	1262
2005	25045142	24124501	20322111	842	3394601	4374383	1214
2006	23924023	23148669	18593951	803	3270948	4463614	1153
2007	27239630	27214988	20942500	770	4043283	4703850	1121
2008	31137774	30979979	25415067	820	4266197	5418439	1191
2009	31759816	32006149	25064482	783	5090440	5690629	1222
2010	32997308	33027943	24930997	755	5874520	5558366	1231
2011	36769039	36151328	28115692	778	5531486	5638484	1168
2012	37715225	36463921	29689249	814	4593389	6365680	1243
2013	39860771	39226226	33073502	843	5253565	6776776	1255
2014	41627246	41415070	35137949	848	5470481	6301489	1132
2015	41114069	41617530	32492212	781	5698423	6052415	1004
2016	30906680	31365330	22839468	728	5049793	6184432	1014
2017	37969824	38620346	27044542	700	5137244	6076804	929
2018	46112592	45628673	30545924	669	4896310	5511261	825
2019	51747199	51860042	38930474	751	4403670	5896124	825
2020	15971201	15826266	14817273	936	1104545	2965813	951
2021	30038961	29357463	30173587	1028	1851922	5830953	1076
2022	51387513	51369026	46477871	905	4276533	7067152	1006
2023 9 Months	45230069	44605295	41999592	942	5100527	7031371	1165

1 - Income from citizen visitors residing abroad.

2 - Expenditures made by domestic residents abroad.

Source: Ministry of Culture and Tourism, Tourism Receipts and Expenditures, <https://yigm.ktb.gov.tr/TR-201116/turizm-gelirleri-ve-giderleri.html>.

Türkiye's tourism statistics are handled in two dimensions as arrivals-departures and expenditure amounts. When the statistics of arrivals by years are examined, it is seen that the number of visitors, which approached 21 million in 2004, increased until 2016 and reached the level of 41 million. It has been determined that the national and international political problems that started in the last quarter of 2015 and continued in 2016 affected the number of arrivals.⁵ The number of arrivals, which fell to 30.9 million in 2016, started to increase until 2020 and reached its historical peak of 51.7 million in 2019. The number of arrivals, which decreased to 15.9 million with the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020, started to rise again with the decrease of the effect of the pandemic and increased to 51.3 million in 2022. In the first 9 months of 2023, the number of arrivals was 45.2 million.

When the departures by years are examined, it is seen that the changes are similar to the arrivals. The number of departures, which was 20.2 million in 2004, reached 41.6 million in 2015. The number of departures, which decreased to 31.3 million in 2016, increased to 51.8 million in 2019, and decreased to 15.8 million with the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020. The number of departures, which started to rise with the decrease of the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic, increased to 51.3 million by 2022. In the first 9 months of 2023, the number of departures was 44.6 million.

When tourism incomes by years are considered, it is seen that the income level, which started with \$17 billion in 2004, reached \$32.4 billion until 2015, albeit with a fluctuating course of increase. Tourism incomes, which fell to \$22.8 billion in 2016, started to rise again and reached \$38.9 billion in 2019. Tourism incomes, which fell again due to the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, decreased to \$14.8 billion in 2020. Tourism incomes, which started to rise again with the decrease of the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic, increased to \$46.4 billion in 2022. In the first 9 months of 2023, tourist income was realized as \$42 billion.

When the average expenditure level per tourist is taken into consideration by years, it has been around 750-850 dollars from 2004 to 2015. The average expenditure was affected by the tourism crisis in 2016 decreased to \$669 in 2018. The average expenditure, which started to rise again from 2019, saw its historical peak in 2021 with

⁵ Yıldız, Ö., Işıldar, P., 2016, Türkiye Turizm Krizi Üzerine Bir İnceleme, Journal of Yasar University, 2020, 15/59, 407-425.

\$1028. Average expenditure in 2022, the last data year available, was \$901. The average expenditure in the first 9 months of 2023 was \$942 billion.

Table 10: Total Household Consumption Expenditure According to COICOP 2 Level (2014-2022)

		2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2022
Total Household Consumption Expenditure (Million TRY/Month)	Coicop 2 level:01. (Food And Non-Alcoholic Beverages)	11998	13415	14826	17343	21250	25012	73392
	Coicop 2 level:02. (Alcoholic Beverages and Tobacco)	2580	2770	3359	3913	4164	5213	10322
	Coicop 2 level:03. (Clothing And Footwear)	3104	3447	3917	4369	5055	6037	15825
	Coicop 2 level:04. (Housing, Water, Electricity, Gas and Other Fuels)	15070	17293	19129	21671	24829	28979	72137
	Coicop 2 level:05. (Furnishings, Household Equipment, Routine Maintenance of The House)	4109	4075	4795	5520	6778	7737	20726
	Coicop 2 level:06. (Health)	1290	1328	1501	1925	2302	2701	6956
	Coicop 2 level:07. (Transport)	10846	11268	13784	16468	19179	19806	68664
	Coicop 2 level:08. (Communications)	2277	2421	2787	2978	4018	4366	9884
	Coicop 2 level:09. (Recreation And Culture)	1850	1906	2119	2407	3026	3676	8169
	Coicop 2 level:10. (Education)	1461	1440	1717	2013	2377	2988	4433
	Coicop 2 level:11. (Hotels, Cafes and Restaurants)	3671	4217	4825	5417	6847	7831	18564
	Coicop 2 level:12. (Miscellaneous Goods and Services)	2610	2826	3192	3863	5088	6090	13135

Source: Turkish Statistical Institute (TURKSTAT), Household Consumption Expenditure Statistics, <https://biruni.tuik.gov.tr/medas/>.

The Classification of Individual Consumption According to Purpose (COICOP) is the international reference classification of household expenditure.⁶ The purpose of the classification, which started to be implemented under the name COICOP in 1999 and took its current form in 2018, is to create a framework for household consumption. The COICOP 2018 has a hierarchical structure consisting of four (4) levels with the number of categories, and therefore the level of detail increasing from the two-digit level to the five-digit level.⁷ The example below demonstrates the coding system:

Division 03 CLOTHING AND FOOTWEAR

Group 03.1 CLOTHING

Class 03.1.1 Clothing materials (SD)

Subclass 03.1.1.0 Clothing materials (SD)

⁶ United Nations, 2018, Classification of Individual Consumption According to Purpose (COICOP) 2018, Statistical Papers, Series M, No. 99, iii.

⁷ United Nations, 2018, op. cit., 5.

The COICOP, whose framework and conditions are determined by the United Nations, is taken as a basis by TURKSTAT in Türkiye and used in the classification of household consumption. TURKSTAT publishes household consumption data at 2 Level and 3 Level, including monthly average expenditure amounts. The data shared annually by TURKSTAT was not shared in 2020 and 2021.

When the COICOP 2 Level data shared by TUIK is examined, it is seen that the division with the highest expenditure by consumers in 2022 is Food and Non-Alcoholic Beverage with a monthly 73392 million TRY. A monthly expenditure of 72137 million TRY is spent on Housing, Water, Electricity, Gas and Other Fuels, which is close to the expenditure made for Food and Non-Alcoholic Beverage. Although the Food and Non-Alcoholic Beverage division is ahead in 2022, it is seen that Housing, Water, Electricity, Gas and Other Fuels is the division with the most expenditure between 2014 and 2019. The third division that consumers spend is the Transport division with 68664 million TRY per month. It was determined that 3671 million TRY was spent monthly in 2014 for Hotels, Cafes and Restaurants, which is also the subject of this study, and this expenditure increased over the years and reached 18564 million TRY in 2022.

Table 11: Total Household Consumption Expenditure According to COICOP 3 Level (2014-2022)

	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2022	
Total Household Consumption Expenditure (Million TRY/Month)	Coicop 3 level:011. (Food)	11198	12496	13779	16174	19758	23262	68359
	Coicop 3 level:012. (Non-Alcoholic Beverages)	800	919	1046	1169	1493	1750	5033
	Coicop 3 level:021. (Alcoholic Beverages)	176	190	205	225	254	418	1015
	Coicop 3 level:022. (Tobacco)	2405	2580	3154	3688	3911	4795	9307
	Coicop 3 level:031. (Clothing)	2438	2674	2979	3356	3835	4677	12062
	Coicop 3 level:032. (Footwear)	667	773	938	1013	1220	1360	3764
	Coicop 3 level:041. (Actual Rentals for Housing)	2588	3117	3501	3952	5013	5664	13083
	Coicop 3 level:042. (Imputed Rentals)	7152	8231	9268	10530	11671	13562	34415
	Coicop 3 level:043. (Maintenance and Repair of The Dwelling)	867	929	1061	1198	1276	1455	3119
	Coicop 3 level:044. (Water Supply and Miscellaneous Services Relating to The Dwelling)	1122	1325	1488	1608	2031	2330	4804
	Coicop 3 level:045. (Electricity, Gas and Other Fuels)	3342	3691	3811	4383	4838	5969	16715
	Coicop 3 level:051. (Furniture and Furnishings, Carpets and Other Floor Coverings)	1402	1317	1607	1799	2178	2205	5957
	Coicop 3 level:052. (Household Textiles)	352	331	416	413	505	605	1317
	Coicop 3 level:053. (Household Appliances)	1092	1075	1205	1507	1724	2110	6692
Coicop 3 level:054. (Glassware, Tableware and Household Utensils)	314	315	370	433	610	716	1535	

Coicop 3 level:055. (Tools and Equipment for House and Garden)	101	108	125	162	159	178	499
Coicop 3 level:056. (Goods and Services for Routine Household Maintenance)	849	929	1071	1205	1602	1922	4726
Coicop 3 level:061. (Medical Products, Appliances and Equipment)	395	391	481	637	706	881	2502
Coicop 3 level:062. (Outpatient Services)	655	674	778	912	1108	1223	3356
Coicop 3 level:063. (Hospital Services)	241	264	242	376	487	597	1098
Coicop 3 level:071. (Purchase of Vehicles)	5415	5506	7617	9121	10395	9773	40029
Coicop 3 level:072. (Operation of Personal Transport Equipment)	3082	3216	3553	4394	5308	6363	20405
Coicop 3 level:073. (Transport Services)	2348	2546	2614	2953	3476	3670	8230
Coicop 3 level:081. (Postal Services)	1,1	0,6	0,7	1,5	0,7	0,9	32
Coicop 3 level:082. (Telephone and Telefax Equipment)	379	543	683	650	1194	1101	3458
Coicop 3 level:083. (Telephone and Telefax Services)	1897	1878	2104	2326	2823	3264	6394
Coicop 3 level:091. (Audio-Visual, Photographic and Information Processing Equipment)	559	496	513	556	659	669	2074
Coicop 3 level:092. (Other Major Durables for Recreation and Culture)	3	18	16	26	44	109	81
Coicop 3 level:093. (Other Recreational Items and Equipment, Gardens and Pets)	216	249	288	394	440	636	1829
Coicop 3 level:094. (Recreational and Cultural Services)	553	568	739	702	936	1196	2585
Coicop 3 level:095. (Newspapers, Books and Stationery)	265	296	334	398	531	616	1387
Coicop 3 level:096. (Package Holidays)	254	278	229	330	416	451	214
Coicop 3 level:101. (Pre-Primary and Primary Education)	325	436	429	472	468	641	737
Coicop 3 level:102. (Secondary Education)	353	369	571	642	759	1151	1308
Coicop 3 level:103. (Post-Secondary Non-Tertiary Education)	236	167	125	186	285	295	518
Coicop 3 level:104. (Tertiary Education)	405	363	459	573	707	698	1414
Coicop 3 level:105. (Education Not Definable by Level)	142	105	133	139	159	203	456
Coicop 3 level:111. (Catering Services)	3367	3884	4362	4907	6235	7173	17256
Coicop 3 level:112. (Accommodation Services)	304	334	463	510	611	658	1308
Coicop 3 level:121. (Personal Care)	1124	1200	1337	1530	1936	2538	6380
Coicop 3 level:123. (Personal Effects N.E.C.)	686	816	672	1195	1752	1729	2711
Coicop 3 level:124. (Social Protection)	66	105	112	134	158	358	471
Coicop 3 level:125. (Insurance)	205	209	431	376	424	599	1975
Coicop 3 level:126. (Financial Services N.E.C.)	4,7	5,3	2,9	5,8	1,7	3,4	19
Coicop 3 level:127. (Other Services N.E.C.)	524	490	637	623	816	863	1580

Source: Turkish Statistical Institute (TURKSTAT), Household Consumption Expenditure Statistics, <https://biruni.tuik.gov.tr/medas/>.

Further detailing the divisions in COICOP 2 Level, the group with the highest monthly expenditure in COICOP 3 Level was the Food group in 2022. In the Food group, monthly expenditure was realized as 68359 million TRY in 2022.

After the Food group, the largest expenditure groups were Purchase of Vehicles with 40029 million TRY and Imputed Rentals with 34415 million TRY. The division defined as Hotels, Cafes and Restaurants at COICOP 2 Level is divided into groups as Catering Services and Accommodation Services at COICOP 3 Level. In both groups, monthly expenditure increases from 2014 to 2022. In 2022, monthly expenditure in the Catering Services group was 17256 million TRY, and in the Accommodation Services group, it was 1308 million TRY.

Table 12: Rate of Consumption Expenditures by Types and Years (2008-2022)

	Survey year	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2022
Types of consumption expenditures (%)	Number of household (millions)	17,79	18,43	18,81	19,31	20,05	20,48	21,37	21,82	22,30	23,03	23,60	24,22	26,50
	Food and non-alcoholic beverages	22,6	23,0	21,9	20,7	19,6	19,9	19,7	20,2	19,5	19,7	20,3	20,8	22,8
	Alcoholic beverages, cigarette and tobacco	3,8	4,1	4,5	4,1	4,2	4,2	4,2	4,2	4,4	4,5	4,0	4,3	3,2
	Clothing and footwear	5,4	5,1	5,1	5,2	5,4	5,3	5,1	5,2	5,2	5,0	4,8	5,0	4,9
	Housing and rent	29,1	28,2	27,1	25,8	25,8	25,0	24,8	26,0	25,2	24,7	23,7	24,1	22,4
	Furniture, houses appliances and home care services	5,8	6,2	6,3	6,4	6,7	6,6	6,8	6,1	6,3	6,3	6,5	6,4	6,4
	Health	1,9	1,9	2,1	1,9	1,8	2,1	2,1	2,0	2,0	2,2	2,2	2,2	2,2
	Transportation	14,1	13,6	15,1	17,2	17,2	17,4	17,8	17,0	18,2	18,7	18,3	16,5	21,3
	Communication	4,4	4,2	4,1	4,0	3,9	4,0	3,7	3,7	3,7	3,4	3,8	3,6	3,1
	Entertainment and culture	2,5	2,6	2,8	2,7	3,2	3,1	3,0	2,9	2,8	2,7	2,9	3,1	2,5
	Educational services	2,0	1,9	2,0	2,0	2,3	2,4	2,4	2,2	2,3	2,3	2,3	2,5	1,4
	Restaurant and hotels	4,4	5,2	5,4	5,7	5,8	5,9	6,0	6,4	6,4	6,2	6,5	6,5	5,8
Various good and services	4,1	4,0	3,7	4,3	4,2	4,3	4,3	4,3	4,2	4,4	4,9	5,1	4,1	
Total		100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

Source: Turkish Statistical Institute (TURKSTAT), Household Consumption Expenditure Statistics, <https://biruni.tuik.gov.tr/medas/>.

While the number of households in Türkiye was 17.79 million in 2008, it increased to 26.50 million in 2022. When the ratios of household consumption according to expenditure types are analyzed, it is seen that the highest rates in 2022 are Food and Non-Alcoholic Beverages with 22.8%, Housing and Rent with 22.4% and

Transportation with 21.3%. While the expenditure on Food and Non-Alcoholic Beverage was 22.6% in 2008, it decreased to 19.5% over the years, but increased to 22.8% again in 2022. While the expenditure rate for Housing and Rent was 29.1% in 2008, it has decreased over the years to 22.4% in 2022. While the expenditure rate for transportation was 14.1% in 2008, it increased to 21.3% in 2022.

The ratio of household expenditure of Restaurant and Hotels, which is the subject of this study, was 4.4% in 2008. The expenditure rate for Restaurant and Hotels has increased over the years, reaching up to 6.5% in 2018 and 2019. The last expenditure rate for Restaurant and Hotels, published in 2022, was 5.8%.

Table 13: Number of Trips by Purpose of Trip (2009-2023/9 Months)

Trips by purpose of trip, 2009-2022 (thousand)															
Years	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023 9 Months
Total	60888	68373	65854	64922	68452	70894	71251	68450	77179	78523	78202	42847	52774	52327	49954
Travel, leisure, vacation	11347	12362	12898	12682	13782	13469	13332	14722	15988	21030	20755	10727	15964	16277	17244
Culture	730	634	546	581	697	708	788	668	973	238	254	121	168	199	171
Visiting relatives	40026	46242	44603	43039	44897	46596	48113	45121	52100	50233	49826	28131	31057	31108	28886
Health	4872	5288	3925	4752	5320	5938	4726	4338	4492	3616	3595	1796	2665	1970	1670
Meeting, conference, courses, seminars	773	779	970	820	977	1027	963	788	789	818	869	325	503	818	237
Commercial relations, fair	675	712	621	546	474	585	493	484	541	458	564	406	614	528	231
Other	2467	2357	2291	2502	2305	2572	2834	2329	2296	2130	2339	1341	1802	1427	1516

Source: Turkish Statistical Institute (TURKSTAT), Household Domestic Tourism Statistics, <https://biruni.tuik.gov.tr/medas/>.

Trips in Türkiye are classified according to the purpose of the trip and published by TURKSTAT. The number of trips, which was 60,9 million in 2009, reached its highest level in 2018 and realized as 78,5 million. With the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic, the number of trips decreased to 42,8 million in 2020 and reached 52,3 million in 2022. Considering the travel purposes, visiting relatives constitute the highest group. Visiting relatives, which reached its highest level in 2017 with 52.1 million, was realized as 31.1 million in 2022. Trips for travel, leisure and vacation increased up to 21 million in 2018 and reached 16.2 million in 2022. Considering the year 2023, it is seen that the figures in the first 9 months of 2023 are almost close to the figures for the whole year of 2022.

Table 14: Amount of Expenditures of Trips by Purpose of Trip (2009-2023/9 Months)

Expenditures of trips by purpose of trip, 2009-2022 (TRY millions)															
Years	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023 9 Months
Total	12216	13844	15641	16725	18417	22601	24410	28033	35306	40266	48911	32250	58105	114317	184060
Travel, leisure, vacation	3694	4200	5130	5550	6219	7368	7612	10030	12357	16552	20426	12496	25536	52549	96847
Culture	150	175	152	189	243	308	328	342	384	145	287	82	199	595	724
Visiting relatives	5975	7061	8023	8485	9091	11188	13097	13795	18010	19043	22223	15427	25389	49503	72323
Health	1265	1278	1195	1264	1584	2060	1811	2084	2558	2510	3336	2261	3978	5752	7360
Meeting, conference, courses, seminars	242	223	288	271	319	401	366	421	542	491	673	236	525	1385	1162
Commercial relations, fair	270	283	245	203	195	294	228	253	332	314	414	515	787	1609	723
Other	621	623	610	763	765	982	967	1108	1122	1210	1553	1233	1690	2925	4921

Source: Turkish Statistical Institute (TURKSTAT), Household Domestic Tourism Statistics, <https://biruni.tuik.gov.tr/medas/>.

Expenditures made during the trips are classified according to the purpose of the trip. In 2022, the number of visits to relatives is more than double that of travel, leisure and vacation, but the amount of spending on travel, leisure and vacation is more. Expenditure for travel, leisure and vacation and visiting relatives increased from 2009 to the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020. With the rise again after the pandemic, the expenditures for travel, leisure and vacation reached 52549 million in 2022. The expenditures made for visiting relatives were 49503 million in 2022. Considering the year 2023, it is seen that the figures in the first 9 months of 2023 exceed the figures for the whole year of 2022.

Table 15: Amount of Average Expenditures per Trips (2009-2023/9 Months)

Average expenditures per trips (TRY), 2009-2022															
Years	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023 9 Months
Total	201	202	238	258	269	319	343	410	457	513	625	753	1101	2185	9972
Travel, leisure, vacation	326	340	398	438	451	547	571	681	773	787	984	1165	1600	3228	14314
Culture	205	277	278	325	349	435	416	513	395	609	1130	674	1186	2994	10029
Visiting relatives	149	153	180	197	202	240	272	306	346	379	446	548	817	1591	7159
Health	260	242	304	266	298	347	383	480	570	694	928	1259	1493	2920	13475
Meeting, conference, courses, seminars	313	286	297	330	326	391	380	534	686	601	774	726	1045	1692	15273
Commercial relations, fair	400	398	394	371	412	503	462	522	614	687	734	1269	1281	3048	9872
Other	252	264	266	305	332	382	341	476	488	568	664	919	938	2050	10222

Source: Turkish Statistical Institute (TURKSTAT), Household Domestic Tourism Statistics, <https://biruni.tuik.gov.tr/medas/>.

Average expenditure amounts per trip are classified according to the purpose of the trip. The average expenditure per trip, which was 201 TRY in 2009, has increased over the years and reached 2185 TRY in 2022. Commercial relations and fair, which was the type of trip with the highest average expenditure of 400 TRY in 2009, reached an average of 3048 TRY in 2022. Travel, leisure and vacation, which had the second largest expenditure average after commercials and fair with an average expenditure of 326 TRY in 2009, has the largest average expenditure of 3228 TRY in 2022. Considering the year 2023, it is seen that the figures in the first 9 months of 2023 exceed the figures for the whole year of 2022.

Table 16: Domestic Tourism Expenditure by Types of Expenditure (2009-2022)

Domestic tourism expenditure by types of expenditure, 2009-2022 Individual Expenditures (TRY millions)															
Years	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023 9 Months
Total	12216	13844	15641	16725	18417	22601	24410	28033	35306	40266	48911	32250	58105	114317	184061
Package tour expenditures	614	606	664	932	1275	1160	1724	2490	2900	3508	3965	1881	5095	10774	17458
Total	11603	13238	14977	15793	17142	21441	22686	25543	32406	36758	44946	30369	53009	103543	166602
Eating and drinking	3347	3840	4555	4884	5124	6643	7336	8633	10957	12284	15645	11789	18234	34885	59794
Accommodation	1040	1069	1403	1412	1601	2192	2289	3115	3754	4888	5933	3710	8122	14806	33830
Health	564	579	529	534	572	854	856	950	1274	1353	2192	1371	2420	3504	4855
Transportation	3706	4429	5030	5367	5916	6759	7109	7767	9649	11746	13889	9412	15300	35093	46648
Clothing and giftware	1744	1947	2248	2238	2498	3156	2974	3089	3902	3897	4330	2396	4557	8356	12574
Other expenditures	947	1071	910	947	960	1155	1588	1822	2627	2267	2548	1504	3691	5996	7986
Trip expenditures made before trip (Clothing, medicines, bag, camera, film, etc.)	256	303	303	410	471	682	533	167	243	324	409	187	685	904	915

Source: Turkish Statistical Institute (TURKSTAT), Household Domestic Tourism Statistics, <https://biruni.tuik.gov.tr/medas/>.

Expenditures made in domestic tourism are classified according to their types. According to the data of 2022, the total expenditure was realized as 114317 million TRY. When package tour expenditures are deducted, the total expenditure is 103543 million TRY. The largest expenditure types in total expenditure are transportation, eating-drinking and accommodation. 35093 million TRY of domestic tourism expenditures was spent on transportation, 34885 million TRY on eating-drinking and

14806 million TRY on accommodation. Considering the year 2023, it is seen that the figures in the first 9 months of 2023 exceed the figures for the whole year of 2022.

Table 17: Number of Employment in Tourism by Years (2014-2021)

Dataset: Enterprises and employment in tourism								
Country	Türkiye							
Variable	Employment							
Unit	Employed							
Year	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Total tourism
Tourism industries	1801084	1926751	1969777	2062809	2222378	2284072	1851788	1897069
Accommodation services for visitors	260777	300182	267589	294958	343928	368941	297322	313745
Hotels and similar establishments	219881	250289	214928	247100	286101	303333	230471	246583
Food and beverage serving industry	1071945	1128515	1164473	1189288	1253134	1305850	1045965	1059197
Passenger transport	311570	324820	362572	391243	411351	399845	344636	350232
Transport equipment rental	15506	13311	15727	24250	27593	28855	27606	24204
Travel agencies and other reservation services industry	46647	49734	51324	44157	50103	50929	40964	56481
Cultural industry	32400	38565	50000	56491	55111	54065	41076	35686
Sports and recreation industry	62240	71624	58092	62422	81158	75587	54220	57525

Source: OECD, Tourism Statistics, <https://stats.oecd.org/>.

According to OECD data, tourism employment in Türkiye has varied over the years. The number of tourism employees, which was 1.80 million in 2014, approached 2.28 million in 2019. The number of tourism workers decreased by 0.43 million in 2020 to 1.85 million due to the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic. The number of tourism employees reached 1.89 million in 2021 with a slight increase by 40000 people.

Considering the working areas of tourism employees, it is seen that three industries stand out. The food and beverage serving industry is the industry with the highest employment in tourism. It is seen that the number of employees in the food and beverage serving industry, which was 1.07 million in 2014, increased to 1.30 million in 2019, and then reached the level of 1.04 million in 2021 with the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic. After the food and beverage services industry, it is seen that the most employees are in the passenger transport industry. It has been determined that passenger transportation employment, which was 311570 in 2014, reached 411351 in

2018, then started to decline and reached 350232 in 2021. Looking at the accommodation industry, it is seen that the number of employees, which was 260777 in 2014, increased to 368941 in 2019. With the COVID-19 pandemic, the number of employees in the accommodation industry was 313745 in 2021.

Table 18: Rate of Tourism Employment in Total Employment by Years (2008-2021)

Dataset: Key tourism indicators														
Key indicator	Total tourism employment (direct) as % of total employment													
Unit	Percentage													
Country Year	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Australia	4,7	4,6	4,6	4,6	4,7	4,7	4,9	4,9	5,1	5,2	5,3	5,0	3,9	..
Austria	4,4	4,4	4,6	4,5	4,6	4,8	..	4,8	4,9	5,0	5,1	5,2	3,5	..
Belgium	6,7
Canada	3,6	3,6	3,5	3,5	3,5	3,5	3,5	3,6	3,6	3,6	3,6	3,6	2,8	2,6
Chile	6,0	6,3	6,3	6,2	6,1	6,1	6,0	6,2	6,4	6,5	7,2	7,2	5,8	6,1
Colombia	7,9	7,9	8,1	8,0	8,1	8,2	8,3	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
Costa Rica	6,6	6,6	6,7	6,5	6,7	6,8	6,8	6,6	6,9	5,3	6,2
Czech Republic	4,6	4,6	4,7	4,6	4,5	4,5	4,4	4,4	4,4	4,4	4,4	4,4	4,2	..
Denmark	7,6	7,7	7,9	8,0	8,2	8,3	8,3	8,5	8,8	8,9	9,0	9,1
Estonia	3,5	3,3	3,3	3,0	3,1	3,8	4,1	4,1	4,1	3,9	4,3	4,4	3,6	3,3
Finland	5,2	5,3	5,5	5,5	5,6	5,5	5,5	5,6	5,8	4,9	..
France	6,8	7,0	7,1	7,1	7,2	7,2	7,2	7,3	7,4	7,5	7,5
Germany	4,0	4,2	4,8	4,9	4,7	3,4	..
Greece	11,6	11,4	11,2	11,6	11,7	11,9	13,1	13,7	14,4	14,3	14,1	14,4	13,8	13,0
Hungary	8,7	8,6	8,6	9,0	9,2	9,1	9,2	10,0	10,0	9,6	9,4	9,5
Iceland	8,6	9,0	9,7	10,3	11,1	11,9	12,8	14,0	15,8	16,9	16,8	15,9	12,0	11,6
Ireland	9,0	9,4	9,3	9,4	9,6	9,6	9,8	10,0	10,2	10,3	10,3	12,3	10,3	..
Israel	3,3	3,2	3,4	3,4	3,4	3,6	3,7	3,7	3,6	3,7	3,6	3,8	3,0	2,7
Italy	8,4	8,3	..	8,8	..	8,9
Japan	6,9	6,9	6,9	6,9	6,9	6,9	9,8	9,6	9,6	9,3	9,5	9,6
Latvia	7,5	7,7	7,7	7,3	8,3	7,8	8,5	8,2	8,9	8,4	8,5	8,3	7,7	7,1
Lithuania	4,0	4,1	4,3	4,5	4,4	4,6	4,8	4,8	4,8	4,9	4,9	5,1	4,7	..
Luxembourg	8,3	8,4	8,4	8,4	8,3	8,2	8,2	8,3	7,6	..
Mexico	5,9	6,0	6,0	6,0	5,9	5,9	5,9	5,9	5,9	5,9	5,8	5,8	5,3	..
Netherlands	5,5	5,6	5,6	5,8	6,0	6,0	6,1	6,2	6,3	6,4	5,5	..

New Zealand	8,5	8,5	8,2	8,0	7,6	7,5	7,3	7,8	8,3	8,0	8,3	8,1	7,9	5,2
Norway	6,3	6,3	6,3	6,5	6,5	6,4	6,5	6,8	6,9	7,1	7,1	7,4
Portugal	9,0	9,2	9,4	9,5	9,6	9,5	9,5	9,7	9,8
Slovak Republic	5,0	5,5	5,3	5,6	5,9	6,7	6,9	6,9	6,9	7,0	7,0	7,6
Slovenia	7,2	7,4	7,4	7,0	7,1	7,0	7,1	7,3	7,7	7,7	7,7	7,7	7,0	7,2
Spain	10,8	11,3	11,5	11,7	11,8	12,2	12,7	13,0	13,3	13,7	13,5	13,5	12,2	12,0
Sweden	3,2	3,3	3,1	3,1	3,3	3,2	3,2	2,5	2,6	2,4	2,4	2,4	2,1	2,1
Switzerland	4,1	4,1	4,1	4,1	4,1	4,1	4,1	4,2	4,2	4,2	4,2	4,2	3,9	..
Türkiye	6,9	7,2	7,2	7,3	7,7	8,1	6,9	6,6
United Kingdom	5,2	5,7	5,0	5,4	5,4	5,0	4,3	5,0	4,7
United States	3,8	3,6	3,6	3,7	3,8	3,8	3,8	3,9	3,9	3,9	3,9	3,9	2,6	..
Argentina	9,8	9,7	9,9	10,0	10,2
Brazil	..	2,3	2,2	2,2	2,3	2,2	2,3	2,4	2,6	2,6	2,5	2,6
Croatia	4,4	4,3	4,4	4,5	4,8	4,9	5,5	5,3	6,0	6,3	6,6	6,8	5,9	5,9
Egypt	13,0	12,6	12,8	13,0	13,0	14,1	16,5	16,2
India	..	4,4	4,6	4,9	5,3
Indonesia	6,8	6,7	6,9	7,8	8,4
Kazakhstan	3,9	4,0	4,1	4,0	4,2	4,1	4,9	5,1	4,8	5,2	5,3
Malta	13,9	14,2	13,7	13,9	14,1	15,2	14,5	14,1	15,5	15,0	15,3	16,9	16,6	15,6
Morocco	4,1	4,1	4,3	4,5	4,6	4,7	4,7	4,7	4,8	4,8	5,0	5,0
Peru	3,2	3,2	3,2	3,2	3,8	3,8	3,9	4,0	4,1	2,2	..
Philippines	10,7	11,2	11,4	11,7	12,1	12,4	12,7	12,8	12,8
Romania	4,6	4,6	4,7	6,6	6,4	6,1	6,0	6,2	6,5	6,3	6,3	6,3	6,1	..
Serbia	3,7	3,8	3,9	4,1	4,2	4,3	4,3
South Africa	4,3	4,2	4,4	4,4	4,5	4,4	4,5	4,0	4,0	3,6	3,7	4,7

Source: OECD, Tourism Statistics, <https://stats.oecd.org/>.

In OECD data, it is seen that the ratio of tourism employment to total employment in Türkiye has taken place since 2014. It is observed that the ratio of tourism employment to total employment in Türkiye peaked in 2019 with 8.1%. It was determined that this rate decreased to 6.9% in 2020 with the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic, and the decrease continued in 2021. Similar to Türkiye, the ratio of tourism employment to total employment reaches up to 14% in Spain and Greece, which have adopted Sea-Sand-Sun tourism.

Table 19: Ratio of Tourism GDP in Total GDP by Years (2008-2021)

Dataset: Key Tourism Indicators														
Key Indicator	Tourism GDP (direct) as % of total GDP													
Unit	Percentage													
Country Year	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Australia	2,9	2,8	2,7	2,7	2,8	2,9	3,0	3,1	3,1	3,1	3,1	2,6	1,6	..
Austria	5,2	5,1	5,4	5,4	5,4	5,4	5,4	5,3	5,3	5,4	5,5	5,6	3,5	..
Belgium	1,9
Chile	3,2	3,3	3,2	3,2	3,5	3,1	3,1	3,4	3,6	3,5	3,3	3,3
Costa Rica	4,3	4,6	4,5	4,6	4,9
Czech Republic	2,6	2,6	2,5	2,5	2,7	2,8	2,7	2,7	2,9	2,9	2,9	2,9	1,5	..
Estonia	4,2	4,7	4,5	4,4	4,3	4,8	5,5
France	7,3	7,5	7,6	7,5	7,5	7,3	7,1	7,2	7,3	7,5	5,3	..
Iceland	..	3,5	3,4	3,7	4,2	4,7	5,5	6,5	8,2	8,0	8,1	8,1	3,6	4,2
Japan	1,9	1,8	1,7	1,7	1,7	1,8	1,7	1,8	1,9	2,0	1,9	2,0
Korea	2,5
Luxembourg	1,3	1,2	1,3	1,3	1,3	1,2	1,0	..
Mexico	8,1	8,2	8,0	7,9	8,0	8,2	8,1	8,2	8,0	8,0	7,9	8,0	6,3	..
Norway	3,0	3,3	3,2	3,4	3,3	3,3	3,3	3,5	3,8	3,7	3,4	3,6
Poland	2,2	1,6	1,6	1,8	2,1	1,3	..	1,2
Slovak Republic	2,9	2,6	2,4	2,6	2,7	2,3	2,1	2,5	2,6	2,6	2,7	2,8
Slovenia	..	4,8	4,8	..	4,8	4,9	..	5,3	..	5,4	3,3	..
Spain	10,2	9,9	10,3	10,5	10,8	10,8	11,0	11,1	11,3	12,1	12,2	12,4	5,5	..
Sweden	2,3	2,4	2,2	2,2	2,3	2,3	2,3	2,7	2,7	2,6	2,6	2,4	1,7	1,9
Croatia	10,2	11,3	11,8
Egypt	..	5,6	6,3	..	4,8	3,9	4,3
India	..	3,8	3,7	3,7	3,8
Indonesia	4,7	4,2	4,1	4,0	4,0	4,0	4,1	4,3	4,7	4,7	4,9	5,0	2,2	..
Malta	5,9
Morocco	..	6,9	7,1	6,9	6,9	6,6	6,7	6,4	6,6	6,8	6,9	7,1
Peru	3,6	3,6	3,7	3,8	3,9	3,9	3,9	3,9	3,9	1,5	1,8
Philippines	5,6	5,8	6,2	6,8	7,0	7,2	7,5	8,2	8,6
Romania	1,8	1,9	1,9	2,0	2,4	2,8	2,8	2,9	3,0
South Africa	3,0	2,9	2,9	2,8	2,9	3,3	3,4	2,9	2,9	2,6	2,7	3,7

Source: OECD, Tourism Statistics, <https://stats.oecd.org/>.

When it is looked at the OECD data, which includes the ratio of the GDP created by tourism to the total GDP, it is seen that there is no data for Türkiye. Many countries such as Germany, Italy and United States are not included in the data showing the ratio of tourism GDP to total GDP in OECD data. Spain, which is among the countries that share data with the OECD on this subject, was determined as the country with the highest ratio of tourism-based GDP to total GDP with 12.4% before the COVID-19 pandemic.

Table 20: Number of Tourism Enterprises by Types and Years (2009-2020)

Dataset: Enterprises and employment in tourism												
Country	Türkiye											
Variable	Enterprises											
Unit	Enterprises											
Year	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Total tourism
Tourism industries	477431	488429	482659	458139	462742	448332	465290	470634	492960	498625	516807	501608
Accommodation services for visitors	12637	14103	14388	14867	15883	17260	18278	19290	21116	21695	23292	23024
Hotels and similar establishments	8575	9000	9299	10558	11557	12885	13709	14592	16350	17241	18991	19091
Food and beverage serving industry	219730	223713	229897	240289	244931	249544	253510	256825	267094	269421	281078	271214
Passenger transport	214181	217493	204509	170534	168248	145104	155773	156201	164475	164939	167150	162567
Transport equipment rental	3517	4013	4725	5857	6531	7598	7790	8307	8809	9423	9901	10424
Travel agencies and other reservation services industry	6784	6932	7296	7354	7247	7774	8812	9156	9240	10113	11264	11195
Cultural industry	2593	2927	3458	4428	4963	5247	5369	5349	5476	5474	5594	5455
Sports and recreation industry	17989	19248	18386	14810	14939	15805	15758	15506	16750	17560	18528	17729

Source: OECD, Tourism Statistics, <https://stats.oecd.org/>.

According to OECD data, 501608 people are working in the tourism sector in Türkiye as of 2020. There are 23024 employees in the accommodation industry, 271214 in the

transportation equipment rental, 11195 in the travel agencies, 5455 in the cultural industry, and 17729 in the sports and recreation sector.

Table 21: Number of Tourist Arrivals by Years (2008-2021)

Dataset: Inbound Tourism															
Country		Türkiye													
Source		Tourism demand surveys (millions)													
Variable Year		2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Total international arrivals		31,14	31,76	33,00	36,77	37,72	39,86	41,63	41,11	30,91	37,97	46,11	51,75	15,97	30,04
Total international arrivals	Overnight visitors (tourists)	29,79	30,19	31,36	34,65	35,70	37,79	39,81	39,48	30,29	37,60	45,77	51,19	15,89	29,93
	Same-day visitors (excursionists)	1,35	1,57	1,63	2,12	2,02	2,07	1,82	1,64	0,62	0,37	0,34	0,56	0,08	0,11
Top markets	Bulgaria	1,25	1,40	1,43	1,49	1,49	1,58	1,69	1,82	1,69	1,85	2,38	2,71	1,24	1,40
	Germany	4,30	4,35	4,21	4,57	4,77	4,81	5,03	5,36	3,83	3,52	4,46	4,99	1,12	3,08
	United Kingdom	1,99	2,23	2,43	2,28	2,16	2,25	2,35	2,27	1,59	1,60	2,22	2,50	0,82	0,39
	Netherlands	0,83	0,99	1,11	1,15	1,40	1,77	1,75	1,91	2,20	2,43	2,07	1,99	0,27	0,65
	Russian Federation	2,87	2,68	3,09	3,45	3,58	4,25	4,46	3,63	0,86	4,70	5,95	7,00	2,12	4,68
	Ukraine	0,72	0,56	0,56	0,59	0,62	0,74	0,64	0,69	1,03	1,27	1,37	1,52	0,98	2,05
	Georgia	1,13	1,38	1,88	1,88	1,19	1,20	1,59	1,70	1,67	2,50	2,00	2,10	0,41	0,29

Source: OECD, Tourism Statistics, <https://stats.oecd.org/>.

As previously reported, the number of tourists coming to Türkiye peaked in 2019 with 51.75 million. In 2019, when the historical peak was experienced, it was determined that 51.19 million visitors were overnight visitors, and 0.56 million visitors were same-day visitors. It is observed that the number of same-day visitors, which reached up to 2 million in 2011 and 2012, decreased over time.

It is seen that the top markets of Turkish tourism are the Russian Federation and Germany. The leadership in the number of visitors in Germany has passed to the Russian Federation over the years. Following these countries, the United Kingdom, Netherlands and Ukraine are Türkiye's important tourism markets. It is seen that the number of visitors from Bulgaria and Georgia, which are neighbors of Türkiye, has also increased over the years.

Table 22: Number of Domestic Tourism Demand by Years (2008-2021)

Dataset: Domestic tourism													
Country	Türkiye												
Source	Tourism demand surveys (millions)												
Variable Year	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Total domestic trips	100,46	111,50	104,17	106,23	112,16	115,09	115,38	106,50	120,87	126,45	124,64	67,14	75,88
Overnight visitors (tourists)	60,89	68,37	65,85	64,92	68,45	70,89	71,25	68,45	77,18	78,52	78,20	42,85	52,77
Same-day visitors (excursionists)	39,57	43,13	38,32	41,30	43,71	44,19	44,13	38,05	43,69	47,92	46,44	24,30	23,11
Nights in all types of accommodation	510,96	555,15	558,27	556,80	557,46	575,87	588,79	605,61	665,19	633,72	637,07	469,09	458,87
Hotels and similar establishments	31,61	34,80	37,44	36,39	40,56	41,32	39,62	48,62	49,79	55,82	51,63	23,57	41,65
Other collective establishments	27,14	17,59	19,14	16,88	20,64	23,21	17,29	17,70	19,03	19,12	19,09	9,93	16,48
Private accommodation	452,21	502,76	501,70	503,53	496,26	511,34	531,87	539,29	596,38	558,79	566,35	435,60	400,74

Source: OECD, Tourism Statistics, <https://stats.oecd.org/>.

According to the OECD's domestic tourism data on Türkiye, the highest number of trips took place in 2018 as 126.45 million. In 2018, when the highest number of trips took place, 78.52 million trips were made for multiple overnight visits and 47.92 million trips were made for same-day trips.

Even though the peak in the number of trips is in 2018, the peak in the number of accommodation per night belongs to 2017. In 2017, a total of 665.19 million accommodation types were realized in all accommodation types. Of these accommodation, 49.79 million were made in hotels and similar establishments, 19.03 million in other collective establishments, and 596.38 million in private accommodation. Although the highest number of accommodation was in 2017, the highest number of accommodation in hotels and similar establishments was realized in 2018. In 2018, 55.82 million accommodations were made in hotels and similar establishments.

It is seen that the COVID-19 pandemic, which started in 2020, significantly reduced the number of domestic tourism trips, the number of overnight or same-day trips, and the number of accommodation. Although these data started to increase in 2021, pre-COVID-19 levels have not been reached yet.

Table 23: Number of Accommodation for Visitors in Hotels and Similar Establishments by Years (2008-2022)

TOURISM INDUSTRIES: Accommodation for visitors in hotels and similar establishments															
TÜRKİYE															
Accommodation for visitors in hotels and similar establishments	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Number of establishments (Units)	2547	2597	2614	2740	2814	2917	3061	3237	8664	11151	11362	11898	12570	13968	19564
Number of rooms (Thousands)	267	286	295	313	328	348	374	394	568	655	674	688	717	760	837
Number of bed-places (Thousands)	563	601	620	656	688	730	784	826	1203	1392	1432	1482	1539	1628	1725
Occupancy rate / rooms (Percent)
Occupancy rate / bed-places (Percent)	51,51	48,90	49,17	51,46	54,34	53,40	52,62	51,95	38,22	46,17	50,87	53,48	22,45	40,08	51,87
Average length of stay (Nights)	3,12	3,13	3,30	3,20	3,35	3,20	3,18	3,09	2,60	2,52	2,65	2,61	2,28	2,49	2,56

Source: UNWTO, Tourism Industries Statistics, <https://www.unwto.org/tourism-statistics/key-tourism-statistics>.

Accommodation statistics in Türkiye are published by UNWTO. In the published data, it is seen that the number of establishments in Türkiye, which was 2547 in 2008, increased to 19564 in 2022. In parallel with the number of establishments, the number of rooms has also increased, reaching 837 thousand in 2022 from 267 thousand in 2008. The number of beds, which was 563 thousand in 2008, reached 1725 thousand in 2022. Although the number of establishments, rooms and beds has increased over the years, the occupancy rates have shown a fluctuating course. The occupancy rate, which was 51.51% in 2008, reached its highest rate of 54.34% in 2012. The occupancy rate, which was at similar rates until 2016, dropped to 38.22% in 2016 due to the crisis with the Russian Federation. The occupancy rate, which started to rise again after the crisis was overcome, increased to 53.48% in 2019, but decreased to 22.45% in 2020 with the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic. The occupancy rate was 51.87% in 2022 with the decrease of the effect of the pandemic. The average length of stay, which was 3.12 in 2008, saw the highest number of 3.35 in 2012. The average length of stay has declined since 2012 and finally stood at 2.56 in 2022.

Table 24: Number of Employees by Tourism Industries (2012-2022)

EMPLOYMENT: Number of employees by tourism industries											
TÜRKİYE											
Number of employees by tourism industries (Thousands)	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Total	1100	1228	1248	1368	1445	1518	1646	1674	1355	1437	1688
Accommodation services for visitors (hotels and similar establishments)	230	260	250	287	252	278	331	352	280	293	355
Other accommodation services
Food and beverage serving activities	676	743	767	840	841	864	905	918	732	748	938
Passenger transportation	165	193	192	204	228	252	264	263	234	238	256
Travel agencies and other reservation services activities	29	32	39	37	42	36	37	41	32	45	48
Other tourism industries	82	88	109	100	77	113	91

Source: UNWTO, Employment Statistics, <https://www.unwto.org/tourism-statistics/key-tourism-statistics>.

Tourism employment statistics in Türkiye are published by UNWTO. The number of tourism employees, which was 1.10 million in 2012, increased to 1.69 million in 2022. As of 2022, 355 thousand of 1.69 million tourism employees work in accommodation services, 938 thousand in food & beverage services, and 256 thousand in passenger transportation. 48 thousand employees work in travel agencies and 91 thousand employees work in other tourism industries.

Table 25: Number of Tourist Arrivals by Years (2008-2022)

INBOUND TOURISM: Arrivals															
TÜRKİYE															
Arrivals (Thousands)	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Total arrivals	31138	31760	32997	36769	37715	39861	41627	41114	30907	37970	46113	51747	15971	30039	51388
Overnights visitors (tourists)	29792	30187	31364	34654	35698	37795	39811	39478	30289	37601	45768	51192	15894	29925	50453
Same-day visitors (excursionists)	1346	1573	1633	2115	2017	2066	1816	1636	618	369	345	555	77	114	935

Source: UNWTO, Inbound Tourism Statistics, <https://www.unwto.org/tourism-statistics/key-tourism-statistics>.

The number of arrivals in Türkiye is published by TURKSTAT and has the same numbers as UNWTO. According to the data interpreted in the previous pages of this study, the year in which Türkiye reached the highest number of arrivals was 2019 with 51.7 million. According to the latest published data, the number of arrivals was 51.4 million in 2022. Of the arrivals in 2022, 50.5 million were overnight visitors and 1 million were same-day visitors.

Table 26: Amount of Tourism Expenditure in the Country (2008-2022)

INBOUND TOURISM: Tourism expenditure in the country															
TÜRKİYE															
	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Tourism expenditure in the country US\$ Millions	26446	26331	26318	30302	32248	38748	40859	36347	26875	32483	37505	45789	16719	33706	57849
Travel	23365	22980	22585	25054	26027	28761	30383	27315	19113	22968	25934	34305	13330	26634	41176
Passenger transport	3081	3351	3733	5248	6221	9987	10476	9032	7762	9515	11571	11484	3389	7072	16673

Source: UNWTO, Inbound Tourism Statistics, <https://www.unwto.org/tourism-statistics/key-tourism-statistics>.

Tourism expenditures in Türkiye are published by UNWTO. Tourism expenditure, which was \$26.4 billion in 2008, reached its historical peak with \$57.8 billion in 2022. Tourism expenditures, which fell to \$13.5 billion in 2020 due to the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, increased to \$57.8 billion in 2022. As of 2022, \$41.1 billion of tourism expenditures is spent on travel, and \$16.7 billion on transportation.

Table 27: Number of Tourist Arrivals by Region (2008-2022)

INBOUND TOURISM: Arrivals by region															
TÜRKİYE															
Arrivals by region (Thousands)	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Total	29792	30187	31364	34653	35698	37795	39811	39478	30289	37601	45768	51192	15894	29925	50453
Africa	204	287	247	301	372	420	491	535	493	590	817	998	298	555	1042
Americas	561	559	550	660	714	790	846	936	593	574	827	1029	258	571	1344
East Asia and the Pacific	554	545	628	721	784	848	1032	1074	620	813	1254	1470	250	203	793
Europe	21198	21142	21666	23501	24167	26157	27263	26411	18761	23874	29429	33517	10020	19116	33005
Middle East	1206	1424	1896	2133	2377	3244	3554	3663	2374	3406	4391	4854	1299	2748	4538
South Asia	1212	1462	1982	1992	1319	1348	1787	1931	1852	2727	2345	2551	517	1367	2828
Other not classified	4857	4768	4395	5345	5965	4989	4838	4929	5595	5617	6705	6774	3253	5366	6903
of which, nationals residing abroad	4798	4681	4364	5311	5929	4948	4787	4866	5552	5558	6622	6672	3222	5302	6810

Source: UNWTO, Inbound Tourism Statistics, <https://www.unwto.org/tourism-statistics/key-tourism-statistics>.

UNWTO publishes statistics about number of tourist arrivals by region. According to these data, Türkiye's largest tourism market is Europe. The number of European tourists from 21.2 million in 2008 increased to 33.5 million in 2019 and decreased to 10 million in 2020 with the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic. With the decrease of the effect of the pandemic, 33 million European tourists came to Türkiye in 2022. Turkish citizens living abroad are among the most important groups visiting Türkiye. The number of visits by Turkish citizens living abroad, which was 4.8 million in 2008, reached 6.8 million in 2022. Middle Eastern tourists also have a significant proportion among visitors to Türkiye. The number of tourists, which was 1.2 million in 2008, reached 4.9 million in 2019, and it was 4.5 million in 2022 with the effect of the pandemic. In 2022, 6.9 million visitors from others not classified and 2.8 million visitors from South Asia also have a significant share in Turkish tourism.

Table 28: Number of Arrivals by Main Purpose (2008-2022)

INBOUND TOURISM: Arrivals by main purpose															
TÜRKİYE															
Arrivals by main purpose (Thousands)	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Total	30980	32006	33028	36151	36464	39226	41415	41618	31365	38620	45629	51860	15826	29357	51369
Personal	28455	30211	31127	33776	34083	36703	38923	39261	29454	36735	43613	49874	15164	28255	49703
Business and professional	2525	1795	1901	2375	2381	2523	2492	2356	1912	1886	2016	1986	662	1102	1666

Source: UNWTO, Inbound Tourism Statistics, <https://www.unwto.org/tourism-statistics/key-tourism-statistics>.

Arrivals in Türkiye are classified according to their purpose and published by UNWTO. According to this classification, arrivals at Türkiye are divided into personal and business-professional reasons. Looking at the data, it is seen that most of the visits to Türkiye are for personal reasons, but business-professional visits also increase from time to time. The number of arrivals based on personal reasons, which was 28.4 million in 2008, peaked at 49.9 million in 2019, and reached 28.2 million in 2021 with the effect of the pandemic. Business-professional arrivals peaked at 2.5 million in 2008 and reached 1.1 million in 2021.

Table 29: Number of Arrivals by Mode of Transport (2008-2022)

INBOUND TOURISM: Arrivals by mode of transport															
TÜRKİYE															
Arrivals by mode of transport (Thousands)	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Total	31138	31760	32997	36769	37716	39861	41627	41114	30907	37970	46113	51747	15971	30039	51388
Air	22974	22912	23101	26026	27733	29418	31034	31040	22425	28114	35230	39829	11765	23573	37985
Water	2680	2669	2122	2709	2528	2616	2493	2371	958	838	1040	1456	310	408	1951
Land	5484	6178	7774	8034	7455	7827	8100	7703	7523	9018	9843	10463	3896	6058	11452

Source: UNWTO, Inbound Tourism Statistics, <https://www.unwto.org/tourism-statistics/key-tourism-statistics>.

The classification of arrivals to Türkiye in terms of transportation is published by UNWTO. It is seen that the airline stands out in the classification made as air, water and land. It was determined that the number of people arriving by air, which was 23 million in 2008, reached its highest point with 39.8 million in 2019 and was 38 million in 2022. While arrivals by land were 5.5 million in 2008, reached its highest point with 11.4 million in 2022. Arrivals by water were 2.7 million in 2008 and followed a fluctuating course over time. The arrivals by water, which decreased to 0.8 million in 2017, increased to 1.5 million again in 2019, and then it was realized as 1.9 million in 2022 with the decrease of the pandemic.

Table 30: Number of Accommodation by Years (2008-2022)

INBOUND TOURISM: Accommodation															
TÜRKİYE															
Accom. (Thousands)	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Total															
Guests	13648	14389	17415	19264	20481	21180	23609	23138	18048	22928	31136	38854	12779	28522	46580
Overnights	56918	59987	74326	78889	90822	89592	97581	96400	77460	80063	112245	132508	40095	93124	148553
Hotels and Similar Establishments															
Guests	13628	14362	17112	18791	19999	20677	22985	22585	17688	22559	30506	38102	12638	28253	45902
Overnights	56865	59874	73924	78257	90100	88860	96501	95551	76744	79495	111331	131480	39788	92503	147161

Source: UNWTO, Inbound Tourism Statistics, <https://www.unwto.org/tourism-statistics/key-tourism-statistics>.

The number of guests coming to Türkiye and the number of overnight stays by these guests are published by UNWTO. Almost all of the guests stay in hotels and similar establishments. While the number of guests staying in hotels and similar establishments was 13.6 million in 2008, the number of overnight stays was 56.9 million. The number of guests and overnight stays in hotels and similar establishment peaked in 2022. In 2022, 46.6 million guests spent 148.6 million nights in hotels and similar establishments.

Table 31: Number of Domestic Accommodation by Years (2008-2022)

DOMESTIC TOURISM: Accommodation															
TÜRKİYE															
Accommodation (Thousands)	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Total															
Guests	11286	12138	12339	14350	15702	17101	17292	20222	41336	39024	40822	42013	29101	42216	48251
Overnights	20832	22930	23832	27617	30332	33091	32449	37481	76852	75747	78442	78479	55228	82910	93969
Hotels and Similar Establishments															
Guests	11274	11855	11879	13700	14906	16194	16264	19056	39653	36736	38345	39445	27636	39948	45963
Overnights	20809	22340	22872	26280	28663	31270	30406	35225	73555	70602	73069	72873	52034	77830	88994

Source: UNWTO, Domestic Tourism Statistics, <https://www.unwto.org/tourism-statistics/key-tourism-statistics>.

The number of domestic tourism guests in Türkiye and the number of overnight stays of these guests are published by UNWTO. Almost all of the guests stay in hotels and similar establishments. While the number of guests staying in hotels and similar establishments was 11.3 million in 2008, the number of overnight stays was 20.8 million. The number of domestic tourism guests and overnight stays, which increased until the pandemic, decreased in 2020. With the decrease of the pandemic effect, the number of domestic tourism guests and overnight stays reached their peak in 2022. In 2022, 46 million domestic tourism guests made 89 million overnight stays.

2.1.1.2. Analysis of Leading Cities of Industry

Accommodation industry is the most important part of hospitality industry. Accommodation can be classified into different categories such as five star, four star, three star and etc. There are also other classifications.

Figure 15: Leading Cities of Accommodation (5 Star Hotels)

Resource: <https://yigm.ktb.gov.tr/genel/turizmtesisleri.aspx>

As seen from the figure 15, there are three important cities which are Antalya, İstanbul and Muğla respectively. 44 % of the five star hotels of Türkiye is located in Antalya. 17 % of the five star hotels of Türkiye is located in İstanbul and lastly 8 % of the five star hotels of Türkiye is located in Muğla.

Figure 16: Percentage of Three Leading Cities (Antalya, İstanbul and Muğla 5 Star Hotels)

Figure 17: Leading Cities of Accommodation (4 Star Hotels)

As seen from the figure, there are three important cities which are Antalya, İstanbul and Muğla respectively. 20,2% of the four star hotels of Türkiye is located in Antalya. 18,3 % of the four star hotels of Türkiye is located in İstanbul and lastly 9,2 % of the four star hotels of Türkiye is located in Muğla.

Figure 18: Percentage of Three Leading Cities (Antalya, İstanbul and Muğla 4 Star Hotels)

2.1.1.2.1. Antalya

There are 352 five star hotels in Antalya which is a seaside city. Antalya can be called as the capital city of Türkiye in terms of tourism and hospitality, especially accommodation. The hotels are both located in the city center and its towns. In figure 19, the distribution of Antalya's five star hotels according to their location is shown.

Figure 19: Distribution of 5 Star Hotels in Antalya

As seen from figure 19, Manavgat town of Antalya has the largest number of five star hotels with 134 hotels. Alanya town of Antalya has the second largest number of five star hotels with 89 hotels. Towns of Serik, Kemer and Aksu follow them respectively.

Figure 20: Distribution of 4 Star Hotels in Antalya

Antalya has 197 four star hotels. As seen from figure 20, Alanya town of Antalya has the largest number of four star hotels with 93 hotels. Manavgat town of Antalya has the second largest number of four star hotels with 46 hotels. Town of Kemer, City Center and Serik follow them respectively.

2.1.1.2.2. İstanbul

İstanbul which is the biggest city of Türkiye in terms of population, has 132 five star hotels. It is both an industrialized region and a tourism city. In figure 21, the distribution of İstanbul's 5 star hotels according to their location is shown. Although İstanbul has seashores, it is generally visited by foreign tourists for cultural aims. It is famous for its history and culture.

Figure 21: Distribution of 5 Star Hotels in İstanbul

As seen from figure 21, Şişli town of İstanbul has the largest number five star hotels with 19 hotels. Beyoğlu town of İstanbul has the second largest number of five star hotels with 14 hotels. Towns of Beşiktaş and Fatih follow them respectively.

Figure 22: Distribution of 4 Star Hotels in İstanbul

İstanbul has 178 four star hotels. As seen from figure 22, Fatih town of İstanbul has the largest number of four star hotels with 58 hotels. Towns of Beyoğlu and Şişli follow them respectively with 45 and 16 hotels.

2.1.1.2.3. Muğla

Muğla has 63 five star hotels. It is located at the south Eagean part of Türkiye. It is a tourism city famous for its coasts and natural beauties. In figure 23, the distribution of Muğla's 5 star hotels according to their location is shown.

Figure 23: Distribution of 5 Star Hotels in Muğla

As seen from figure 23, Bodrum has the largest number of five star hotels with 31 hotels. Marmaris town of Muğla has the second largest number of five star hotels with 19 hotels. Towns of Fethiye, Milas and Ortaca follow them respectively.

Figure 24: Distribution of 4 Star Hotels in Muğla

Muğla has 90 four star hotels. As seen from figure 24, Bodrum town of Muğla has the largest number of four star hotels with 33 hotels. Towns of Marmaris and Fethiye follow them respectively with 29 and 17 hotels.

2.1.1.2.4. İzmir

İzmir which is the third biggest city of Türkiye in terms of population has 31 five star hotels. In figure 25, the distribution of İzmir's 5 star hotels according to their location is shown below.

Figure 25: Distribution of 5 Star Hotels in İzmir

As seen from figure 25, Çeşme town of İzmir has the largest number of five star hotels with 12 hotels. Towns of Menderes and Selçuk follow respectively.

Figure 26: Distribution of 4 Star Hotels in İzmir

As seen from figure 26, city center of İzmir has the largest number of four star hotels with 21 hotels.

2.1.1.2.5. Ankara

Ankara is the capital city of Türkiye. It is also the second biggest city of Türkiye in terms of population. It has 30 five star hotels. In figure 27, the distribution of Ankara's 5 star hotels according to their location is shown below.

Figure 27: Distribution of 5 Star Hotels in Ankara

As seen from figure 27, Çankaya town of Ankara has the largest number of five star hotels with 16 hotels. Yenimahalle town of Ankara has the second largest number of five star hotels with 7 hotels. There are also four star hotels in Ankara. Most of them are located in Çankaya.

Figure 28: Distribution of 4 Star Hotels in Ankara

2.1.1.2.6. Aydın

Aydın has important tourism destinations that are well-known towns such as Kuşadası and Didim. These are generally preferred by foreign tourists. There are 20 five star hotels in Aydın city. 13 of these hotels are located in Kuşadası and 7 of these hotels are located in Didim.

Figure 29: Distribution of 5 Star Hotels in Aydın

There are also four star hotels in Aydın. 23 of these hotels are located in Kuşadası. The rest of the hotels are located in Efeler, Didim and Sultanhisar.

Figure 30: Distribution of 4 Star Hotels in Aydın

2.1.1.2.7. Bursa

Bursa is the fourth biggest city of Türkiye in terms of population. It is an industrialized city and also famous for its historical and cultural places. It has a mountain named Uludağ that is mostly preferred for winter tourism.

Figure 31: Distribution of 5 Star Hotels in Bursa

As seen from figure 31, there are 10 five star hotels in Bursa. These are located at the center towns named Nilüfer and Osmangazi. There are 7 five star hotels in Nilüfer and 3 five star hotels in Osmangazi. There are also 28 four star hotels in Bursa. Most of them are located in the old town of Bursa called Osmangazi.

Figure 32: Distribution of 4 Star Hotels in Bursa

2.1.1.2.8. Nevşehir

Nevşehir is famous for its fairy chimneys worldwide. It has 10 five star hotels that are mostly located in the town of Ürgüp. In addition, there are 15 four star hotels in Nevşehir. Four star hotels of Nevşehir are located in Ürgüp, city center, Avanos and Kozaklı. The distribution of five and four star hotels can be seen from the figures 33 and 34 below.

Figure 33: Distribution of 5 Star Hotels in Nevşehir

Figure 34: Distribution of 4 Star Hotels in Nevşehir

2.1.1.2.9. Afyonkarahisar

Afyonkarahisar that stands out as a capital city of hot springs and spas, is an important junction of railway, highway and air traffic in West-Türkiye. It has 9 five star hotels and 3 four star hotels.

Figure 35: Distribution of 5 Star Hotels in Afyonkarahisar

Figure 36: Distribution of 4 Star Hotels in Afyonkarahisar

2.1.1.2.10. Gaziantep

Gaziantep is an important city in terms of domestic tourism especially for gastronomy. There are 7 five star hotels and 16 four star hotels in Gaziantep. The hotels are located in Şehitkamil and Şahinbey as seen from the figures below.

Figure 37: Distribution of 5 Star Hotels in Gaziantep

Figure 38: Distribution of 4 Star Hotels in Gaziantep

2.1.1.2.11. Denizli

Denizli is famous for its cultural and natural beauties. Thermal health tourism is also important for Denizli like Afyonkarahisar. There is Pamukkale which is a unique natural beauty. Pamukkale meaning "cotton castle" in Turkish, is a natural site in Denizli Province in southwestern Türkiye. The area is famous for a carbonate mineral left by the flowing of thermal spring water. It is located in Türkiye's Inner Aegean region, in the River Menderes valley, which has a temperate climate for most of the year.

Figure 39: Distribution of 5 Star Hotels in Denizli

Because of Pamukkale being an important tourism destination in Denizli, most of the hotels are located in Pamukkale. There are 7 five star hotels and 8 four star hotels in Denizli.

Figure 40: Distribution of 4 Star Hotels in Denizli

2.1.1.2.12. Balıkesir

Balıkesir has seashores both in Marmara and Aegean seas. Ayvalık, Edremit and Burhaniye towns are located at the Aegean coast of Balıkesir. There are 4 five star hotels and 14 four star hotels in Balıkesir.

Figure 41: Distribution of 5 Star Hotels in Balıkesir

Figure 42: Distribution of 4 Star Hotels in Balıkesir

2.1.1.2.13. Çanakkale

Çanakkale is an important destination especially for Turkish history. In addition, it has coasts both in Marmara and Aegean regions like Balıkesir. There are 2 five star hotels in Çanakkale. Besides, there are 9 four star hotels in Çanakkale. These are shown below.

Figure 43: Distribution of 4 and 5 Star Hotels in Çanakkale

2.1.1.3. Market Analysis

There are totally 1189 three star hotels in Türkiye according to the data of Culture and Tourism Ministry 2022. İstanbul has the biggest number of three star hotels. Antalya, Muğla, Ankara and İzmir follow İstanbul respectively. 29 cities have 921 three star hotels which means the majority of 3 Star Hotels in Türkiye.

Figure 44: Distribution of 3 Star Hotels in Türkiye (Top 29 Cities)

Figure 45: Distribution of 3 Star Hotels in Türkiye

Three star hotels are one of the most important part of hospitality industry because they generally offer bed and breakfast. This feature allows tourists to attend to the destination's local facilities such as tours, shopping, eating and drinking, entertaining, visiting historical, cultural and natural sites of the destination.

Figure 46: Distribution of 3 Star Hotels in İstanbul

İstanbul has 152 three star hotels. As seen from figure 46 (the distribution of three star hotels in İstanbul), most of the three star hotels are located in Fatih, which is a historical region. Beyoğlu and Şişli towns follow respectively.

Figure 47: Distribution of 3 Star Hotels in Antalya

There are 103 three star hotels in Antalya. Approximately half of these hotels are located in Alanya. 25 of these hotels are located at the city center. In addition, 16 hotels are located in Kemer and 11 are located in Manavgat.

Figure 48: Distribution of 3 Star Hotels in Muğla

There are 100 three star hotels in Muğla. As seen from figure 48, most of these hotels are located in Marmaris, Bodrum and Fethiye destinations.

2.1.1.3.1. Market Concentration

The growing number of visitors is making the hospitality industry in Türkiye an attractive market for investors. The country registered 40 million visitor arrivals in 2018 and 51.9 million in 2019 which is a rise of 13.7% from the previous year. The tourism industry in Türkiye is primarily driven by its rich culture and heritage. The country has set the target to welcome 50 million travelers as a part of Vision 2023 goal and to generate USD 50 billion for the same. In support of this, the Ministry of Culture and Tourism lifted restrictions on seasonal resorts concept in some areas and is allowing them to operate the full year cycle. With this move, the existing resort managements are promoting their respective resorts all year long by turning themselves with the seasons by turning resorts depending upon the seasons. These initiatives helped the country to record growing numbers of average daily revenue (ADR) and revenue per available room (RevPAR). For the year 2018, Türkiye registered a 6.5% growth in ADR, a 3.9% increase in RevPAR (3.9%), and the occupancy rate also increased by 2.5%. Türkiye has more than 900 hotel chains present in the country that are offering more than 170000 rooms of different segments/class. There are around 60 brands in the country of which more than 70% are domestic brands. The cities with high number of rooms are Antalya, Istanbul, and Mugla with 883, 745 and 503 hotels respectively.⁸

Figure 49: Hospitality Market Size of Türkiye

⁸ <https://www.mordorintelligence.com/industry-reports/hospitality-industry-in-Türkiye>

A complete background analysis of the hospitality industry in Türkiye, which includes an assessment of the industry associations, overall economy, and emerging market trends by segments, significant changes in the market dynamics, and market overview, is covered in this report. Turkish hospitality industry can be segmented by some criteria. One of these criteria is type. In Turkish hospitality industry there are two types of hotels. These are chain hotels and independent hotels. Turkish hospitality industry can also be segmented by using the quality of service offered to tourists. There are different type of segmentation according to different hotels. Independent hotels are generally segmenting by star criteria like 5 star, 4 star and so on. In spite of this, international chain hotels and most domestic chain hotels use different terms such as Budget and Economy Hotels, Mid and Upper Mid-scale Hotels, Luxury Hotels and etc. The mid and upper mid-scale segment hotels are occupying a higher share of the total market.

The tourist arrivals to country are recording a growing number and visitors from foreign countries are on the rise. The statistical data revealed that Türkiye generated more than USD 1 billion from the hospitality industry. The country has more than 900 hotels that are providing more than 170000 rooms across the country. The mid and upper mid-scale segment occupied a major share of the market, with more than 500 properties across the country, followed by the luxury segment, with around 320 properties.

Figure 50: Distribution of Hotel Chains in Türkiye by Scale

Source: Mordor Intelligence

According to the Turkish Statistical Institute, Istanbul was the top arriving destination in Türkiye for 2019 with nearly 15 million tourist arrivals of which around 33% are from foreign countries followed by Antalya with 14.65 million and Northwestern province of Edirne with around 4.3 million visitors. With these rising numbers of visitors, the country generated USD 34.5 billion tourism revenue in 2019 which was a new record high and was made a 17% increase when compared to USD 29.5 billion it generated in 2018. In order to accommodate this growing number of visitors, more than 1000 rooms from different hotel brands are being added and are going to be added to the supply during 2018-2021, in Istanbul.

Figure 51: Upcoming Pipeline of Hotels (By Major Areas)

The industry is largely dominated by domestic brands, whereas the international brands have addressed most of the supply. The region has been attracting a great number of investors and has more diversified profiles of such companies. The franchising model is dominating the market. Accor SA, InterContinental Hotels Group, Marriott International, Inc, Wyndham Hotels & Resorts Inc. are the major companies operating in hospitality industry in Türkiye.

Figure 52: Market Concentration

Turkey Hospitality Market Leaders

- 1 Accor SA
- 2 InterContinental Hotels Group
- 3 Marriott International, Inc
- 4 Wyndham Hotels & Resorts Inc
- 5 Rixos Hotels

*Disclaimer: Major Players sorted in no particular order

Market Concentration

Source: Mordor Intelligence

2.1.1.3.2. Leading Companies of Industry

2.1.1.3.2.1. ACCOR S.A.

Accor S.A. is a French multinational hospitality company that owns, manages and franchises hotels, resorts and vacation properties. It is the largest hospitality company in Europe, and the sixth largest hospitality company worldwide. Accor operates in 5,300 locations in over 110 countries. Its total capacity is approximately 777,714 rooms. It owns and operates brands in many segments of hospitality: Luxury (Raffles, Fairmont, Sofitel), premium (MGallery, Pullman, Swissôtel), midscale (Novotel, Mercure, Adagio), and economy (ibis, hotelF1). Accor also owns companies specialized in digital hospitality and event organization, such as onefinestay, D-Edge, ResDiary, John Paul, Potel & Chabot and Wojo. The company is headquartered in Issy-les-Moulineaux, France, and is a constituent of the CAC Next 20 index in the Paris stock exchange.

Figure 53: ACCOR SA Number of Brands (Worldwide)

Accor Sa has 44 different hotel brands and 5400 hotels in 110 countries. Accor Sa has identified hospitality market segments as below.

3. Economy
4. Midscale
5. Premium
6. Luxury
7. Lifestyle by Ennismore

It has 6 hotel brands in “economy” segment, 5 hotel brands in “midscale” segment, 10 hotel brands in “premium” segment, 8 hotel brands in “luxury” segment and 15 hotel brands in “lifestyle by Ennismore” segment. These brands are shown according to the segments in Table 32.

Table 32: Brands of ACCOR SA in Segments (Worldwide)

Economy	Midscale	Premium	Luxury	Lifestyle by Ennismore
BreakFree	Adagio	Angsana	Banyan Tree	About Ennismore
greet	Handwritten Collection	Art Series	Emblems	21c Museum Hotel
hotelF1	Mantra	Grand Mercure	Fairmont	25hours Hotels
ibis	Mercure	Mantis	onfinestay	Delano
ibis budget	Novotel	MGallery	Orient Express	Gleneagles
ibis Styles		Mövenpick	Raffles	Hyde

		Peppers	Rixos	JO&JOE
		Pullman	Sofitel	Mama Shelter
		Swissôtel		Mondrian
		The Sebel		Morgans Originals
				SLS
				SO/
				The Hoxton
				TRIBE
				Working From_

In Table 33, the hotels of Accor SA are given according to the cities and segments. Accor SA has 62 hotels in various cities of Türkiye. Most of the hotels are located in İstanbul, Antalya and Muğla. Accor SA bought Rixos Hotels which was a local hotel chain in 2017.⁹

Table 33: Brands of ACCOR SA in Segments (Türkiye)

CITY	HOTELS	SEGMENT
Adana	İbis Adana	Economy
Ankara	Mövenpick Ankara	Premium
Ankara	Downtown/Grand Mercure Ankara	Premium
Ankara	İbis Ankara Airport	Economy
Antalya	Rixos Downtown Antalya	Luxury
Antalya	Rixos Beldibi	Luxury
Antalya	Rixos Sungate	Luxury
Antalya	The Land of Legends Kingdom	Luxury
Antalya	Rixos Premium Belek	Luxury
Antalya	Club Prive by Rixos Belek	Luxury
Antalya	Rixos Premium Tekirova	Luxury
Bursa	Mövenpick Hotel and Thermal Spa Bursa	Premium
Bursa	İbis Bursa	Economy
Diyarbakır	Novotel Diyarbakır	Midscale
Gaziantep	İbis Gaziantep	Economy
Gaziantep	Novotel Gaziantep	Midscale
Eskişehir	İbis Eskişehir	Economy
İstanbul	Mercure İstanbul Sirkeci Hotel	Midscale
İstanbul	The Galata İstanbul Hotel - Mgallery	Premium

⁹ <https://www.turizmuncel.com/haber/rixos-etkisi-accor-her-sey-dahil-otel-sayisini-200e-cikaracak>

İstanbul	Novotel İstanbul Bosphorus	Midscale
İstanbul	Rixos Pera İstanbul	Luxury
İstanbul	Sofitel İstanbul Taksim	Luxury
İstanbul	The Artisan İstanbul Mgallery	Premium
İstanbul	Swissotel The Bosphorus İstanbul	Premium
İstanbul	Mercure İstanbul Bomonti	Midscale
İstanbul	Mercure İstanbul Altunizade	Midscale
İstanbul	İbis Styles İstanbul Bomonti	Economy
İstanbul	Mövenpick İstanbul Golden Horn	Premium
İstanbul	İbis İstanbul Zeytinburnu	Economy
İstanbul	Novotel İstanbul Zeytinburnu	Midscale
İstanbul	Fairmont Quasar İstanbul	Luxury
İstanbul	Mövenpick Hotel İstanbul Bosphorus	Premium
İstanbul	Raffles İstanbul	Luxury
İstanbul	İbis Styles İstanbul Merter	Economy
İstanbul	Mercure İstanbul Bakırköy	Midscale
İstanbul	İbis Styles İstanbul Ataşehir	Economy
İstanbul	Mercure İstanbul Ümraniye	Midscale
İstanbul	Mövenpick Living İstanbul Çamlıvadi	Premium
İstanbul	Mercure İstanbul West Hotel & Convention Center	Midscale
İstanbul	Pullman İstanbul Hotel & Convention Center	Premium
İstanbul	Mövenpick Living İstanbul	Premium
İstanbul	İbis İstanbul West	Economy
İstanbul	İbis İstanbul Esenyurt	Economy
İstanbul	Mövenpick Hotel İstanbul Asia Airport	Premium
İstanbul	İbis İstanbul Tuzla Hotel	Economy
İzmir	Mövenpick İzmir	Premium
İzmir	Swissotel Büyük Efes İzmir	Premium
İzmir	İbis İzmir Alsancak	Economy
İzmir	İbis Styles İzmir Bornova	Economy
Kayseri	İbis Kayseri	Economy
Kayseri	Novotel Kayseri	Midscale
Muğla	Rixos Premium Göcek Adult Only	Luxury
Muğla	Rixos Premium Bodrum	Luxury
Muğla	Mgallery The Bodrum Hotel Yalıkavak	Premium
Muğla	Swissotel Resort Bodrum Sahili	Premium
Muğla	Club Prive By Rixos Göcek	Luxury
Konya	Novotel Konya	Midscale
Konya	İbis Konya	Economy

Malatya	Mövenpick Malatya Hotel	Premium
Trabzon	Mövenpick Hotel Trabzon	Premium
Trabzon	Mercure Trabzon Hotel	Midscale
Trabzon	Novotel Trabzon	Midscale

Figure 54: ACCOR SA Number of Hotels According to Segments

Accor SA has been operating in four segments in Türkiye. These segments are “economy”, “midscale”, “premium” and “luxury”. It has 18 hotels in premium segment, 16 hotels in economy segment, 14 hotels in midscale segment and 14 hotels in luxury segments.

Table 34: Brands of ACCOR SA in Economy Segment (Türkiye)

CITY	HOTELS	SEGMENT
Adana	İbis Adana	Economy
Ankara	İbis Ankara Airport	Economy
Bursa	İbis Bursa	Economy
Gaziantep	İbis Gaziantep	Economy
Eskişehir	İbis Eskişehir	Economy
İstanbul	İbis Styles İstanbul Bomonti	Economy
İstanbul	İbis İstanbul Zeytinburnu	Economy
İstanbul	İbis Styles İstanbul Merter	Economy
İstanbul	İbis Styles İstanbul Ataşehir	Economy
İstanbul	İbis İstanbul West	Economy

İstanbul	İbis İstanbul Esenyurt	Economy
İstanbul	İbis İstanbul Tuzla Hotel	Economy
İzmir	İbis İzmir Alsancak	Economy
İzmir	İbis Styles İzmir Bornova	Economy
Kayseri	İbis Kayseri	Economy
Konya	İbis Konya	Economy

When we focus on the economy segment, it is seen that the hotels are located in big cities of Anatolia. These destinations do not have seashores, in other words they do not target tourists for sea, sun and sand.

Table 35: Brands of ACCOR SA in Luxury Segment (Türkiye)

CITY	HOTELS	SEGMENT
Antalya	Rixos Downtown Antalya	Luxury
Antalya	Rixos Beldibi	Luxury
Antalya	Rixos Sungate	Luxury
Antalya	The Land of Legends Kingdom	Luxury
Antalya	Rixos Premium Belek	Luxury
Antalya	Club Prive by Rixos Belek	Luxury
Antalya	Rixos Premium Tekirova	Luxury
İstanbul	Rixos Pera İstanbul	Luxury
İstanbul	Sofitel İstanbul Taksim	Luxury
İstanbul	Fairmont Quasar İstanbul	Luxury
İstanbul	Raffles İstanbul	Luxury
Muğla	Rixos Premium Göcek Adult Only	Luxury
Muğla	Rixos Premium Bodrum	Luxury
Muğla	Club Prive By Rixos Göcek	Luxury

When it is looked at the luxury segment, it is seen that the hotels are located in Antalya and Muğla which are the most important destinations especially for “sea, sun and sand” tourism segment.

Table 36: Brands of ACCOR SA in Midscale Segment (Türkiye)

CITY	HOTELS	SEGMENT
Diyarbakır	Novotel Diyarbakır	Midscale
Gaziantep	Novotel Gaziantep	Midscale
İstanbul	Mercure İstanbul Sirkeci Hotel	Midscale
İstanbul	Novotel İstanbul Bosphorus	Midscale
İstanbul	Mercure İstanbul Bomonti	Midscale
İstanbul	Mercure İstanbul Altunizade	Midscale
İstanbul	Novotel İstanbul Zeytinburnu	Midscale

İstanbul	Mercure İstanbul Bakırköy	Midscale
İstanbul	Mercure İstanbul Ümraniye	Midscale
İstanbul	Mercure İstanbul West Hotel & Convention Center	Midscale
Kayseri	Novotel Kayseri	Midscale
Konya	Novotel Konya	Midscale
Trabzon	Mercure Trabzon Hotel	Midscale
Trabzon	Novotel Trabzon	Midscale

The midscale segment of Accor SA consists of hotels mostly located in İstanbul. It also has hotels in two big cities of south-east anatolia region (Diyarbakır and Gaziantep), has hotels in two big cities of middle anatolia region and has hotels in one of the biggest cities of east blacksea region of Türkiye.

Table 37: Brands of ACCOR SA in Premium Segment (Türkiye)

CITY	HOTELS	SEGMENT
Ankara	Mövenpick Ankara	Premium
Ankara	Downtown/Grand Mercure Ankara	Premium
Bursa	Mövenpick Hotel and Thermal Spa Bursa	Premium
İstanbul	The Galata İstanbul Hotel - Mgallery	Premium
İstanbul	The Artisan İstanbul Mgallery	Premium
İstanbul	Swissotel The Bosphorus İstanbul	Premium
İstanbul	Mövenpick İstanbul Golden Horn	Premium
İstanbul	Mövenpick Hotel İstanbul Bosphorus	Premium
İstanbul	Mövenpick Living İstanbul Çamlıvadi	Premium
İstanbul	Pullman İstanbul Hotel & Convention Center	Premium
İstanbul	Mövenpick Living İstanbul	Premium
İstanbul	Mövenpick Hotel İstanbul Asia Airport	Premium
İzmir	Mövenpick İzmir	Premium
İzmir	Swissotel Büyük Efes İzmir	Premium
Muğla	Mgallery The Bodrum Hotel Yalıkavak	Premium
Muğla	Swissotel Resort Bodrum Sahili	Premium
Malatya	Mövenpick Malatya Hotel	Premium
Trabzon	Mövenpick Hotel Trabzon	Premium

Accor SA hotels offer value for the premium segment in various cities of Türkiye including İstanbul, Ankara, İzmir, Bursa and etc. These cities are the biggest four cities of Türkiye.

Figure 55: ACCOR SA Number of Hotels According to the Market Segments in Cities of Türkiye

2.1.1.3.2.2. InterContinental Hotel Group

InterContinental Hotels Group (IHG), marketed as IHG Hotels & Resorts, is a British multinational hospitality company headquartered in Windsor, England. It is listed on the London Stock Exchange and the New York Stock Exchange. It is also a constituent of the FTSE 100 Index.

Figure 56: IHG Number of Brands (Worldwide)

IHG has 18 different hotel brands and has hotels approximately in 6000 destinations. IHG has identified hospitality market segments as below.

8. Essentials
9. Premium
10. Luxury and Lifestyle
11. Suites Collection
12. Exclusive Partners

It has 3 hotel brands in “essentials” segment, 4 hotel brands in “premium” segment, 6 hotel brands in “luxury and lifestyle” segment, 4 hotel brands in “suites” segment and 1 hotel brand in “exclusive partners” segment. These brands are shown according to the segments in Table 38.

Table 38: Brands of IHG in Segments (Worldwide)

Luxury and Lifestyle	Premium	Essentials	Suites Collection	Exclusive Partners
SIX SENSES	VOCO	Holiday Inn Express	ATWELL SUITES	IBEROSTAR BEACHFRONT RESORTS
REGENT	HUALUXE	Holiday Inn	STAYBRIDGE SUITES	
INTERCONTINENTAL HOTELS&RESORTS	EVEN	avid	Holiday Inn Club Vacations	
VIGNETTE COLLECTION	CROWNE PLAZA		CANDLEWOOD SUITES	
KIMPTON HOTELS&RESTAURANTS				
HOTEL INDIGO				

In Table 39, the hotels of IHG are given according to the cities and segments. Accor SA has 28 hotels in various cities of Türkiye. Most of the hotels are located in İstanbul and Ankara.

Table 39: Brands of IHG in Segments (Türkiye)

CITY	HOTELS	SEGMENT
Ankara	Crowne Plaza Ankara	Premium
Ankara	Holiday Inn Express Ankara-Airport	Essentials
Ankara	Holiday Inn Ankara-Kavaklıdere	Essentials
Ankara	Holiday Inn Ankara-Çukurambar	Essentials
Antalya	Crowne Plaza Antalya	Premium
Antalya	Holiday Inn Antalya-Lara	Essentials
Bursa	Crowne Plaza Bursa	Premium
Bursa	Holiday Inn Bursa-City Centre	Essentials
Gaziantep	Holiday Inn Gaziantep-Şehitkamil	Essentials
İstanbul	Six Senses Kocatas Mansions İstanbul	Luxury and Lifestyle
İstanbul	Intercontinental İstanbul	Luxury and Lifestyle
İstanbul	Crowne Plaza İstanbul-Old City	Premium
İstanbul	Crowne Plaza İstanbul-Harbiye	Premium
İstanbul	Crowne Plaza İstanbul-Florya	Premium
İstanbul	Crowne Plaza İstanbul-Oryapark	Premium
İstanbul	Crowne Plaza İstanbul-Asia	Premium
İstanbul	Crowne Plaza İstanbul Tuzla Viaport Marina	Premium
İstanbul	Holiday Inn Express İstanbul-Altunizade	Essentials
İstanbul	Holiday Inn Express İstanbul-Ataköy Metro	Essentials
İstanbul	Holiday Inn İstanbul-Old City	Essentials
İstanbul	Holiday Inn İstanbul City	Essentials
İstanbul	Holiday Inn İstanbul-Şişli	Essentials

İstanbul	Holiday Inn İstanbul-Kadıköy	Essentials
İstanbul	Holiday Inn İstanbul-Tuzla Bay	Essentials
Kayseri	Holiday Inn Kayseri-Düvenönü	Essentials
Manisa	Holiday Inn Express Manisa-West	Essentials
Muğla	Six Senses Kaplankaya	Luxury and Lifestyle
Trabzon	Holiday Inn Trabzon-East	Essentials

IHG has been operating for three segments in Türkiye. These segments are named as “essentials”, “premium” and “luxury and lifestyle”. It has 16 hotels in essentials segment, 9 hotels in premium segment and 3 hotels in luxury and lifestyle segment.

Figure 57: IHG Number of Hotels in Türkiye According to Segments

When we focus on the essentials segment, it is seen that the hotels are located in big cities of Anatolia. Most of the hotels are located in İstanbul and Ankara.

Table 40: Brands of IHG in Essentials Segment (Türkiye)

CITY	HOTELS	SEGMENT
Ankara	Holiday Inn Express Ankara-Airport	Essentials
Ankara	Holiday Inn Ankara-Kavaklıdere	Essentials
Ankara	Holiday Inn Ankara-Çukurambar	Essentials
Antalya	Holiday Inn Antalya-Lara	Essentials
Bursa	Holiday Inn Bursa-City Centre	Essentials
Gaziantep	Holiday Inn Gaziantep-Şehitkamil	Essentials
İstanbul	Holiday Inn Express İstanbul-Altunizade	Essentials
İstanbul	Holiday Inn Express İstanbul-Ataköy Metro	Essentials
İstanbul	Holiday Inn İstanbul-Old City	Essentials
İstanbul	Holiday Inn İstanbul City	Essentials
İstanbul	Holiday Inn İstanbul-Şişli	Essentials
İstanbul	Holiday Inn İstanbul-Kadıköy	Essentials
İstanbul	Holiday Inn İstanbul-Tuzla Bay	Essentials
Kayseri	Holiday Inn Kayseri-Düvenönü	Essentials
Manisa	Holiday Inn Express Manisa-West	Essentials
Trabzon	Holiday Inn Trabzon-East	Essentials

IHG hotels offer value for the premium segment in various cities of Türkiye including İstanbul, Ankara, Antalya and Bursa.

Table 41: Brands of IHG in Premium Segment (Türkiye)

CITY	HOTELS	SEGMENT
Ankara	Crowne Plaza Ankara	Premium
Antalya	Crowne Plaza Antalya	Premium
Bursa	Crowne Plaza Bursa	Premium
İstanbul	Crowne Plaza İstanbul-Old City	Premium
İstanbul	Crowne Plaza İstanbul-Harbiye	Premium
İstanbul	Crowne Plaza İstanbul-Florya	Premium
İstanbul	Crowne Plaza İstanbul-Oryapark	Premium
İstanbul	Crowne Plaza İstanbul-Asia	Premium
İstanbul	Crowne Plaza İstanbul Tuzla Viaport Marina	Premium

When it is looked at the luxury and lifestyle segment, IHG has 3 hotels in İstanbul and Muğla.

Table 42: Brands of IHG in Luxury and Lifestyle Segment (Türkiye)

CITY	HOTELS	SEGMENT
İstanbul	Six Senses Kocatas Mansions İstanbul	Luxury and Lifestyle
İstanbul	Intercontinental İstanbul	Luxury and Lifestyle
Muğla	Six Senses Kaplankaya	Luxury and Lifestyle

Figure 58: IHG Number of Hotels According to the Market Segments in Cities of Türkiye

2.1.1.3.2.3. Marriott International

Marriott International, Inc. is an American multinational company that operates, franchises, and licenses lodging including hotel, residential and timeshare properties. It is headquartered in Bethesda, Maryland. The company was founded by J. Willard Marriott and his wife Alice Marriott. Marriott is the largest hotel chain in the world by the number of available rooms. It has 30 brands with 8,000 properties containing 1,423,044 rooms in 139 countries and territories. Of these 8,000 properties, 2,149 are operated by Marriott, and 5,493 are operated by others pursuant to franchise

agreements. The company also operates 20 hotel reservation centers. Marriott International, Inc. was formed in 1993 when Marriott Corporation split into two companies: Marriott International, Inc., which franchises and manages properties, and Host Marriott Corporation (now Host Hotels & Resorts), which owns properties.

Figure 59: MARRIOTT Segmentation (Worldwide)

Marriott International has five main market segments worldwide. Four of these segments are divided into two sub-segments also. These sub-segments are named as classic and distinctive. For example, luxury segment is divided into two sub-segments as distinctive luxury and classic luxury.

Figure 60: MARRIOTT Number of Brands According to Sub Segments (Worldwide)

Marriott has 31 hotel brands worldwide. Five of these brands are in the “classic select” segment, four of these brands are in the “distinctive luxury” segment, four of these brands are in the segment of “distinctive premium”, four of these brands are in the segment of “classic premium”. The distribution of Marriott hotel brands according to the segments are shown in Figure 60.

Table 43: Brands of Marriott in Segments (Türkiye)

CITY	HOTELS	SEGMENT	SUB-SEGMENT
Adana	Sheraton Grand Adana	Premium	Classic Premium
Ankara	JW Marriott Hotel Ankara	Luxury	Classic Luxury
Ankara	Lugal, a Luxury Collection Hotel, Ankara	Luxury	Distinctive Luxury
Ankara	Sheraton Ankara Hotel & Convention Center	Premium	Classic Premium
Bursa	Aloft Bursa Hotel	Select	Distinctive Select
Bursa	Sheraton Bursa Hotel	Premium	Classic Premium
İstanbul	JW Marriott İstanbul Bosphorus	Luxury	Classic Luxury
İstanbul	AC Hotel İstanbul Maçka	Select	Distinctive Select
İstanbul	Adahan DeCamondo Pera, Autograph Collection	Collections	Collections
İstanbul	Burdock Hotel İstanbul, Autograph Collection	Collections	Collections
İstanbul	Courtyard İstanbul West	Select	Classic Select

İstanbul	Delta Hotels İstanbul Kağıthane	Premium	Classic Premium
İstanbul	Delta Hotels İstanbul Levent	Premium	Classic Premium
İstanbul	JW Marriott Hotel İstanbul Marmara Sea	Luxury	Classic Luxury
İstanbul	Marriott Executive Apartments İstanbul Fulya	Longer Stays	Classic Longer Stays
İstanbul	İstanbul Marriot Hotel Asia	Premium	Classic Premium
İstanbul	İstanbul Marriott Hotel Şişli	Premium	Classic Premium
İstanbul	Renaissance İstanbul Polat Bosphorus Hotel	Premium	Distinctive Premium
İstanbul	Renaissance Polat İstanbul Hotel	Premium	Distinctive Premium
İstanbul	Residence Inn İstanbul Ataşehir	Longer Stays	Classic Longer Stays
İstanbul	The Ritz-Carlton İstanbul	Luxury	Classic Luxury
İstanbul	Gezi Hotel Bosphorus, İstanbul, a Member of Design Hotels	Collections	Collections
İstanbul	The Bank Hotel İstanbul, a Member of Design Hotels	Collections	Collections
İstanbul	Four Points by Sheraton İstanbul Kağıthane	Select	Distinctive Select
İstanbul	Le Meridien İstanbul Etiler	Premium	Distinctive Premium
İstanbul	Sheraton Grand İstanbul Ataşehir	Premium	Classic Premium
İstanbul	Sheraton İstanbul Ataköy Hotel	Premium	Classic Premium
İstanbul	Sheraton İstanbul City Center	Premium	Classic Premium
İstanbul	Sheraton İstanbul Esenyurt	Premium	Classic Premium
İstanbul	Sheraton İstanbul Levent	Premium	Classic Premium
İstanbul	The St. Regis İstanbul	Luxury	Classic Luxury
İstanbul	DeCamondo Galata, a Tribute Portfolio Hotel	Collections	Collections
İstanbul	W İstanbul	Luxury	Distinctive Luxury
İstanbul	The Westin İstanbul Nişantaşı	Premium	Distinctive Premium
İstanbul	Orientbank Hotel İstanbul, Autograph Collection	Collections	Collections
İzmir	İzmir Marriott Hotel	Premium	Classic Premium
İzmir	Renaissance İzmir Hotel	Premium	Distinctive Premium
İzmir	Four Points by Sheraton İzmir	Select	Distinctive Select
İzmir	Reges, a Luxury Collection Resort&Spa Çeşme	Luxury	Distinctive Luxury
Muğla	The Bodrum EDITION	Luxury	Distinctive Luxury
Muğla	Le Meridien Bodrum Beach Resort	Premium	Distinctive Premium
Muğla	Caresse, a Luxury Collection Resort &Spa Bodrum	Luxury	Distinctive Luxury
Samsun	Sheraton Grand Samsun Hotel	Premium	Classic Premium

Marriott has 43 hotels in Türkiye. They are located in seven cities of Türkiye. 29 of these hotels are in İstanbul. Marriott has nine sub-segments worldwide and it has hotels for eight of these segments in Türkiye. Half of its hotels are in the “classic premium” segment in Türkiye. Distribution of these hotels according to segments are shown in Figure 61.

Figure 61: MARRIOTT Number of Hotels in Türkiye According to Segments

The city and hotel names are given in tables according to the segment below. There are five hotels in the classic luxury segment. Four of them are located in İstanbul. There are five hotels in the distinctive luxury segment. Most of them are located at the seashores.

Table 44: Brands of Marriott in Classic Luxury Sub Segment (Türkiye)

CITY	HOTELS	SEGMENT	SUB-SEGMENT
Ankara	JW Marriott Hotel Ankara	Luxury	Classic Luxury
İstanbul	JW Marriott İstanbul Bosphorus	Luxury	Classic Luxury
İstanbul	JW Marriott Hotel İstanbul Marmara Sea	Luxury	Classic Luxury
İstanbul	The Ritz-Carlton İstanbul	Luxury	Classic Luxury
İstanbul	The St. Regis İstanbul	Luxury	Classic Luxury

Table 45: Brands of Marriott in Distinctive Luxury Sub Segment (Türkiye)

CITY	HOTELS	SEGMENT	SUB-SEGMENT
Ankara	Lugal, a Luxury Collection Hotel, Ankara	Luxury	Distinctive Luxury
Muğla	The Bodrum EDITION	Luxury	Distinctive Luxury
Muğla	Caresse, a Luxury Collection Resort & Spa Bodrum	Luxury	Distinctive Luxury
İstanbul	W İstanbul	Luxury	Distinctive Luxury
İzmir	Reges, a Luxury Collection Resort&Spa Çeşme	Luxury	Distinctive Luxury

There are fourteen hotels in the classic premium segment. Most of them are in İstanbul as seen in Table 46.

Table 46: Brands of Marriott in Classic Premium Sub Segment (Türkiye)

CITY	HOTELS	SEGMENT	SUB-SEGMENT
Adana	Sheraton Grand Adana	Premium	Classic Premium
Ankara	Sheraton Ankara Hotel & Convention Center	Premium	Classic Premium
Bursa	Sheraton Bursa Hotel	Premium	Classic Premium
İstanbul	Delta Hotels İstanbul Kağıthane	Premium	Classic Premium
İstanbul	Delta Hotels İstanbul Levent	Premium	Classic Premium
İstanbul	İstanbul Marriot Hotel Asia	Premium	Classic Premium
İstanbul	İstanbul Marriott Hotel Şişli	Premium	Classic Premium
İstanbul	Sheraton Grand İstanbul Ataşehir	Premium	Classic Premium
İstanbul	Sheraton İstanbul Ataköy Hotel	Premium	Classic Premium
İstanbul	Sheraton İstanbul City Center	Premium	Classic Premium
İstanbul	Sheraton İstanbul Esenyurt	Premium	Classic Premium
İstanbul	Sheraton İstanbul Levent	Premium	Classic Premium
İzmir	İzmir Marriott Hotel	Premium	Classic Premium
Samsun	Sheraton Grand Samsun Hotel	Premium	Classic Premium

There are six hotels in the distinctive premium segment. Most of them are located in İstanbul like other segments.

Table 47: Brands of Marriott in Distinctive Premium Sub Segment (Türkiye)

CITY	HOTELS	SEGMENT	SUB-SEGMENT
Muğla	Le Meridien Bodrum Beach Resort	Premium	Distinctive Premium
İstanbul	Renaissance İstanbul Polat Bosphorus Hotel	Premium	Distinctive Premium
İstanbul	Renaissance Polat İstanbul Hotel	Premium	Distinctive Premium
İstanbul	Le Meridien İstanbul Etiler	Premium	Distinctive Premium
İstanbul	The Westin İstanbul Nişantaşı	Premium	Distinctive Premium
İzmir	Renaissance İzmir Hotel	Premium	Distinctive Premium

Marriott has also hotels for classic select, distinctive select, classic longer stays and collections segments. Detailed information is given in the tables below.

Table 48: Brands of Marriott in Classic Select Sub Segment (Türkiye)

CITY	HOTELS	SEGMENT	SUB-SEGMENT
İstanbul	Courtyard İstanbul West	Select	Classic Select

Table 49: Brands of Marriott in Distinctive Select Sub Segment (Türkiye)

CITY	HOTELS	SEGMENT	SUB-SEGMENT
Bursa	Aloft Bursa Hotel	Select	Distinctive Select
İstanbul	AC Hotel İstanbul Maçka	Select	Distinctive Select
İstanbul	Four Points by Sheraton İstanbul Kağıthane	Select	Distinctive Select
İzmir	Four Points by Sheraton İzmir	Select	Distinctive Select

Table 50: Brands of Marriott in Classic Longer Stays (Türkiye)

CITY	HOTELS	SEGMENT	SUB-SEGMENT
İstanbul	Marriott Executive Apartments İstanbul Fulya	Longer Stays	Classic Longer Stays
İstanbul	Residence Inn İstanbul Ataşehir	Longer Stays	Classic Longer Stays

Table 51: Brands of Marriott in Collections Sub Segment (Türkiye)

CITY	HOTELS	SEGMENT	SUB-SEGMENT
İstanbul	Adahan DeCamondo Pera, Autograph Collection	Collections	Collections
İstanbul	Burdock Hotel İstanbul, Autograph Collection	Collections	Collections
İstanbul	Gezi Hotel Bosphorus, İstanbul, a Member of Design Hotels	Collections	Collections
İstanbul	The Bank Hotel İstanbul, a Member of Design Hotels	Collections	Collections
İstanbul	DeCamondo Galata, a Tribute Portfolio Hotel	Collections	Collections
İstanbul	Orientbank Hotel İstanbul, Autograph Collection	Collections	Collections

Figure 62: Marriott Number of Hotels According to the Market Segments in Cities of Türkiye

2.1.1.3.2.4. Wyndham Hotels and Resorts Inc.

Wyndham Hotels & Resorts, Inc. is an American hotel company based in Parsippany, New Jersey, United States. It describes itself as the largest hotel franchisor in the world, with 9,280 locations. It has a portfolio of 20 hotel brands, including Baymont, Days Inn, Howard Johnson, La Quinta, Ramada, Super 8, Travelodge, and Wyndham. The company was formed on June 1, 2018, as a spin-off from Wyndham Worldwide, which is now known as Travel + Leisure.

Figure 63: Wyndham Number of Brands According to Segments (Worldwide)

Wyndham has 103 hotels in Türkiye. 33 of these hotels are located in İstanbul. Wyndham has six segments worldwide and it has hotels for all of these segments in Türkiye. Distribution of these hotels according to segments are shown in Table 52.

Table 52: Brands of Marriott in Segments (Türkiye)

CITY	HOTELS	SEGMENT
Adiyaman	Ramada by Wyndham Adiyaman	Midscale
Ankara	Days Hotel by Wyndham Ankara Cankaya	Economy
Ankara	Ramada by Wyndham Ankara	Midscale
Ankara	TRYP by Wyndham Ankara Oran	Lifestyle
Ankara	Wyndham Ankara	Upscale

Antalya	Ramada Plaza by Wyndham Antalya	Midscale
Antalya	Ramada Resort by Wyndham Lara	Midscale
Antalya	Ramada Resort by Wyndham Side	Midscale
Antalya	Wyndham Garden Lara	Midscale
Aydın	Ramada Resort by Wyndham Akbük	Midscale
Aydın	Wyndham Residences Kuşadası Golf and Spa	Upscale
Balıkesir	Ramada Residences by Wyndham Balıkesir	Midscale
Balıkesir	Ramada Resort by Wyndham Kazdağları Thermal and Spa	Midscale
Bodrum	La Quinta by Wyndham Bodrum	Midscale
Bodrum	Ramada Resort by Wyndham Bodrum	Midscale
Bozbuğ	Ramada Residences by Wyndham Bozbuğ	Midscale
Bursa	Ramada by Wyndham Bursa Nilüfer	Midscale
Bursa	Ramada by Wyndham Bursa Çekirge Thermal and Spa	Midscale
Bursa	Ramada by Wyndham Gemlik	Midscale
Diyarbakır	Ramada by Wyndham Diyarbakır	Midscale
Diyarbakır	Wyndham Garden Diyarbakır	Midscale
Edirne	Ramada Hotel & Suites by Wyndham Edirne	Midscale
Elazığ	Ramada by Wyndham Elazığ	Midscale
Erzurum	Ramada by Wyndham Erzurum	Midscale
Eskişehir	Ramada Encore by Wyndham Eskişehir	Midscale
Eskişehir	Ramada Plaza by Wyndham Eskişehir	Midscale
Gebze	Ramada Encore by Wyndham Gebze	Midscale
Giresun	La Quinta by Wyndham Giresun	Midscale
Giresun	Ramada by Wyndham Giresun Piraziz	Midscale
Gümüşhane	Ramada by Wyndham Gümüşhane	Midscale
Hatay	Ramada by Wyndham İskenderun	Midscale
Hendek	Ramada by Wyndham Sakarya Hendek	Midscale
Isparta	Ramada by Wyndham Isparta	Midscale
İstanbul	Days Hotel by Wyndham İstanbul Esenyurt	Economy
İstanbul	Days Hotel by Wyndham İstanbul Maltepe	Economy
İstanbul	İstanbul New Airport Hotel Trademark Collection by Wyndham	Upscale
İstanbul	La Quinta by Wyndham İstanbul Güneşli	Midscale
İstanbul	Ramada Encore by Wyndham İstanbul Basın Express	Midscale
İstanbul	Ramada Encore by Wyndham İstanbul Avcılar	Midscale
İstanbul	Ramada Encore by Wyndham İstanbul Bayrampaşa	Midscale
İstanbul	Ramada Encore by Wyndham İstanbul Kartal	Midscale
İstanbul	Ramada by Wyndham Beylikdüzü	Midscale
İstanbul	Ramada by Wyndham İstanbul Alibeyköy	Midscale
İstanbul	Ramada by Wyndham İstanbul Florya	Midscale
İstanbul	Ramada by Wyndham İstanbul Golden Horn	Midscale
İstanbul	Ramada by Wyndham İstanbul Grand Bazaar	Midscale
İstanbul	Ramada by Wyndham İstanbul Old City	Midscale
İstanbul	Ramada by Wyndham İstanbul Şile	Midscale
İstanbul	Ramada by Wyndham İstanbul Taksim	Midscale
İstanbul	Ramada Hotel & Suites by Wyndham İstanbul Merter	Midscale
İstanbul	Ramada Hotel & Suites by Wyndham İstanbul Şişli	Midscale
İstanbul	Ramada Plaza by Wyndham İstanbul Ataköy	Midscale

İstanbul	Ramada Plaza by Wyndham İstanbul City Center	Midscale
İstanbul	Ramada Plaza by Wyndham İstanbul Sultanahmet	Midscale
İstanbul	Ramada Plaza by Wyndham İstanbul Tekstilkent	Midscale
İstanbul	Ramada Plaza by Wyndham Silivri	Midscale
İstanbul	TRYP by Wyndham İstanbul Şişli Hotel	Lifestyle
İstanbul	TRYP by Wyndham İstanbul Basın Express	Lifestyle
İstanbul	TRYP by Wyndham İstanbul Taksim	Lifestyle
İstanbul	TRYP by Wyndham İstanbul Sancaktepe	Lifestyle
İstanbul	TRYP by Wyndham İstanbul Ataşehir	Lifestyle
İstanbul	TRYP by Wyndham İstanbul Topkapı	Lifestyle
İstanbul	Wyndham Grand İstanbul Europe	Distinctive
İstanbul	Wyndham Grand İstanbul Kalamış Marina Hotel	Distinctive
İstanbul	Wyndham Grand İstanbul Levent	Distinctive
İstanbul	Ramada by Wyndham İstanbul Ümraniye	Midscale
İzmir	Ramada Encore by Wyndham İzmir	Midscale
İzmir	Ramada Hotel & Suites by Wyndham İzmir Kemalpaşa	Midscale
İzmir	Ramada Plaza by Wyndham İzmir	Midscale
İzmir	Ramada by Wyndham İzmir Aliağa	Midscale
İzmir	Ramada by Wyndham Tire	Midscale
İzmir	Wyndham Grand İzmir Özdilek	Distinctive
İzmit	Ramada Plaza by Wyndham İzmit	Midscale
Kahramanmaraş	Ramada by Wyndham Elbistan	Midscale
Kahramanmaraş	Ramada Plaza by Wyndham Kahramanmaraş	Midscale
Kayseri	Wyndham Grand Kayseri	Distinctive
Kocaeli	Ramada Plaza by Wyndham İstanbul Asia Airport	Midscale
Kocaeli	TRYP by Wyndham İzmit	Lifestyle
Konya	Ramada Plaza by Wyndham Konya	Midscale
Konya	Ramada by Wyndham Karapınar	Midscale
Kuşadası	Ramada Hotel & Suites by Wyndham Kuşadası	Midscale
Kuşadası	Ramada Resort by Wyndham Kuşadası	Midscale
Malatya	Ramada Plaza by Wyndham Malatya Altın Kayısı	Midscale
Mardin	Ramada Plaza by Wyndham Mardin	Midscale
Mersin	Ramada Resort by Wyndham Kızkalesi	Midscale
Mersin	Ramada by Wyndham Mersin	Midscale
Nevşehir	Ramada by Wyndham Kapadokya	Midscale
Niğde	Ramada by Wyndham Niğde	Midscale
Ordu	Ramada Plaza by Wyndham Ordu	Midscale
Ordu	Ramada Resort by Wyndham Ünye	Midscale
Rize	Ramada Plaza by Wyndham Rize	Midscale
Rize	Ramada by Wyndham Rize Fındıklı	Midscale
Sakarya	Ramada by Wyndham Sakarya	Midscale
Samsun	Ramada Plaza by Wyndham Samsun	Midscale
Sivas	Ramada by Wyndham Sivas	Midscale
Soma	Ramada by Wyndham Soma	Midscale
Tekirdağ	Hawthorn Suites by Wyndham Çerkezköy	Extended Stay
Tekirdağ	Ramada by Wyndham Tekirdağ	Midscale
Tekirdağ	Wyndham Çerkezköy	Upscale

Trabzon	Ramada Plaza by Wyndham Trabzon	Midscale
Uşak	Ramada by Wyndham Uşak	Midscale
Van	Ramada by Wyndham Van	Midscale
Yalova	Ramada by Wyndham Yalova	Midscale

Wyndham has 103 hotels for six different segments in Türkiye. 82 of these hotels are in the midscale segment. The distribution of these hotels are given in Figure 64.

Figure 64: Wyndham Number of Hotels in Türkiye According to Segments

The distribution of the hotels according to the segments is given in the Tables below.

Table 53: Brands of Wyndham in Distinctive Segment (Türkiye)

CITY	HOTELS	SEGMENT
İstanbul	Wyndham Grand İstanbul Europe	Distinctive
İstanbul	Wyndham Grand İstanbul Kalamış Marina Hotel	Distinctive
İstanbul	Wyndham Grand İstanbul Levent	Distinctive
İzmir	Wyndham Grand İzmir Özdilek	Distinctive
Kayseri	Wyndham Grand Kayseri	Distinctive

Table 54: Brands of Wyndham in Upscale Segment (Türkiye)

CITY	HOTELS	SEGMENT
Ankara	Wyndham Ankara	Upscale
Aydın	Wyndham Residences Kuşadası Golf and Spa	Upscale
İstanbul	İstanbul New Airport Hotel Trademark Collection by Wyndham	Upscale
Tekirdağ	Wyndham Çerkezköy	Upscale

Table 55: Brands of Wyndham in Lifestyle Segment (Türkiye)

CITY	HOTELS	SEGMENT
Ankara	TRYP by Wyndham Ankara Oran	Lifestyle
İstanbul	TRYP by Wyndham İstanbul Şişli Hotel	Lifestyle
İstanbul	TRYP by Wyndham İstanbul Basın Express	Lifestyle
İstanbul	TRYP by Wyndham İstanbul Taksim	Lifestyle
İstanbul	TRYP by Wyndham İstanbul Sancaktepe	Lifestyle
İstanbul	TRYP by Wyndham İstanbul Ataşehir	Lifestyle
İstanbul	TRYP by Wyndham İstanbul Topkapı	Lifestyle
Kocaeli	TRYP by Wyndham İzmit	Lifestyle

Table 56: Brands of Wyndham in Midscale Segment (Türkiye)

CITY	HOTELS	SEGMENT
Adıyaman	Ramada by Wyndham Adıyaman	Midscale
Ankara	Ramada by Wyndham Ankara	Midscale
Antalya	Ramada Plaza by Wyndham Antalya	Midscale
Antalya	Ramada Resort by Wyndham Lara	Midscale
Antalya	Ramada Resort by Wyndham Side	Midscale
Antalya	Wyndham Garden Lara	Midscale
Aydın	Ramada Resort by Wyndham Akbük	Midscale
Balıkesir	Ramada Residences by Wyndham Balıkesir	Midscale
Balıkesir	Ramada Resort by Wyndham Kazdağları Thermal and Spa	Midscale
Bodrum	La Quinta by Wyndham Bodrum	Midscale
Bodrum	Ramada Resort by Wyndham Bodrum	Midscale
Bozbuğ	Ramada Residences by Wyndham Bozbuğ	Midscale
Bursa	Ramada by Wyndham Bursa Nilüfer	Midscale
Bursa	Ramada by Wyndham Bursa Çekirge Thermal and Spa	Midscale
Bursa	Ramada by Wyndham Gemlik	Midscale
Diyarbakır	Ramada by Wyndham Diyarbakır	Midscale

Diyarbakır	Wyndham Garden Diyarbakır	Midscale
Edirne	Ramada Hotel & Suites by Wyndham Edirne	Midscale
Elazığ	Ramada by Wyndham Elazığ	Midscale
Erzurum	Ramada by Wyndham Erzurum	Midscale
Eskişehir	Ramada Encore by Wyndham Eskişehir	Midscale
Eskişehir	Ramada Plaza by Wyndham Eskişehir	Midscale
Gebze	Ramada Encore by Wyndham Gebze	Midscale
Giresun	La Quinta by Wyndham Giresun	Midscale
Giresun	Ramada by Wyndham Giresun Piraziz	Midscale
Gümüşhane	Ramada by Wyndham Gümüşhane	Midscale
Hatay	Ramada by Wyndham İskenderun	Midscale
Hendek	Ramada by Wyndham Sakarya Hendek	Midscale
Isparta	Ramada by Wyndham Isparta	Midscale
İstanbul	La Quinta by Wyndham İstanbul Güneşli	Midscale
İstanbul	Ramada Encore by Wyndham İstanbul Basın Express	Midscale
İstanbul	Ramada Encore by Wyndham İstanbul Avcılar	Midscale
İstanbul	Ramada Encore by Wyndham İstanbul Bayrampaşa	Midscale
İstanbul	Ramada Encore by Wyndham İstanbul Kartal	Midscale
İstanbul	Ramada by Wyndham Beylikdüzü	Midscale
İstanbul	Ramada by Wyndham İstanbul Alibeyköy	Midscale
İstanbul	Ramada by Wyndham İstanbul Florya	Midscale
İstanbul	Ramada by Wyndham İstanbul Golden Horn	Midscale
İstanbul	Ramada by Wyndham İstanbul Grand Bazaar	Midscale
İstanbul	Ramada by Wyndham İstanbul Old City	Midscale
İstanbul	Ramada by Wyndham İstanbul Şile	Midscale
İstanbul	Ramada by Wyndham İstanbul Taksim	Midscale
İstanbul	Ramada Hotel & Suites by Wyndham İstanbul Merter	Midscale
İstanbul	Ramada Hotel & Suites by Wyndham İstanbul Şişli	Midscale
İstanbul	Ramada Plaza by Wyndham İstanbul Ataköy	Midscale
İstanbul	Ramada Plaza by Wyndham İstanbul City Center	Midscale
İstanbul	Ramada Plaza by Wyndham İstanbul Sultanahmet	Midscale
İstanbul	Ramada Plaza by Wyndham İstanbul Tekstilkent	Midscale
İstanbul	Ramada Plaza by Wyndham Silivri	Midscale
İstanbul	Ramada by Wyndham İstanbul Ümraniye	Midscale
İzmir	Ramada Encore by Wyndham İzmir	Midscale
İzmir	Ramada Hotel & Suites by Wyndham İzmir Kemalpaşa	Midscale
İzmir	Ramada Plaza by Wyndham İzmir	Midscale
İzmir	Ramada by Wyndham İzmir Aliağa	Midscale
İzmir	Ramada by Wyndham Tire	Midscale
İzmit	Ramada Plaza by Wyndham İzmit	Midscale
Kahramanmaraş	Ramada by Wyndham Elbistan	Midscale
Kahramanmaraş	Ramada Plaza by Wyndham Kahramanmaraş	Midscale
Kocaeli	Ramada Plaza by Wyndham İstanbul Asia Airport	Midscale
Konya	Ramada Plaza by Wyndham Konya	Midscale
Konya	Ramada by Wyndham Karapınar	Midscale
Kuşadası	Ramada Hotel & Suites by Wyndham Kuşadası	Midscale
Kuşadası	Ramada Resort by Wyndham Kuşadası	Midscale

Malatya	Ramada Plaza by Wyndham Malatya Altın Kayısı	Midscale
Mardin	Ramada Plaza by Wyndham Mardin	Midscale
Mersin	Ramada Resort by Wyndham Kızıkalesi	Midscale
Mersin	Ramada by Wyndham Mersin	Midscale
Nevşehir	Ramada by Wyndham Kapadokya	Midscale
Niğde	Ramada by Wyndham Niğde	Midscale
Ordu	Ramada Plaza by Wyndham Ordu	Midscale
Ordu	Ramada Resort by Wyndham Ünye	Midscale
Rize	Ramada Plaza by Wyndham Rize	Midscale
Rize	Ramada by Wyndham Rize Fındıklı	Midscale
Sakarya	Ramada by Wyndham Sakarya	Midscale
Samsun	Ramada Plaza by Wyndham Samsun	Midscale
Sivas	Ramada by Wyndham Sivas	Midscale
Soma	Ramada by Wyndham Soma	Midscale
Tekirdağ	Ramada by Wyndham Tekirdağ	Midscale
Trabzon	Ramada Plaza by Wyndham Trabzon	Midscale
Uşak	Ramada by Wyndham Uşak	Midscale
Van	Ramada by Wyndham Van	Midscale
Yalova	Ramada by Wyndham Yalova	Midscale

Table 57: Brands of Wyndham in Economy Segment (Türkiye)

CITY	HOTELS	SEGMENT
Ankara	Days Hotel by Wyndham Ankara Cankaya	Economy
İstanbul	Days Hotel by Wyndham İstanbul Esenyurt	Economy
İstanbul	Days Hotel by Wyndham İstanbul Maltepe	Economy

Table 58: Brands of Wyndham in Extended Stay Segment (Türkiye)

CITY	HOTELS	SEGMENT
Tekirdağ	Hawthorn Suites by Wyndham Çerkezköy	Extended Stay

Figure 65: Wyndham Number of Hotels According to the Market Segments in Cities of Türkiye

2.1.1.3.2.5. Hilton Hotels and Resorts

Hilton Hotels & Resorts (formerly known as Hilton Hotels) is a global brand of full-service hotels and resorts and the flagship brand of American multinational hospitality company Hilton. The original company was founded by Conrad Hilton. As of December 30, 2019, 584 Hilton Hotels & Resorts properties with 216,379 rooms in 94 countries and territories are located across six continents. This includes 61 properties that are owned or leased with 219,264 rooms, 272 that are managed with 119,612 rooms, and 251 that are franchised with 77,451 rooms. In 2020, Fortune magazine ranked Hilton

Hotels & Resorts at number one on their Fortune List of the Top 100 Companies to Work for in 2020 based on an employee survey of satisfaction.

Figure 66: Hilton Number of Brands According to Segments (Worldwide)

Hilton Hotels and Resorts has 77 hotels in Türkiye. It proposes value for seven market segments with 19 brands worldwide. It has three brands for luxurious getaways segment, one brand for local escapes segment, two brands for premium experiences segment, two brands for curated collections, three brands for a suite for every guest, four brands for elevated essentials and one brand for vacation ownership.

Table 59: Brands of Hilton in Segments (Worldwide)

BRANDS	SEGMENT
Waldorf Astoria Hotels&Resorts	Luxurious getaways
LXR Hotels & Resorts	Luxurious getaways
CONRAD Hotels & Resorts	Luxurious getaways
Canopy by Hilton	Local escapes
Signia by Hilton	Premium experiences
Hilton Hotels&Resorts	Premium experiences
CURIO COLLECTION by Hilton	Curated collections
DOUBLETREE by Hilton	Premium experiences
TAPESTRY COLLECTION by Hilton	Curated collections
EMBASS SUITES by Hilton	A suite for every guest
TEMPO by Hilton	Local escapes
MOTTO by Hilton	Local escapes
Hilton Garden Inn	Elevated essentials

Hampton by Hilton	Elevated essentials
tru by Hilton	Elevated essentials
spark by Hilton	Elevated essentials
HOMEWOOD SUITES by Hilton	A suite for every guest
HOME2 SUITES by Hilton	A suite for every guest
Hilton GRAND VACATIONS	Vacation ownership

Table 60: Brands of Hilton in Segments (Türkiye)

CITY	HOTELS	SEGMENT
Adana	Adana HiltonSA	Premium experiences
Adana	DoubleTree by Hilton Adana	Premium experiences
Afyonkarahisar	DoubleTree by Hilton Afyonkarahisar	Premium experiences
Ankara	Ankara HiltonSA	Premium experiences
Ankara	Hilton Garden Inn Ankara Dikmen	Elevated essentials
Ankara	Hilton Garden Inn Ankara Gimat	Elevated essentials
Ankara	DoubleTree by Hilton Ankara İncek	Premium experiences
Antalya	DoubleTree by Hilton Antalya City Centre	Premium experiences
Antalya	DoubleTree by Hilton Antalya-Kemer	Premium experiences
Nevşehir	DoubleTree by Hilton Avanos - Kapadokya	Premium experiences
Balıkesir	Hilton Garden Inn Balıkesir	Elevated essentials
İzmir	Hilton Garden Inn İzmir Bayraklı	Elevated essentials
İzmir	DoubleTree by Hilton İzmir Alsancak	Premium experiences
İzmir	DoubleTree by Hilton İzmir Airport	Premium experiences
Manisa	DoubleTree by Hilton Manisa	Premium experiences
İzmir	Hampton by Hilton İzmir Aliağa	Elevated essentials
Aydın	DoubleTree by Hilton Kuşadası	Premium experiences
Muğla	DoubleTree by Hilton Bodrum Marina Vista	Premium experiences
Muğla	DoubleTree by Hilton Bodrum Işıl Club Resort	Premium experiences
Muğla	Susona Bodrum LXR Hotels&Resorts	Luxurious getaways
Muğla	The Bo Vue Hotel Bodrum Curio Collection by Hilton	Curated collections
Bolu	Hampton by Hilton Bolu	Elevated essentials
Bursa	Hampton by Hilton Bursa	Elevated essentials
Bursa	Hilton Bursa Convention Center&Spa	Premium experiences
Elazığ	DoubleTree by Hilton Elazığ	Premium experiences
Erzincan	Hilton Garden Inn Erzincan	Elevated essentials
Erzurum	Hilton Garden Inn Erzurum	Elevated essentials
Eskişehir	Hilton Garden Inn Eskişehir	Elevated essentials
Kütahya	Hilton Garden Inn Kütahya	Elevated essentials
Gaziantep	Hampton by Hilton Gaziantep	Elevated essentials

Gaziantep	DoubleTree by Hilton Gaziantep	Premium experiences
Hakkari	DoubleTree by Hilton Yüksekova	Premium experiences
Isparta	Hilton Garden Inn Isparta	Elevated essentials
İstanbul	DoubleTree by Hilton İstanbul-Old Town	Premium experiences
İstanbul	DoubleTree by Hilton İstanbul-Sirkeci	Premium experiences
İstanbul	Hampton by Hilton İstanbul Old City	Elevated essentials
İstanbul	Hagia Sofia Mansions İstanbul Curio Collection by Hilton	Luxurious getaways
İstanbul	DoubleTree by Hilton İstanbul Piyalepaşa	Premium experiences
İstanbul	DoubleTree by Hilton İstanbul Topkapı	Premium experiences
İstanbul	Hilton İstanbul Bosphorus	Premium experiences
İstanbul	Hampton by Hilton İstanbul Zeytinburnu	Elevated essentials
İstanbul	Hilton İstanbul Bomonti Hotel&Conference Center	Premium experiences
İstanbul	Conrad İstanbul Bosphorus	Luxurious getaways
İstanbul	DoubleTree by Hilton İstanbul Moda	Premium experiences
İstanbul	DoubleTree by Hilton İstanbul Esentepe	Premium experiences
İstanbul	Hilton İstanbul Bakırköy	Premium experiences
İstanbul	Hampton by Hilton İstanbul Ataköy	Elevated essentials
İstanbul	Hilton İstanbul Kozyatağı	Premium experiences
İstanbul	Hilton İstanbul Maslak	Premium experiences
İstanbul	DoubleTree by Hilton İstanbul Ümraniye	Premium experiences
İstanbul	Hilton Garden Inn İstanbul Atatürk Airport	Elevated essentials
İstanbul	Hilton Mall of İstanbul	Premium experiences
İstanbul	Hampton by Hilton İstanbul Kayaşehir	Elevated essentials
İstanbul	DoubleTree by Hilton İstanbul Avcılar	Premium experiences
İstanbul	Hilton Garden Inn İstanbul Beylikdüzü	Elevated essentials
İstanbul	Hampton by Hilton İstanbul Arnavutköy	Elevated essentials
İstanbul	Hampton by Hilton İstanbul Kurtköy	Elevated essentials
İstanbul	DoubleTree by Hilton İstanbul Tuzla	Premium experiences
Kocaeli	Hilton Garden Inn Kocaeli Şekerpınar	Elevated essentials
Yalova	Hilton Garden Inn Yalova	Elevated essentials
Tekirdağ	Hampton by Hilton Çerkezköy	Elevated essentials
Kahramanmaraş	Hampton by Hilton Kahramanmaraş	Elevated essentials
Konya	Hilton Garden Inn Konya	Elevated essentials
İzmir	DoubleTree by Hilton Çeşme Alaçatı Beach Resort	Premium experiences
Mardin	Hilton Garden Inn Mardin	Elevated essentials
Mersin	Mersin HiltonSA	Premium experiences
Muğla	Hilton Dalaman Sarigerme Resort &Spa	Premium experiences
Ordu	Hampton by Hilton Ordu	Elevated essentials
Bartın	Hilton Garden Inn Safranbolu	Elevated essentials

Samsun	Hampton by Hilton Samsun	Elevated essentials
Tekirdağ	Hilton Garden Inn Çorlu	Elevated essentials
Çanakkale	Hampton by Hilton Çanakkale Gallipoli	Elevated essentials
Trabzon	DoubleTree by Hilton Trabzon	Premium experiences
Van	DoubleTree by Hilton Van	Premium experiences
Çanakkale	DoubleTree by Hilton Çanakkale	Premium experiences
Şanlıurfa	Hilton Garden Inn Şanlıurfa	Elevated essentials
Şanlıurfa	DoubleTree by Hilton Şanlıurfa	Premium experiences

Figure 67: Hilton Number of Hotels in Türkiye According to Segments

Table 61: Brands of Hilton in Luxurious Getaways Segment (Türkiye)

CITY	HOTELS	SEGMENT
Muğla	Susona Bodrum LXR Hotels&Resorts	Luxurious getaways
İstanbul	Hagia Sofia Mansions İstanbul Curio Collection by Hilton	Luxurious getaways
İstanbul	Conrad İstanbul Bosphorus	Luxurious getaways

Table 62: Brands of Hilton in Premium Experiences Segment (Türkiye)

CITY	HOTELS	SEGMENT
Adana	Adana HiltonSA	Premium experiences
Adana	DoubleTree by Hilton Adana	Premium experiences
Afyonkarahisar	DoubleTree by Hilton Afyonkarahisar	Premium experiences
Ankara	Ankara HiltonSA	Premium experiences
Ankara	DoubleTree by Hilton Ankara İncek	Premium experiences
Antalya	DoubleTree by Hilton Antalya City Centre	Premium experiences
Antalya	DoubleTree by Hilton Antalya-Kemer	Premium experiences
Nevşehir	DoubleTree by Hilton Avanos - Kapadokya	Premium experiences
İzmir	DoubleTree by Hilton İzmir Alsancak	Premium experiences
İzmir	DoubleTree by Hilton İzmir Airport	Premium experiences
Manisa	DoubleTree by Hilton Manisa	Premium experiences
Aydın	DoubleTree by Hilton Kuşadası	Premium experiences
Muğla	DoubleTree by Hilton Bodrum Marina Vista	Premium experiences
Muğla	DoubleTree by Hilton Bodrum Işıl Club Resort	Premium experiences
Bursa	Hilton Bursa Convention Center&Spa	Premium experiences
Elazığ	DoubleTree by Hilton Elazığ	Premium experiences
Gaziantep	DoubleTree by Hilton Gaziantep	Premium experiences
Hakkari	DoubleTree by Hilton Yüksekova	Premium experiences
İstanbul	DoubleTree by Hilton İstanbul-Old Town	Premium experiences
İstanbul	DoubleTree by Hilton İstanbul-Sirkeci	Premium experiences
İstanbul	DoubleTree by Hilton İstanbul Piyalepaşa	Premium experiences
İstanbul	DoubleTree by Hilton İstanbul Topkapı	Premium experiences
İstanbul	Hilton İstanbul Bosphorus	Premium experiences
İstanbul	Hilton İstanbul Bomonti Hotel&Conference Center	Premium experiences
İstanbul	DoubleTree by Hilton İstanbul Moda	Premium experiences
İstanbul	DoubleTree by Hilton İstanbul Esentepe	Premium experiences
İstanbul	Hilton İstanbul Bakırköy	Premium experiences
İstanbul	Hilton İstanbul Kozyatağı	Premium experiences
İstanbul	Hilton İstanbul Maslak	Premium experiences
İstanbul	DoubleTree by Hilton İstanbul Ümraniye	Premium experiences
İstanbul	Hilton Mall of İstanbul	Premium experiences
İstanbul	DoubleTree by Hilton İstanbul Avcılar	Premium experiences
İstanbul	DoubleTree by Hilton İstanbul Tuzla	Premium experiences
İzmir	DoubleTree by Hilton Çeşme Alaçatı Beach Resort	Premium experiences
Mersin	Mersin HiltonSA	Premium experiences
Muğla	Hilton Dalaman Sarigerme Resort &Spa	Premium experiences
Trabzon	DoubleTree by Hilton Trabzon	Premium experiences

Van	DoubleTree by Hilton Van	Premium experiences
Çanakkale	DoubleTree by Hilton Çanakkale	Premium experiences
Şanlıurfa	DoubleTree by Hilton Şanlıurfa	Premium experiences

Table 63: Brands of Hilton in Curated Collections Segment (Türkiye)

CITY	HOTELS	SEGMENT
Muğla	The Bo Vue Hotel Bodrum Curio Collection by Hilton	Curated collections

Table 64: Brands of Hilton in Elevated Essentials Segment (Türkiye)

CITY	HOTELS	SEGMENT
Ankara	Hilton Garden Inn Ankara Dikmen	Elevated essentials
Ankara	Hilton Garden Inn Ankara Gimat	Elevated essentials
Balıkesir	Hilton Garden Inn Balıkesir	Elevated essentials
İzmir	Hilton Garden Inn İzmir Bayraklı	Elevated essentials
İzmir	Hampton by Hilton İzmir Aliağa	Elevated essentials
Bolu	Hampton by Hilton Bolu	Elevated essentials
Bursa	Hampton by Hilton Bursa	Elevated essentials
Erzincan	Hilton Garden Inn Erzincan	Elevated essentials
Erzurum	Hilton Garden Inn Erzurum	Elevated essentials
Eskişehir	Hilton Garden Inn Eskişehir	Elevated essentials
Kütahya	Hilton Garden Inn Kütahya	Elevated essentials
Gaziantep	Hampton by Hilton Gaziantep	Elevated essentials
Isparta	Hilton Garden Inn Isparta	Elevated essentials
İstanbul	Hampton by Hilton İstanbul Old City	Elevated essentials
İstanbul	Hampton by Hilton İstanbul Zeytinburnu	Elevated essentials
İstanbul	Hampton by Hilton İstanbul Ataköy	Elevated essentials
İstanbul	Hilton Garden Inn İstanbul Atatürk Airport	Elevated essentials
İstanbul	Hampton by Hilton İstanbul Kayaşehir	Elevated essentials
İstanbul	Hilton Garden Inn İstanbul Beylikdüzü	Elevated essentials
İstanbul	Hampton by Hilton İstanbul Arnavutköy	Elevated essentials
İstanbul	Hampton by Hilton İstanbul Kurtköy	Elevated essentials
Kocaeli	Hilton Garden Inn Kocaeli Şekerpınar	Elevated essentials
Yalova	Hilton Garden Inn Yalova	Elevated essentials
Tekirdağ	Hampton by Hilton Çerkezköy	Elevated essentials
Kahramanmaraş	Hampton by Hilton Kahramanmaraş	Elevated essentials

Konya	Hilton Garden Inn Konya	Elevated essentials
Mardin	Hilton Garden Inn Mardin	Elevated essentials
Ordu	Hampton by Hilton Ordu	Elevated essentials
Bartın	Hilton Garden Inn Safranbolu	Elevated essentials
Samsun	Hampton by Hilton Samsun	Elevated essentials
Tekirdağ	Hilton Garden Inn Çorlu	Elevated essentials
Çanakkale	Hampton by Hilton Çanakkale Gallipoli	Elevated essentials
Şanlıurfa	Hilton Garden Inn Şanlıurfa	Elevated essentials

Figure 68: Hilton Number of Hotels According to the Market Segments in Cities of Türkiye

2.1.1.3.2.6. Radisson Hotel Group

Radisson Hotels is an international hotel chain headquartered in the United States. A division of the Radisson Hotel Group, it operates the brands Radisson Blu, Radisson Red, Radisson Collection, Country Inn & Suites, and Park Inn by Radisson, among others. In June 2022, Radisson Hotels agreed to be purchased by Choice Hotels for \$675 million. The deal closed on August 11, 2022.

Radisson hotel group has 12 brands worldwide as seen in Table 65.

Table 65: Brands of Radisson in Segments (Worldwide)

SEGMENT	NUMBER OF BRANDS
Exceptional	Radisson Collection
Feel the difference	Radisson Blu
Simply Delightful	Radisson
Enjoy It	Radisson Red
Selected For You	Radisson Individuals
Feel the Authentic	Park Plaza
Feel Good	Park Inn by Radisson
Welcome Home	Country Inn & Suites by Radisson
VIBRANT, SMART, GENUINE	Prizeotel
Dream in colour	Art'otel

Table 66: Brands of Radisson in Segments (Türkiye)

CITY	HOTELS	SEGMENT
Ankara	Park Inn by Radisson Ankara Çankaya	Feel Good
Ankara	Radisson Blu Hotel Ankara	Feel the difference
Muğla	Radisson Collection Hotel Bodrum	Exceptional
Diyarbakır	Radisson Blu Hotel Diyarbakır	Feel the difference
Eskişehir	Nova Vista Deluxe&Suites Eskişehir, a member of Radisson Individuals	Selected For You
Eskişehir	Nova Vista Eskişehir Centrum Hotel, a member of Radisson Individuals	Selected For You
İstanbul	Park Inn by Radisson İstanbul Airport, Odayeri	Feel Good
İstanbul	Park Inn by Radisson İstanbul Asia Kavacık	Feel Good
İstanbul	Park Inn by Radisson İstanbul Ataşehir	Feel Good
İstanbul	Park Inn by Radisson İstanbul Atatürk Airport	Feel Good
İstanbul	Radisson Blu Bosphorus Hotel, İstanbul	Feel the difference
İstanbul	Radisson Blu Hotel&Spa Tuzla	Feel the difference
İstanbul	Radisson Blu Hotel İstanbul Asia	Feel the difference

İstanbul	Radisson Blu Hotel İstanbul Ottomare	Feel the difference
İstanbul	Radisson Blu Hotel İstanbul Pera	Feel the difference
İstanbul	Radisson Blu Hotel İstanbul Şişli	Feel the difference
İstanbul	Radisson Collection Hotel Vadistanbul	Exceptional
İstanbul	Radisson Hotel İstanbul Harbiye	Simply Delightful
İstanbul	Radisson Hotel İstanbul Sultanahmet	Simply Delightful
İstanbul	Radisson Hotel President Old Town İstanbul	Simply Delightful
İstanbul	Radisson Residences Avrupa TEM İstanbul	Simply Delightful
İstanbul	Radisson Residences Vadistanbul	Simply Delightful
İstanbul	Royan Hotel Hagia Sophia İstanbul, a member of Radisson Individuals	Selected For You
İzmir	Park Inn by Radisson İzmir	Feel Good
İzmir	Radisson Hotel İzmir Aliğa	Simply Delightful
İzmir	Radisson Blu Resort&Spa Çeşme	Feel the difference
Antalya	Radisson Blu Hotel Kaş	Feel the difference
Kayseri	Radisson Blu Hotel Kayseri	Feel the difference
Kayseri	Radisson Blu Hotel, Mount Erciyes	Feel the difference
Ordu	Radisson Blu Hotel Ordu	Feel the difference
Sakarya	Radisson Blu Hotel Sakarya	Feel the difference
Samsun	Park Inn by Radisson Samsun	Feel Good
Trabzon	Radisson Blu Hotel Trabzon	Feel the difference

Figure 69: Radisson Number of Hotels in Türkiye According to Segments

Table 67: Brands of Radisson in Exceptional Segment (Türkiye)

CITY	HOTELS	SEGMENT
Muğla	Radisson Collection Hotel Bodrum	Exceptional
İstanbul	Radisson Collection Hotel Vadistanbul	Exceptional

Table 68: Brands of Radisson in Feel the Difference Segment (Türkiye)

CITY	HOTELS	SEGMENT
Ankara	Radisson Blu Hotel Ankara	Feel the difference
Diyarbakır	Radisson Blu Hotel Diyarbakır	Feel the difference
İstanbul	Radisson Blu Bosphorus Hotel, İstanbul	Feel the difference
İstanbul	Radisson Blu Hotel&Spa Tuzla	Feel the difference
İstanbul	Radisson Blu Hotel İstanbul Asia	Feel the difference
İstanbul	Radisson Blu Hotel İstanbul Ottomare	Feel the difference
İstanbul	Radisson Blu Hotel İstanbul Pera	Feel the difference
İstanbul	Radisson Blu Hotel İstanbul Şişli	Feel the difference
İzmir	Radisson Blu Resort&Spa Çeşme	Feel the difference
Antalya	Radisson Blu Hotel Kaş	Feel the difference
Kayseri	Radisson Blu Hotel Kayseri	Feel the difference
Kayseri	Radisson Blu Hotel, Mount Erciyes	Feel the difference
Ordu	Radisson Blu Hotel Ordu	Feel the difference
Sakarya	Radisson Blu Hotel Sakarya	Feel the difference
Trabzon	Radisson Blu Hotel Trabzon	Feel the difference

Table 69: Brands of Radisson in Simply Delightful Segment (Türkiye)

CITY	HOTELS	SEGMENT
İstanbul	Radisson Hotel İstanbul Harbiye	Simply Delightful
İstanbul	Radisson Hotel İstanbul Sultanahmet	Simply Delightful
İstanbul	Radisson Hotel President Old Town İstanbul	Simply Delightful
İstanbul	Radisson Residences Avrupa TEM İstanbul	Simply Delightful
İstanbul	Radisson Residences Vadistanbul	Simply Delightful
İzmir	Radisson Hotel İzmir Aliğa	Simply Delightful

Table 70: Brands of Radisson in Selected for You Segment (Türkiye)

CITY	HOTELS	SEGMENT
Eskişehir	Nova Vista Deluxe&Suites Eskişehir, a member of Radisson Individuals	Selected For You
Eskişehir	Nova Vista Eskişehir Centrum Hotel, a member of Radisson Individuals	Selected For You
İstanbul	Royan Hotel Hagia Sophia İstanbul, a member of Radisson Individuals	Selected For You

Table 71: Brands of Radisson in Feel Good Segment (Türkiye)

CITY	HOTELS	SEGMENT
Ankara	Park Inn by Radisson Ankara Çankaya	Feel Good
İstanbul	Park Inn by Radisson İstanbul Airport, Odayeri	Feel Good
İstanbul	Park Inn by Radisson İstanbul Asia Kavacık	Feel Good
İstanbul	Park Inn by Radisson İstanbul Ataşehir	Feel Good
İstanbul	Park Inn by Radisson İstanbul Atatürk Airport	Feel Good
İzmir	Park Inn by Radisson İzmir	Feel Good
Samsun	Park Inn by Radisson Samsun	Feel Good

Figure 70: Radisson Number of Hotels According to the Market Segments in Cities of Türkiye

2.1.1.3.2.7. Meeting Point Hotels

Founded by FTI Group in September 2015, Meeting Point Hotels is an international hospitality company with a portfolio of currently five brands comprising more than 60 properties with more than 13,000 rooms, around 7,000 talents in 8 countries.

The company's portfolio includes Labranda Hotels & Resorts, Design Plus Hotels, Kairaba Hotels & Resorts, Lemon & Soul Hotels. Additionally, the company also manages properties with unique characteristics, providing distinctive experiences under the umbrella Managed by MP Hotels, such as Aquaworld Belek by Meeting Point Hotels.

Couples, singles and families, sun-seekers, sports fanatics or experience and culturally driven, wide hotel range has just the right choice for everyone. The resorts and hotels are located on the Canary Islands, Morocco, Malta, Italy, Greece, Croatia, Türkiye and Egypt.

There are 12 hotels in Türkiye. Meeting Point Hotels use different brand names in Turkish hospitality industry such as Labranda, Kairaba and Managed by Meeting Point Hotels. The hotels are located at the seashores.

Table 72: Brands of Meeting Point Hotels in Türkiye

CITY	HOTELS
İzmir (Alaçatı)	Kairaba Alaçatı Beach Resort&Spa
İzmir (Alaçatı)	Design Plus Seya Beach Hotel
Antalya (Alanya)	Labranda Alantur Resort
Antalya (Belek)	Aquaworld Belek Managed by Meeting Point Hotels
Muğla (Bodrum)	Labranda TMT
Muğla (Bodrum)	Kairaba Bodrum Imperial Hotel
Aydın (Kuşadası)	Labranda Ephesus Princess
Muğla (Marmaris)	Labranda Mares Marmaris
Muğla (Bodrum)	Senses Hotel Managed by Meeting Point Hotels
Muğla (Marmaris)	Marmaris Bay Resort Managed by Meeting Point Hotels
Antalya (Side)	Labranda Excelsior Side
İzmir (Seferihisar)	Labranda Lebedos Princess

2.1.1.3.2.8. Hyatt Hotels

Hyatt Hotels Corporation, commonly known as Hyatt Hotels & Resorts, is an American multinational hospitality company headquartered in the Riverside Plaza area of Chicago that manages and franchises luxury and business hotels, resorts, and vacation properties. Hyatt Hotels & Resorts is one of the businesses managed by the Pritzker family.

The Hyatt Corporation came into being upon purchase of the Hyatt House, at Los Angeles International Airport, on September 27, 1957. In 1969, Hyatt began expanding internationally. Hyatt has grown by developing new properties and through acquisitions, with the biggest growth coming from the acquisition of AmeriSuites (later rebranded Hyatt Place) in 2004, Summerfield Suites (later rebranded Hyatt House) in 2005, and Two Roads Hospitality in 2018.

Hyatt Hotels have 28 brands worldwide. There are 6 hotels in Türkiye.

Table 73: Brands of Hyatt Hotels in Türkiye

CITY	HOTELS	SEGMENT
İstanbul	Grand Hyatt İstanbul	Timeless Collection
İstanbul	Hyatt Centric Levent İstanbul	Boundless Collection
Kocaeli	Hyatt House Gebze	Timeless Collection
İstanbul	Hyatt Regency İstanbul Ataköy	Timeless Collection
İzmir	Hyatt Regency İzmir İstinyePark	Timeless Collection
İstanbul	Park Hyatt İstanbul Maçka Palas	Timeless Collection

2.1.1.3.2.9. Best Western Hotels

Best Western International, Inc. owns the Best Western Hotels & Resorts brand, which licenses to over 4,700 hotels worldwide. The franchise, with its corporate headquarters in Phoenix, Arizona, includes more than 2,000 hotels in North America. The brand was founded by M. K. Guertin in 1946. As of December 2021, Larry Cuculic is the president and CEO of Best Western. In 1964, Canadian hotel owners joined the system. Best Western then expanded to Mexico, Australia, and New Zealand in 1976.

Table 74: Brands of Best Western Hotels in Türkiye

CITY	HOTELS	SEGMENT
Antalya	Vib Best Western Antalya	Boutique
Antalya	BW Best Western PLUS Khan Hotel	Timeless
İzmir	BWP PREMIER BEST WESTERN Karşıyaka Convention&Spa Hotel	Timeless
İzmir	BW Best Western PLUS Hotel Konak	Timeless
İstanbul	WorldHotels Elite The Marmara Taksim	Aspirational
Ankara	BW Best Western PLUS Center Hotel Ankara	Timeless

2.1.1.3.2.10. Dedeman Hotels & Resorts

Dedeman Hotels & Resorts International always offers the same superior quality of service because the goal is to introduce all the guests to "Traditional Dedeman Hospitality."

With more than 50 years of experience in Türkiye and the world, Dedeman Hotels & Resorts International offers promising cooperation to its business partners as a strong brand with its conscious strategy and awareness. Dedeman is the largest international hotel chain in Türkiye that has developed successfully and is "hosting the world" today. As of 2022, Dedeman offers privileges to the esteemed guests with 19 hotels in 16 cities and 2 countries.

As Dedeman International Hotels & Resort, we compete with world brands in different geographies. Today, we are very proud to represent the example of Turkish hospitality, friendly service and working with love in the hotels in Kazakhstan and Northern Iraq.

Dedeman aims to thrive in different geographies, especially in the Balkans, the Middle East and Africa, with the vision of becoming a regional and then worldwide brand. With all these short- and medium-term plans, we aim to increase the growth on the basis of hotels and rooms by 100 percent, increase the number of employees by 70 percent, and increase the turnover we manage by 5 times by 2025. Dedeman has four brands and 22 hotels.

Table 75: Brands of Dedeman Hotels in Türkiye

CITY	HOTELS
İstanbul	Dedeman Bostancı
Şırnak	Dedeman Cizre
İstanbul	Dedeman İstanbul
Kocaeli	Dedeman Kartepe
Kayseri	Dedeman Kayseri
Konya	Dedeman Konya
Erzurum	Dedeman Palandöken
Erzurum	Dedeman Palandöken Ski Lodge
Şanlıurfa	Dedeman Şanlıurfa
Tokat	Dedeman Tokat
Van	Dedeman Van Resort & Aquapark
Zonguldak	Dedeman Zonguldak
Adıyaman	Park Dedeman Adıyaman
İstanbul	Park Dedeman Bostancı
Denizli	Park Dedeman Denizli
Elazığ	Park Dedeman Elazığ
Eskişehir	Park Dedeman Eskişehir
Gaziantep	Park Dedeman Gaziantep
Kastamonu	Park Dedeman Kastamonu
Trabzon	Park Dedeman Trabzon
Kars	R2S by Dedeman Sarıkamış
Eskişehir	Smart by Dedeman Eskişehir
İstanbul	Dedeman Küçükyalı İstanbul (Open soon)
Samsun	Elina Managed by Dedeman Samsun (Open soon)
Kars	Qrista Managed by Dedeman (Open soon)
Diyarbakır	Rest & More by Dedeman Diyarbakır (Open soon)
Mersin	Rest & More by Dedeman Mersin Erdemli (Open soon)
Karabük	Rest by Dedeman Karabük (Open soon)
Adana	Dedeman Adana (Open soon)
Nevşehir	Dedeman Kapadokya (Open soon)
Düzce	Park Dedeman Düzce (Open soon)
Ankara	Park Dedeman Kızılay Ankara (Open soon)

2.1.1.3.2.11. Anemon Hotels

Anemon Tourism was established in 1970. It is one of the biggest national hospitality brands since 1990. Its business concept is focused on city hotels. Its unique sales proposition is best price for best quality. It has 24 hotels in 20 different cities. Detailed information is given in Table 76.

Table 76: Brands of Anemon Hotels in Türkiye

CITY	HOTELS	SEGMENT
Adana	Anemon Adana	5 Star/City Hotel and Congress purpose
Ankara	Anemon Ankara	4 Star/City Hotel and Congress purpose
Hatay	Anemon Antakya	4 Star/City Hotel and Congress purpose
Aydın	Anemon Aydın	4 Star/City Hotel and Congress purpose
İstanbul	Anemon Bakırköy	City Hotel
İzmir	Anemon Çiğli	4 Star / City Hotel
Denizli	Anemon Denizli	5 Star/City Hotel and Congress purpose
Diyarbakır	Anemon Diyarbakır	City Hotel
İzmir	Anemon Ege Hotel	City Hotel and Congress Purpose
Eskişehir	Anemon Eskişehir	5 Star/City Hotel and Congress purpose
İstanbul	Anemon Galata	City Hotel/Butik Hotel
Hatay	Anemon İskenderun	5 Star/City Hotel and Congress purpose
İzmir	Anemon İzmir	4 Star/City Hotel and Congress purpose
Nevşehir	Anemon Kapadokya	Opening Soon
Konya	Anemon Konya	4 Star/City Hotel and Congress purpose
Manisa	Anemon Kula	
Malatya	Anemon Malatya	5 Star/City Hotel and Congress purpose
Manisa	Anemon Manisa	5 Star/City Hotel and Congress purpose
Mardin	Anemon Mardin	5 Star/City Hotel and Congress purpose
Mersin	Anemon Mersin	
Ordu	Anemon Ordu	4 Star/City Hotel and Congress purpose
Samsun	Anemon Samsun	5 Star/City Hotel and Congress purpose
Trabzon	Anemon Trabzon	
Uşak	Anemon Uşak	
Manisa	Villa Estet by Anemon	

2.1.1.3.2.12. Divan Hotels

Divan which is a company of Koç Holding has 17 hotels worldwide. Twelve of these hotels are located in Türkiye. It has only one brand. The hotels are located in nine cities of Türkiye. The names and locations of these hotels can be seen from Table 77.

Table 77: Brands of Divan Hotels in Türkiye

CITY	HOTELS
İstanbul	Divan İstanbul
İstanbul	Divan İstanbul Asia
İstanbul	Divan İstanbul City
Muğla	Divan Bodrum
Bursa	Divan Bursa
Mersin	Divan Mersin
Diyarbakır	Divan Diyarbakır
Adana	Divan Adana
Ankara	Divan Ankara
Ankara	Divan Çukurhan
Tekirdağ	Divan Çorlu
Gaziantep	Divan Gaziantep

2.1.1.3.2.13. Other National Hotel Companies

There are three big national hotel groups in Türkiye that are mentioned above. In addition, there also other national hotel companies that are smaller such as TUI Group, Crystal Hotels, Barut Hotels, Delphin Hotels, Stone Group, Kaya Hotels, Voyage Group, Larissa Hotels, Paloma Hotels, Limak Hotels and Titanic Hotels. The information is given about these companies below.

1. TUI Hotels

The center of the company is in Antalya, Türkiye. It has 16 hotels in Türkiye. The hotels are located in Muğla and Antalya. Detailed information is given in Table 78.

Table 78: Brands of TUI Hotels in Türkiye

CITY	HOTELS
Muğla	TUI BLUE Grand Azur
Antalya	TUI BLUE Pascha Bay
Antalya	TUI BLUE Palm Garden
Muğla	TUI BLUE Sarigerme Park
Muğla	TUI BLUE Seno
Muğla	TUI BLUE Tropical
Antalya	TUI MAGIC LIFE Masmavi
Antalya	TUI MAGIC LIFE Belek
Muğla	TUI MAGIC LIFE Bodrum
Muğla	TUI MAGIC LIFE Sarigerme
Antalya	TTH Hydros Club
Muğla	Holiday Village Türkiye
Antalya	Pegasos Club
Antalya	Pegasos Resort
Antalya	Pegasos Royal
Antalya	Pegasos World

2. Crystal Hotels

Crystal hotels has 18 hotels, mostly established in Antalya. It is a company of Kilit Hospitality Group (KHG). Detailed information is given in Table 79.

Table 79: Brands of Crystal Hotels in Türkiye

CITY	HOTELS
Antalya (Belek)	Crystal Family
Antalya (Belek)	Crystal Waterworld
Antalya (Belek)	Crystal Paraiso Verde
Antalya (Belek)	Crystal Boutique Beach
Antalya (Belek)	Crystal Club World of Colours
Antalya (Belek)	Crystal Tat Beach
Antalya (Kemer)	Crystal Flora Beach
Antalya (Kemer)	Crystal De Luxe
Antalya (Kemer)	Crystal Aura Beach
Antalya (Kemer)	Crystal Prestige Elite

Antalya (Side)	Crystal Palace Luxury
Antalya (Side)	Crystal Sunset Luxury
Antalya (Side)	Crystal Admiral
Antalya (Lara)	Crystal Centro
Antalya (Side)	Crystal Sunrise Luxury
Antalya (Alanya)	Crystal Land of Paradise
Muğla (Bodrum)	Crystal Green Bay
Nevşehir (Kapadokya)	Crystal Kaymaklı

3. Barut Hotels

Barut hotels has 15 hotels, mostly operating in Antalya. It uses different brands for its hotels such as Barut, Akra and etc. Detailed information is given in Table 80.

Table 80: Brands of Barut Hotels in Türkiye

CITY	HOTELS	SEGMENT
Antalya (Side)	Acanthus Cennet Barut Collection	Luxury
Antalya (Side)	Arum Barut Collection	Luxury
Antalya (Side)	Barut B Suites	
Antalya (Side)	Barut Hemera	
Antalya (Side)	Barut Sunwing Side Beach	
Antalya (Side)	TUI BLUE Barut Andız	
Antalya (Lara)	Bayou Villas	
Antalya (Lara)	Lara Barut Collection	Luxury
Aydın (Didim)	Anda Barut Collection	Luxury
Antalya (Lara)	Akra Hotel	Urban Social
Antalya (Lara)	Akra V	Urban Social
Antalya (Kemer)	Akra Kemer	Heartful Living
Antalya (Manavgat)	Akra Sorgun Tui Blue Sensatori	Heartful Living
Muğla (Fethiye)	Akra Fethiye Tui Blue Sensatori	Heartful Living
Muğla (Fethiye)	Akra Fethiye The Residence Tui Blue Sensatori	Heartful Living

4. Delphin Hotels & Resorts

Delphin brand has 7 hotels in Antalya. It uses two different brand names. Detailed information is given in Table 81.

Table 81: Brands of Delphin Hotels in Türkiye

CITY	HOTELS
Antalya (Lara)	Delphin Imperial
Antalya (Lara)	Delphin Be Grand Resort
Antalya (Lara)	Delphin Palace
Antalya (Lara)	Delphin Diva
Antalya (Alanya)	Delphin Deluxe
Antalya (Alanya)	Botanik Platinum
Antalya (Alanya)	Botanik Hotel&Resort

5. Stone Group

Stone Group was established in 1995. It has one hotel in Antalya Belek region (Adam&Eve Hotel), two hotels in Antalya Lara region (Royal Seginus Hotel, Royal Holiday Palace) and two hotels in Antalya Side region (Royal Dragon Hotel, Royal Alhambra Palace). All of these hotels are five star hotels as seen in Table 82.

Table 82: Brands of Stone Group Hotels in Türkiye

CITY	HOTELS	SEGMENT
Antalya (Belek)	Adam & Eve +16 Hotel	5 Star
Antalya (Lara)	Royal Seginus Hotel	5 Star
Antalya (Lara)	Royal Holiday Palace	5 Star
Antalya (Side)	Royal Dragon Hotel	5 Star
Antalya (Side)	Royal Alhambra Palace	5 Star

6. Kaya Hotels & Resorts

Kaya Holding, which was established in 1974 by Burhanettin Kaya, is undertaking activities in fields of construction, tourism, finance, oil, energy and beverages with its 8 companies and more than 2500 employees. Kaya Holding group companies, which have specialized in their own fields, are directly or indirectly getting into contact with thousands of customers around the world and providing services for global markets as well as local markets especially in tourism and construction businesses. Detailed information is given in Table 83.

Table 83: Brands of Kaya Hotels in Türkiye

CITY	HOTELS
Antalya (Belek)	Kaya Palazzo Golf Resort
Muğla (Bodrum)	Kaya Palazzo Resort & Residence Le Chic
Bolu (Kartalkaya)	Kaya Palazzo Ski & Mountain Resort
Ankara	Kaya Palazzo Hotel & Residences
Antalya (Belek)	Kaya Belek
Antalya (Side)	Kaya Side
İzmir	Kaya İzmir Thermal & Convention
İstanbul	Kaya İstanbul Fair & Convention
Bolu	Kaya Green Park
Bursa	Kaya Uludağ
Bolu (Kartalkaya)	Dorukkaya Ski & Mountain Resort

7. Voyage Group

Starting its business life with Etstur which was founded in 1991 through a ground-breaking entrance into Turkish tourism industry, Etsgroup offers various holiday options with Didimtur, Ucuzailet.com, Otelpuan.com, Odamax.com, Voyage Hotels and Maxx Royal Resorts.

Etsgroup provides service as the leading tourism group in the industry by adding the mission of keeping customer satisfaction at the highest level and providing high standards of service quality which also is the company's core principle. Offering tour packages that cover over a thousand hotels and resorts within the country and

approximately 60 destinations abroad, the group also provides many services including domestic cultural tours, incentive groups, airplane tickets and car rental.

Established in 1994 based on these achievements, Voyage Hotels feature four different Voyage Hotels. The properties, each having a different concept with their architectures and atmosphere, stand out with their high standard and best quality services.

Voyage Hotels welcome guests with their restaurants serving flavours from different world cuisines, various activity and entertainment facilities. Besides standing out with its award-winning properties Voyage is also known for being a nature-friendly hotel as well as standing out with its awarded properties. Taking precautions in order to prevent any damage to the trees during construction and leaving the trees corresponding the buildings in place set Voyage Hotels apart from the other properties.

Table 84: Brands of Voyage Hotels in Türkiye

CITY	HOTELS
Antalya (Belek)	Voyage Belek Golf&Spa
Antalya (Manavgat)	Voyage Sorgun
Muğla (Bodrum)	Voyage Torba
Muğla (Bodrum)	Voyage Torba Private

8. Larissa Hotels

There are 8 hotels in Türkiye. Most of the hotels are located in Kemer. All of the Larissa Hotels are located in Antalya. In table 85, the brands of these hotels are listed.

Table 85: Brands of Larissa Hotels in Türkiye

CITY	HOTELS
Antalya (Side)	Larissa Beach Club Side
Antalya (Kemer)	Larissa Hotel Beldibi
Antalya (Kemer)	Larissa Inn
Antalya (Kemer)	Larissa Mare Beach
Antalya (Kemer)	Larissa Sultan's Beach
Antalya (Kemer)	Fun&Fun Club Sapphire
Antalya (Side)	Otium Family Stone Palace
Antalya (Kemer)	Otium Park Club Akman

9. Paloma Hotels

Paloma hotels was established 40 years ago and believes in sustainability and sustainable tourism. It also has a program named “tastes of Paloma”. It has hotels in Antalya, İzmir and Aydın.

Table 86: Brands of Paloma Hotels in Türkiye

CITY	HOTELS
Antalya (Side)	Paloma Finesse
Antalya (Side)	Paloma Orenda
Antalya (Side)	Paloma Perissia
Antalya (Side)	Paloma Oceana
Antalya (Belek)	Paloma Grida
Antalya (Kemer)	Paloma Foresta
İzmir (Özdere)	Paloma Pasha
Aydın (Kuşadası)	Paloma Marina Suites

10. Limak Hotels

Limak has entered the tourism sector in 1995 with Limak Arcadia. The investments have been continued acting on the principle of being a pioneer and leader in every sector of operation; Limak Limra has been taken into service at Antalya Kemer in 1998 and Limak Atlantis at Antalya Belek in 2002.

In 2000, the Limak International Hotels & Resort brand has been created and the “Warm Hospitality & Excellent Service” slogan has been registered as the brand commitment. Limak Ambassadors has been the first step into urban hotel management in 2006, while Limak Lara has been presented to the country tourism at Antalya Lara in the same year. In 2010, the first thermal boutique hotel of Türkiye, Limak Yalova Thermal has been taken into service. Meanwhile, Limak Eurasia Hotel has started to serve at İstanbul Kavacık in 2011.

Services are offered throughout the year at the facilities and occupancy ratios over 80 percent are maintained consistently. Limak Tourism Group hosts guests from almost 40 different countries around the world, as well as its domestic guests.

Limak Tourism Group has increased the number of its hotels to 8 with the new hotel - Cyprus Deluxe Hotel that has been taken into operation in Cyprus in 2018, and reached a bed capacity over 6000. Limak Cyprus Deluxe also qualifies as the first international investment of the group. Limak Tourism Group is continuing its investments with an urban hotel project in Skopje, Macedonia.

Table 87: Brands of Paloma Hotels in Türkiye

CITY	HOTELS
Antalya (Lara)	Limak Lara Deluxe Hotel & Resort
Antalya (Belek)	Limak Arcadia Sport Resort Hotel
Ankara	Limak Ambassadors Hotel
Antalya (Kemer)	Limak Limra Hotel & Resort
İstanbul	Limak Eurasia Luxury Hotel
Antalya (Belek)	Limak Atlantis Deluxe Hotel & Resort
Yalova	Limak Thermal Boutique Hotel

11. Titanic Hotels

Titanic Hotels is operating 13 hotels in Türkiye and Germany. The group has continued to grow exponentially ever since, opening the first hotel in Istanbul in 1998. In 2003 the group has opened its third property, named after the famous ship Titanic, as pioneer of theme hotels in Antalya. The property itself was shaped like a cruise ship and became one of the landmark properties at the region ever since its opening. Later, all the hotels of the group were branded under Titanic Hotels. With the opening of Titanic Comfort Kurfürstendamm in 2021, Titanic Hotels has reached a total number of 13 hotels both in Antalya, Istanbul, Bodrum and Berlin.

Table 88: Brands of Paloma Hotels in Türkiye

CITY	HOTELS
Antalya	Titanic Mardan Palace
Antalya	Titanic Deluxe Golf Belek
Antalya	Titanic Deluxe Lara
Muğla (Bodrum)	Titanic Luxury Collection Bodrum
İstanbul	Titanic Business Kartal
İstanbul	Titanic Port Bakırköy
İstanbul	Titanic City Taksim
İstanbul	Titanic Comfort Şişli
İstanbul	Titanic Anadolu Gebze

2.1.2. Food and Beverage

Türkiye is an emerging, largely free economy with a robust production capacity for agricultural goods, textiles, vehicles, and construction materials. According to the latest prediction by the International Monetary Fund (IMF), Türkiye's GDP in 2022 is on track to increase year-over-year by about 4 percent, which is down from 11 percent the previous year. Economic growth in 2023 is predicted to stay flat year-to-year at 3.9 percent because of continued economic uncertainties, both at home and abroad.

In hopes of raising the country's economic growth trajectory, the government has cut interest rates and made other market interventions. The unorthodox rate cuts, in parallel with rising international energy and commodity prices, have fueled record inflation and the depreciation of the TRY. The Turkish government's interventions to minimize the effects of skyrocketing inflation and stabilize the TL continue to have limited success. The government is expected to continue its market-stabilizing efforts, especially ahead of general elections in 2023.¹⁰

Rising inflation and a depreciating currency has increased operational costs (e.g., rent, electricity) for food service companies in Türkiye, forcing them to raise their sales prices. The pandemic had earlier obliged these companies to adapt and cut costs to stay competitive. In particular, fast-food companies such as Burger King, Popeyes and Usta Doner were able to survive the pandemic since they could efficiently deliver food to customers at a low cost. Meantime, persistent inflation has eroded consumers' buying power, causing them to switch to cheaper dining-out options, such as fast food and street stalls.¹¹

The demand for restaurant home delivery service continues to expand as consumers increasingly desire greater convenience. Most full-service restaurants have now collaborated with Yemek Sepeti, Türkiye's largest online food and beverage delivery service company to deliver food to customers' doorsteps. In addition, many limited service restaurants, like fast food chains, have deployed their own motorized scooter delivery service.

¹⁰GAIN, Food Service: Hotel, Restaurant, Institutional in Türkiye, October-2022

¹¹GAIN, Food Service: Hotel, Restaurant, Institutional in Türkiye, October-2022

The HRI sector continues to recover from the negative effects of COVID-19 lockdowns and restrictions during 2020 and most of 2021. By the end of 2021, restaurant sales figures surpassed pre-COVID-19 levels in terms of TRY but not in U.S. dollar terms. Meantime, the number of food service outlets remained below pre-pandemic levels.

Table 89: Consumer Food Service Value, Number of Outlets and Number of Transactions

CONSUMER FOOD SERVICE	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Retail Sales Prices (USD million y-o-y)	20,832	20,136	19,456	19,901	9,326	15,039
Retail Sales Prices (USD million fixed rate) *	7,618	8,881	11,387	13,659	7,920	15,039
Number of Outlets (count)	117,669	123,187	129,406	132,406	108,490	122,682
Number of Transactions (millions)	3,909	4,222	4,768	5,154	2,037	4,067

Source: Euromonitor International, 2022

*Fixed in 2021 prices

Table 90: Number of Outlets per Type of Food Service

CONSUMER FOODSERVICE by TYPES (unites)	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Full- Service Restaurants	44,324	46,105	46,646	46,541	33,137	41,181
Cafes/Bars	45,285	46,354	46,866	46,221	38,088	41,442
Limited- Service Restaurants (Fast Food)	17,578	18,706	21,733	24,216	23,644	25,876
Street Stalls/ Kiosks	4,490	4,507	4,540	4,560	6,627	3,678
Self- Service Cafeterias	5,992	7,515	9,621	10,908	9,994	10,505
Total Consumer Food Service	117,669	123,187	129,406	132,446	108,490	122,682

Source: Euromonitor International, 2022

Tourism is important to the wellbeing of the Turkish economy and the country's HRI sector. In 2019, before COVID-19, approximately 45 million tourists visited Türkiye. During the first half of 2022, there were 19.5 million tourists, who spent approximately \$14 billion. In 2021, the tourism sector started showing signs of recovery with the number of tourists increasing. Most tourists are from Russia, Germany, Ukraine, Bulgaria and Iran. Tourists tend to stay at beach resorts and all-inclusive hotels in Antalya and along Türkiye's Mediterranean coast.¹²

¹²GAIN, Food Service: Hotel, Restaurant, Institutional in Türkiye, October-2022

2.1.2.1. Size and Growth of Industry

Commercial Food Service

The Turkish food service sector is large, highly fragmented, and can be divided into two categories: commercial and institutional food service. Commercial food service consists of full-service, self-service restaurants (mostly restaurants called *esnaf lokantasi* serving Turkish home-style restaurants), limited-service restaurants (e.g., fast food), as well as cafes/bars, home-delivery/takeaway outlets, street stalls/kiosks; serving approximately at 140,000 locations throughout the country in 2017 according to EMI. In 2021, there were about 123,000 commercial food service restaurants in Türkiye with sales of more than 120 billion TL. Food service value by type of food service can be seen in figure 71 below.¹³

Figure 71: Food Service Value of Türkiye in TRY

Source: Euromonitor International, 2022

Interestingly, sales in terms of TL exceeded pre-pandemic levels because of inflation. However, sales in USD terms and the numbers of restaurants and transactions lagged behind pre-pandemic levels. It will probably take a few more years for sales (USD terms) and the number of restaurants to reach where they were prior to the pandemic.

¹³GAIN, Food Service: Hotel, Restaurant, Institutional in Türkiye, October-2022

Full-service restaurants, which were hit the hardest during the pandemic, saw the largest increase in sales in 2021. The increase in tourism will benefit the HRI sector, especially full-service restaurants. At the same time, food sales for cafes/bars and limited-service restaurants in 2021 increased year-over-year but at a slower pace compared to full-service restaurants. Both the number of and sales at limited-service restaurants, especially pizza restaurants, bakeries, and coffee shops, is expected to expand in the future as Turks search for cheaper alternatives amid diminishing purchasing power. Of particular interest, the number of coffee shops has increased in parallel with a fivefold increase in per capita coffee consumption over the last 15 years.¹⁴

Fast food restaurants have been performing better compared to full service and fine-dining outlets. There are approximately 140,000 food service outlets in Türkiye in all segments. The industry is very fragmented with mostly small stand-alone restaurants. Five thousand institutional food service companies are serving corporations, hospitals, schools, universities, state and municipal offices, nursing homes, and some military bases, either via cooking in their own facilities and delivering the food or cooking on customer premises.

As of 2018, the number of restaurants (restaurants, hotel restaurants, fast food restaurants and take-out restaurants) in Türkiye has exceeded 600 thousand. In 2011, the size of entire food industry was 17.5 billion dollars. According to the report published by Zomato in 2019, 12499 new restaurants were opened in İstanbul in 2019. The number of restaurants that stand out with their vegan and vegetarian features reached 1081. With these, the number of restaurants in İstanbul reached 31268.¹⁵

Due to the changing profile of tourists and the economic difficulties in the country, with high food inflation rates and the depreciating TRY, spending in full-service restaurants has declined. At the same time, the increasing number of double income households with less time for cooking at home in this time of economic slowdown caused cheaper options such as fast food outlets, home delivery, and street stalls to become more attractive. Consumers are expected to remain price-sensitive in the near term.

¹⁴GAIN, Food Service: Hotel, Restaurant, Institutional in Türkiye, October-2022

¹⁵ Earnado, Food and Beverage Industry Report, 2021.

According to the data of the Ministry of Culture and Tourism, it is seen that the total number of Tourism Licenced Food and Beverage Establishments was 1160 in 2021. "The figure 72 below illustrates the distribution of these Establishments according to different types. Among these facilities, 30 are Tourism Investment Licensed, and 1130 are Tourism Establishment Licensed. The table in 91 provides detailed information about the capacities of Tourism Investment Licensed and Tourism Establishment Licensed establishments."

Figure 72: Number of Food and Beverage Establishments With Tourism Licensed

Source: Ministry of Tourism Certificated Accommodation and Food and Beverage Establishment Statistics, 2002-2021

Table 91: Number of Tourism Licensed Food and Beverage Establishments

Number of Tourism Licensed Food and Beverage Establishments (31.12.2021)					
Type	Class	Tourism investment licensed		Tourism establishment licensed	
		Establishment	Capacity (Person)	Establishment	Capacity (Person)
Total		30	10013	1130	346494
Restaurant	Total	6	1956	493	185100
	Luxury			1	600
	1st Class	6	1956	426	173580
	2nd Class			66	10920

Cafe	Total	1	150	3	260
	Class (None)	1	150	3	260
Private Establishment	Total	1	1220	347	71301
	Class (None)	1	1220	347	71301
Daily Establishment	Total	17	4700	69	22478
	Class (None)	17	4700	69	22478
Floating Establishment	Total	1	405	27	11886
	Class (None)	1	405	27	11886
Winter Sports and Ski Establishments	Total	3	750		
	Class (None)	3	750		
Theme Park	Total	1	832	1	450
	Class (None)	1	832	1	450
Breakpoint	Total			15	8065
	Class (None)			15	8065
Gastronomy	Total			175	46954
	Class (None)			175	46954

Source: Ministry of Tourism Licensed Accommodation and Food and Beverage Establishment Statistics, 2002-2021

When examining the distribution of Food and Beverage Establishments by regions, it is observed that these facilities are concentrated in the Marmara and Aegean regions. The following table 92 provides details on the distribution of Tourism Licensed Food and Beverage Establishments across regions and their respective capacities.

Table 92: Distribution and Number of Food and Beverage Establishments by Regions

NUMBER OF TOURISM LICENSED FOOD AND BEVERAGE ESTABLISHMENTS ACCORDING TO THE STATISTICAL REGIONAL CLASSIFICATION				
STATISTICAL REGIONAL UNIT CLASSIFICATION	Tourism investment licensed		Tourism establishment licensed	
	Establishment	Capacity (Person)	Establishment	Capacity (Person)
TR1 İstanbul	4	2276	499	153139
TR2 West Marmara	1	350	43	13802
TR3 Aegean	9	2105	162	45346
TR4 East Marmara	2	710	94	28608
TR5 West Anatolia			139	40190

TR6 Mediterranean	7	2872	64	20129
TR7 Central Anatolia	1	150	10	3210
TR8 West Black Sea	1	600	26	7433
TR9 East Black Sea	2	450	19	5947
TRA Northeast Anatolia	2	150	1	110
TRB Centraleast Anatolia			12	5250
TRC Southeast Anatolia	1	350	61	23330
Total	30	10013	1130	346494

Source: Ministry of Tourism Licensed Accommodation and Food and Beverage Establishment Statistics, 2002-2021

Istanbul, with a total of 503 Tourism Licensed Food and Beverage Establishments, stands out as the leading hub for the food and beverage sector on its own. The following table displays the numbers and capacities of Tourism Licensed Food and Beverage Establishments in Istanbul, categorized by different types.

Table 93: Number of Tourism Licensed Food and Beverage Establishments According to Their Types And Classes (İstanbul)

NUMBER OF TOURISM LICENSED FOOD AND BEVERAGE ESTABLISHMENTS ACCORDING TO THEIR TYPES AND CLASSES (İSTANBUL)					
Type	Class	Tourism investment licensed		Tourism establishment licensed	
		Establishment	Capacity (Person)	Establishment	Capacity (Person)
Total		4	2276	499	153139
Restaurant	Total	3	1056	186	83062
	Fine Dining			1	600
	1st Class	3	1056	150	75720
	2nd Class			35	6742
Café	Total			3	260
	Class (None)			3	260
Private Establishment	Total	1	1220	207	38001
	Class (None)	1	1220	207	38001
Daily Establishment	Total			17	6657
	Class (None)			17	6657
Floating Establishment	Total			24	11504
	Class (None)			24	11504
Gastronomy	Total			62	13655

	Class (None)			62	13655
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Source: Ministry of Tourism Licensed Accommodation and Food and Beverage Establishment Statistics, 2002-2021

Table 94: Number of Tourism Licensed Food and Beverage Establishments According to Their Types and Classes (West Marmara)

NUMBER OF TOURISM LICENSED FOOD AND BEVERAGE ESTABLISHMENTS ACCORDING TO THEIR TYPES AND CLASSES (WEST MARMARA)					
Type	Class	Tourism investment licensed		Tourism establishment licensed	
		Establishment	Capacity (Person)	Establishment	Capacity (Person)
Total		1	350	43	13802
Restaurant	Total			20	6589
	1st Class			19	6439
	2nd Class			1	150
Café	Total			6	1438
	Class (None)			6	1438
Private Establishment	Total	1	350	3	590
	Class (None)	1	350	3	590
Daily Establishment	Total			2	2310
	Class (None)			2	2310
	Total			12	2875
	Class (None)			12	2875

Source: Ministry of Tourism Licensed Accommodation and Food and Beverage Establishment Statistics, 2002-2021

Table 95: Number of Tourism Licensed Food and Beverage Establishments According to Their Types and Classes (Aegea)

NUMBER OF TOURISM LICENSED FOOD AND BEVERAGE ESTABLISHMENTS ACCORDING TO THEIR TYPES AND CLASSES (AEGEA)					
Type	Class	Tourism investment licensed		Tourism establishment licensed	
		Establishment	Capacity (Person)	Establishment	Capacity (Person)
Total		9	2105	162	45346
Restaurant	Total	1	300	61	20863
	1st Class	1	300	56	20383
	2nd Class			5	480
Private Establishment	Total			39	6948

	Class (None)			39	6948
Daily Establishment	Total	7	1400	12	4065
	Class (None)	7	1400	12	4065
Floating Establishment	Total	1	405	2	278
	Class (None)	1	405	2	278
Breakpoint	Total			2	575
	Class (None)			2	575
Gastronomy	Total			46	12617
	Class (None)			46	12617

Source: Ministry of Tourism Licensed Accommodation and Food and Beverage Establishment Statistics, 2002-2021

Table 96: Number of Tourism Licensed Food and Beverage Establishments According to Their Types and Classes (East Marmara)

NUMBER OF TOURISM LICENSED FOOD AND BEVERAGE ESTABLISHMENTS ACCORDING TO THEIR TYPES AND CLASSES (EAST MARMARA)					
Type	Class	Tourism investment licensed		Tourism establishment licensed	
		Establishment	Capacity (Person)	Establishment	Capacity (Person)
Total		2	710	94	28608
Restaurant	Total	1	250	52	17171
	1st Class	1	250	49	16906
	2nd Class			3	265
Private Establishment	Total			24	6770
	Class (None)			24	6770
Daily Establishment	Total	1	460	7	2085
	Class (None)	1	460	7	2085
Breakpoint	Total			1	120
	Class (None)			1	120
Gastronomy	Total			10	2462
	Class (None)			10	2462

Source: Ministry of Tourism Licensed Accommodation and Food and Beverage Establishment Statistics, 2002-2021

Table 97: Number of Tourism Licensed Food and Beverage Establishments According to Their Types and Classes (West Anatolia)

NUMBER OF TOURISM LICENSED FOOD AND BEVERAGE ESTABLISHMENTS ACCORDING TO THEIR TYPES AND CLASSES (WEST ANATOLIA)			
Type	Class	Tourism establishment licensed	
		Establishment	Capacity (Person)
Total		139	40190
Restaurant	Total	82	25475
	1st Class	66	23027
	2nd Class	16	2448
Private Establishment	Total	29	6908
	Class (None)	29	6908
Daily Establishment	Total	9	2430
	Class (None)	9	2430
Breakpoint	Total	3	1260
	Class (None)	3	1260
Gastronomy	Total	16	4117
	Class (None)	16	4117

Source: Ministry of Tourism Licensed Accommodation and Food and Beverage Establishment Statistics, 2002-2021

Table 98: Number of Tourism Licensed Food and Beverage Establishments According to Their Types and Classes (Mediterranean)

NUMBER OF TOURISM LICENSED FOOD AND BEVERAGE ESTABLISHMENTS ACCORDING TO THEIR TYPES AND CLASSES (MEDITERRANEAN)					
Type	Class	Tourism investment licensed		Tourism establishment licensed	
		Establishment	Capacity (Person)	Establishment	Capacity (Person)
Total		7	2872	64	20129
Restaurant	Total			18	6050
	1st Class			16	5600
	2nd Class			2	450
Private Establishment	Total			20	5281
	Class (None)			20	5281
Daily Establishment	Total	6	2040	14	2721
	Class (None)	6	2040	14	2721
Floating Establishment	Total			1	104

	Class (None)			1	104
Theme Park	Total	1	832		
	Class (None)	1	832		
Breakpoint	Total			3	1590
	Class (None)			3	1590
Gastronomy	Total			8	4383
	Class (None)			8	4383

Source: Ministry of Tourism Licensed Accommodation and Food and Beverage Establishment Statistics, 2002-2021

Table 99: Number of Tourism Licensed Food and Beverage Establishments According to Their Types and Classes (Central Anatolia)

NUMBER OF TOURISM LICENSED FOOD AND BEVERAGE ESTABLISHMENTS ACCORDING TO THEIR TYPES AND CLASSES (CENTRAL ANATOLIA)					
Type	Class	Tourism investment licensed		Tourism business licensed	
		Establishment	Capacity (Person)	Establishment	Capacity (Person)
Total		1	150	10	3210
Restaurant	Total			4	1445
	1st Class			4	1445
Café	Total	1	150		
	Class (None)	1	150		
Private Establishment	Total			2	610
	Class (None)			2	610
Daily Establishment	Total			2	605
	Class (None)			2	605
Theme Park	Total			1	450
	Class (None)			1	450
Gastronomy	Total			1	100
	Class (None)			1	100

Source: Ministry of Tourism Licensed Accommodation and Food and Beverage Establishment Statistics, 2002-2021

Table 100: Number of Tourism Licensed Food and Beverage Establishments According to Their Types and Classes (West Blacksea)

NUMBER OF TOURISM LICENSED FOOD AND BEVERAGE ESTABLISHMENTS ACCORDING TO THEIR TYPES AND CLASSES (WEST BLACKSEA)					
Type	Class	Tourism investment licensed		Tourism business licensed	
		Establishment	Capacity (Person)	Establishment	Capacity (Person)
Total		1	600	26	7433
Restaurant	Total			17	5549
	1st Class			15	5304
	2nd Class			2	245
Private Establishment	Total			7	1089
	Class (None)			7	1089
Winter Sports and Ski Establishments	Total	1	600		
	Class (None)	1	600		
Gastronomy	Total			2	795
	Class (None)			2	795

Source: Ministry of Tourism Licensed Accommodation and Food and Beverage Establishment Statistics, 2002-2021

Table 101: Number of Tourism Licensed Food and Beverage Establishments According to Their Types and Classes (East Blacksea)

NUMBER OF TOURISM LICENSED FOOD AND BEVERAGE ESTABLISHMENTS ACCORDING TO THEIR TYPES AND CLASSES (EAST BLACK SEA)					
Type	Class	Tourism investment licensed		Tourism business licensed	
		Establishment	Capacity (Person)	Establishment	Capacity (Person)
Total		2	450	19	5947
Restaurant	Total			11	4306
	1st Class			11	4306
Private Establishment	Total			6	1281
	Class (None)			6	1281
Daily Establishment	Total	2	450		
	Class (None)	2	450		
Gastronomy	Total			2	360
	(Sınıfı Yok)			2	360

Source: Ministry of Tourism Licensed Accommodation and Food and Beverage Establishment Statistics, 2002-2021

Table 102: Number of Tourism Licensed Food and Beverage Establishments According to Their Types and Classes (NorthEast Anatolia)

NUMBER OF TOURISM LICENSED FOOD AND BEVERAGE ESTABLISHMENTS ACCORDING TO THEIR TYPES AND CLASSES (NORTHEAST ANATOLIA)					
Type	Class	Tourism investment licensed		Tourism business licensed	
		Establishment	Capacity (Person)	Establishment	Capacity (Person)
Total		2	150	1	110
Restaurant	Total			1	110
	1st Class			1	110
Winter Sports and Ski Establishments	Total	2	150		
	Class (None)	2	150		

Source: Ministry of Tourism Licensed Accommodation and Food and Beverage Establishment Statistics, 2002-2021

Table 103: Number of Tourism Licensed Food and Beverage Establishments According to Their Types and Classes (CentralEast Anatolia)

NUMBER OF TOURISM LICENSED FOOD AND BEVERAGE ESTABLISHMENTS ACCORDING TO THEIR TYPES AND CLASSES (CENTRALEAST ANATOLIA)			
Type	Class	Tourism business licensed	
		Establishment	Capacity (Person)
Total		12	5250
Restaurant	Total	10	3665
	1st Class	9	3605
	2nd Class	1	60
Daily Establishment	Total	1	645
	Class (None)	1	645
Gastronomy	Total	1	940
	Class (None)	1	940

Source: Ministry of Tourism Licensed Accommodation and Food and Beverage Establishment Statistics, 2002-2021

Table 104: Number of Tourism Licensed Food and Beverage Establishments According to Their Types and Classes (SouthEast Anatolia)

NUMBER OF TOURISM LICENSED FOOD AND BEVERAGE ESTABLISHMENTS ACCORDING TO THEIR TYPES AND CLASSES (SOUTHEAST ANATOLIA)					
Type	Class	Tourism investment licensed		Tourism business licensed	
		Establishment	Capacity (Person)	Establishment	Capacity (Person)
Total		1	350	61	23330
Restaurant	Total	1	350	31	10815
	1st Class	1	350	30	10735
	2nd Class			1	80
Private Establishment	Total			7	2975
	Class (None)			7	2975
Daily Establishment	Total			4	2680
	Class (None)			4	2680
Breakpoint	Total			4	2210
	Class (None)			4	2210
Gastronomy	Total			15	4650
	Class (None)			15	4650

Source: Ministry of Tourism Licensed Accommodation and Food and Beverage Establishment Statistics, 2002-2021

"Domestic tourism expenditure also constitutes a significant input for the food and beverage sector. When the distribution of expenditure types in total travel expenditures are analyzed, it is seen that the expenditure types, which have the second highest shares, was eating and drinking expenditures with 29.8% in 2022. "As seen in the table 105 below, the amount spent by domestic tourists on food and beverage in 2021 increased from 18 billion 234 million 366 thousand TL to 34 billion 884 million 996 thousand TL in 2022 and reached a total of 36 billion 193 million 665 thousand TL in 2023."¹⁶

¹⁶ Ministry of Tourism Licensed Accommodation and Food and Beverage Establishment Statistics, 2002-2023.

Table 105: 2009-2022 Domestic Tourism Expenditure by Types of Expenditure and Quarters

Year	Package tour expenditures	Eating and drinking	Accommodation	Transportation
2009	613634	3346897	1039959	3705799
2010	605679	3839675	1068978	4428906
2011	664061	4555155	1402713	5029706
2012	932435	4884311	1412272	5366830
2013	1274597	5123880	1600964	5916310
2014	1159814	6643053	2192097	6758773
2015	1723958	7336305	2288932	7108739
2016	2490316	8632555	3115309	7766935
2017	2899922	10957325	3753780	9649226
2018	3507822	12283998	4887560	11746411
2019	3964996	15644988	5933370	13889437
2020	1880908	11789078	3710050	9411965
2021	5095471	18234366	8121933	15300151
2022	10774129	34884996	14806099	35093124
2023	11753665	36193665	24790403	26788933

Source: Ministry of Tourism Licensed Accommodation and Food and Beverage Establishment Statistics, 2002-2023

On the other hand, the tourism sector is of great importance in terms of its capacity to create employment opportunities for the country. Total tourism sector employment was 2.284.072 in 2019. Contribution of Food and beverage serving industry to total tourism sector was 1.305.850 with the highest rate.¹⁷

¹⁷ Tourism Sector in Türkiye, Presidency of The Republic of Türkiye, Investment Office, Invest Türkiye, 2020.

Table 106: Enterprises and Employment in Tourism

Türkiye: Enterprises and employment in tourism

	Number of establishments ¹	Number of persons employed				
	2020	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Total
Tourism industries	501 608	2 062 809	2 222 378	2 284 072	1 851 788	1 897 069
Accommodation services for visitors	23 024	294 958	343 928	368 941	297 322	313 745
Hotels and similar establishments	19 091	247 100	286 101	303 333	230 471	246 583
Food and beverage serving industry	271 214	1 189 288	1 253 134	1 305 850	1 045 965	1 059 197
Passenger transport	162 567	391 243	411 351	399 845	344 636	350 232
Air passenger transport	186
Railways passenger transport	.. c
Road passenger transport	159 178
Water passenger transport	3 203
Passenger transport supporting services
Transport equipment rental	10 424	24 250	27 593	28 855	27 606	24 204
Travel agencies and other reservation services industry	11 195	44 157	50 103	50 929	40 964	56 481
Cultural industry	5 455	56 491	55 111	54 065	41 076	35 686
Sports and recreation industry	17 729	62 422	81 158	75 587	54 220	57 525
Retail trade of country-specific tourism characteristic goods
Other country-specific tourism industries
Other industries

Sources: OECD Tourism Trends and Policies 2022, p.290.

2.1.2.2. Classification of Industry

Food and beverage operations include various types of restaurants (bistros, brasseries, coffee shops, first class/ fine dining, ethnic, themed), cafes, cafeterias, takeaways, canteens, function rooms, tray service operations, lounge service operations, home delivery operations and room service operations for hotel guests. Examples of the types of operation are given below.^{18 19}

Bistro: Often a smaller establishment with check tablecloths, bentwood chairs, cluttered décor and friendly informal staff. Tends to offer honest basic and robust cooking.

Brasseire: This is generally a large, styled room with a long bar, normally serving one-plate items rather than formal meals (though some offer both). Often it is possible just to have a drink, coffee or snack. Service provided by waiters, often in traditional style of long aprons and black waistcoats.

¹⁸<https://www.studocu.com/in/document/indian-institute-of-food-processing-technology/btech-food-technology/bhm-102t-super/30121785>.

¹⁹ <https://www.coursehero.com/file/43996337/BHM-102Tpdf>.

New Wave Brasserie (Gastro dome): Slick modern interior design, coupled with similar approaches to contemporary cuisine and service. Busy and bustling and often large and multileveled.

Coffee Shop: Similar to brasserie style operations, often themed. May be open all day and serve all meal types from breakfast through to supper.

First Class Restaurant: Usually formal fine dining restaurants with classical preparation and presentation of food and offering a high level of table (silver, gueridon and/ or plated) service. Often associated with classic / haute cuisine.

Restaurant: Term used to cover a wide variety of operation. Price, level and type of service, décor, styles, cuisines and degree of choice varies enormously across the range of type of operation. Service ranges from full table service to assisted service such as carvery style operations.

International Restaurant: Indian, oriental, Asian, Spanish, Greek, Italian, Creole and just some of the many types of cuisine available, with establishments tending to reflect specific ethnic origins. Many of the standard dishes are now appearing within a range of other menu types.

Themed Restaurant: Often international in orientation, for example, Icelandic hot rock with food prepared and cooked at the table. ' Beni Hana' oriental theme again with food prepared and cooked at table. Also includes themes such as jungle, rainforest or music/ opera, where waiting staff perform as well as serve.

Destination Restaurant: A destination restaurant is one that has a strong enough appeal to draw customers from beyond its community.

International Destination Restaurant: Often Michelin starred fine dining restaurants, offering a distinctive personality cuisine, ambiance, beverages and service. Usually table service at various levels but mostly personal and highly attentive. Generally considered as the home of gastronomy. Expensive but also value laden.

Health Food and Vegetarian Restaurants: Increasing specialization of operation into vegetarianism and health foods (though vegetarian food is not necessarily healthy), to meet lifestyle needs as well as dietary requirements.

Cafeteria: Primarily self-service with customer choosing selection from a counter or counters in varying designs and layouts. Originally developed for the industrial feeding market but now seen in a variety of sectors.

Popular Catering and Fast Food Outlets: Developed from table service teashops and cafes through to steakhouse and now incorporating snack bars, kiosks, diners, take aways and cafeterias with modern day burger, chicken and fish concept and with ethnic foods also being incorporated. Meeting the needs of all day meal dining and also the need for grab and go service, especially for the leisure, industrial and travelling markets.

Public Houses: Licensed environment primarily for drinking alcoholic beverages. May be simply a serving bar with standing room for customer or may have more plus surrounding incorporating the offer of a variety of foods.

Wine Bars: Often a mixture of bar and brasserie style operation, commonly wine themed serving a variety of foods.

Drive Through: A drive-through is a type of fast-food restaurant without seating; diners receive their food in their cars and drive away to eat. Most fast-food restaurants offer take-out: Ready-to-eat hot food in disposable packaging for the customer to eat off-site.

Café & Coffee House: Cafés are open for breakfast and serve full hot breakfasts. In some areas cafés offer outdoor seating. Coffee houses are casual restaurants without table service that emphasize coffee and other beverages; typically a limited selection of cold foods such as pastries and perhaps sandwiches are offered as well.

Business Centre: Commercial premises usually used by the occupier for a short period of time on the basis of the membership, for a reason like meeting, conference, small seminars etc. During this the food and beverage service provide to this member.

Kiosks: A small open-fronted hut or cubicle from which newspapers, refreshments, tickets, etc. are sold.

Snack Bars: A snack bar usually refers to an inexpensive food counter that is part of a permanent structure where snack foods and light meals are sold.

Fine dining Restaurant: This kind of restaurant primarily caters to the requirement of the affluent market segment which wants to experience fine dining. The restaurant may either offer dishes of one particular region or country or exotic dishes from various cuisines, wines, spirits and digestives. It is open mostly by during dinner time. The ambience and décor of the restaurant will be elegant are rich. The dining chair has arm rest. All the tables will be covered with good quality linen and napkin.

Banquets: Banquets is the highest revenue generating section of food and beverage department. Various types of functions like conferences, board meetings, cocktails parties, weddings, state banquets, etc are organized in the banquet room or hall of a hotel.

Cafeteria: The traditional cafeteria system consists of a straight line of counters containing a variety of hot and cold dishes. The customers start at the end of a line, pick up a tray and move along the length of the counter as they select dishes they want to have. The cashier who is seated at the end of the counter makes bills for the items selected and collects payment. This form of service is widely followed in institutional and industrial establishment.²⁰

2.1.2.3. Analysis of Leading Cities of Industry

Türkiye is the 18th most populous country in the world and is distinguished into many provinces. As can be observed in Figure 73, the Turkish provinces have very different sizes and climates, which plays a large role regarding population levels. The west of the country is the population core of the country while the population becomes smaller towards the east of the country. Türkiye's population is largely urban with 75% of individuals living in urban centers. Istanbul alone accounts for 18% of the total population of the country.²¹

Türkiye forms a key crossroads bringing together various cultures and ethnic groups between Europe and Asia. The country also incorporates numerous climates and biomes, from the Mediterranean climate on its west to the more continental climate found in the interior and east of the country. The country is further surrounded by the Mediterranean and Black seas. Most of Türkiye's larger urban centers are located

²⁰<https://www.coursehero.com/file/43996337/BHM-102Tpdf/>

²¹The Food And Beverage Market Entry Handbook: Türkiye, A Practical Guide To The Market in Türkiye For European Agri-Food Products, European Commission, European Research Executive Agency (REA), February, 2022.

towards the west of the country, such as Izmir and Istanbul, although the capital city Ankara is more centrally located. Other large urban centers are located along the Mediterranean coast of the country, such as Bursa and Adana. Within the east of the country, there are fewer large urban centers with the bigger cities being Diyarbakir and Malatya. Within the snapshot of important markets for EU food and beverages in Türkiye, the cities of Istanbul, Izmir, Ankara, Bursa and Antalya stand out. These cities are key urban centers in Türkiye for EU business, as well as being large tourism hotspots for EU citizens arriving in Türkiye.²²

Figure 73: Provinces of Türkiye by population

Source: Agra CEAS based on various

Türkiye has undergone a large urbanisation process in recent decades. Türkiye had an urban population percentage of 25% in 1950, which today stands at 76%²³. The majority of the hotels and resorts are concentrated in the south and west coasts of Türkiye and in large cities. Below, the prominent cities in Türkiye's tourism are examined in terms of food and beverage activities.

2.1.2.3.1. İstanbul

Istanbul is Türkiye's most populous city, with about 18% of the nation's total population living there. The city, which is surrounded by a crucial international choke point between the Black Sea and the Mediterranean through the strait of the Bosphorus, has historically and still is one of the most strategically situated cities in the world. Due to its three major airports and ports, rail and road connections to the EU, and by far the

²²The Food And Beverage Market Entry Handbook: Türkiye, A Practical Guide To The Market in Türkiye For European Agri-Food Products, European Commission, European Research Executive Agency (REA), February, 2022.

²³Urbanization in Türkiye 2021, Statista, 2023, <https://www.statista.com/statistics/255487/urbanization-in-Türkiye/>

biggest number of prospective consumers within Türkiye, Istanbul is the best site for EU food and beverages to enter Türkiye.

Istanbul is the most visited city in Türkiye, hence tourism plays a significant role in the city's economy. Due to the city's popularity as a tourist destination, there is a high demand for cuisine and drinks from the European Union. Irish bars, French restaurants, and Greek cafes are all commonplace in the city. Istanbul holds several significant food events every year that can be used to promote EU foods and drinks. These occasions include the yearly WorldFood Istanbul conference and the annual Istanbul Street Festival in October. Istanbul is a major economic hub in Türkiye, therefore its residents have more purchasing power than people in most other parts of the country, which makes it easier for them to buy food and drink from the EU. Because a significant number of travelers are passing through the city on their way to or from Europe, Africa, or Asia, this presents an additional marketing opportunity. On their way to a third location, 12 million people are thought to pass through Istanbul annually on average.²⁴

Istanbul offers a wide variety of food and beverage options to satisfy this demand. The Ministry of Culture and Tourism's "Tourism Establishment Certificate" and "Tourism Investment Certificate" data on the catering facilities' capabilities are shown in the table below. The combined capacity of the facilities holding a "Tourism Establishment Certificate" is 157,908 people, while the combined capacity of the facilities holding a "Tourism Investment Certificate" is 1,406. Examining the location of the facilities reveals that Beyoğlu, Beşiktaş, Şişli, Eminönü (excluding entertainment venues), and Bakırköy and Kadıköy on the Anatolian Side are the major focal points on the European Side.²⁵

²⁴Istanbul Travel guide, Insight guides (available at <https://www.insightguides.com/destinations/europe/Türkiye/istanbul>), Istanbul city guide, All About Istanbul (available at <http://www.allaboutistanbul.com/>), Geography of Istanbul, Easy Expat (available at <https://www.easyexpat.com/en/guides/Türkiye/istanbul/overview/geography.htm>).

²⁵Türkiye Ve İstanbul Bölgesi'nde Turizm, İstanbul Kalkınma Ajansı, Temmuz, 2012.

Table 107: Number and Capacity of Food and Beverage Facilities in İstanbul with Tourism Establishment Certificate- Tourism Investment Certificate

Facility Type and Class	Establishment Certificate		Tourism Investment Certificate	
	Number of Facilities	Capacity	Number of Facilities	Capacity
Gastronomy	108	22.043	0	0
Day facility	16	6.207	1	350
Cafeteria	5	925	0	0
1. Class restaurant	136	71.056	3	1.056
2. Class restaurant	32	6.430	0	0
Fine dining	1	600	0	0
Private facility	215	39.143	0	0
Floating facility	24	11.504	0	0
Total	537	157.908	4	1.406

Resource: Republic of Türkiye Ministry of Culture and Tourism, General Directorate of Investments and Enterprises

2.1.2.3.2. İzmir

Izmir is a city in Anatolia's extreme western region that is close to Greece. The city, which is Türkiye's third most populated, is a major cultural and tourist destination. Izmir is an important hub in the region for the entry of goods and individuals, with the port of Izmir being the main port in Türkiye used for exports. The port of Izmir facilitates the movement of goods and individuals throughout the Mediterranean Sea including the ports of Athens and Thessaloniki in Greece.²⁶

Izmir has a number of historic ruins that represent the city's historical importance, including monuments from the Roman Empire. A total of 1.2 million tourists visited the city in 2019 before the COVID-19 outbreak, which is mostly attributable to this and the city's closeness to other important tourist destinations like the Greek islands. Additionally, a significant factor in the city's desire for EU foods and beverages is the high number of tourists who travel there each year.²⁷

²⁶Visit Izmir, Aegean food summit (available at <https://www.visitizmir.org/en/Destinasyon/10862>); A brief introduction to Izmir, Root Invest Izmir (available at <https://rootinvest.net/a-brief-introduction-to-the-city-of-izmir/>); All about Türkiye (available at <https://www.allaboutTürkiye.com/izmir.html>).

²⁷Visit Izmir, Aegean food summit (available at <https://www.visitizmir.org/en/Destinasyon/10862>); A brief introduction to Izmir, Root Invest Izmir (available at <https://rootinvest.net/a-brief-introduction-to-the-city-of-izmir/>); All about Türkiye (available at <https://www.allaboutTürkiye.com/izmir.html>).

Izmir is frequently cited as one of Türkiye's more socially liberal cities, with more Western social norms and less taboos against drinking. As a result, regarding alcohol consumption, Izmir is generally more liberal.²⁸

Izmir is located on the Aegean coast of Türkiye, and the city's cuisine is heavily influenced by the Aegean and Mediterranean regions. There are some popular local foods of Izmir include Boyoz (A pastry made from dough and filled with a mixture of tahini and eggs), Kumru (A type of sandwich made with sesame-covered bread, sucuk (Turkish sausage), grilled cheese, tomato, and pickles), İzmir köfte (Meatballs made from ground beef or lamb mixed with onions, garlic, breadcrumbs, and spices. They are usually served with tomato sauce and rice or bulgur) and Zeytinyağlı yaprak sarma (Stuffed grape leaves filled with rice, onions, pine nuts, and herbs, cooked in olive oil). These are just a few examples of the many delicious foods that can be found in Izmir. The city's cuisine is diverse, and visitors can enjoy a wide variety of dishes from traditional Turkish cuisine to international flavors.

Izmir plays host to a number of events throughout the year including trade fairs, congresses and exhibitions. One of the larger events, the Aegean cuisine summit, is held in the city annually and showcases foods from both Türkiye and abroad. The city also has several food bazaars which help to facilitate the distribution of food and beverages to citizens of the city.²⁹ Slow Food Izmir organizes various events and activities throughout the year, including farmers' markets, food tastings, workshops, and seminars. The organization also supports local food producers and advocates for policies that promote sustainable and traditional food production methods.³⁰

2.1.2.3.3. Ankara

The second-most populous city in Türkiye after Istanbul is Ankara, which serves as the nation's capital. The then-relatively tiny settlement of Angora was designated as the capital city and given the new name of Ankara by the Turkish Grand Assembly in 1920. Ankara's population has increased quickly since becoming the country's capital, and thanks to the central government's encouragement of investment and habitation, the

²⁸Visit Izmir, Aegean food summit (available at <https://www.visitizmir.org/en/Destinasyon/10862>); A brief introduction to Izmir, Root Invest Izmir (available at <https://rootinvest.net/a-brief-introduction-to-the-city-of-izmir/>); All about Türkiye (available at <https://www.allaboutTürkiye.com/izmir.html>).

²⁹Visit Izmir, Aegean food summit (available at <https://www.visitizmir.org/en/Destinasyon/10862>); A brief introduction to Izmir, Root Invest Izmir (available at <https://rootinvest.net/a-brief-introduction-to-the-city-of-izmir/>); All about Türkiye (available at <https://www.allaboutTürkiye.com/izmir.html>).

³⁰ <https://www.izmir.bel.tr/tr/Haberler/izmir-uluslararası-fuar-icin-ev-sahipligine-hazir/46985/156>.

city is now a significant economic hub for Türkiye. Some of Türkiye's most significant strategic institutions, notably the aerospace and defense industries, are based in Ankara. One of the largest weaponry manufacturing operations in the world has its headquarters in the city. Additionally, the city also has assembly factories for a number of international automakers, which serves as another draw for residents. The city's employment is largely dependent on the presence of numerous important governmental institutions, notably the divisions of the ministries and the numerous foreign embassies that have relocated there.

As of today, there are 5.6 million people living in Ankara. The city is a key market for EU foods and beverages because it is the country's capital, its industrial and service economies have grown recently, and it is strategically located in the interior of the country, allowing it to serve as a key economic hub outside of Türkiye's more populous western region. The presence of EU embassy workers in Ankara serves as an additional market for the city's numerous modest French, Irish, and German-themed food and beverage establishments. Ankara experiences less tourism than other Turkish cities because the majority of tourists from the EU are presumably there for business-related reasons.³¹ With options ranging from traditional Turkish haunts to a variety of upscale fine dining restaurants, the city provides a diverse dining scene because of its blend of old heritage and current, metropolitan flavor.

2.1.2.3.4. Antalya

On Anatolia's southwest coast, the city of Antalya is encircled by the Taurus Mountains. The city has Türkiye's fifth-highest population. One of Türkiye's busiest travel destinations is Antalya, which had 13.6 million visitors in 2019 prior to the COVID-19 epidemic. The fact that Antalya offers air service to many significant EU cities makes it even easier for EU nationals to visit the city. An estimated 30% of all visitors arriving in Türkiye are thought to be travelling to Antalya.

Due to the abundance of ancient remains dating from the Ottoman era to the ancient Greeks, tourists are attracted to the city. Greek restaurants, Italian restaurants, and Irish pubs are among the EU-themed food service establishments that are present in the city as a result of the significant number of tourists from the EU. The main factor that

³¹ The Food And Beverage Market Entry Handbook: Türkiye, A Practical Guide To The Market in Türkiye For European Agri-Food Products, European Commission, European Research Executive Agency (REA), February, 2022, p.13.

makes Antalya a significant market for EU foods and drinks is tourism, as consumption of EU foods and drinks, such as alcohol, is more widespread in the city than it is across the rest of the nation.

The gastronomy in Antalya is predominantly of Mediterranean origin, and two particularly well-liked dishes are piyaz (made of tahini, garlic, and baked beans) and sis kofte (hot meatballs cooked on a stick). The city has also played host to a number of events, including as the September festival and the Golden Orange Film Festival in Antalya. Once the more immediate effects of COVID-19 have been reversed, Antalya is anticipated to see a comeback in tourism, making the city an appealing future market for EU foods and beverages in Türkiye.³²

2.1.2.3.5. Bursa

The fourth-largest city in terms of population in Türkiye is the city of Bursa, which lies close to Istanbul. Bursa served as the Ottoman empire's historical capital and continues to be significant as Istanbul's primary economic rival in the Marmara region. With businesses like FIAT, Renault, and Bosch based in the city, Bursa is the main base of automobile manufacturing in Türkiye. Additionally, Bursa is a sizable dairy producer, and the city is widely recognized throughout Türkiye for its superior dairy goods. Due to its proximity to Mount Uludag, one of Türkiye's more well-known ski resorts, Bursa draws a number of tourists. Historically, the city's primary economic sector was agriculture, but as the city has increasingly been industrialized, this has changed.

Due to its size, proximity to the EU, and closeness to Istanbul, which promotes cross-city commerce, this city stands out as a significant market snapshot for EU foods and beverages. Being the second-most populous city in the Marmara area, which borders the EU members Bulgaria and Greece, the city serves as a desirable export hub for goods from the EU as well as other nations. The population of the city is still rising as Istanbul, which is close, experiences an increase in population. As a result, Bursa stands out as a crucial secondary market in the Marmara region, which is anticipated

³²Introduction of Antalya, AsiaVtour (available at https://www.asiavtour.com/Türkiye_Antalya_Introduction_a575.html), Overview of tourism activities in Antalya, Get Your Guide (available at <https://www.getyourguide.com/destinations/antalya-1172/>), Visiting Antalya, Visit Türkiye (available at <https://www.visasTürkiye.com/antalya-travel-guide/>).

to continue expanding in significance as a result of the region's population increase and the presence of significant international corporations.³³

2.1.2.3.6. Eskişehir

Eskişehir is a city in northwestern Türkiye and it has a rich culinary culture that reflects the region's history and geography. Since Eskişehir is a university city, food and beverage opportunities are very active. There are many budget-friendly restaurants, cafes, fast food chains and street delicacies in the city.

According to the data updated in December 2018, there are twenty-seven food and beverage facilities in Eskişehir with tourism establishment certificate. Of these; Seventeen are first class restaurants (the duration of this status is not clear because the regulation has changed), one is a second class restaurant, five are private facilities, and four are daily facilities. Considering all of the food and beverage businesses operating in the city center of Eskişehir, it is seen that there are many businesses ranging from small and large restaurants that offer only local and limited dishes (such as çibörek, ravioli, balaban) to Chinese, Mexican and Italian restaurants that offer world cuisine. The existence of food and beverage businesses is positive for a destination that wants to advance in the field of tourism. However, the fact that the local cuisine is not presented in all its lines in the food and beverage establishments operating in Eskişehir, and that there is local food only in the establishments specializing in "some regional dishes" and in a small number of establishments where some of the local dishes are tried to be served together with other dishes is an important shortcoming³⁴.

Businesses that will offer local food in the districts as well as in the center of Eskişehir should be encouraged. Because, in order to promote the local cuisine and to keep it alive, the food and beverage businesses operating in the region have great duties. Local dishes will be recognized as they are made, kept alive as they are known, and thus the culture will be able to continue. Local food presentation will also make a positive contribution to food and beverage businesses. According to Hjalager and Richards (2002), serving local food in restaurants gives businesses both competitive advantage and market success. In addition, local dishes not only give superiority to

³³Bursa Travel guide, lonely planet (available at <https://www.lonelyplanet.com/Türkiye/bursa>), Why Bursa Türkiye is a must visit, travel awaits (available at <https://www.travelawaits.com/2496241/things-to-do-in-bursa-Türkiye/>).

³⁴ BEBKA, Eskişehir İlinin Turizm Kaynaklarının Mekânsal Analizi ve Turizm Pazarlama Stratejisi Sonuç Raporu, 2020.

food and beverage businesses or affect the destination choice of tourists, but also contribute to creating new business opportunities in the region and supporting regional development.³⁵

2.1.2.3.7. Gaziantep

Gaziantep city was included in the UNESCO Creative Cities Network program in 2015 with its gastronomy field. 60% of the population in Gaziantep works in the gastronomy sector. About half (49%) of the companies owned by the city are focused on the food sector such as spices, grains and vegetables. In Gaziantep, gastronomy means intercultural fusion and social harmony.³⁶

The sustainable projects committed by Gaziantep, which applied for the UNESCO Creative Cities Network gastronomy field, are as follows ³⁷

- Neighborhood Kitchens
- Registering heritage: Herbs
- Barrier-Free Workshop
- Cultural Exchange with Silk Road Cities
- International Gastronomy Festival
- Improving Storage-Marketing Conditions of Spices

Gaziantep realized its first activity in 2011, which aims to carry its local cuisine from the local to the global and to increase intercultural relations, by organizing a festival called "GastroAntep" with the participation of approximately 250,000 visitors. For the purposes of this festival, both the local flavors and culture and history of Gaziantep were introduced in an international context. A total of 230 chefs, 90 of whom were UNESCO chefs, participated in the festival and many famous chefs made presentations. International Gaziantep Gastronomy Festival (GastroAntep), which will be held for the 4th time this year, will take place between 15-18 September with the theme of "Sustainability". At the international festival that will once again bring

³⁵ Hjalager, A. M., & Richards, G. (2003). *Tourism and Gastronomy*. Routledge.

³⁶ <https://en.unesco.org/creative-cities/gaziantep>, 25.04.2023

³⁷ Mutlu, H (2019). "Unesco Gastronomi Alanında Rehber Kriterlerin Gaziantep Gastronomisi Açısından Değerlendirilmesi", *Uluslararası Sosyal Araştırmalar Dergisi*, 12(67), 929-963.

Gaziantep to the world stage with its ancient cuisine; World-renowned Michelin-starred chefs, Türkiye's famous chefs, hotel and restaurant investors, industry representatives and professionals, gourmets, life coaches, dietitians, food producers, gastronomy students, agricultural producers, suppliers and academics will come together.³⁸

The city of Gaziantep also received an award within the scope of the 2015 theme of "Local Gastronomy and Tourism" of the European Destinations of Excellence Project (EDEN).³⁹

According to the 2020 November TÜRSAB Gaziantep report, the types of accommodation facilities, the number of hotels, the number of rooms and the number of beds in Gaziantep province are given in Table 108.

Table 108: Types of Accommodation Facilities and Number of Hotels, Rooms and Beds

Type	Number of hotel	Number of room	Number of bed
Municipality certified	16	554	1.074
Establishment certificated	49	3.929	7.839
Investment certificated	13	1.044	2.201
Total	78	5.527	11.114

Source: TÜRSAB, 2020

Of the accommodation facilities with establishment certificate, 6 are five-star, 13 are four-star, and 16 are three-star. According to the data of Gaziantep Ministry of Culture and Tourism, domestic and foreign tourists entering through the border gates are given in Table 109.

³⁸ <https://www.gaziantep.bel.tr/tr/haberler/uluslararasi-4-gastroantep-festivali-basliyor>, 24.04.2023

³⁹ <https://www.gaziantepgastronomy.com/en/gaziantep-mutfag%CC%86i/>, 24.04.2023

Table 109: Distribution of Domestic and Foreign Tourists Entering Through Border Gates by Years

Years	Domestic	Foreign	Total
2012	88.523	125.274	213.797
2013	68.322	150.102	218.424
2014	74.966	31.874	106.840
2015	77.018	27.424	104.442
2016	95.241	26.038	121.279
2017	100.030	34.124	134.154
2018	113.740	45.897	159.637
2019	133.289	66.644	199.933
2020	43.099	24.441	67.540

Source: <https://gaziantep.ktb.gov.tr>

In Table 110 the number of tourists staying in hotels with establishment certificates of Gaziantep province is given.

Table 110: Distribution of Tourists Staying in Hotels with Establishment Certificate by Years

Years	Domestic	Foreign	Total
2012	253.043	48.327	301.370
2013	269.225	45.371	314.596
2014	310.325	123.875	434.200
2015	359.332	95.311	454.643
2016	395.065	80.249	475.314
2017	524.660	98.357	623.017
2018	562.563	113.339	675.902
2019	593.592	125.220	718.812
2020	363.999	58.864	422.863

Source: <https://gaziantep.ktb.gov.tr>

According to the TÜRSAB 2020 report, the number of domestic and foreign tourists entering the facilities in Gaziantep is given in Table 111.

When the domestic and foreign tourists visiting the accommodation facilities in Gaziantep are examined, it is seen that there was an increase of 10.16% in 2019 compared to the previous year. The distribution of foreign tourists entering the accommodation facilities in Gaziantep is given in Table 111. When table 111 is examined, it is seen that Gaziantep city attracts tourists from many parts of the world.

Table 111: Distribution of Foreign Tourists Entering Accommodation Facilities by Nationality

Country	Number of Entries
Iraq	44.147
Germany	8.186
Iranian	4.070
United States of America	3.207
Italy	2.744
Jordan	2.300
People's Republic of China	2.279
Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus	2.112
England (United Kingdom)	1.915
France	1.881

Source: TÜRSAB, 2020

2.1.2.3.8. Hatay/Antakya

Hatay (2017), which is included in the UNESCO Creative Cities Network program with its gastronomy, has a multicultural structure due to its location on the Ancient Silk Road. Due to its location, it has been the center of spice trade for hundreds of years. It earns 60% of its income from the trade of medicinal and aromatic plants. Many different organizations such as Hatay Agriculture Fair and Hatay Kunepe Festival are organized in order to promote the local food culture and their agricultural diversity.⁴⁰

Hatay, which is included in the UNESCO Creative Cities Network Program, has foreseen that it will contribute to the purposes of UNESCO:⁴¹

⁴⁰Sağdıç, E. (2022). Motivasyon Kaynağı Olarak Yiyecek ve İçecekler: Gastronomi Şehirleri Üzerine Bir Araştırma (Master's thesis, Necmettin Erbakan Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü).

⁴¹ <https://en.unesco.org/creative-cities/hatay>, 24.04.2023

- Establishing an agri-food park consisting of farmers, women, suppliers and retailers in order to achieve success in the field of gastronomy,
- Establishment of the Food Academy, which will organize trainings and certificate programs by chefs and professionals in this field,
- Collaborating with other UNESCO Creative Cities Network gastronomy cities,
- Organizing the World Gastronomy Kitchen Fair and ensuring the participation of other Creative Cities in this fair,
- Providing consultancy and training on agriculture, food and gastronomy to women and children who come to Hatay city as refugees.

The statistical information of the locals and foreigners entering the city from the provincial borders of Hatay according to the years is given in Table 112.

Table 112: Domestic and Foreign Statistics Entering the City from the Provincial Borders

Years	Domestics	Foreign	Total
2012	223.627	345.269	568.896
2013	98.760	412.232	510.992
2014	114.670	423.084	537.754
2015	111.463	157.130	268.593
2016	125.081	161.150	286.231
2017	125.808	182.654	308.462
2018	116.913	186.804	303.717
2019	114.210	179.264	293.474
2020	39.976	67.754	107.730
2021(Jan-Oct)	28.889	140.984	169.873

Source: <https://hatay.ktb.gov.tr>

Table 113 showed that the number of entrances to Hatay, which progressed stagnantly until 2015, decreased after 2015 as a result of some political events. The reason for the decline in 2020 can be seen as COVID-19.

Table 113: Number of Tourists Entering Accommodation Facilities

Years	Domestic	Foreign	Total
2018	677.964	61.980	739.944
2019	682.936	56.538	739.474
2019(jan-agu)	459.343	39.520	498.863
2020(jan-agu)	307.719	15.620	323.339

Source: TÜRSAB Hatay Report, 2020

In 2023, following the earthquake in Hatay, the impact on the food and beverage sector was significant. Businesses in this sector experienced disruptions in operations, supply chain challenges, and potential damage to infrastructure. The extent of the effects varied, with some establishments facing temporary closures and others dealing with reduced customer demand.

2.1.2.3.9. Nevşehir

The Kapadokya Region, which is on the World Heritage List, is within the Kayseri-Aksaray-Niğde triangle in the Central Anatolia Region of Türkiye and its geographical area exceeds 5000 km².⁴² This region of Central Anatolia, which has a very different cultural feature, is one of Türkiye's most attractive tourist destinations and most important tourism centers with its magnificent and unique landforms and historical heritage. Recently, local cuisine is recognized as one of the most important heritages of destinations or a country. Nevşehir, which is rich in natural beauties and culture, also has an authentic and rich cuisine. While Nevşehir and Kapadokya touristic region reflects the traditional Turkish cuisine, it has a remarkable local cuisine as it contains the cultures of the civilizations that reigned in the region before and after, and various religious accumulations.⁴³

When the leading dishes of Kapadokya cuisine are listed, it will be seen that the dishes prepared by mixing cereal varieties and pulses products with meat attract attention. The use of cooking tools such as clay pots and casseroles is common in the local

⁴² Aydan, Ö., & Ulusay, R. (2003). Geotechnical and geoenvironmental characteristics of man-made underground structures in Kapadokya, Türkiye. *Engineering Geology*, 69(3-4), 245-272.

⁴³Buyruk, M. Y. (2022). Turistlerin yerel yiyecek-içecek tercihleri ve memnuniyet durumlarının araştırılması: Kapadokya örneği (Master's thesis, Nevşehir Hacı Bektaş Veli Üniversitesi).

cuisine. With the use of such containers for years, original dishes such as **kuru fasulye** (ağ pakla) in pots, **Nevşehir tava** ve **güveçte yaprak sarması** have emerged.⁴⁴

In Kapadokya, there are restaurants and cafes serving many traditional Turkish cuisine, which attract the attention of local and foreign tourists. The food and beverage facilities in the region reflect the international cuisine as well as serving local delicacies. Kapadokya is also famous for its wine culture. Some wineries in the area offer wine tasting tours and tours with information about wine production.⁴⁵ There are also markets in Kapadokya where organic products of local producers are sold.

2.1.2.4. Leading Companies of Industry

Leading companies of food and beverage industry can be classified into four categories. These categories are full-service restaurants, limited-service restaurants, fast-food chains and Michelin awarded restaurants.

2.1.2.4.1. Full-Service Restaurants

Full-service restaurants, which were hit the hardest during the pandemic, saw the largest increase in sales in 2021. Some of the important full-service restaurants are listed below in table 114. The increase in tourism will benefit the food sector, especially full-service restaurants. Interestingly, sales in terms of TL exceeded prepandemic levels because of inflation. However, sales in USD terms and the numbers of restaurants and transactions lagged behind pre-pandemic levels. It will probably take a few more years for sales (USD terms) and the number of restaurants to reach where they were prior to the pandemic.⁴⁶

Table 114: Full-Service Restaurants

1.Big Chefs (Casual)
2.Mid-Point (Casual)
3.Kitchenette (Casual)
4.The House Café (Casual)

⁴⁴Buyruk, M. Y. (2022). Turistlerin yerel yiyecek-içecek tercihleri ve memnuniyet durumlarının araştırılması: Kapadokya örneği (Master's thesis, Nevşehir Hacı Bektaş Veli Üniversitesi).

⁴⁵ <http://www.Kapadokyaexplorer.com/detay.php?id=232&cid=172>

⁴⁶GAIN, Food Service: Hotel, Restaurant, Institutional in Türkiye ,October-2022, https://Apps.Fas.Usda.Gov/Newgainapi/Api/Report/Downloadreportbyfilename?Filename=Food%20service%20%20hotel%20restaurant%20institutional_Ankara_Türkiye_Tu2022-0045.Pdf

5.Leman Kultur (Casual)
6.Happy Moon's (Casual)
7.Cook Shop (Casual)
8.Kirinti (Casual)
9.SushiCo (Casual)
10.Eataly Türkiye (Casual)
11.Mezalluna(non-casual)
12.Paper Moon Türkiye (Non-casual)
13.Nusret (Casual, Steak)
14.Gunaydin Et (Kebap, Steak)
15.Kosebasi Kebap
16.Develi Kebap
17. Kasibeyaz Kebap
18. Gelik (Kebap)
19. Tike (Kebap)
20. Hamdi Kebap

The results of the 'Food and Drink Research', which was held by Metro Türkiye, in cooperation with the research and consultancy company KONDA in 31 provinces with the participation of 2,725 people in March 2022 indicated that full service restaurants come first in eating out preferences. The rate of preference for kebabs and fish places almost doubled in 2022 when compared to 2017.⁴⁷ According to Trip Advisor 2023 data, the top 10 seafood restaurants in Istanbul are listed in the table 115 below.

Table 115: Top 10 Seafood Restaurants in Istanbul

	Restaurant	Score
1	Nova Roma Terrace & Restaurant	5
2	Zerzevan Fish & Kebab House	5
3	GRACE Rooftop Restaurant	5
4	Hagia Sophia Terrace Restaurant	5
5	Şiva lobster fish restaurant	5
6	As You Sea Seafood & Kebab	5
7	Rainbow Fish & Meat Restaurant	5
8	By Ferro Fish&kebab House	5
9	Gardenia Bistro Restaurant	5
10	Safi Roof Lounge	5

⁴⁷ Metro&Konda Yeme İçme Araştırması, <https://brosurler.metro-tr.com/yeme-icme-arastirmasi-basin-toplantisi/page/3>

During the last decade, there have been several foreign full-service restaurants/brands that entered the Turkish market but later left for different reasons. Some of the restaurants that came and went, include El Torito, TGI Friday's, Chili's, Jamie Oliver, Tom's Kitchen, Spice Market, Hakkasan, Benihana, Armani Café, Ciprani, Bice, Nando's, Laduree, De Silvano, Rainforest Café, P.F. Chang's, and Hard Rock Café. Some foreign chains, such as Zuma, downsized their footprint. Foreign cafés such as Paul's and Baskin Robbins have also left Türkiye.⁴⁸ According to one food industry contact, the reason these restaurants didn't last or had to reduce the size of the operations was because their menu prices were too expensive compared to other dining-out options, especially fast-food options.

Foreign cafés such as Paul's and Baskin Robbin's also left Türkiye. Cheese Cake Factory has decided not to get into the market due to restrictions on some ingredients. Türkiye has not authorized use of any biotech products in food and maintains a zero-tolerance policy. Many local fine dining restaurants also closed or reduced their number of outlets. This can be partly attributed to the decreasing number of western tourists in large cities and shrinking purchasing power of the upper-middle class has caused these exits and cut-backs in the foreign chain restaurant brands and non-casual full-service and especially fine-dining segment. On the other hand, foreign fast food chains such as McDonalds, Arby's, Popeye's etc. and café chains such as Starbucks continued expansion through opening more outlets in the last decade, including over the last few years.⁴⁹

2.1.2.4.2. Limited-Service Restaurants

In contrast to foreign full-service restaurants, foreign fast-food restaurants, such as Popeyes, Burger King, and others, are quite popular in the market since menu items are typically cheaper. Food sales for cafes/bars and limited-service restaurants in 2021 also increased year-on-year but at a slower pace compared to full-service restaurants. Both the number of and sales at limited service restaurants, especially pizza

⁴⁸ GAIN, Food Service: Hotel, Restaurant, Institutional in Türkiye October 2022 https://Apps.Fas.Usda.Gov/Newgainapi/Api/Report/Downloadreportbyfilename?Filename=Food%20service%20%20hotel%20restaurant%20institutional_Ankara_Türkiye_Tu2022-0045.Pdf

⁴⁹ GAIN, Food Service: Hotel, Restaurant, Institutional in Türkiye October-2022 https://Apps.Fas.Usda.Gov/Newgainapi/Api/Report/Downloadreportbyfilename?Filename=Food%20service%20%20hotel%20restaurant%20institutional_Ankara_Türkiye_Tu2022-0045.Pdf, p.6

restaurants, bakeries, and coffee shops, is expected to expand in the future as Turks search for cheaper alternatives amid diminishing purchasing power. Of particular interest, the number of coffee shops has increased in parallel with a fivefold increase in per capita coffee consumption over the last 15 years.⁵⁰ The results of the 'Food and Drink Research 2022', indicated that the rate of those who say that they often and always drink coffee outside has increased by 50% compared to 2017. The rate of those who say they always drink coffee outside has more than doubled.⁵¹

Some of the important limited-service restaurants and Coffee Shops are listed below in table 116.

Table 116: Limited-Service Restaurants and Coffee Shops

Fast Food	Pizza Chains	Coffee Shops
1. McDonald's Türkiye	1. Pizza Hut	1. Starbucks Türkiye
2. Burger King Türkiye	2. Papa John's	2. Kahve Dunyasi
3. Arby's Türkiye	3. Domino's	3. Caffé Nero
4. Kentucky Fried Chicken Türkiye	4. Little Caesars	4. Tchibo
5. Popeye's Türkiye	5. Pizza	5. Caribou Türkiye
6. Carl's Jr. Türkiye	6. Bafetto	6. Gloria Jean's Türkiye
7. Subway Türkiye	7. Pizza Bulls	7. Barrie's Coffee & Tea Türkiye
8. Bereket Doner	8. Panino Pizza	8. Lavazza Türkiye
9. Bay Doner	9. Pasaport Pizza	9. KahveciHacibaba
10. Usta Donerci	10. Pizza House	10. Gonul Kahvesi
11. Tavuk Dunyasi	11. Pizza Raffaele	11. Kahve Duragi
12. Kofteci Ramiz	12. Tadim Pizza	12. Kahve Diyari
13. Sultanahmet Koftecisi	13. Sampi Pide (Turkish style pizza)	13. Kahve Deryasi
14. Kasap Doner	14. Neli Pide (Turkish style)	14. TheEspresso Lab
15. Etiler Marmaris	15. Bafra Pide (Turkish style)	15. Bayramefendi Osmanli Kahvecisi
16. Oses Cigkofte	16. Citir Usta (Turkish style)	16. Kocatepe Kahve Evi
17. Komagene	17. Pidem (Turkish style)	
18. Kahta Cigkofte		
19. Cigkoftem		
20. Simit Sarayi		
21. Sbarro Türkiye		
22. Ekrem Coskun Doner		

⁵⁰GAIN, Food Service: Hotel, Restaurant, Institutional in Türkiye ,October-2022, https://apps.fas.usda.gov/newgainapi/api/report/downloadreportbyfilename?filename=Food%20service%20%20hotel%20restaurant%20institutional_Ankara_Turkiye_Tu2022-0045.Pdf.

⁵¹Metro&Konda Yeme İçme Araştırması, <https://brosurler.metro-tr.com/yeme-icme-arastirmasi-basin-toplantisi/page/3>.

2.1.2.4.3. Fast-Food Chains

We can see that chain restaurants are leading the sector in limited-service restaurants and coffee shops. The ranking of both international and domestic top 10 fast food chain restaurants and coffee shops according to the market share is given below in Table 117 and Table 118 for the year 2019 and 2020.

Table 117: Top10 Foreign Fast Food Chain Brands in Türkiye (by market share)

Number	Year 2019	Year 2020
1.	Burger King (USA)	Burger King (USA)
2.	Mc Donald's (USA)	Starbucks (USA)
3.	Popeye's (USA)	Domino's Pizza (USA)
4.	Kentucky Fried Chicken (USA)	Mc Donald's (USA)
5.	Subway (USA)	Kentucky Fried Chicken (USA)
6.	Arby's (USA)	Popeye's (USA)
7.	Carl's Jr. (USA)	Little Caesar (USA)
8.	Sbarro (USA)	Arby's (USA)
9.	Pinkberry (USA)	Subway (USA)
10.	Krispy Kreme (USA)	Krispy Kreme (USA)

Source: CIA World Fact Book: Euromonitor International: Turkish Statistical Institute; Trade Monitor International

Table: 118: Top10 Domestic Fast Food Chain Brands in Türkiye (by market share)

Number	Year 2019	Year 2020
1.	Tavuk Dünyası	Komagene Ciğköfte
2.	Komagene Ciğköfte	Tavuk Dünyası
3.	Oses Ciğköfte	Kahve Dünyası
4.	Simit Sarayı	Oses Ciğköfte
5.	Pidem	Ekrem Coşkun Döner
6.	Bereket Döner	Pidem
7.	Bay Döner	Big Chef's
8.	Ekrem Coşkun Döner	Bay Döner
9.	Usta Döner	Mid Point
10.	Çiğ Köftem	Günaydın

Sources: CIA World Fact Book :Euromonitor International:Türkish Statistical Institute; Trade Monitor International

2.1.2.4.4. Michelin Awarded Restaurants

In addition to chains, fine dining restaurants constitute an important part of the sector. These restaurants have menus based on non-national, rather world cuisines, where creative dishes are served, seasonal and local ingredients are used, appealing to individuals with high purchasing power, restaurant atmosphere and service are at the highest level, prices are kept above the standards. These restaurants make customer feel special and at the same time stay healthy. Customers pay for an elegant and luxurious experience. These restaurants, which satisfy their customers, employees and owners, have a very high profit margin. Professional and experienced employees require high-cost employees. The investment cost and the high expenses are among the negative aspects of the fine dining restaurant. The main fine dining restaurants in Istanbul are listed below.

Table 119: Fine Dining Restaurants

Restaurants
Zuma
Paper Moon
Nusr-et
Da Mario
Nobu
Vogue
Spago
360
Sunset Bar & Grill
Lacivert
Hotel Based Restaurants
16 Roof, Swissotel
Mikla
Spago
Tugra
Shang Palace
Toro
Novikov

According to the 2023 evaluation results of Michelin Guide Istanbul, one of the most respected restaurant evaluation systems in the world, 5 restaurants in Istanbul have been awarded with Michelin star and 10 restaurants received a Bib Gourmand (award for great food at reasonable prices). Below is a list of Michelin award-winning restaurants in İstanbul.⁵²

Table 120: Michelin Awarded Restaurants

Restaurant	Award	Location
TURK /Fatih Tutak	2 Michelin Star	Şişli
Araka /Z.Pınar Taşdemir	1 Michelin Star	Yeniköy
Mikla /Mehmet Gürs	1 Michelin Star	Beyoğlu
Neolokal/ Maksut Aşkar	1 Michelin Star Green Star	Galata
Nicole Aylin Yazıcı	1 Michelin Star	Beyoğlu
Pandeli	Bib Gourmand	Egyptian Bazaar
Karaköy Lokantası	Bib Gourmand	Karaköy
Alaf	Bib Gourmand	Beşiktaş
Aheste	Bib Gourmand	Beyoğlu
Tersane	Bib Gourmand	Beyoğlu
Giritli	Bib Gourmand	Ahırkapı
Calipso	Bib Gourmand	Küçükyalı
Cuma	Bib Gourmand	Çukurcuma
Sade 5 Denizler Mutfağı	Bib Gourmand	Teşvikiye
Amanda Bravo	Bib Gourmand	Bebek

⁵²<https://guide.michelin.com/en/article/michelin-star-revelation/53-restaurants-spotlighted-in-the-first-selection-of-the-michelin-guide-istanbul>, 24.04.2023

2.2. Industry Dynamics

2.2.1. Industry Macro Environment

Strategic management consists of planning, implementation and evaluation stages, as in the decision-making process in general terms. Many strategic management tools have been developed to assist managers for strategic analysis. Among them, PESTEL analysis is the most widely used. PESTEL analysis, short for **P**olitical, **E**conomic, **S**ocial, **T**echnological, **E**nvironmental and **L**egal, is used to enable organizations to discover and evaluate factors that may affect them today and in the future. The analysis examines the opportunities and threats arising from six external factors related to the business situation. Although it is mostly used in the current situation analysis of strategic planning, it is possible to have a positive perspective while doing market research, creating marketing strategies, developing products and making better decisions for the organization with the results of PEST analysis. Organizations that successfully monitor and respond to changes in the macro environment can differentiate themselves from the competition and thereby gain a competitive advantage over others.^{53, 54, 55} The PESTEL model, which explains the business dynamics of the future, can be easily applied to every industry sector.⁵⁶ PESTEL analysis can also be applied to the tourism sector of a country, as it deals with the macroeconomic effects of the international environment with a six-factor structure.⁵⁷

⁵³ Stoyanova, Z., & Harizanova, H. (2017). Analysis of the External Environment of Green Jobs in Bulgaria. *Economic Alternatives*, 1, 122- 136.

⁵⁴ Kara, E. (2018). A contemporary approach for strategic management in tourism sector: pestel analysis on the city Muğla, Türkiye. *İşletme Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 10(2), 598-608.

⁵⁵ Bhuiyan, M. A., Zhang, Q., Xuan, W., Rahman, M. K., & Khare, V. (2023). Does good governance promote sustainable tourism? A systematic review of PESTEL analysis. *SN Business & Economics*, 3(1), 33.

⁵⁶ Johnson, Gerry et al. (2011). *Exploring strategy: Text & cases*. Harlow: Financial Times Prentice Hall.

⁵⁷ Gregorić, Marina (2014). "PESTEL analysis of tourism destinations in the perspective of business tourism (MICE)." In *Tourism and hospitality industry 2014 (Congress proceedings)* (pp. 551-565).

Figure 74: PESTEL Analysis

P	Political Factors Political stability, Tax policies, Labor policies, Trade policies, Security policies
E	Economic Factors National Income, Unemployment Rates, Demand, Inflation, Labor, Exchange Rate, Investments, Competition
S	Social Factors Culture, Generations, Lifestyles, Health consciousness, Consumer lifestyle
T	Technological Factors Innovation, Technology Investments, Automation, Technological Awareness
E	Environmental Factors Environment, Climate, Laws on recycling, Waste management, Heat Pollution, Natural disasters
L	Legal Factors Employee Protection Laws, Consumer Protection Laws, Intellectual Property Laws

PESTEL analysis is a highly used management tool that helps to identify the effect of multiple macro factors on their growth. PESTEL analysis allows you to consider the influence of six factors; political, economic, social, technological, environmental, and legal. A detailed PESTEL analysis of the Accommodation Industry can show how these factors support the expansion of the hotel industry or hinder its growth.

2.2.1.1. Political Factors

The hospitality sector covers many businesses due to its structure and diversity. Political factors and their consistency are important for all businesses. When it comes to business or leisure visitors, **stability** is very important in a country. Without stability, visitors will hesitate to come to the country and this will negatively affect the revenues of hotels and restaurants.

The tourism sector is highly vulnerable to terrorism, migration, social and political crises.⁵⁸ **Security policies** refer to policies made to ensure security and stability throughout the country. These policies can include the security of hotel and restaurant businesses and the security of businesses for tourists. Insecurity in policies and political issues,⁵⁹ ⁶⁰ terrorism and violence have an impact on tourism demand.⁶¹ ⁶² The threat of terrorism is an important factor for the hospitality sector. Moreover, political relations with other countries can significantly affect the sector. For example, in 2015, following the Russian jet incident, many bilateral agreements between Türkiye and Russia broke down. One of the sectors most affected by this situation was the tourism sector. With the decrease in the number of Russian tourists, the tourism sector experienced one of its worst times in 2016.⁶³

The hotels and restaurants need to keep a track of the changes that are made in the various policies related to taxation, labor force, environmental regulations, etc. Especially, **regulations** in various areas such as product safety, employee health and safety, environmental regulations, etc. should be followed and complied with.

The tourism sector is a sector where labor-intensive methods are used in the production of goods and services. Regulations made by hotel and restaurants regarding their employees refer to **labor policies**. These policies cover issues such as employee rights and personal rights, staff recruitment, recruitment process, trainings. These policies can affect the operating costs of hotel and restaurant businesses.⁶⁴

Changes in **tax policies** can directly affect the profitability of businesses. In particular, hotel and restaurant businesses are often subject to high tax rates. If the **corporate tax** reduce the business have an advantage to do better quality service at a lower cost. If it increases, the opposite result may occur. The corporate tax rate in Türkiye, which was 20%, has been increased to 25% for corporate income for 2021 and 23% for corporate income for 2022. For 2023, this rate is set at 20%.⁶⁵ If the government

⁵⁸ Çolak, O., & Batman, O. (2019). Crisis Management in Tourism: The Case of İstanbul. *Safran Kültür ve Turizm Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 2(3), 351-371.

⁵⁹ Sönmez, S. & Graefe, A. R. (1998). Determining future travel behavior from past travel experience and perceptions of risk and safety. *Journal of Travel Research*, 37, 171– 177.

⁶⁰ Bach, R. L. (2003). Global mobility, inequality and security. *Journal of Human Development*, 4, 2, 227-245.

⁶¹ Ryan, C. (1993). Crime Violence Tourism and Terrorism: An accidental or intrinsic relationship? *Tourism Management*, 14(3): 173-83.

⁶² Pizam, A. & Smith, G. (2000). Tourism and terrorism: A quantitative analysis of major terrorist acts and their impact on tourism destinations. *Tourism Economics*, 6(2), 123– 138.

⁶³ <https://ilke.org.tr/turizm-sektoru-2020-yili-degerlendirmesi>

⁶⁴ Şit, M. (2016). Employment Contribution of Tourism Sector in Türkiye. *Akademik Yaklaşımlar Dergisi*, 7(1), 101-117.

⁶⁵ https://www.vergidegundem.com/pb_kurumlar_vergisi_oranlari.

increases taxes, it will further increase the price for hotel and restaurant businesses, which will have a negative impact on their sales.

In 2023, a decision was taken regarding the implementation of the **tourist tax**. A bill was submitted to the General Assembly of the Grand National Assembly of Türkiye in 2007 for the implementation of the tourist tax, which is applied in many countries around the world, in our country; however, due to the reactions from the tourism sector, the bill was not passed by the commission and was not accepted.⁶⁶ Later, the accommodation tax, which was introduced in the revised Article 34 of the Expense Taxes Law No. 6802 dated 13/7/1956, entered into force on January 1, 2023.⁶⁷

COVID-19 has adversely affected the hotel and restaurant. Due to the lockdowns imposed by governments across the world, hotel and restaurants were closed. The sector has gone through difficult times. Hotels were one of the areas where the pandemic made its impact felt intensely. During this period, the hotel industry experienced four times more revenue decline than the two previous crises combined. Many hotels experienced significant reductions in their workforce and many were forced to close temporarily or permanently. Some arrangements have also been made for companies experiencing difficulties in the payment process of canceled reservations.⁶⁸ In addition, credit packages have been established by public banks to mitigate the negative effects. The Banks Association of Türkiye announced that TL 10 billion in loans will be provided to the tourism sector. The aim was to support businesses with the called Tourism Support Package Implementation.⁶⁹

Trade policies are policies that regulate trade relations between countries. These policies can have a direct impact on the supply chains and international business of hotel and restaurant businesses. Tourism activities may increase the import tendency in a country as they attract technological investments.⁷⁰ Hotels and restaurants to be effective and successful, it needs to be able to work well with external organizations. Because, supply chain mainly focuses on increasing economic values.⁷¹

⁶⁶ Özkan, E., & Sümerli Sarıgül, S. (2019). Mali İdarelerde Yeni Vergi Modeli: Turist Vergisi Uygulamaları Ve Türkiye Değerlendirmesi. *Vergi Raporu*.

⁶⁷ <https://www.resmigazete.gov.tr/eskiler/2022/12/20221214-6.htm>.

⁶⁸ <https://www.resmigazete.gov.tr/eskiler/2020/05/20200515-8.htm>.

⁶⁹ <https://www.tursab.org.tr/assets/uploads/arastirmalar/COVID-19-surecinde-turkiye-ve-dunya-turizmi.pdf>.

⁷⁰ Bulut, E. (2000). Türk Turizminin Dünyadaki Yeri ve Dış Ödemeler Bilançosundaki Etkisi. *Gazi Üniversitesi İ.İ.B.F. Dergisi*, 2, 71-86.

⁷¹ Aigbedo, H. (2021). Impact of COVID-19 on the hospitality industry: A supply chain resilience perspective. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 98, 103012.

2.2.1.2. Economic Factors

Economic factors can play an important role in shaping the strategy and decisions of businesses in the sector. One of them is the **hospitality sector**. **Accommodation** and **food & beverage** are the key component of the hospitality sector.

Macroeconomic indicators such as gross domestic product, economic growth, inflation rates, interest rates, and unemployment rates can affect the industry in different ways. In developing countries, income from the tourism sector is used to solve macroeconomic problems. In developed countries, it is used within the sector. This means that developing countries have given importance to the development of the tourism sector in order to create employment opportunities, provide foreign currency inflows and balance between regions.⁷²

Macroeconomic systems have an effect on various sectors. Moreover, the hospitality sector comes to the fore in consumer-related economic factors and gains importance. The economic factors affect consumer spending. Within the macroeconomic system, **accommodation** and **food & beverage** businesses are directly affected by **demand**. When it is considered for the tourism sector, it is seen that tourist demand is similarly effective. Therefore, issues such as the number of tourists, tourists' expenditures and preferences can have a significant impact on the decisions of hotel and restaurant businesses. The number of visitors by years was realized as shown in the figure.⁷³

⁷² Uşaklı, A. & Ünlüöner, K. (2015). Turizm Gelirlerinin Hesaplanmasına Yönelik Yaklaşımlar. Ankara: Detay Yayıncılık.

⁷³ <https://data.tuik.gov.tr/Bulten/Index?p=Turizm-Istatistikleri-IV-Ceyrek-Ekim-Aralik-ve-Yillik.-2022-49606>.

Figure 75: Number of Departing Visitors (2012–2022)

The Tourism sector in Türkiye constitutes 5% of the national income directly and 12% indirectly. The financial structure of the sector was adversely affected by the regional political fluctuation after 2015 and the foreign currency borrowing in the currency crisis in 2018. In 2019, approximately 52 million foreign tourists were served and a revenue of 34.5 billion dollars was obtained.⁷⁴ By the year 2020, there was a period of recession due to the global pandemic. One economic factor that would always be a risk for the hospitality sector is the potential for recession.

The impact of COVID-19 and consequent lockdowns had some consequences in the hospitality sector. As of March 2020, when the pandemic started, the number of tourists coming to the country decreased by 70%, and after the borders were closed, the number of tourists decreased to almost zero in April and May.⁷⁵

According to data released by the Republic of Türkiye Ministry of Culture and Tourism the number of province-based visitors decreased significantly during the pandemic period.

⁷⁴ <https://ttd.org.tr/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/Turizm-Sektorunun-Yeniden-Yapilanmasi.pdf>

⁷⁵ <https://ttd.org.tr/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/Turizm-Sektorunun-Yeniden-Yapilanmasi.pdf>

Figure 76: Number of Visitors in January-October

Number of visitors in January-October ⁷⁶				
City	Years			Change % 2020/2019
	2018	2019	2020	
İstanbul	11330081	12690376	4154021	-67.3
Antalya	12008939	14135788	3099687	-78.1
Muğla	2702403	3203258	668049	-79.1
İzmir	966068	1150397	280072	-75.7

Compared to 2019, 2020 tourism income decreased by 61.7%.⁷⁷ The graphic representations are as follows.

Figure 77: Tourism Income (2012–2022)

Considering the COVID-19 issue in terms of economic factors, the result that came to the fore was the decrease in income. On the other hand, it has been stated that it seems possible to reach 2019 tourism revenues after COVID-19 in 2022 and beyond.⁷⁸ Tourism revenue realized in 2022 was \$46 billion, exceeding 2019.⁷⁹

⁷⁶ <https://yigm.ktb.gov.tr/TR-9851/turizm-istatistikleri.html>

⁷⁷ <https://data.tuik.gov.tr/Bulten/Index?p=Turizm-Istatistikleri-IV.Ceyrek:-Ekim-Aralik-ve-Yillik,-2022-49606>

⁷⁸ <https://ttyd.org.tr/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/Turizm-Sektorunun-Yeniden-Yapilanmasi.pdf>

⁷⁹ <https://data.tuik.gov.tr/Bulten/Index?p=Turizm-Istatistikleri-IV.Ceyrek:-Ekim-Aralik-ve-Yillik,-2022-49606>

World Travel & Tourism Council (WTTC)⁸⁰ has a forecast by 2032 the sector's contribution to the nations GDP could reach nearly US\$117 billion, representing 11% of the total economy.

The efficiency of the operation of the financial markets has an impact on the ability of the **accommodation** such as hotels to raise capital at a fair price. A similar situation is also valid for **food & beverage** such as restaurants. On the other hand, if **inflation** which is a macroeconomic indicator increases the cost of personnel, materials, etc. increases and this leads to high prices for both accommodation and food & beverage sectors. The graphic representations of the inflation ratio in Türkiye are as follows.

Figure 78: Inflation Ratio in Türkiye (2019-2023)

Türkiye faced during 2021 macroeconomic problems and these problems went from bad to worse over the first half of 2022.⁸¹ Türkiye inflation rate for 2021 was 19.60%, a 7.32% increase from 2020. In 2022, Türkiye inflation rate was 72.3%.⁸² These macroeconomic problems affected the hospitality sector as well as many other sectors. Consequently, it is important to keep the inflation rate lower, otherwise, costs for the sector will increase. Otherwise, high inflation may cause businesses to change their pricing strategies and service quality.

⁸⁰ <https://wtcc.org/news-article/Turkiyes-travel-and-tourism-sector-to-grow-at-twice-the-rate-of-the-national-economy>

⁸¹ Euromonitor International, Consumer Foodservice in Türkiye, 2023.

⁸² <https://data.tuik.gov.tr/Bulten/Index?p=Turizm-Istatistikleri-IV.Ceyrek:-Ekim-Aralik-ve-Yillik.-2022-49606>.

The hospitality sector is a **labor**-intensive industry. Hotel and restaurant businesses make an important contribution to the workforce. Therefore, employee costs are an important economic factor. Increasing costs can potentially affect the profitability of the businesses. It is important to create employment in a global economy that is stagnant with the increasing population in world. For this reason, Türkiye is in an advantageous position in terms of creating direct and indirect employment in the tourism sector⁸³. The sector supports nearly 2.6 million jobs across the country. The sector is expected to create more than 716,000 new jobs over the next decade.⁸⁴ Changes in the labor market can lead businesses to make changes in areas such as employee pay, and hiring decisions.

Developing countries may face some unstable economic factors. Unstable conditions would affect sectors and one of them is the hospitality sector. For instance, **exchange rate** changes are important in the hospitality sector, especially when considering tourism. In other words, changes in exchange rates can directly affect the costs of hotel and restaurant businesses. Currency stability is important for **investments**. An unstable currency would discourage investors. This situation may reduce investments in the hospitality sector. In the current state, fluctuations in the economy and increases in interest rates make borrowing more difficult or costlier than before. It makes it difficult to make new investments.

Another important factor is **competition**. Accommodation and food & beverage sectors have a highly competitive. Most important competitive factor is price competition. In addition to price competition, this competition can also take the form of opening new businesses and gaining customer loyalty. These competitive factors can have an impact on the profitability of businesses.

In the Tourism Strategy Master Plan, the most critical issue for the sector to reach the \$65 billion tourism income targeted for 2023 is the need to strengthen the weak financial structure of the sector. The tourism sector has a great importance in reducing the current account deficit and maintaining the balance with its foreign exchange earning effect.⁸⁵ In conclusion, determining the economic policies by taking into

⁸³ Çetin, İ., İçöz, O. & Toker, B. (2018). Employment in Tourism Industry and International Labor Law. *Uluslararası Turizm Ekonomi ve İşletme Bilimleri Dergisi*, 2(2), 52-64.

⁸⁴ <https://wtc.org/news-article/Türkiyes-travel-and-tourism-sector-to-grow-at-twice-the-rate-of-the-national-economy>.

⁸⁵ <https://tyd.org.tr/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/Turizm-Sektorunun-Yeniden-Yapilanmasi.pdf>.

account the economic factors are vital both for the businesses and for the whole sector. Economic factors affect business performance and how business grows in the near future.

2.2.1.3. Social Factors

Organizational culture is strongly influenced by societal norms, values, and trends. Understanding demographic trends, power structures, consumer spending patterns and common beliefs can help the hospitality industry. In the hospitality industry, information from social and environmental analyzes can be used to target consumer groups and increase the attractiveness of offered products to potential buyers.⁸⁶

People's preferences and spending habits shape the society and culture they belong to, making them a very important external factor for the hotel industry. The age group of travelers also plays an important role in these choices. Changes in demographic patterns such as the aging population, migration trends and socio-economic variables are of great importance for the hospitality industry. Studying demographics can help the hospitality industry select the right market segment(s) with high growth potential. The aging of the world population means the increase in the third age tourism group, which has a high travel potential, and creates the opportunity to use accommodation facilities out of season. Migration events negatively affect the social structure and quality of life.⁸⁷

Travelers are from different classes and age groups. When X, Y and Z generations are considered as today's customer profile, it is necessary to know their general characteristics, to understand their accommodation preferences and to create products and services accordingly. Studies for Türkiye have revealed that the Z generation tends to benefit from natural and cultural opportunities more than both X and Y generations, relax, seek novelty, and travel for exploration purposes. In addition, it has been observed that the X and Y generations care more about shopping opportunities than the Z generation. In addition, especially the Y and Z generations tend to prefer hostels rather than big hotels.⁸⁸ According to the studies, customers in the age group of 40-49 pay attention to the selection of the accommodation business they will choose, while

⁸⁶ <https://www.case48.com/pestel-case/1962-Hotel-Industry>.

⁸⁷ <https://www.sbb.gov.tr/wpcontent/uploads/2020/04/TurizmOzellhtisasKomisyonuRaporu.pdf>.

⁸⁸ ÇÖP, S., S. İBİŞ & Ö. KIZILDEMİR. (2020). Seyahat Motivasyonlarının X, Y ve Z kuşaklarına göre farklılıklarının incelenmesi üzerine bir araştırma. *OPUS International Journal of Society Researches*, 16(30), 2528-2550.

customers in the age group of 50 and above prefer simple accommodation businesses that do not have much luxury and are familiar. Young people, on the other hand, prefer accommodation establishments such as holiday villages and camping. Studies show that the 15-40 age group is the first to travel. In addition, it has been determined that tourists aged between 35-44 are more inclined to group travel and use accommodation facilities more during their travels. These studies reveal that the age factor is important in participating in touristic activities. On the other hand, the age factor is also important in determining the region to be traveled, the transportation vehicle, the choice of accommodation facility and the final purpose of the trip. As age increases, the tendency to participate in tourism movements decreases. The age group that travels the least is those aged 65 and over. Elderly tourists are more inclined to participate in health tourism and especially to participate in thermal facilities; On the other hand, young people prefer to participate in exhausting trips, go to distant holiday destinations, and travel to countries with different cultures and lifestyles⁸⁹.

In general, the rate of participation in tourism in Türkiye is very low. This is due to low disposable income. For this reason, it is only possible for retirees in Türkiye to participate in tourism within the framework of mass tourism for social purposes, since they generally have middle and lower income levels.

As a destination country, Türkiye is a country close to Europe in terms of distance. This proximity is an advantage in terms of benefiting from third age tourism from the mentioned countries. On the other hand, the climate of Türkiye is very suitable for the elderly and retired people. It is possible to benefit from the sea on the Mediterranean and Aegean coasts, especially in spring and autumn. This is a factor that can attract retirees and elderly people to these regions during the spring and autumn months. When it comes to the participation of the third age group in tourism, only sea tourism should not come to mind. ⁹⁰

Türkiye which is in an advantageous position in terms of medical tourism, spa & wellness and thermal tourism, disabled and third age tourism, has an important tourism potential with its cultural riches, historical background, geographical location,

⁸⁹ Belber, B. G. (2007). Tatil turizmde turistlerin konaklama işletmesi tercihine kültürün etkisi ve konaklama işletmeleri üzerine bir uygulama.

⁹⁰ YILDIRIM, S. (1997). Üçüncü yaş turizmi ve bunun Türkiye açısından değerlendirilmesi. *Anatolia: Turizm Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 8(1), 77-81.

transportation opportunities, climate and natural beauties. Türkiye also has an important health tourism potential with its high quality and technology standards, advanced health service delivery, internationally accredited health enterprises, qualified workforce and low cost advantage. When all these are taken into account, it can be said that Türkiye has a very high potential in terms of third age tourism, if the elderly in the Middle East, the Balkans and other neighboring countries are also taken into account. In recent years in Türkiye, under the title of "Program for the Development of Health Tourism", third age tourism has also become one of the priority issues. In this program, 150,000 foreign tourists and an income of 750,000,000 dollars are targeted within the framework of advanced age tourism (www.sbb.gov.tr). In third age tourism, tourists constitute 6% of foreign tourists visiting Türkiye. On average, more than 2 million foreign tourists have traveled to Türkiye within the framework of third age tourism. While Türkiye is among the top seven countries in the world in terms of geothermal resource potential with high mineralization content, it ranks first in Europe and third in thermal spring applications. Türkiye has many geothermal resources and advanced medical tourism infrastructure. By combining these opportunities with five-star hotels, including major hotel chains with spa & wellness, it offers cheaper and higher quality tourism packages to third-year-old tourists. There are approximately 43 "Advanced Age Friendly Hotels" in Türkiye⁹¹.

In the 11th Development Plan of the Presidency of Türkiye, the issue of carrying out promotional and investment activities for the development of health tourism, which will increase the average length of stay in tourism and ensure the spread of tourism throughout the year, is included⁹².

Anatolia, the home of civilizations, has many beliefs. Therefore, there is a wide variety of places to visit to attract those who are interested in holy values. Urfa Balıklı lake, rock churches in Kapadokya, Sürmene Monastery in Trabzon, Santa Claus's house in Demre, Virgin Mary's house in Ephesus, our assets such as the first seven churches built in the name of Mary and mentioned in the Bible, the Sacred Relics in Istanbul Topkapı Palace and the remains of mythological gods are the first examples that come to mind. All businesses operating in the tourism sector, especially the Ministry of

⁹¹ Bulut, A. (2022). Türkiye'nin Üçüncü Yaş Turizm Potansiyeli ve Geleceği2, Yönetim, Ekonomi ve Pazarlama Araştırmaları Dergisi, 6(4), 231-249.

⁹² <https://www.sbb.gov.tr/wpcontent/uploads/2020/04/TurizmOzellhtisasKomisyonuRaporu.pdf>.

Tourism, are required to carry out promotional and marketing activities that will offer this potential to the third age group and other tourists⁹³.

Due to COVID-19, people are afraid of interacting with various people and prefer to stay at home. These changes in people's behavior also negatively affected the accommodation sector. Some measures were taken in the accommodation sector to address these concerns of the people and it was necessary to make new regulations. Therefore, in the marketing activities to be carried out, it will be of great benefit for accommodation businesses to classify the potential customers according to the generations and then go to the product and service design in line with the prominent interests and expectations of each generation⁹⁴.

Changes in values, beliefs and life styles, changing patterns of work and leisure, demographic changes, changing mix in the ethnic and religious background of the population- all will have their influence on the sustenance of the industry. The growing gender, ethnic and cultural diversity in workforce creates challenges and opportunities in variably to every industry⁹⁵. However, consumer preferences matter a lot in this industry. For example, after the COVID-19, tourists prefer to have their private accommodations. While there was more demand for the city center and urban areas, this interest has shifted to rural areas after the COVID-19 pandemic⁹⁶.

Accommodation industry is affected by various social factors such as consumer lifestyle, consumer demographics, population growth rate, culture and gender ratio. As people's incomes increase, their spending habits also change. Thus, their willingness to spend on leisure activities increases, which is important for the hospitality industry. Also, this will affect the accommodation industry in the future as the lifestyles of people around the world evolve.

Culture is considered as an important variable for the hospitality industry. Every society has its own unique norms and values that play an important role in shaping consumer behavior. The hospitality industry must develop local teams and partnerships to adapt marketing strategies to cultural context and understand societal attitudes and norms⁹⁷.

⁹³ YILDIRIM, S. (1997). Üçüncü yaş turizmi ve bunun Türkiye açısından değerlendirilmesi. *Anatolia: Turizm Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 8(1), 77-81.

⁹⁴ <https://www.mbaskool.com/pestle-analysis/companies/18162-hilton.html>.

⁹⁵ <https://phdessay.com/pestle-analysis-of-hospitality-industry/>

⁹⁶ <https://freepestelanalysis.com/pestel-analysis-of-hospitality-industry/>

⁹⁷ <https://www.case48.com/pestel-case/1962-Hotel-Industry>.

Türkiye's richness in terms of gastronomy and culinary culture play an important role in the accommodation sector.

Today's accommodation industry is highly competitive, with lots of new players coming in from time to time. Most guests book a hotel after reading reviews or because of recommendations from family, friends or peers. Therefore, building the accommodation industry depends on people's opinions and overall impressions.

Socio-cultural factors that help food & beverage businesses develop a supply-demand model are under this factor. These are traditions, cultural values and beliefs, population growth, age distribution, career attitude and more. By examining these factors, companies can also identify a potential market⁹⁸.

Increasing awareness of organic food is a social factor that will affect the growth of the restaurant industry in the years to come. As awareness has increased, people have realized how bad fast food is for their bodies. As a result, many people have stopped eating fast food. This has caused the demand for fast food to decrease. Food & beverage businesses and companies must be aware of the nutritional preferences of the market in which they will launch their products. Nowadays, many people have started to pay attention to their diet and avoid salty, spicy, fatty and sugary foods. Because it causes diabetes, high blood pressure and other health problems. For this reason, food & beverage businesses should research their customers' preferences well. Healthy eating and exercise trends are becoming popular with people. They use smart watches and other technological gadgets to maintain their health and diet. Such trends have kept people away from unhealthy and fast foods. Many food businesses are now changing their cooking styles and switching to an organic-based diet to keep up with health trends. The COVID-19 pandemic is an important cause of changes in dietary habits. Deloitte Türkiye investigated the impact of the epidemic on the food & beverage industry with the report "The Present and Future of the Restaurant Industry Under the Impact of COVID-19". Accordingly, 15% of consumer's state that they start to consume more home-cooked food, while 29% state that they eat healthy. It is stated that the main purpose of consuming healthy foods is to gain immunity⁹⁹.

⁹⁸ <https://www.edrawmax.com/article/restaurant-industry-pestel-analysis.html>.

⁹⁹ <https://www2.deloitte.com/tr/tr/pages/consumer-business/articles/COVID-19-etkisinde-restoran-sektorunun-bugunu-ve-gelecegi.html>.

In addition, people's busy lifestyles have increased their dependence on ready-to-eat foods instead of home-cooked meals. Although the interest in healthy and organic foods is increasing, the popularity of fast-food style foods should not be ignored, especially with the young population in the country. The fast food industry is also affected by social changes in Türkiye. The first thing to be addressed is the increasing purchasing power of the Turkish people. Average income levels have increased each year since the beginning of the last decade, reaching more than \$13,000 in 2016. Turkish people, who have more money to spend, thus spend more on consumer goods as well as basic needs, and this causes a change in their eating habits. According to Eurostat's research, Turkish people work 9 hours more per week than Europeans do, so they do not have enough time to prepare meals at home.

Demographically, Türkiye is home to Europe's youngest population. The average age in the country is around 30; 45% of respondents to the Mediabrands/Insight Research survey are between the ages of 16-34. Developing brand loyalty with younger segments of the population, including 15.6% of the population aged 15-24, is key to building a long-term business presence in Türkiye. This segment of the population is much more likely to use the internet and actively engage with social media platforms, making social media platforms, an important channel for product marketing for this segment of the population takes the food to a new dimension and this situation makes its impact more felt in Türkiye.

2.2.1.4. Technological Factors

Technology is the fourth factor of PESTEL analysis. Rapid technological progress and technological diffusion around the world has increased the importance of understanding technological factors in strategic decision-making. Some of the technological factors are – population access to technology, access to greater information, supply chain disruption because of technology, innovation in customer services, rate of technology driven change, access to mobile phones driving empowerment, innovation in product offerings, etc.¹⁰⁰

The development of information and communication technologies has led to the adoption of innovative marketing techniques to improve cooperation with customers.

¹⁰⁰ <https://www.case48.com/pestel-case/1962-Hotel-Industry>.

The widespread use of social media has also affected the accommodation sector. The hospitality industry takes advantage of the opportunities offered by social media marketing to improve business performance.

In the Presidential 11th Development Plan, it is planned to make regulations, especially internet-based applications, in order for the tourism sector to benefit more effectively from the sharing economy, and to support R&D activities and technology-based applications in the sector¹⁰¹.

The hospitality industry must carefully evaluate the ongoing technological innovations in order to stay ahead of the competition. Analysis of 5G and identifying its potential to deliver positive business outcomes through improved user experience, increased speed and expanded access should be watched closely. Technological innovations can bring major transformations in the industry and reset the rules of success for market players.

Today, almost all accommodation establishments have their own websites. Also the vast majority of the population has a smartphone for internet access and also has access to computers and laptops. Thus, accommodation businesses can make ticket sales and promote their businesses with reservation, customer acceptance, thanks to internet facilities. In this context, using information technologies increases the service quality of accommodation businesses and enables them to increase their income.

Today, many accommodation businesses have the opportunity to provide their customers with cheaper and 24 hours uninterrupted service by making online reservations through their own websites. At the same time, the internet enables accommodation businesses to perform first-hand facility and room promotions. Guests make reservations by seeing the room occupancy rates, prices, types of services of the accommodation business with images, animations and graphics, thus minimizing the effects of false image that will occur on the guests of the intermediary institutions or hearsay information. Technology investments made by accommodation businesses increase the speed and efficiency of activities and enable savings by reducing costs.

¹⁰¹ <https://www.sbb.gov.tr/wpcontent/uploads/2020/04/TurizmOzellhtisasKomisyonuRaporu.pdf>.

Many hotels use websites for booking and secure payment. AI-based customer support system and secure application provide customers with a smooth and satisfying experience. With a few clicks, guests can book a hotel anywhere and anytime.

Technology has enabled guests to receive comfortable and safe accommodation. Accommodation companies use advanced technologies to provide the best service to their guests.

Social media has enabled hotels to reach more customers through advertisements. It can affect the reputation of the hotel positively or negatively. Travel websites allow tourists to write reviews that keep hotels competitive.

Use of robotics and chatbots powered by artificial intelligence is turning out to be the differentiating factor in the hospitality industry. Hilton added artificial intelligence to its suite of digital concierge services which helps to convince more number of potential customers to use Hilton's web site for booking rather than third party websites like hostels.com. This also helps Hilton to strengthen its relationship with more than 34 million guests it serves annually. The chatbot is built using a predictive technology by Ibm Watson. Hilton is also testing quasi-concierge robot as Hilton. These technologies are adding to differentiated customer experience provided by market leaders such as Hilton¹⁰².

Factors such as innovation, automation, technical awareness and more that affect a business's production, distribution and communication operations are covered by technological factors.

Technological developments have brought the internet to large masses and businesses have started to market their products through social media. Companies in the food & beverage industry are doing the same. As a result, the demand for food & beverage products has increased significantly.

Technological advances such as accepting payments via smartphones, ordering food online and operating CCTV cameras from mobile phones have generated new revenues for the restaurant industry. Automation is the future of the restaurant industry. Introducing the latest software to manage companies' accounts can lead to fewer

¹⁰² <https://www.swotandpestle.com/hilton-worldwide-holdings-inc>.

errors and more profits. Technology has also provided companies with a space to experiment with promotional strategies to reach more people quickly and leave a lasting impression¹⁰³.

Some food businesses, such as McDonald's, have adopted technology automation tools such as cooking robots, self-ordering, payment systems, and online orders and delivery systems. The use of automation technology and robots will make food preparation efficient and reduce labor costs. It will result in greater profitability and less human error.

2.2.1.5. Environmental Factors

Environmental factors have gained importance in recent years as consumers become more conscious and selective. Conscious consumer is important because of environmental targets, recycling targets and carbon footprint targets set by governments. Conscious consumers have the most important role in the transformation of businesses. Environmental factors can be evaluated as follows.

- Environmental laws
- Climate change
- Laws on recycling
- Waste management
- Use of environmentally friendly products and practices
- Weather conditions
- Heat
- Pollution
- Natural disasters (earthquake, flood, etc.)

As extreme weather conditions become more common, hospitality businesses need to plan how to adapt to these changes. In addition, as can be seen from the rise of Corporate Sustainability Responsibility (CSR) initiatives, it is increasingly important for accommodation businesses to be environmentally friendly through their activities. Examples of CSR initiatives include carbon footprint reduction efforts and shifts to renewable materials and energy sources.

¹⁰³ <https://www.edrawmax.com/article/restaurant-industry-pestel-analysis.html>.

Considering the environmental factor, the noise situation, location, distance to the center, transportation situation, traffic situation, climate changes, natural disasters and the land structure where the business is located play an important role.

In line with sustainability goals, regulation of purchasing processes with sustainable policy, energy management, water use management, wastewater management, waste management, management of the use and application of chemicals, contribution to the protection of nature and biodiversity, and encouraging the implementation of environmental management systems are beneficial for both accommodation and food & beverage sectors. It is very important. For this purpose, the following steps should be taken for both the **accommodation and food & beverage** sectors.¹⁰⁴

- ✓ Enabling sector stakeholders to act jointly on energy efficiency and to take measures to prevent environmental pollution
- ✓ Minimizing the use of limited and non-renewable resources in businesses in the sector
- ✓ Carrying out studies that deal with possible income and job losses in the accommodation and food & beverage industry under different scenarios due to the change or shift of the tourism season caused by climate change and global warming.
- ✓ Increasing planning and implementation methods to reduce greenhouse gas emissions from the main components of the accommodation and food & beverage industry
- ✓ Encouraging the reduction of food waste to prevent food loss and waste in accordance with the food waste hierarchy, planning for this at every stage of the food chain, developing waste prevention protocols and determining reduction targets
- ✓ Dissemination of storage systems consisting of systematically spreading solid wastes to a carefully selected and prepared area in a way that will not harm the environment and human health, and covering it with soil in order to successfully carry out solid waste management.
- ✓ Separation of wastes for the effective and efficient implementation of recycling practices

¹⁰⁴ T.C., Kalkınma Bakanlığı, On Birinci Kalkınma Planı (2019-2023), Turizm Özel İhtisas Komisyonu Raporu, Ankara, 2018.

- ✓ Working with the Ministry of Energy and Natural Resources on support and incentive mechanisms related to the use of renewable energy sources.
- ✓ Criteria of inspection and certification systems such as green star, green key, blue flag, and blue card for minimizing the environmental impact of accommodation facilities are reviewed and disseminated and encouraged to cover all facilities.
- ✓ Exemption of environmentally friendly accommodation facilities certified from the employment of environmental engineers and the supervision of the Ministry of Environment and Urbanization.

During the EU harmonization process, one of the most important policies of Türkiye is environmental policy. Below are the strategies and action plans implemented in this regard.

- ✓ The Green Key Program, which supports the initiatives to protect the environment by awarding them, has been carried out in our country by the Turkish Environmental Education Foundation since 2011.
- ✓ EU Integrated Environmental Harmonization Strategy (2007-2023) in Türkiye on environmental issues,
- ✓ Turkish National Action Program to Combat Desertification, National Biological Diversity Strategy and Action Plan 2007,
- ✓ National Climate Change Strategy Document,
- ✓ The Communiqué on Issuing an Environmentally Friendly Accommodation Facility Certificate was published on 19 June 2017 in order to regulate the procedures and principles regarding the protection of the environment, raising environmental awareness, encouraging and encouraging positive contributions to the environment, and evaluating the efforts of the sector in the direction of environmental awareness within the scope of sustainable tourism. In our country, where environmentally friendly accommodation facility certification has continued since 2008, the number of green star accommodation facilities, which was 142 in 2014, reached 450 in 2018.

As a result of the activities of **hotel businesses**, negative effects on the environment arise. The direct and indirect effects of hotel businesses on environmental destruction can be considered as follows.^{105, 106}

- ✓ Leakage of hotel wastewater into the soil and contamination of groundwater
- ✓ Decrease of underground water resources due to excessive water withdrawal from artesian such as garden irrigation and pool filling.
- ✓ Air pollution by exhaust gases emitted by vehicles bringing tourists and supplies to the hotel
- ✓ Coastal structuring and extinction of breeding environments for some living species
- ✓ Visual pollution created by communication lines such as electricity and telephone
- ✓ Visual pollution created by directional signs such as advertisements and billboards
- ✓ Compression of the soil and erosion due to vehicles coming to the hotel and walking around the hotel
- ✓ Cutting of trees for construction, road constructions, power lines
- ✓ The historical places visited by the people who come to the hotel are eroded due to noise, vibration, heat change, pollution.
- ✓ Waste thrown into the environment by the tourists staying in the hotels, both in the hotel and outside the hotel
- ✓ Excessive use of drugs for rodent control
- ✓ Fertilizer etc. for garden arrangement. excessive use of pesticides and soil pollution
- ✓ Bringing artificial industrial structures into the ecosystem
- ✓ Air pollution by emission gases emitted from heating and cooling systems used in hotels
- ✓ Noise pollution caused by entertainment activities in hotels

Sustainability means consuming today's natural resources without endangering future generations. For this reason, it is of great importance for future generations that

¹⁰⁵ Aslanertik, B. E., & Özgen, I. (2007). Otel işletmelerinde çevresel muhasebe. *Dokuz Eylül Üniversitesi İşletme Fakültesi Dergisi*, 8(2), 163-179.

¹⁰⁶ Mesci, Z. (2014). Otellerin çevreci uygulamalarının değerlendirilmesi: yeşil yıldızlı bir otel işletmesinde örnek olay çalışması. *Seyahat ve Otel İşletmeciliği Dergisi*, 11(1).

projects with very high energy consumption, such as Tourism Facilities, receive international environmental management certificates and contribute to their businesses and our country's economy by saving. Without sacrificing their service quality, and setting an example for other sectors by protecting the environment and natural resources.

The tourism sector covers 25% of the cake of negativities that trigger global warming, such as carbon dioxide and greenhouse gas emissions. For this reason, especially in the last few years, this industry has started to turn a clean slate within itself and keep up with the change. The most defining factor that distinguishes sustainable hotels, which also make their impact felt in Türkiye, is that they have international environmental management certificates.

The biggest advantage of obtaining this certificate for the hotels is the decrease in energy consumption figures varying between 20-60%, decrease in operating costs, increase in satisfaction of employees and guests, increase in indoor environmental quality and consequently decrease in ventilation-related diseases¹⁰⁷. Therefore, in order to eliminate or improve all these negative effects, it is important for environmental sustainability that the enterprises in the accommodation sector have environmental management certificates. There are a number of international and national environmental management certificates that **hotels** can obtain. Environmental Management System (ISO 14000), Environmental Management and Audit Program (EMAS), American Green Building Certification (LEED) are among these documents. Apart from international documents, there are also local applications such as the Blue Flag Project, Environmental Impact Assessment (CED) Report, Green Star, White Star, Environmental Management System (ISO 14001) and Greening Hotels Projects developed by the relevant institutions in order to support the environmentally friendly activities of hotel businesses in Türkiye.^{108, 109, 110}

¹⁰⁷ Doğru, N., LEED Sertifikalı Otellerin Sürdürülebilir Turizmdeki Yeri, 25 Tem 2017, Date of update: 23 Tem 2020, Date of access: 31.03.2023 <https://www.ecobuild.com.tr/post/2017/07/25/leed-sertifikal%C4%B1-otellerin-s%C3%BCrd%C3%BCr%C3%BClebilir-turizmdeki-yeri>.

¹⁰⁸ Roderick, Y., McEwan, D., Wheatley, C., & Alonso, C. (2009, July). Comparison of energy performance assessment between LEED, BREEAM and Green Star. In *Eleventh international IBPSA conference* (pp. 27-30).

¹⁰⁹ Hüseyinli, E., & Esen, S. K. (2018). Türkiye'deki Otellerin Çevre Dostu Uygulamalarına Yönelik Müşteri Farkındalığının İncelenmesi. *Kırklareli Üniversitesi İktisadi Ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi*, 7(3), 162-175.

¹¹⁰ Andújar, J. M., & Melgar, S. G. (2020). Energy Efficiency in Buildings. *Huelva: MDPI*.

- ✓ **Blue Flag Project:** The label given to the beaches and marinas by the International Environmental Education Foundation by considering the water quality according to certain parameters for lake and sea waters.
- ✓ **Eco-Management and Audit Scheme (EMAS):** It was established by the European Commission in 1993 to evaluate, report and improve activities such as reducing energy consumption, paper consumption, waste generation, greenhouse gas emissions related to the environmental performance of companies.
- ✓ **Environmental Management System (ISO 14001):** It is a management system created with the aim of protecting the environment and natural structure and published by the International Standards Organization (ISO). The environmental management system is a management system model established on the basis of risk analysis, which essentially aims to reduce the use of natural resources and minimize the damage to soil, water and air. It was created with the aim of minimizing the damage to the environment.
- ✓ **Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design (LEED):** LEED Certification is a system that rates green buildings, developed by the USGBC (United States Green Building Council), that is, the American Green Building Council. The purpose of the certificate is to develop and disseminate environmentally responsible design, practice and operating standards at the building and city scale.
- ✓ **Building Research Establishment Environmental Assessment Method (BREEAM):** Developed in England in 1990, BREEAM is the first criteria-based certification system for buildings.
- ✓ **White Star:** It is aimed to control the amount of water, electricity, energy, chemical and solid waste used in touristic establishments and thus to minimize the possible damages to the environment and natural resources. Prepared by the Turkish Hoteliers Federation (TUROFED).
- ✓ **Greening Hotels Project:** The Greening Hotels project, which continues in cooperation with TUROB, Bureau Veritas and Sustainability Academy; aims to increase the awareness of the tourism sector on sustainability and the motivation of accommodation facilities to be sensitive to the environment. With the awareness that the most important way to increase competitiveness in the tourism sector today is the tourism sector to act with sustainable tourism

principles; Making significant contributions to the development of sustainable tourism, the Greening Hotels Project also increases the number of environmentally sensitive consumers and encourages facilities to be greener.

- ✓ **Green Star:** Reducing the consumption of energy, water, environmentally harmful substances and minimizing the amount of waste, increasing energy efficiency to a high level, encouraging the use of renewable energy sources, planning and realizing accommodation establishments in an environmentally friendly manner starting from the investment phase, ensuring that the facility is compatible with the environment. deals with ecological architecture and raising awareness about environmental sensitivity. It is a project developed by the Ministry of Culture and Tourism in accordance with EU and international criteria.
- ✓ **Environmental Impact Assessment Report (CED):** It is a report developed to protect the environment and human health, to prevent pollution and to ensure sustainable development. It is carried out by the Ministry of Environment and Urbanization, Department of Prevention of Environmental Problems.

Within the scope of sustainability, **Green Restaurant** practices have come to the fore in the **food & beverage** sector as well as in hotels. The green restaurant was defined by Lorenzini in 1994 as buildings designed or reconstructed with an emphasis on environmentalism and energy saving. While 53% of Türkiye's total crop, animal, and fish supply is lost after harvest before it reaches the consumer, 10% of fruit and vegetables go to waste, 15% in the market, and 15% in homes. In the food & beverage sector, 325 thousand tons of food waste is generated annually. According to the data of the Türkiye Waste Prevention Foundation, the economic equivalent of total food waste is 214 billion TRY per year.¹¹¹ In this direction, it can be said that the green generation restaurant movement, constitutes an important start for Türkiye. There are various national and international green restaurant certification organizations. These certificates are briefly given below.^{112,113,114,115}

¹¹¹ <https://www.ekoig.com/bizim-buyuk-israfimiz/> (8 October 2021 - Date of Access: 05.04.2023).

¹¹² Şimşek, N., & Akdağ, G. (2017). Sürdürülebilir gastronomi turizmi kapsamında yeşil nesil restoranları incelenmesi. *The Journal of Academic Social Science Studies*, 60(2), 351-368.

¹¹³ Yazıcıoğlu, İ., & Aydın, A. (2018). Yeşil restoran uygulamaları üzerine nitel bir araştırma: İstanbul Örneği. *Gazi Üniversitesi Turizm Fakültesi Dergisi*, (1), 55-79.

¹¹⁴ Dilek, S., E. (2016). Sürdürülebilir Turizm Uygulamaları, (Editör: N. Koçak) içinde, Sürdürülebilir Turizm Yönetimi (ss. 219-303). Ankara: Detay Yayıncılık.

¹¹⁵ <https://www.turizmgunlugu.com/2021/02/22/yesil-restoran-olabilme-sartlari-nedir/>.

- ✓ **The Green Restaurant Association (GRA):** is an association founded by various national associations in the USA (San Diego) in 1990 with the mission of creating an environmentally and sustainable restaurant industry. Among the categories prepared by the Green Restaurant Association (GRA), energy, water, waste, disposable units, reducing the use of chemical products and pollution, sustainable food and sustainable building materials are taken into consideration.
- ✓ **Sustainable Restaurant Association (SRA):** It is a non-profit organization established in 2010 to ensure the sustainability of the food & beverage industry in the UK. Within the framework of sustainability of the Sustainable Restaurant Association, it provides consultancy services and accreditation in areas under three categories focused on society, resources and the environment.
- ✓ **Green Table Australia (GTA):** A training and certification program that supports and validates restaurants, cafes, catering businesses in Australia that are reducing their negative impact on the environment.
- ✓ **The Green Table Network (GTN):** Founded in Canada in 2007, it is a non-profit organization that accepts food service operators, committed to providing the highest quality and delicious food, as well as improving the damage they cause to the environment.
- ✓ **Green Generation Restaurant Movement:** The Green Generation Restaurant Movement, which started on a national scale in 2014, emerged as an initiative to establish and spread the understanding of sustainability in restaurant business. The Green Generation Restaurant Movement is a project initiated with the cooperation of the Tourism Restaurant Investors and Operators Association (TURYID), Unilever Food Solutions, İstanbul Beşiktaş Municipality and Boğaziçi University, under the leadership of the Wildlife Conservation Foundation (WWF Türkiye).

In addition to all these, Green Building rating systems such as LEED, Green Star and BREEAM are among the certificates used in the **food & beverage** industry.

2.2.1.6. Legal Factors

“Legal” is the sixth factor of PESTEL analysis. The laws and regulations of the country really affect the operation of the hotel in which it operates. Legal factors are also closely linked to political factors and economic factors. It is important for hotels to know the changes in the law and to follow them so that they can make the necessary changes. The hospitality industry cannot enter a new market without thoroughly examining the legal environment and regulatory structure of the new consumer market. For the Hospitality Industry, it may cause undesirable situations such as infringement of competitive advantage as a result of intellectual property rights violations and damage to corporate image due to violation of consumer/employee/environmental protection standards. Therefore, the hospitality industry should consider employee protection laws, consumer protection laws and intellectual property laws when exploring a new market.^{116, 117}

Employee protection laws (discrimination and health and safety): The Hotel Industry must comply with employee health and safety laws, as some countries have strict regulations to ensure worker safety. Providing a safe working environment for the workforce is the ethical and moral obligation of the Hospitality Industry. Similarly, anti-discrimination laws (such as equal employment opportunity) need to be carefully scrutinized when developing human resources practices, as discriminatory lawsuits against employers' damage organizational image and affect organizations' ability to attract and retain talent.

Occupational Health and Safety Law No. 6331 prepared by the Ministry of Labor and Social Security is also applied in the accommodation food & beverage sector. Within the scope of this law, hazards and risks related to occupational health and safety in the hotel and restaurant businesses are handled as physical (noise, lighting, temperature etc.), chemical, biological, ergonomic and mechanical, and psychosocial factors.

¹¹⁶ <https://www.case48.com/pestel-case/1962-Hotel-Industry>.

¹¹⁷ Epik, H., & Gökşen, Y. (2020). Küçük otellerde kurumsal strateji belirleme için bir karar destek sistemi: Pilot çalışma. *Acta Infologica*, 4(1), 11-19.

In addition to all these, it is important for employers to know the requirements of Labor Law No. 4857, both in **hotels and the food & beverage** sector.

Consumer protection laws: Data protection has become an important issue due to consumer privacy and security concerns. The Hospitality Industry should review data protection regulations to protect customer data. In addition, there are laws to set the maximum price, ensure and maintain a certain standard of quality.

As of 31 December 2021, the Law on the Protection of Personal Data No. 6698 has been inclusive of all companies in Türkiye. Hotels were among the businesses where KVKK was first applied. Hotels have to give more importance to privacy as they deal with both natural and legal persons. With this law, hotels will not be able to share their private information records with any person or institution unless there is a judicial investigation.

The images and pictures taken for advertising or promotion of customers on holiday in hotels are secured within the scope of KVKK. In this way, both the private life of the customer will not be violated and the loss of the image of the enterprises will be prevented.

There are special articles within the scope of KVKK. According to the law; Special contracts are made with the personnel working in the unit called the front office. Employees are prevented from receiving, sharing or deciphering private information about customers. Again, e-mails or other sharing made over the private wi-fi lines of the hotels are also legally secured within the scope of privacy. Private server networks have also been established for hotels to provide more secure service to their customers.

Intellectual property laws: Intellectual property regulations are designed to protect companies' patents and valuable ideas. Failure to protect intellectual property rights may result in loss of competitive advantage, which may weaken the Hospitality Industry's position against other market players.

2.2.2. Industry Micro Environment

It is difficult for companies to stay competitive in the markets where accommodation businesses are located. In order to gain a competitive advantage, companies should analyze their customers well and be able to respond to their increasingly complex requests. Because today, customers see themselves as members of a large group and demand that they be treated accordingly. Today, businesses that are aware of this and know their customers and respond to their requests are successful (Yıldırım & Çakırlı, 2020).

2.2.2.1. Customers

- **Domestic Customers**

Activities of residents travelling to and staying in places outside of their usual environment but within their own country are called Domestic Tourism. There is Household Domestic Tourism research conducted by TUIK since 2009. With the household domestic tourism research, it is aimed to determine the settlements, profile and travel qualities visited by the household members travelling in the country. Therefore, in this context, the following tables have been created by using TUIK data.

In Table 121, travel expenditures of domestic tourists between 2009 and 2022 are presented according to their expenditure types.

Table 121: Domestic Tourism Expenditure by Types of Expenditure (2009-2022)

Years	Total	Package tour expenditures	Individual Expenditures							
			Total	Eating and drinking	Accommodation	Health	Transportation	Clothing and Giftware	Other Expenditures	Trip expenditures made before trip (Clothing, medicines, bag, camera, film, etc.)
2009	12216339	613634	11602705	3346897	1039959	563735	3705799	1743622	947041	255651
2010	13843504	605679	13237826	3839675	1068978	578775	4428906	1947013	1071476	303003
2011	15641262	664061	14977201	4555155	1402713	529313	5029706	2247555	909987	302772
2012	16725035	932435	15792600	4884311	1412272	534492	5366830	2238099	946708	409888
2013	18416817	1274597	17142220	5123880	1600964	571790	5916310	2497768	960252	471255
2014	22601201	1159814	21441387	6643053	2192097	854328	6758773	3155854	1154862	682420
2015	24409560	1723958	22685602	7336305	2288932	856404	7108739	2974316	1587703	533203
2016	28033083	2490316	25542766	8632555	3115309	950265	7766935	3089239	1821776	166688
2017	35305804	2899922	32405882	10957325	3753780	1273779	9649226	3901606	2627436	242731
2018	40266153	3507822	36758331	12283998	4887560	1353284	11746411	3896637	2266538	323903
2019	48910856	3964996	44945860	15644988	5933370	2192184	13889437	4329643	2547619	408619
2020	32250278	1880908	30369370	11789078	3710050	1371086	9411965	2396320	1503785	187086
2021	58104752	5095471	53009281	18234366	8121933	2420448	15300151	4556810	3690758	684816

Table 122: Distribution of Domestic Tourists by Travel Purpose

Year	Total	Travel, leisure, vacation	Culture	Visiting relatives	Health	Meeting, conference, courses, seminars	Commercial relations, fair	Other
2009	60888	11347	730	40026	4872	773	675	2467
2010	68373	12362	634	46242	5288	779	712	2357
2011	65854	12898	546	44603	3925	970	621	2291
2012	64922	12682	581	43039	4752	820	546	2502
2013	68452	13782	697	44897	5320	977	474	2305
2014	70894	13469	708	46596	5938	1 027	585	2572
2015	71251	13332	788	48113	4726	963	493	2834
2016	68450	14722	668	45121	4338	788	484	2329
2017	77179	15988	973	52100	4492	789	541	2296
2018	78523	21030	238	50233	3616	818	458	2130
2019	78202	20755	254	49826	3595	869	564	2339
2020	42847	10727	121	28131	1796	325	406	1341
2021	52774	15964	168	31057	2665	503	614	1802

It is seen that the most travels are made in 2018 – 2019, and the most travel is made for the purpose of visiting relatives and vacations in all years.

Table 123: Number of Trips of Domestic Visitors by type of Accommodation (2009-2022)

Year	Total	Hotel	Pension	Own house	House of friend or relative	Other
2009	60888	5801	1264	3571	46420	3836
2010	68373	6760	1197	4700	52240	3475
2011	65854	7572	1205	4327	49111	3638
2012	64922	7577	1210	3609	48832	3695
2013	68452	7795	1535	5129	49768	4226
2014	70894	7950	1600	4555	51623	5167
2015	71251	8999	1418	5237	51090	4507
2016	68450	10604	1323	3894	47933	4696
2017	77179	11827	1317	4081	54903	5051
2018	78523	12488	1579	4923	54024	5509
2019	78202	12479	1904	5532	53042	5245
2020	42847	5260	1082	4089	29410	3007
2021	52774	9601	1457	4034	33346	4336

It is seen that the most frequent accommodation type in all years is the house of friends or relatives, and the hotel is the second.

Table 124: Number of Trips of Domestic Visitors by Age Groups (2009-2022)

Year	Total	0-14	15-24	25-44	45-64	65+
2009	60888	13359	8077	22506	13630	3314
2010	68373	14847	9284	24997	15343	3901
2011	65854	14173	8284	24999	14851	3548
2012	64922	14095	8386	24312	14738	3391
2013	68452	14754	8248	25807	15937	3706
2014	70894	14522	8753	26660	16340	4619
2015	71251	14488	8578	26755	16928	4501
2016	68450	13718	7858	26512	15862	4501
2017	77179	15670	9134	28977	18433	4965
2018	78523	16367	9139	29019	19215	4783
2019	78202	15275	8596	29106	19981	5243
2020	42847	8672	4811	17107	9958	2299
2021	52774	10318	5959	20241	12976	3280

When Table 124 is examined, it is seen that domestic tourists between the ages of 25 and 44 travel more than other age groups in all years.

- **International Customers**

According to the **Border Entry Statistics** announced by the Ministry of Culture¹¹⁸ and Tourism and TUIK¹¹⁹, the graph of foreign visitors coming to our country between 2013 and 2022 is presented below.

¹¹⁸ <https://yigm.ktb.gov.tr/TR-249709/yillik-bultenler.html>

¹¹⁹ <https://data.tuik.gov.tr/Bulten/Index?p=Turizm-Istatistikleri-IV.Ceyrek:-Ekim-Aralik-ve-Yillik>

Figure 79: Number of Inbound Foreign Tourists (2013-2022)

When Figure 79 is examined, it is seen that the number of foreign tourists coming to our country followed a parallel situation in 2013, 2014 and 2015, a decrease was experienced in 2016, and an increasing trend in 2017, 2018 and 2019. It is also seen in the chart that it reached the lowest number in 2020, which is the COVID-19 period. In the following period, there was a rapid increase in the number of foreign tourists.

Figure 80: Number of Inbound Foreign Tourists (Monthly - 2022)

Considering the months of 2022, it is seen that the summer months (June - July - August) are the months with the highest number of foreign tourists.

The distribution of foreign visitors according to the provinces they come from is presented on the map of Türkiye.

Figure 81: Distribution of Foreign Visitors to Türkiye by Provinces - 2022

When Figure 82 is examined, it is seen that the most visited province is Istanbul, followed by Thrace, Aegean and Mediterranean provinces.

Figure 82: Distribution of Inbound Foreign Tourists by Vehicle (Monthly - 2022)

Considering the months of 2022, it is seen that foreign tourists mostly come to our country by air transportation.

Figure 83: Number of Inbound Foreign Tourists by Continents (2022)

It is seen that foreign tourists mostly come from Europe-OECD countries and the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS) countries.

Table 125: Top Visitor Countries (2020 – 2022)

Country	2020	2021	2022
Germany	1118932	3085215	5679194
USA	148937	371759	1013478
Bulgaria	1242961	1402795	2882512
France	311708	621493	986090
Georgia	410501	291852	1514813
Holland	271526	645601	1244756
UK	820709	392746	3370739
Iraq	387587	836624	1208895
Iranian	385762	1153092	2331076
Poland	145908	585076	1135903
Romania	269076	496178	886555
Russian Fed.	2128758	4694422	5232611
Ukraine	997652	2060008	675467

When Table 125 is examined, it is seen that the country with the highest number of visitors in 2020 and 2021 is the Russian Federation, and in 2022 it is Germany.

Figure 84: Top Visitor Countries (2020 – 2022)

When Figure 126 is examined, it is seen that the country sending the highest number of tourists to our country between 2020 and 2022 is the Russian Federation, followed by Germany in the second place.

Table 126: Minimum Visitor Countries (2020 – 2022)

Country	2020	Country	2021	Country	2022
Malta	3258	Chile	3815	Malta	16321
New Zealand	2879	Singapore	2951	New Zealand	15448
Luxembourg	2228	New Zealand	2746	Luxembourg	13186
Southern Cyprus	2207	Southern Cyprus	2471	Southern Cyprus	11254
Iceland	541	Iceland	962	Iceland	4070

When Table 126 is examined, it is seen that Iceland, Southern Cyprus, Luxembourg and New Zealand are the countries that send the least visitors in all years.

Table 127: Distribution of Foreign Tourists by Purpose of Arrival

Year	Travel, entertainment, sportive or cultural activities	Visiting relatives and friends	Education, training (less than a year)	Health or medical reasons (less than a year)	Shopping	Business (conferences, meetings, assignments etc.)	Other
2012	24953961	6792033	231152	240682	934204	2224844	968339
2013	26817201	7239397	195918	300102	1000734	2404344	1164596
2014	28740654	7332325	183351	473896	1099326	2381482	1074300
2015	28738633	7502233	150190	395019	1187589	2260244	1253998
2016	18234867	8184670	104253	400699	1280137	1844404	1236625
2017	23737720	9535640	106158	467302	1566050	1812796	1341174
2018	30888281	9264254	118389	594851	1488904	1948409	1221913
2019	36077029	10063958	142075	701046	1691594	1904427	1078098
2021	19042762	7469644	75195	670730	810306	1050784	199837
2022	34493205	10948412	155008	1258382	2356255	1541231	502031
Total	271724313	84332566	1461689	5502709	13415099	19372965	10040911

* Except 2020 (COVID-19)

When the purpose of arrival of foreign tourists between 2012 and 2022 is examined, it is seen that "travel, entertainment, sports and cultural activities" are the first in the purpose of arrival, and "Education, internship (less than 1 year)" is the least.

Figure 85: Change Rates of Foreign Tourists' Arrival Purposes by Years

When Figure 85 is examined, it is seen that there is a significant increase in the purpose of foreign tourists, especially for "health and medical reasons (less than 1 year)", in 2022 compared to the previous year. This situation shows that health tourism in Türkiye has increased significantly in 2022 compared to other years. Likewise, it is seen that foreign tourists coming for "shopping" show a significant increase in 2022 compared to the previous year.

2.2.2.2. Competitors

One of the main sources of competition, "competition among existing competitors" is the main factor that determines the profitability of businesses in the sector. The main factors that determine the intensity of competition in the sector and play a role in the formation of the level of competition; The number of competitors in the sector, the difference of competitors, the difference in production or service, excess capacity and exit barriers, cost situations (economies of scale and fixing rates of variable costs), supply & demand structure and growth rate of the market, price elasticity of tourism demand and income elasticity.¹²⁰

Although there are many enterprises in the tourism sector in Türkiye, investments in this field continue rapidly. Although the number of enterprises in the sector is very high, the rapid increase in the number of enterprises entering the sector brings many problems in terms of tourism in our country. The increase in the number of accommodation establishments has maximized the intensity of competition in both the domestic and foreign markets. For this reason, hotel operators stated for the first time that the main problem in **tourism is excess supply**. The intensification of competition requires a review of the marketing strategies of hotel businesses. For this purpose, accommodation establishments have often started to prefer the price, which is the easiest marketing weapon to use, by sacrificing quality, and they have integrated their low price strategy with the all-inclusive system. The all-inclusive system enables tourism businesses to increase their occupancy rates, to offer different accommodation

¹²⁰ Keklik Okul, F. (2019). "Antalya Turizm Sektörünün Porter'in 5 Güç Analizi Çerçevesinde İncelenmesi", International Social Sciences Studies Journal, 5(44): 5163-5176.

options, to extend the tourism season, to strengthen their financial structures and to plan many activities better.¹²¹

- **Accommodation**

Tourism has a privileged importance, especially in economies with important touristic destinations, tourism potential and service sector-dominated economies. This situation causes competition among the countries with these characteristics in order to get a larger share from the tourism sector.¹²²

It is known that the focal point of international tourism movements is Europe, and within Europe the Mediterranean area. Türkiye is the country that receives the highest share from Eastern Mediterranean tourism among the countries of Southern Cyprus, Israel and Egypt, which are within the scope of the Eastern Mediterranean countries. When we look at the four countries in the Mediterranean region (France, Spain, Italy and Greece), they have a very large part of the international tourist traffic in the region. Spain, France, Italy and Greece are countries that are members of the EU, located in the Mediterranean region, took part in the tourism sector long before Türkiye and have reached important agreements until today. Especially France, Spain and Italy are among the top touristic countries that earn the most. Although the beginning of Greece was later, it could have received a significant amount of barter compared to its potential. In addition to summer holidays, France has a very large winter holiday, cultural, rural and business tourism potential. The fact that historical development has a long history since the "Grand Tours" shows France's superiority in tourism¹²³.

Türkiye ranks 3rd in the list of countries that receive the most tourists in 2022, announced by the United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO). According to these data, France ranked first, followed by Spain. Italy, which is an important competitor of Türkiye in Europe, is in the fifth place.

¹²¹ Keklik Okul, F. (2019). "Antalya Turizm Sektörünün Porter'in 5 Güç Analizi Çerçevesinde İncelenmesi", *International Social Sciences Studies Journal*, 5(44): 5163-5176.

¹²² Akın, A., Akın, A., & Erkmen, A. Türk Ve Yunan Turizm Sektörünün Swot Analizi İle Değerlendirilmesi., 2018.

¹²³ Yıldırğan, M. S., Kingır, S., & Batman, O. (2021), A Study on the Comparative Analysis of Türkiye and Its Mediterranean Competitors in the Travel and Tourism (T&T) Competitiveness Report). *Journal of Tourism & Gastronomy Studies*, 9(5 (Special)), 73-90.

Other countries that make up the top ten of this list are United States of America, Mexico, Greece, England, Germany and Portugal. According to the report, in 2020, when the epidemic emerged and spread rapidly, tourism destinations around the world suffered great losses and Türkiye's rivals saw bottom levels that year.

Looking at the UNWTO data, Spain, one of Türkiye's leading competitors in tourism, decreased by 76 percent in the first 8 months, while Greece experienced a decline of 81 percent in the first 7 months. While Italy's loss in tourism in the first 7 months of the year was 43%, Croatia, one of the rising destinations of the Mediterranean basin in recent years, experienced a 53% loss in the 8-month period. In Portugal, another important destination in the Mediterranean basin, the loss in the 8-month period was 40 percent, while the loss in Egypt was 82%.¹²⁴¹²⁵

In line with these data, it can be said that Türkiye's important competitors in Europe in terms of tourism and hotel management are France, Spain, Italy and Greece. In this direction, the chart below, which was created based on UNWTO data, shows the tourist numbers of Türkiye and its competitors.

Figure 86: International Tourist Arrivals

¹²⁴ (<https://www.aa.com.tr/tr/ekonomi/turkiyenin-turizmdeki-rakipleri-dip-seviyeleri-gordu/2074473>).

¹²⁵ <https://www.unwto.org/tourism-statistics/key-tourism-statistics>.

While international tourist arrivals were 51.2 million in 2019, this number decreased by 69% due to COVID-19 to approximately 15.9 million visitors in 2020. Due to the epidemic, it is seen that 2020 had a 6% better year in visitor traffic than the world average, and there was an increase of over 14% in visitor traffic. While Türkiye minimized the losses in tourism revenues in this process, it implemented sustainable activities and practices in a short time in order to maintain its competitiveness.¹²⁶¹²⁷

The World Economic Forum has started to publish quite comprehensive reports, also known as the Travel and Tourism Competitiveness Index (TTCI), on the competitiveness of tourism, which started with 124 countries since 2007. The aim of the index, which is published every two years, is to act as a strategic tool to measure the factors that make tourism development attractive in different countries and to allow all stakeholders to work together for development. In addition, the index aims to contribute to national growth and social welfare by increasing the competitiveness of the tourism industry in national economies. The World Economic Forum last published the Travel and Tourism Competitiveness Index in 2019, and updated it in 2021 as the Travel and Tourism Development Index (TTDI). TTDI benchmarks and measures “a set of factors and policies that enable the sustainable and resilient development of the Travel and Tourism (T&T) sector and consequently contribute to the development of a country”. The new framework provides a useful and flexible tool for leaders and practitioners to benchmark performance and evaluate T&T development, management and long-term strategies by addressing the myriad factors that contribute to more resilient and sustainable destinations and travel markets overall. Some of the most notable framework and methodology differences between the TTCI and TTDI include the additions of new pillars, including Non-Leisure Resources, Socioeconomic Resilience and Conditions, and T&T Demand Pressure and Impact. The index is comprised of five subindexes (used for presentation and categorization purposes only), 17 pillars and 112 individual indicators, distributed among the different pillars.¹²⁸¹²⁹

Aside from the United States (2nd), the top 10 scoring countries are high-income economies in the Europe and Eurasia or Asia-Pacific regions. Japan tops the ranking,

¹²⁶ <https://kpmg.com/tr/tr/home/gorusler/2021/08/sektorel-bakis-2021.html>.

¹²⁷ Göral, R. ve Yurtlu, M. (2021). Uluslararası Seyahat ve Turizm Rekabetçilik Endeksi Kapsamında, Türkiye'nin Güçlü ve Zayıf Yönlerinin Değerlendirilmesi, *Sosyal, Beşeri ve İdari Bilimler Dergisi*, 4(6): 544-576.

¹²⁸ WEF Travel-Torism Report,2021.

¹²⁹ Öncüer, M. E., & Muca, E. K., 2022, Güney Avrupa Ülkelerinin Seyahat Ve Turizm Rekabet Gücü Açısından. Karşılaştırılması, *Journal of Gastronomy, Hospitality and Travel*, 2022, 5(4), 1687-1704.

with fellow regional economies Australia and Singapore coming in 7th and 9th, respectively. Meanwhile, Italy joined the top 10 (up from 12th in 2019) in 2021, while Canada slid out (10th to 13th). The remaining top 10 TTDI performers are Spain (3rd), France (4th), Germany (5th), Switzerland (6th) and the United Kingdom (8th). Vietnam experienced the greatest improvement in score (+4.7%, 60th to 52nd) on the overall index, while Indonesia (+3.4%, 44th to 32nd) and Saudi Arabia (+2.3%, 43rd to 33rd) had the greatest improvement in rank. Meanwhile, Malaysia (-3.0%, 29th to 38th), India (-2.6%, 46th to 54th) and Mongolia (-2.1%, 76th to 84th) had the largest declines in ranking. Türkiye, on the other hand, was ranked 45th in this report.¹³⁰

According to the report, the factors contributing to Türkiye in terms of competition are; data on its cultural and touristic potential and air transport infrastructure. However, it is seen that the biggest problems arise in the fields of environmental sustainability, safety, security, human resources and labor market. In this respect, the issue of environmental sustainability is seen as a critical element in Türkiye's competitive race with its important competitors in the Mediterranean basin. On the other hand, violence, crime and terrorist incidents are among the other important factors that make Türkiye score negatively in terms of tourism competition.¹³¹ While Türkiye is at the forefront of world rankings in terms of its rich cultural heritage, it ranked last among the four competing European countries discussed above. Infrastructure index includes airline transportation, ground and port infrastructure, and tourist service infrastructure. Among these factors, Türkiye ranks 3rd after France and Spain in terms of air transport infrastructure. One of the most important factors of the increase in foreign tourism demand for Türkiye in recent years is the low price of Turkish tourism products compared to countries such as Spain and Italy. In addition to all these, tourism revenues do not increase in the same way, the quality of the service has decreased because cheap products are provided. It is seen that there has not been much progress in the preparation of information and communication technologies. Türkiye needs to make more efforts in this regard. To summarize briefly; factors contributing to Türkiye's competitiveness are air transportation infrastructure, cultural resources, tourist service infrastructure, developments in tourism infrastructure, business travel, political rules and regulations, travel and tourism demand. The factors that put a negative score on

¹³⁰ WEF Travel-Tourism Report, 2021.

¹³¹ WEF, 2019.

Türkiye 's competitiveness are; environmental sustainability, security, human resources and labor market and natural resources. If we go into detail, there may be factors such as traffic accidents, terrorism, murder and violence, protection of natural resources, health measures, number of doctors, location and port infrastructure, internet usage, internet subscription.¹³²

According to the report, the general situation of Spain, France, Italy, Greece and Türkiye is summarized in the table below.

Table 128: The Travel & Tourism Development Index Country Rankings

	SPAIN	FRANCE	ITALY	GREECE	TÜRKİYE
International Tourist Arrivals	31181	48395	26888	14705	29925
Travel & Tourism Development Index	3	4	10	28	45
Enabling Environment subindex	30	22	39	42	64
Travel and Tourism Policy and Enabling	11	37	36	20	31
Infrastructure subindex	2	5	11	19	29
Travel and Tourism Demand Drivers	5	6	10	31	20
Travel and Tourism Sustainability subindex	32	22	33	51	104
Business Environment pillar	47	29	59	82	64
Safety and Security pillar	18	47	52	63	90
Health and Hygiene pillar	25	6	16	11	63
Human Resources and Labour Market pillar	38	30	34	44	56
ICT Readiness pillar	17	20	42	37	52
Prioritization of Travel & Tourism pillar	22	79	55	4	33
International Openness pillar	5	7	12	16	75
Price competitiveness pillar	90	101	100	106	18
Air Transport Infrastructure pillar	8	10	19	22	14
Ground and Port Infrastructure pillar	16	10	18	37	40
Tourist Service Infrastructure pillar	3	13	6	9	37
Natural Resources pillar	11	9	15	42	49
Cultural Resources pillar	3	7	1	21	13
Non-Leisure Resources pillar	11	9	19	39	23
Environmental Sustainability pillar	39	14	40	33	102
Socioeconomic Resilience & Conditions pillar	25	10	20	36	77
T&T Demand Pressure & Impact pillar	81	108	91	110	103

¹³² Yıldırğan, M. S., Kingir, S., & Batman, O. (2021), A Study on the Comparative Analysis of Türkiye and Its Mediterranean Competitors in the Travel and Tourism (T&T) Competitiveness Report). *Journal of Tourism & Gastronomy Studies*, 9(5 (Special)), 73-90.

When a general evaluation of Türkiye and its competitors in the Mediterranean region is made, the following can be mentioned; besides being a Mediterranean country and lying on the shores of the Black Sea, Türkiye is a peninsula surrounded by seas on all sides, surrounded by the Sea of Marmara, which seems like an inland sea, and the Aegean Sea between Greece and itself. It is a country that acts as a bridge between Europe and Asia, so it is placed in a transitional destination causing many cultures to interact. Being a synthesis of the East and the West, it draws attention with its extraordinary cultural assets. Having the chance to live in different geographies during the four seasons at the same time, Türkiye has a very diverse climate. The climate and geographical structure provide opportunities for all kinds of tourism activities (coast, winter, mountain, country, bird watching, sports, etc.). Since it has hosted many civilizations since the beginning of early history, it is possible to come across archaeological remains from any period of history in any corner of Türkiye. Unlike France, Spain and Greece, which are its competitors in the tourism sector, which are all EU member Mediterranean countries, Türkiye 's history in the sector is not very long and significant progress has been made despite late participation. Supply sources need to be protected for the sustainability of tourism, which provides an important exchange income for France, Spain, Italy, Greece and Türkiye located around the Mediterranean and has an important place in international tourism activities.

Spain, a Mediterranean country, ranks first in world tourism. An important feature of Spanish tourism is related to accommodation tours. A large number of visitors stay in accommodation facilities unlike hotels such as apartments, detached houses, bungalows or rental houses, second residences and temporary residences.¹³³ Accommodation tours of Spain excluding hotels have an important position in the world. According to the latest UNWTO data, the number of tourists coming to Spain is 31.2 million. In total there were around 53,174 accommodation establishments in Spain in 2020, including hotels, camping grounds, recreational parks, holiday and other short-stay accommodation.¹³⁴ In 2021, Spain was the most popular EU destination for

¹³³ YILDIRGAN, M. S., KINGIR, S., & BATMAN, O. (2021), A Study on the Comparative Analysis of Türkiye and Its Mediterranean Competitors in the Travel and Tourism (T&T) Competitiveness Report). *Journal of Tourism & Gastronomy Studies*, 9(5 (Special)), 73-90.

¹³⁴ <https://www.statista.com/statistics/413421/number-of-short-stay-accommodation-establishments-in-spain/>

international tourists, with 114 million nights spent in tourist accommodation, or 19% of the EU total.¹³⁵

The Spanish hotel industry contributes a great deal to its country's economy, and it is also one of the main drivers of the entire European market. In 2020, hotels and similar lodgings in Spain generated the fifth-largest revenue in the continent, adding up to approximately seven billion euros. In the previous year, Spain had accounted for around one-third of the chain hotels in Europe. As a leading player in this industry, several international chains are part of the Spanish hotel landscape. At the top of the 2021 ranking was the U.S. American company Marriott International, accounting for more than 13 thousand rooms. Nonetheless, domestic hotel chains are the leaders of the market, with Meliá Hotels International and Barceló Hotel Group at the top of the list. In the last years, the number of registered companies operating in the hotel industry in Spain—which includes hostels, apartment hotels, motels— has remained relatively stagnant at approximately 12.5 thousand, except for 2018 when the number peaked at 13.5 thousand. Most of the Spanish hotel companies fall under the category 'microbusinesses', with over half of them employing up to two people. For the most part, the hotel industry in Spain is driven by international tourists, while most domestic travelers would rather stay at other types of accommodation. In 2021, foreign overnight travelers made up around two-thirds of guests at hotels and hostels in Spain, which reverted the distribution shown in 2020, when because of the COVID-19 pandemic, domestic tourists constituted the largest share of hotel customers in the country. In the first year of the global COVID-19 crisis, hotels and similar accommodation establishments in Spain experienced a drop of roughly 80 percent in the number of international guests. In 2021, the total had grown back to 20 million tourists, representing a year-over-year increase of approximately 86 percent. However, this figure was still 63 percent below pre-pandemic levels, suggesting that the full recovery path might take several years to complete. From a bed occupancy perspective, the rates between October and December 2021 were the closest to the figures of 2019, while April and May 2021 stayed the furthest away from pre-COVID-19 rates.¹³⁶

¹³⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Tourism_statistics&oldid=587265#Nights_spent_abroad_by_EU_residents:_Luxembourg_leads_in_nights_per_inhabitant

¹³⁶ <https://www.statista.com/topics/7746/hotel-industry-in-spain/#topicOverview>.

France has everything to offer: beaches, culture, history, cuisine and stunning landscapes. For beach resorts and a sunny, Mediterranean climate, head to the South of France and in particular the French Riviera. If anyone is interested in culture, Paris is a must see as it is a world capital of art and culture. Normandy in the west of France is steeped in history - from William the Conqueror to World War Two's Normandy landings. But if anyone wants to discover a different side to France, visit the Midi Pyrenees in the South west, whose unique culture, history and landscape sets it apart from the well known tourist regions.¹³⁷

The hospitality market in **France** is estimated at USD 20.5 billion in the current year and is poised to register a CAGR of greater than 1.5% during the forecast period. After an unprecedented year in 2020 due to COVID-19, 2021 marked the slow recovery of hotel industry performances toward their pre-crisis levels in France. Several phases were identified, with the first half of the year still very much affected by COVID restrictions, followed by the second period of clear improvement, driven by the coastal regions and the French province from the summer onwards, and finally, a gradual recovery in Paris at the end of the year. Overall, the French hotel industry closed in 2021 with a 43% drop in turnover compared to 2019. The French hotel sector performance indicators continued to improve during 2022, confirming the positive trend observed for the entire first quarter of 2022. Although still down from the March 2019 performance, occupancy increased eight points compared to February 2022, reaching 56%. RevPAR also showed a slight increase during March 2022, but it remains down 3% from 2019 performance. Only the average revenue per room rented confirmed its increase compared to 2019, posting an 8% increase to EUR 95 (USD 101.3) in March 2022. While encouraging for the coming months and the sector's recovery, this upward trend is likely to be impacted by continued inflation, rising wages, and energy prices due, in particular, to the war in Ukraine. France has large leading international hotel groups such as Accor and Louvre. But unlike in many countries, 83 percent of the French hotels between one and four stars (60 percent in Paris) are independent with less financial backing and profitability. They belong either to individuals or to special-purpose vehicles, set up for individual tax exemption schemes. Ninety-three percent of

¹³⁷ <https://www.europeaninternships.com/hospitality-management-in-france-in-hotels-and-restaurants.htm>.

the bookings go through online tourism agencies (“OTAs”) and this system is favorable for both large groups and independent hotels.¹³⁸

When international tourists come to France on vacation, or when the French tourists themselves travel within their country, there are many accommodation options available. Hotels, campgrounds, holidays rentals, and more - the French accommodation offering is diverse and has the potential to meet any budget. The accommodation sector, combined with the restaurant sector, generates a turnover of several billion euros each year in France. Hotels and campgrounds are the two most significant types of accommodation in this sector, both in terms of the number of establishments and the number of overnight stays. 2020 was a landmark year for the industry, regardless of the nature of the accommodation. The coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic led to a significant drop in the French hospitality sector because of the requirement for most accommodation facilities to be closed for several weeks or months. Moreover, severe restrictions on international travel and tourism also meant that international tourists became scarcer in 2020.

After more than a year of the pandemic, French travelers were asked about the type of accommodation they would choose for their summer vacations in 2021. The survey revealed that nearly 40 percent planned to book a vacation rental, and 37 percent planned to stay with friends or family. Apart from staying with loved ones, individual accommodation options were seen as an appropriate alternative given the current pandemic situation.¹³⁹

Italy is traditionally one of the most popular tourist destinations in Europe. Italy, which serves winter sports tourism and holidays in addition to the seaside in the Mediterranean, is also a very important country in terms of cultural tourism. Italy, which is a very attractive tourism country with its geographical location, climate and natural beauties, shows that it has an important part of the historical and artistic features of the world.¹⁴⁰

¹³⁸ <https://www.researchandmarkets.com/reports/5012549/hospitality-industry-in-france-growth-trends>.

¹³⁹ <https://www.statista.com/topics/8258/accommodation-in-france/#editorsPicks>.

¹⁴⁰ YILDIRGAN, M. S., KINGIR, S., & BATMAN, O. (2021), A Study on the Comparative Analysis of Türkiye and Its Mediterranean Competitors in the Travel and Tourism (T&T) Competitiveness Report). *Journal of Tourism & Gastronomy Studies*, 9(5 (Special)), 73-90.

Calabria in the South West of Italy is primarily a mountainous region with landscapes of natural beauty as well as being rich in art and culture. Tuscany is well known for its reputation as the "cradle of all-time art" The region of Lazio is known for its landscapes and ancient volcanic districts as well being the home to Italy's capital: Rome. In the North of Italy, Lombardy holds the major Italian lakes and many cultural museums with Milan as its regional capital. ¹⁴¹The hospitality industry in Italy is recording a growing revenue. This growth is attributed to the rising the tourism industry, which recorded a growth of EUR 100 billion and welcomed more than 63 million tourists, in 2018. The demand from domestic companies and different European Union countries has become the key driver for the tourism industry, and it accounted for around 60% of the tourism industry in Italy. This trend is reflecting on the growth of domestic and international, branded hotels, and their chains, with double the difference in their presence rate, across the country. The international visitors are highly restricted to Milan and Rome in high numbers, followed by Florence and Venice. Rome became the home for high luxury branded brands, with more than 45, 5-stars hotels that are international brands. The hospitality industry in Italy is the largest market, and it occupies the fourth position in the world, in terms of a number of available rooms, with a total of around 1 million rooms, preceded by the United States, China, and Japan. Italy is also registering more number of overnight stays. Most of the international brands are performing as management contracts in the region.¹⁴²

Greece is one of the leading countries in the tourism sector of Europe with its cultural and touristic features. The main objectives of Greek tourism policies are; to strengthen the competitiveness of the tourism sector, to improve the general infrastructure by improving the service quality, to take advantage of the empty and missing capacity, to apply a balanced supply model, to prepare and implement an environment.¹⁴³

Greece has many natural tourism resources as well as cultural tourism, especially in Thessaloniki, Athens and Olympia. Bird watching, skiing, cave tourism, water sports, mountain climbing, trekking, etc. in areas with natural formations such as mountains, lakes, rivers and canyons in the region. Many touristic activities can be done.

¹⁴¹ <https://www.europeaninternships.com/hospitality-management-in-italy-in-hotels-and-restaurants.htm>.

¹⁴² <https://www.researchandmarkets.com/reports/5176876/hospitality-industry-in-italy-growth-trends>.

¹⁴³ Yildirgan, M. S., Kingir, S., & Batman, O. (2021), A Study On The Comparative Analysis of Türkiye and Its Mediterranean Competitors In The Travel And Tourism (T&T) Competitiveness Report). *Journal Of Tourism & Gastronomy Studies*,9(5 (Special)), 73-90.

Aegean Islands and Crete, which are the most tourist-attracting regions of Greece, are areas built on sea, sand and sun tourism. A large number of accommodation establishments, mostly two- and three-star, operate on the islands, which attract heavy tourists between June and September. Destinations such as Rhodes, Crete, Kos, Santorini and Samos are accepted as centers preferred by foreign tourists and playing an important role in the island tourism of Greece. Türkiye, which is surrounded by seas on three sides; It is a Mediterranean country that has land in Europe and Asia; It borders with Greece in the Eastern Thrace Region. Greece and Türkiye are neighboring countries that are similar both traditionally and geographically. However, these two actors trying to get a share from the global market in terms of tourism revenues are also rivals of each other in the Mediterranean. As of 2022, Türkiye is in the 3rd place among the countries attracting the most tourists, and Greece is in the 17th place. According to the Travel and Tourism Development Index (TTDI), Türkiye ranks 45th and Greece 28th.¹⁴⁴

- **Food & Beverage**

Turkish Cuisine is one of the most important and oldest cuisines in the world, which has the ability to offer a wide variety of products because it contains different flavors from seven different regions. Changes in geographical regions have also affected Turkish Cuisine. Türkiye is a country preferred for gastronomy tourism with its deep-rooted history, rich cuisine and touristic attraction. We have cities such as Adana, Mersin, Hatay, Urfa, Mardin, which are famous for their local flavors and give importance to gastronomy tourism.

It is thought that Türkiye, which has a richer potential than many countries in the world in terms of gastronomy, will provide a significant increase in the country's tourism revenues when it succeeds in reflecting this feature on tourism.

Cultural interaction, which is the result of Türkiye 's geographical location, climatic characteristics and hosting many cultures, has also added diversity to the culinary culture. In our country, which has an important gastronomic value with these aspects, these values should be adequately promoted and these values should be preserved and transferred to future generations. In addition, gastro tourism routes created in

¹⁴⁴ Akın, A., Akın, A., & Erkmen, A. Türk Ve Yunan Turizm Sektörünün Swot Analizi İle Değerlendirilmesi., 2018.

various countries in our country should be created and plans containing gastro tourism activities and goals should be prepared. This type will also be an effort to support rural development. For this reason, it will be beneficial for rural areas, local governments and tourism companies to work together to organize gastro tourism activities together.¹⁴⁵

The countries where gastronomy tours are concentrated in Europe are **France, Spain, Italy, Portugal** and **Ireland**. Activities carried out in gastronomic tours; visits to local cheese producers, participation in cheese making at workshops, truffle foraging in rural areas, visits to local markets, olive oil tastings and visits to olive oil producers, cooking lessons from famous chefs, vineyards and vintage events, wine tastings and visits to producers, local food and beverage festivals Italian and French cuisines, one of the most famous and well-established cuisines of Europe, come to the fore with their quality, product variety and taste.¹⁴⁶

It is known that gastronomy tourism in the world has increased rapidly in recent years and has an important place in contributing to both city development and the country's economy. For example, when it is thought that the reason why tourists visiting France attract 40 million visitors to a city like Paris alone is the Eiffel tower or French gastronomy, it causes the importance of gastronomy to be given to other countries. However, it is thought that approximately 10% of these tourists travel for this purpose. In addition, the city of Lyon, France, is among the UNESCO world heritage sites and has gained importance in terms of gastronomic tourism with its wines, Michelin-starred restaurant, restaurants with famous chefs and food culture. It is another city.

The France foodservice market size was EUR94.2 billion (\$111.4 billion) in 2021. However, take-away transactions representing a significant percentage of revenue in restaurant channels recorded strong growth in QSR and FSR during 2016–21. QSR remained the largest foodservice channel in terms of value sales. Moreover, owing to a rise in takeaway sales, the channel recorded value growth during 2016–21.¹⁴⁷

¹⁴⁵ Küçükkömürler, S., Şırvan, N. B., & Sezgin, A. C. (2018). Dünyada Ve Türkiye'de Gastronomi Turizmi. *Uluslararası Turizm Ekonomi Ve İşletme Bilimleri Dergisi*, 2(2), 78-85.

¹⁴⁶ Erbay, M., & Sabur, D. G. (2022). Gastronomi Turizmi Kapsamında Pazarlama Stratejileri: Türkiye ve Avrupa Örneği. *Journal of Tourism and Gastronomy Studies*, 10(1), 649-670.

¹⁴⁷ <https://www.globaldata.com/store/report/france-foodservice-market-analysis/>

There are 159,909 Restaurants & Takeaway Food Operators businesses in France as of 2023, a decline of -0.2% from 2022. The Restaurants & Takeaway Food Operators industry in France has low market share concentration and the largest business is Compass. The number of businesses in the Restaurants & Takeaway Food Operators industry in France has remained steady over the five years between 2018 – 2023.¹⁴⁸

There are 74,100 Restaurants & Takeaway Food Operators businesses in **Spain** as of 2023, an increase of 0.4% from 2022. The number of businesses in the Restaurants & Takeaway Food Operators industry in Spain has grown 0.4% per year on average over the five years between 2018-2023. The Restaurants & Takeaway Food Operators industry in Spain has low market share concentration and the largest business is Burger King Spain.¹⁴⁹

The Spanish foodservice profit sector was valued at \$100.9 billion in 2021. The market is projected to grow at a CAGR of more than 8% during the forecast period. Pub, club and bar continues to be the largest profit sector service channel in terms of value sales, followed by FSR. QSR was the fourth-largest channel in the Spanish profit sector. With the easing of restrictions and the revival of tourist visits, dine-ins will continue to dominate most foodservice channels, especially FSR. To boost their popularity among consumers, coffee & tea shop channel operators have been broadening their menu offerings and including a variety of cuisines/dishes that focus on health and nutritional aspects. The key companies in the Spain foodservice market are McDonald's Corporation, Restaurant Brands International, Yum! Brands Inc., Restalia Group, Telepizza Group SA, Pizza Hut, Zena Group, La Tagliatella, Lizarran, Starbucks Espana, Luigi Lavazza, the Coca-Cola Company, Rodilla Group, Café & Té, Beer & Food S.A, and Ibersol Group.¹⁵⁰

Barcelona is one of the most preferred and frequently mentioned cities in the world of gastronomy. So much so that 30% of Barcelona's tourism income is from gastronomy. The reason for this is that it hosts the most respected chefs in the world and has the most reservation requests "El Bulli" and the three Michelin star "El Racode Can Fabes"

¹⁴⁸ <https://www.ibisworld.com/france/industry-statistics/restaurants-takeaway-food-operators/3420/>

¹⁴⁹ <https://www.ibisworld.com/spain/industry-statistics/restaurants-takeaway-food-operators/3420/#:~:text=There%20are%2074%2C100%20Restaurants%20%26%20Takeaway,increase%20of%200.4%25%20from%202022>

¹⁵⁰ <https://www.globaldata.com/store/report/spain-foodservice-market-analysis/#:~:text=The%20Spanish%20foodservice%20profit%20sector.8%25%20during%20the%20forecast%20period.>

restaurants. has an important place in the world of gastronomy with its chocolates and local gastronomy elements that integrate with the city. Thousands of people travel to Barcelona every year, which is one of the cities that can bring gastronomy to the fore along with its historical and cultural structure. While the number of foreign visitors who flock to the market called “La Boqueria” to eat and get to know the local elements is around 2,500 per day, it is stated that this number is equal to the number of visitors to the Picasso Museum.¹⁵¹

There are 155,785 Restaurants & Takeaway Food Operators businesses in Italy as of 2023, a decline of 0% from 2022. The number of businesses in the Restaurants & Takeaway Food Operators industry in Italy has remained steady over the five years between 2018 - 2023. The Restaurants & Takeaway Food Operators industry in Italy has low market share concentration and the largest business is McDonald's Development Italy.¹⁵²

The Italian foodservice profit sector was valued at \$120.5 billion in 2021. The market is projected to grow at a CAGR of more than 6% during the forecast period. In 2021, take-away and dine-in services gradually resumed operations, supporting transactions in the quick-service restaurant (QSR) channel. Coffee and tea shop was the largest channel in Italy's overall profit sector while the full-service restaurant (FSR) was the second-largest foodservice channel. A fall in consumer confidence during the pandemic crisis adversely impacted the pub, club, and bar channel sales. The key companies in the Italy foodservice market are McDonald's Corporation, Restaurant Brands International, Alice Pizza, La Piadineria Italy, Yum! Brands Inc., Cigierre Spa, Gruppo Cremonini, Gruppo Sebeto, A Cento S.p.A, Hard Rock Café, Caffè Pascucci Torrefazione S.p.A., Segafredo Zanetti S.p.a., and illycaffè S.p.A.¹⁵³

The Tuscany region of Italy is famous for its truffles, Florentine meat dishes, Chianti wine, and Lucca's olive oils, and for this reason, thousands of tourists visit the region every year for tasting.¹⁵⁴

¹⁵¹ <https://yemek.win/2018/09/20/dunyada-gastronomi-turizmi-nasildir/>

¹⁵² <https://www.ibisworld.com/italy/industry-statistics/restaurants-takeaway-food-operators/3420/>

¹⁵³ <https://www.globaldata.com/store/report/italy-foodservice-market-analysis/>

¹⁵⁴ <https://yemek.win/2018/09/20/dunyada-gastronomi-turizmi-nasildir/>

2.2.2.3. National Agencies and Organizations

The hospitality sector is a serious factor in the development and growth of national economies. As in any other sector, the organizations and agencies that shape the sector play an important role in this development.

There are four main national agencies and organizations with which the sector can be directly associated and which have been established under a legal framework. The first of these is the **Ministry of Culture and Tourism**. The remaining organizations are the **Union of Chambers and Commodity Exchanges of Türkiye (TOBB)**, which has a Tourism Council, the **Association of Turkish Travel Agencies (TURSAB)** and the **Association of Tourist Guides (TUREB)**, established by law. Other stakeholders, which play important roles in the sector, generally operate as **non-governmental organizations**.¹⁵⁵

- **Government Agencies**

The hospitality sector is of great importance for the country's economy. Under the tourism heading of the Eleventh Development Plan, the importance and purpose of tourism is described. Under this heading, "the main objective is to diversify and develop tourism in line with changing consumer trends and technological developments, to extend the season, to improve service quality and to attract visitors with a higher spending tendency to our country, to increase the duration of accommodation and non-accommodation expenditures, to realize the transformation of the sector within the framework of each destination-specific and focused approach, and to contribute to economic and social development by considering the balance of protection and utilization."¹⁵⁶ Because of the importance the sector is supported by the government with tax incentives, legal regulations, exemptions, subsidies, and etc.

Governance requires cooperation between actors/stakeholders. The Ministry, Special Provincial Administrations, local governments and universities stand out as the main public finance resources to be used in this field. The investments expected from the public and private sectors can be in the areas of accommodation, café, food &

¹⁵⁵ <https://www.sbb.gov.tr/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/TurizmOzellhtisasKomisyonuRaporu.pdf>

¹⁵⁶ https://www.sbb.gov.tr/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/On_Birinci_Kalkinma_Plani-2019-2023.pdf

beverage, guidance services, recognition, agency tour programs, tourism investments, transportation, protection, infrastructure, etc.¹⁵⁷

In order to implement tourism strategies and achieve targets, it is crucial that the entire society, including public institutions and organizations, the business world and civil society organizations, move in harmony in line with common goals.¹⁵⁸

The authority that creates and develops policies is an important factor. In general, tourism policies of countries are developed and implemented by national tourism agencies. The structure, role and function of these organizations vary from country to country. Tourism policies before 80s were more state-centered in Türkiye. After mid-1980s and with the maturation of the private sector and their capabilities, tourism policies became less state centric in the country.¹⁵⁹

1- Ministry of Culture and Tourism

The Ministry of Culture and Tourism plays a regulatory role in the development of the tourism sector and is involved in many different areas such as planning, implementation, certification, promotion, marketing and guidance.¹⁶⁰ Later, this law was reorganized by presidential decree dated 10.07.2018. The duties and powers of the Ministry of Culture and Tourism are as follows.¹⁶¹

- To research, develop, protect, preserve, maintain, evaluate, disseminate, promote and adopt national, spiritual, historical, **cultural and touristic values** and thereby contribute to the strengthening of national unity and economic development,
- To direct public institutions and organizations related to **culture and tourism**, to cooperate with these institutions, to develop communication and cooperate with local administrations, non-governmental organizations and the private sector; to provide cash assistance to projects to be realized by local administrations, associations established by public institutions and organizations or to support public personnel, associations and foundations

¹⁵⁷ Çıracı, H., Turgut, S., & Kerimoğlu, E. (2009). Sürdürülebilir turizm gelişimi için bir yönetim modeli. *İtÜdergisi/a*, 7(2).

¹⁵⁸ <https://yigm.ktb.gov.tr/Eklenti/906.ttstratejisi2023pdf.pdf?0>

¹⁵⁹ Ateş Özalp, S. (2015). Network governance model in tourism administration: a case of Türkiye, METU.

¹⁶⁰ <https://yigm.ktb.gov.tr/Eklenti/906.ttstratejisi2023pdf.pdf?0>

¹⁶¹ <https://www.ktb.gov.tr/TR-96130/kurulus-ve-gorevler.html>

whose main purpose is culture, arts, tourism and promotion activities and private theaters,

- To protect historical and **cultural assets**,
- To utilize, develop and market all the opportunities of the country favorable to **tourism** in order to make tourism a productive sector of the national economy,
- To direct all kinds of investment, communication and development potential in the fields of **culture and tourism**,
- Providing immovable properties related to **culture and tourism investments**, expropriating them when necessary, making and having made their surveys, projects and constructions,
- To carry out activities to promote Türkiye's **touristic assets** in every field and to carry out promotion services related to culture and tourism.

Figure 87: Departments of the Ministry of Culture and Tourism¹⁶²

Within the scope of 2022 **Financial Assistance Projects**, the Ministry sent a total of 98.598.000 TL appropriation, including 15.000.000 TL for Winter Tourism Infrastructure Applications, 23.000.000 TL for Thermal Tourism Infrastructure Applications, 60.000.000 TL for Drinking Water and Sewerage Line Construction and 598.000 TL for Service Building Maintenance and Repair.¹⁶³

¹⁶² <https://www.ktb.gov.tr/TR-96682/birimlerimiz.html>

¹⁶³ <https://yigm.ktb.gov.tr/TR-311906/2022-yili-mali-yardim-projeleri.html>

2- Union of Chambers and Commodity Exchanges of Türkiye (TOBB)

The Union of Chambers and Commodity Exchanges of Türkiye is a confederation of all local chambers of commerce, industry and maritime as well as commodity exchanges in Türkiye. TOBB is the supreme professional organization and legal representative of the private sector in Türkiye. TOBB is the supreme organization of 365 chambers and stock exchanges (Chambers of Commerce, Chambers of Industry, Chambers of Commerce and Industry, Chamber of Commerce and Industry, Chamber of Shipping and Commodity Exchange) spread across 81 provinces and 160 districts.¹⁶⁴

In 2012, the TOBB was elected as Vice President of the Board of Directors of the United Nations World Tourism Organization's Affiliated Members (Private Sector). Regular Tourism Sector Council meetings are organized within TOBB to discuss developments and policies in the sector.¹⁶⁵

3- The Association of Turkish Travel Agencies (TURSAB)

A non-profit institution and a legal personality, established in 1972. The Association of Turkish Travel Agencies effectively represents the tourism sector and increases social consciousness. It takes an active role in developing legal restrictions. In addition to that, it helps to develop the performance of their members and staff. It regulates the environment of competition. It raises the service standards in the sector by organizing training activities that will contribute to the professional development of Travel Agencies. TURSAB is considered the first organized organization in the tourism sector.¹⁶⁶

TURSAB is a member of important international organizations such as the United Nations World Tourism Organization, the International Federation of Travel Agencies Associations (UFTAA), the Group of Travel Agencies and Tour Operators Associations within the European Union (ECTAA). In case of any dissatisfaction, tourists coming to Türkiye have to make refund requests to TURSAB "Consumer Complaints Department", "Consumer-Agency Relations Commission" and "Arbitration Board". Refund requests, which are also called advertisement in the sector. The guest who

¹⁶⁴ https://www.tobb.org.tr/Sayfalar/Kurulus_Gorev_Organ.php

¹⁶⁵ <https://www.sbb.gov.tr/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/TurizmOzellhtisaskomisyonuRaporu.pdf>

¹⁶⁶ <https://www.tursab.org.tr/hakkimizda>

has stayed and left the facility is demanding back some, all or more of the money he/she has paid on the grounds that he/she has not received compensation for the issues he/she was not satisfied with during his/her stay at the facility.¹⁶⁷

4- Association of Tourist Guides (TUREB)

The Association of Tourist Guides (TUREB) was established on 22.06.2012 in accordance with the Law on the Profession of Tourist Guiding and is a professional supreme organization in the nature of 28 public institutions with 13 chambers organized throughout Türkiye, including 7 Professional Chambers and 6 Regional Professional Chambers. With all its units established in accordance with the law, it works to ensure that guides play a more effective role in the country's tourism, to promote the country in line with cultural and tourism policies, and to prevent illegal guiding activities.¹⁶⁸

- **Other Civil Society Organizations**

Some of the non-governmental organizations in the tourism sector in Türkiye are as follows;¹⁶⁹

- **Turkish Hoteliers Federation (TUROFED):** Providing effective and regular service to its members, establishing professional unity and solidarity, realizing the cooperation of associations with each other and with the center, coordinating the relations of members with public-private sector institutions and organizations related to tourism are among the important objectives of TÜROFED.¹⁷⁰
- **Hotel Association of Türkiye (TUROB):** To carry out scientific and practical studies on tourism related issues, problems and solutions and to contribute to such studies, to ensure the development of tourism and touristic facilities in accordance with the requirements of tourism and changing trends, to ensure coordination among its members and with departments, institutions, organizations and persons involved in tourism, to represent its members within and outside the sector, and monitoring national and international developments

¹⁶⁷ <https://www.sbb.gov.tr/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/TurizmOzellhtisasKomisyonuRaporu.pdf>

¹⁶⁸ <https://www.sbb.gov.tr/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/TurizmOzellhtisasKomisyonuRaporu.pdf>

¹⁶⁹ <https://www.sbb.gov.tr/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/TurizmOzellhtisasKomisyonuRaporu.pdf>

¹⁷⁰ <https://www.turofed.org.tr/amac-ve-hedefler>

and working on necessary measures, plans and projects are important objectives of TÜROB.¹⁷¹

- **Turkish Tourism Investors Association (TTYD):** The Turkish Tourism Investors Association (TTYD), as the voluntary representative organization of the tourism sector, represents the Turkish tourism sector on a national and global scale, and aims to carry Turkish tourism to a leading position in the world by ensuring the development of the sector in line with sustainable development goals on both investment and business basis and the interaction of the sector on a global scale with its members consisting of all tourism components of the sector.¹⁷²

- **Tourism Academics Association (TUADER):** The main purpose of the Association of Tourism Academics is to become a national professional tourism organization in Türkiye and to be an umbrella institution for tourism academics. In line with this purpose, multifaceted studies are carried out with all institutional stakeholders to carry out various activities at local, national and international level with a participatory approach.¹⁷³

- **Istanbul & Marmara, Aegean, Mediterranean and Blacksea Regions Chamber of Shipping (IMEAK):** The most important objectives of IMEAK, which is also known as the Chamber of Shipping, are to protect the interests of its members, to meet the common needs of seafarers, to ensure the development of the maritime profession, to facilitate professional activities, to establish common rules, to advise the authorities on maritime problems and at the same time to protect the discipline, ethics and solidarity of the maritime profession.¹⁷⁴

- **Mersin Chamber of Shipping (MDTO):** To meet the common needs of its members to facilitate their professional activities, to ensure the development of the maritime profession in accordance with the general interests are important objectives of MDTO.¹⁷⁵

- **Marine Tourism Association (DTBD):** The aim of the association is to ensure mutual solidarity among the organizations and their members who invest and operate in the field of marine tourism, to conduct research on professional, social

¹⁷¹ <https://www.turob.com/tr/hakkmzda/tuerob-hakkinda/>

¹⁷² <https://ttyd.org.tr/en/hakkimizda/>

¹⁷³ <https://tuader.org/hakkimizda/>

¹⁷⁴ <https://www.denizticaretodasi.org.tr/tr/sayfalar/hakkimizda>

¹⁷⁵ <https://www.mdto.org.tr/tr/hakkimizda>

and technical issues related to the sector and to provide guidance in these matters, to establish sectoral discipline and to contribute to the development of marine tourism in our country, to increase its international competitiveness, to carry out joint activities for the promotion of our country and maritime tourism, to assist in defending the rights and interests of its members against private and legal persons and to apply for legal remedies for this purpose, to ensure the development of infrastructure by cooperating with relevant public institutions and organizations and to ensure the execution of other common services within this framework.¹⁷⁶

- **Professional Hotel Managers Association (POYD):** The Association was established to develop professionalism in the hotel management sector, to strengthen cooperation and communication among sector managers: to seek joint solutions to the problems of the sector and the manager; to ensure that the manager finds his real role and place in the sector. POYD advocates the determination of Professional Standards and the transition to certification in the hotel management profession in our country, as in developed tourism countries, by presenting papers at National Congresses and meetings.¹⁷⁷
- **Tourism Hotel Managers Association (TUROYD):** The Association aims to provide its members with training and career opportunities throughout their professional lives, and to provide opportunities for the legal and managerial needs of the businesses in which they operate.¹⁷⁸
- **International Federation of SKAL Associations (Türkiye):** ,The primary objective of the SKAL Federation of Türkiye, in addition to providing support for growth, is to provide direction and support to the clubs within its body, to produce projects, to strengthen its weight within the sector, to raise awareness of the public and the sector by organizing useful meetings, to create friendship, common understanding and cooperation among the clubs and among its members working in the tourism industry.¹⁷⁹
- **Turkish Restaurant & Entertainment Association (TURYİD):** TURYİD is a pioneering non-governmental organization founded with the basic ideas of bringing the sector together for the first time in parallel with the rapidly developing

¹⁷⁶ <https://denizturizmbirligi.org.tr/dernek-tuzuqu/>

¹⁷⁷ <https://poyd.org/poyd>

¹⁷⁸ <https://turoyd.org/hakkimizda/>

¹⁷⁹ <https://www.skalturkiye.com/skal-nedir>

gastronomy world in the world and finding solutions to the problems of the food, beverage and entertainment industries. It continues to work with a mission that brings the contribution of gastronomy to export, tourism, country brand, diplomacy and culture starting from agriculture to the agenda for the first time with the title Gastro Economy and makes the social dimensions of gastronomy visible.¹⁸⁰

- ***Cooks and Pastry Culinary Confederation (TASPAKON)***: TAŞPAKON was established to contribute to the development of the art of cookery and pastry, cooks and pastry makers in Türkiye, to protect the values belonging to our country's cuisine and local cuisines by making them suitable for today's living standards, to raise awareness on this issue and contribute to increasing consumption, to increase professional and social solidarity among cooks and pastry makers in our country, to cooperate with and support individuals and organizations working in line with their service issues.¹⁸¹

- ***Turkish Culinary Federation (TAFED)***: The aim of TAFED is to gather all regional associations in Türkiye under the same roof and to contribute to the development of the culinary profession in our country and in the world, to better position the profession both legally and socially, to support the vocational training of culinary artisans and to bring them to higher levels, to support young people and women and to bring them into this profession.¹⁸²

- ***Turkish Tourism Writers and Journalists Association (TUYED)***: TUYED has united tourism journalists, reporters, writers, editors and academics under the roof of an association. TUYED members aim to share their experience and know-how in the travel industry with the public as well as the industry and to organize and develop tourism journalism and publishing, which has become a necessity.¹⁸³

- ***South Marmara Association of Touristic Hoteliers and Operators (GUMTOB)***: The aim of our Association is to carry out scientific and practical studies on tourism-related issues, problems and solutions, to contribute to these studies, to ensure the development of tourism and touristic facilities in accordance with tourism requirements, to ensure liaison and coordination among its members and with public institutions and organizations that are directly or

¹⁸⁰ <https://turyid.org/turyid-hakkinda/>

¹⁸¹ <http://www.taspakon.org.tr/Biz>

¹⁸² <http://tafed.org.tr/tafed-hakk%C4%B1m%C4%B1zda.html>

¹⁸³ <https://tuyed.org.tr/hakkimizda/>

indirectly related to tourism, and to represent our members within and outside the sector.¹⁸⁴

- **Foundation for Environmental Education in Türkiye (TURCEV):** TURCEV was established under the leadership of the Ministry of Tourism with the aim of launching the Blue Flag Program in our country. It started its activities with the approach that the Blue Flag, which has become widespread in countries with developed tourism in the Mediterranean basin, which includes healthy swimming water, equipped beaches, good environmental management and environmental awareness activities, is also important for tourism and the environment.¹⁸⁵
- **Restaurants and Tourism Association (TURES):** TURES is the most influential NGO operating in the food & beverage sector. TURES aims to promote, keep alive and carry this deep-rooted culture to the next generations by looking at the Turkish culinary world from the perspective of ahilik.¹⁸⁶
- **Türkiye Tourism Promotion and Development Agency (TGA):** Established on July 15, 2019, Türkiye Tourism Promotion and Development Agency (TGA) was established to make Türkiye a brand and a popular destination in the domestic and international tourism market through short, medium and long-term communication and marketing activities; to discover, develop and promote tangible and intangible natural, cultural, biological and human heritage assets; to increase Türkiye's tourism capacity, to increase the ratio of tourism investments to the national economy and to improve service quality. In line with the tourism strategies and policies determined by the Ministry of Culture and Tourism, the Agency will carry out all promotional, marketing and communication activities that will serve Türkiye's tourism goals, promote and market existing tourism opportunities worldwide, discover, develop, and establish potential tourism areas. The Agency operates under the Ministry of Culture and Tourism. With a team of distinguished Board of Directors with significant experience in domestic and international tourism, the Türkiye Tourism, Promotion and Development Agency will make every effort to contribute to and strengthen Türkiye's position in the international market, brand Türkiye as a globally sought-after destination, increase the number and profitability of tourists hosted by Türkiye, facilitate

¹⁸⁴ <https://www.gumtob.org.tr/>

¹⁸⁵ http://www.turcev.org.tr/V2/icerikDetay.aspx?icerik_id=11

¹⁸⁶ <https://tures.org.tr/hakkimizda>

potential investment projects in the tourism sector and contribute to the development of cities.¹⁸⁷

▪ **Small and Medium Scaled Industry Development and Support Directorate (KOSGEB):** On the other hand, KOSGEB is an important agency especially in the food & beverage sector. It is a related organization of the Ministry of Industry and Technology. KOSGEB aims to increase the share of SMEs and entrepreneurs in economic and social development by enabling them to achieve an innovative, technological and competitive structure through effective support and services.¹⁸⁸ KOSGEB is a public organization established to improve the place of enterprises in the economy. For this reason, it provides opportunities to many entrepreneurs under different headings.¹⁸⁹ For example, it provides grants and loans to entrepreneurs who want to open a restaurant.

• Programmes Supporting Tourism

Some of the programmes supporting tourism in Türkiye are given below.

- **Safe Tourism Certification Program:** One of the first of its kind, Safe Tourism Certification Program led by Culture and Tourism Ministry has been developed with the contributions of Ministry of Health, Ministry of Internal Affairs, Ministry of Foreign Affairs and in cooperation with all the stakeholders in the industry. Türkiye's Safe Tourism Certification Program has been made mandatory for accommodation facilities with 30 or more rooms and optional for accommodation facilities with less than 30 rooms and other areas as of 01.01.2021.¹⁹⁰ As of March 2023, the number of active certified facilities was 3658 and the number of active certified accommodation was 3514 under the Safe Tourism Certification Program.¹⁹¹
- **Türkiye Sustainable Tourism Industry Criteria (TR-I):** Another practice has been the identification of *Türkiye Sustainable Tourism Industry Criteria (TR-I)*. TR-I have been built to ensure sustainable growth of the Turkish tourism industry and to develop a common understanding about Turkish tourism with the participation of all tourism stakeholders. TR-I was developed to be

¹⁸⁷ <https://www.tga.gov.tr/hakkinda/>

¹⁸⁸ [https://webdosya.kosgeb.gov.tr/Content/Upload/Dosya/Mevzuat/2020/KOSGEB_Stratejik_Plan%C4%B1_\(2019-2023\).pdf](https://webdosya.kosgeb.gov.tr/Content/Upload/Dosya/Mevzuat/2020/KOSGEB_Stratejik_Plan%C4%B1_(2019-2023).pdf)

¹⁸⁹ <https://www.kosgeb.gov.tr/site/tr/baglanti/DesteklenenSektor>

¹⁹⁰ <https://www.tga.gov.tr/turkiyenin-guvenli-turizm-programi-hakkinda/>

¹⁹¹ <https://tga.gov.tr/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/Mart-2023-Aylik-Faaliyet-Raporu.pdf>

implemented by accommodation facilities and tour operators. In this respect, TR-I includes both criteria that comply with the social and cultural structure of Türkiye and globally recognized sustainable tourism criteria. TR-I was established under four main themes: sustainable management; socio-economic impacts; cultural impacts and environmental impacts. The scope of the TR-I includes the following issues.¹⁹²

- The criteria serve as basic guidelines for enterprises of all sizes that wish to become more sustainable and aim to ensure these enterprises contribute to the sustainable growth of tourism in Türkiye.
- The criteria help to increase awareness in the Turkish society, visitors, travelers, the tourism industry and tourism investors on the principles and practices of sustainable tourism.
- The criteria serve as a framework aimed at effective promotion and marketing for recognizing sustainable tourism providers.
- The criteria make a significant contribution in Türkiye to fully fill its obligations arising from the Paris Agreement on Climate Change and the European Green Deal within the scope of sustainable tourism and various environmental labels.
- Define a basic approach and framework aimed at the cooperation of government, civil society, NGOs, academia and private sector to further develop sustainable tourism policies, practices and requirements.
- Serve as basic guidelines for education and training bodies, such as universities and tourism schools.
- Provide leadership to the industry and investors in a manner as to encourage and promote sustainability practices.
- Help to provide greater access to various markets by increasing the competitiveness of Türkiye within the scope of the criteria in the growing global tourism market and sustainable tourism products and provide guidance for both travelers and travel agencies in choosing enterprises that adopt sustainable tourism practices.

¹⁹² <https://tga.gov.tr/surdurulebilir-turizm-programi-hakkinda/>

Within the scope of the Sustainable Tourism Program, as of March 2023, the number of facilities that received the 1st Stage Certificate was 415, the number of the 3rd Stage Certificate was 155 and the total number of certified and certified accommodation was 650.¹⁹³

2.2.3. Internal Dynamics of Hospitality Industry

2.2.3.1. Accommodation-SWOT/Resources and Capabilities

Tourism is one of the largest industries in the world getting currencies to global economy and creating new job opportunities as well as providing socio-cultural interactions. It is also one of the most important industries by means of creating employment and generating revenues.

Right after the Second World War people have started to travel a lot more than before. Life standards were getting better, disposable incomes of the household were becoming higher, spare times for long vacations were also possible. Mainly because of these reasons, especially citizens of developed countries have started to travel all around the world. Air transportation has also gained significance, right after the foundations of International Air Transport Association, (IATA) in 1945 and International Civil Aviation Organization, (ICAO) in 1947. Besides the hospitality sector, especially accommodation sector is the most important part of tourism. Türkiye is an attractive destination with its historical sites, cultural background, prosperous museums, unique ancient sites, Turkish Riviera and natural beauty. In the last two decades, Türkiye increased its tourist arrivals. SWOT analysis is done for Turkish accommodation sector below.

STRENGTHS

- High service quality,
- Availability of an excellent coastline, a wide range of natural attractions, unique historical and archaeological sites and a suitable climate during 12 months,
- Strong government support behind the industry,
- Sufficient number of beds in hotels (Bed capacity is high especially at seashores),
- Sufficient number of hotels,

¹⁹³ <https://tga.gov.tr/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/Mart-2023-Aylik-Faaliyet-Raporu.pdf>

- Various types of accommodation for all market segments,
- The variety of tourism products (sea tourism, winter tourism, culture tourism, yacht tourism, congress tourism, medical tourism and etc.),
- Unique sites (Cappadoccia, Pamukkale travertines),
- Various kinds of restaurants (International and Turkish cuisine),
- Sufficient number of gastro-tourism destinations such as Gaziantep, Hatay, Şanlıurfa, Afyon and etc.

WEAKNESSES

- The increase of uneducated seasonal employees,
- Low number of tourist guides,
- Lack of strategic perspective to hospitality management,
- All inclusive system,
- Lack of marketing skills,
- Lack of market researches,
- Lack of experience and social awareness in preserving historical and cultural sites when compared to European countries and cities,
- Not employing qualified tourism personnel,
- Lack of touristic tours in hotels.

OPPORTUNITIES

- Increase of tourist arrivals to Türkiye,
- Unutilised potential in niche tourism such as yachting,
- Tourism policy supporting niche markets in tourism,
- Price policy.

THREATS

- Increasing competition,
- Tax on alcohol,
- Bureaucratic obstacles,
- Economic crisis on EU countries,
- Recession on global economies,
- Lack of land for new hotel investments in downtown.

2.2.3.2. Food and Beverage-SWOT/Resources and Capabilities

Group of business strategies and alignments is required for organisations to achieve sets of goals in a specific time period. The business alignments and strategies are business “high-level plans for reaching specific business objectives”. Organisations investigate data elements relevant to business alignments and strategies by employing SWOT analysis in different business scenarios¹⁹⁴.

The SWOT analysis of the Turkish food and beverage industry is summarized below.

STRENGTHS

- Large population base, approx. 80 million: Young and growing; middle and upper middle classes are growing.
- Consumers are quality-conscious.
- Recent strong and steady GDP growth, as well as more dual income households, drives new demand for food service, especially fast-food, self-service food service and casual full-service as well as home delivery/takeaway.
- With many Turks travelling abroad compared to a decade ago, people are more aware of new cuisines and new ingredients.
- Well-developed increased adoption of western style consumption habits in urban centers, coupled with high levels of tourism, means that EU food and beverage products are popular.
- Due to the Customs Union and alignment process, Türkiye has similar food legislation to the EU: For EU exporters, meeting requirements in the EU means they are generally met to a significant extent in Türkiye. Turkish standards are arguably closer to EU standards than those of many other third countries.
- The Turkish market is close to Europe, which typically means fast shipping times (generally 3-5 days).

WEAKNESSES

- Products imported from the EU are likely to be more expensive than those that are locally produced, and consumers in Türkiye appreciate domestic products.

¹⁹⁴ Design of a SWOT Analysis Model and its Evaluation in Diverse Digital Business Ecosystem Contexts, *Procedia Computer Science*, 159, 1145-1154.

- Largely Muslim country, therefore prospects for imports of pork are very limited; although consumption of alcoholic beverages is viewed as more acceptable in Türkiye compared to other countries in the region, growth prospects are affected.
- Population remains geographically dispersed over a fairly large land area, despite increased urbanisation.
- Türkiye should not be seen as one market but rather multiple markets within one country. Different approaches may need to be taken but care is also needed to ensure that approaches are coherent.

OPPORTUNITIES

- Many of Türkiye's major urban centers, including Istanbul, Bursa and Izmir, are in close proximity to the EU with established logistical links.
- Some local casual full-service restaurants are updating and improving menus with new tastes every season. This is an opportunity for new ingredients to enter.
- Consumption of certain products (e.g. fresh beef and poultry; some fruit categories; processed products) is expected to grow.
- Premiumisation trend emerging within the younger and urban population.
- Current trends among the more affluent Turkish consumers such as healthiness and sustainability can be pursued by EU producers who are familiar with these trends from the EU market context.

THREATS

- Value of the Lira currency prone to fluctuate wildly and recent depreciation limits the ability of Turkish consumers to purchase food and beverages imported from the EU.
- Due to Muslim religion, strict requirements for meat and alcoholic beverages (ban on advertising).
- Türkiye's strong and expanding economic diplomacy and trade relations with countries in the Balkans and North/West of Africa, including FTA agreements

with a number of competitors such as Israel, Serbia and Egypt, may partly displace imports from the EU.^{195 196}

Food Service

The Turkish food service sector is large and highly fragmented; it can be divided into commercial and institutional food services. Commercial food service consists of full-service restaurants, self-service restaurants, cafes/bars, and street stalls/kiosks. Agents in Türkiye are sometimes importers, distributors, wholesalers, commission-based traders, or a combination. Local representatives will have experience in market development and the contact information of potential buyers, such as the food processors that are likely to use imported products. Finding a local agent is a safe approach for entry into the market, especially for medium and small enterprises keen to start exporting to Türkiye.¹⁹⁷

Business Environment

The business environment of Türkiye follows many parallels to that of other European countries with the need to dress formally and the need to be punctual. Türkiye has undergone many economic shifts in recent decades which has seen the growth of a new and varied service sector. Despite rapid economic growth in recent years, many regions particularly within the interior and eastern regions of the country have lower standards of infrastructure and economic development compared to the more prosperous regions surrounding Istanbul and Izmir. As the economic core of Türkiye is located along its western coast from Istanbul to Izmir it is likely that most business meetings will take place in this region of the country.¹⁹⁸

Key operational Considerations and Challenges: Summary

Key challenges to bear in mind when operating in the Turkish market are:

- English, French and German may be spoken by some Turks particularly in Istanbul and other tourist hotspots, despite this however make sure to bring an interpreter.

¹⁹⁵ The Food and Beverage Market Entry Handbook: TÜRKİYE, European Commission

¹⁹⁶ GAIN, Food Service: Hotel, Restaurant, Institutional in Türkiye, October-2022

¹⁹⁷ The Food and Beverage Market Entry Handbook: TÜRKİYE, European Commission

¹⁹⁸ The Food and Beverage Market Entry Handbook: TÜRKİYE, European Commission

- The economic and population core is centered around the city of Istanbul which is home to 19% of the population and accounts for 31% of Türkiye's GDP.
- It must be remembered that the country is majority Muslim, and this affects both export opportunities and requirements.
- The local currency has been prone to large shifts in value in recent years, which makes it a difficult currency to operate with in the long term.
- The standard of infrastructure and economic development is much higher in the west of the country compared to the east, which needs to be respected.
- Turkish consumers are still likely to visit traditional grocery outlets such as a food market of the bazaar, and this is a more prominent pattern within the interior and eastern regions of the country.¹⁹⁹

3. IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY

3.1. Impact of COVID-19 on Accommodation Industry

As cases of COVID-19 started to increase in Türkiye, precautions and safety measures were strengthened. Türkiye imposed travel bans on 68 countries. Türkiye decided to quarantine all passengers returning from all the countries with the travel ban for 14 days. All schools in Türkiye were suspended and distance education started via online channels and TV. Additionally, all gathering places such as restaurants, cafes, cinemas, theaters and gyms stopped their business activities²⁰⁰.

After Türkiye imposed travel bans on 68 countries, including some of its most important markets, many tourism reservations were cancelled and hotel occupancy rates dropped below 30% in some areas. With significant restrictions for non-essential travel globally, the half of flights to more than 68 countries, and reservation cancellations, the tourism industry was being severely hit with a low chance of a rebound, at least until the middle of the third quarter of 2020. Passenger travel was estimated to be severely affected both domestically and internationally. Consumption was hit by a massive blow

¹⁹⁹ The Food and Beverage Market Entry Handbook: TÜRKİYE, European Commission

²⁰⁰ www.kearney.com, 2020.

to tourism and restrictive domestic activity. A prediction about this at the beginning of COVID-19 can be seen in Figure 88²⁰¹.

Figure 88: Consumption in COVID-19

In the modern era, tourism activities and international mobility have reached a global scale. But in the third month following the first reported case, many countries restricted international mobility as a preventive measure against the virus. Some countries closed their borders entirely and others restricted border crossings. On the other hand, countries warned their citizens not to travel unless it is necessary. By taking these measures and defensive actions to stop the spreading of the virus, international mobility almost stopped in the world and tourism activities had been delayed. Tourism is one of the most sensitive sectors to crises such as wars, terrorist attacks, natural disasters and other kinds of unwanted phenomena. Normally, tourism demand and forecasts could be done by some objective methods, but coronavirus pandemic changed all the circumstances and affected all the conditions in the economic cycle²⁰².

²⁰¹ www.kearney.com, 2020.

²⁰² Günay et al, 2020.

Clearly, COVID-19 can be distinguished from other outbreaks through its characteristics, such as the rapid and wide spread of the virus, uncertainty of the infection process and treatment, and the fact that it directly and suddenly affected tourism due to mandatory travel restrictions. Tourism was the first affected industry and was expected to be the last to recover due to its postponable and hedonic nature. Tourism all over the World had nearly come to a halt due to the wider and more severe travel restrictions imposed compared with other outbreaks, and travel had been entirely restricted in many countries, except for mandatory cases. Many airline companies and tour operators ceased their activities, and many accommodation units were forced to discontinue their operations. These far-reaching constraints, which affected the entertainment and leisure sectors, had caused the global supply chain to suffer as well²⁰³.

Türkiye's main tourist generating market, Europe, is one of the regions most affected by the pandemic. Unfortunately, apart from a few city hotels, many tourism businesses, airlines, travel agencies, tourist restaurants, and transporters had been closed with many of them necessitating the layoff of employees. Türkiye reached the highest number of visitors in 2019 at approximately 52 million, which is the also the highest in the tourism history of Türkiye. In the same year, the tourism industry generated approximately 35 billion USD of tourism income (TUIK, 2020). Even before COVID-19 infiltrated Türkiye, cancellations especially in the Far East market and Anatolian tours started. In addition, independent travelers cancelled or postponed holiday plans since the pandemic occurred at a time when early bookings were made.

As previously mentioned, tourism requires human mobility. Thus, it was one of the first and most severely affected industries by COVID-19. At the same time, the tourism industry in Türkiye was expected to enter a long-term recovery process after those of other industries because tourism was not a compulsory consumption. The recovery was expected to progress according to the order of impact. After the domestic market, tourism was predicted to begin recovery starting from Asia-Pacific countries, where the effects of the epidemic were weakened²⁰⁴.

²⁰³ Göktepe and Çetin, 2020.

²⁰⁴ OECD 2020-12-16.

Türkiye Ministry of Culture and Tourism initiated the Safe Tourism Certification Programme in May 2020, with contributions from the Ministries of Health, Transport and Infrastructure, Interior and Foreign Affairs, and in co-operation with key stakeholders. It sets out to visitors the measures for undertaking tourism activities safely, and provides criteria for businesses to operate safely. Measures and criteria aim to ensure passenger and employee health, as well as the safety of transport vehicles and other tourism facilities. Hospitality industry was expected to be affected as explained below²⁰⁵.

- Hotels. Globally, hotels reported having extremely low occupancy rates, or experienced closures on a massive scale. Big hotel chains saw their stock price plunge as a result. In Europe it was estimated that 76% of hotels were closed. According to STR, in the first week of May many countries had an average occupancy rate lower than 30%.
- Restaurants. Food and catering service providers were required in many countries to increase social spacing in eating establishments, limit their activity to delivery only in some instances, or entirely shut down activities. Even as restrictions were being lifted, food-related activities were still limited. In the United States, the National Restaurant Association estimated that the industry's sales would decline by USD 225 billion during the three months from March, prompting the loss of between five and seven million jobs³⁰. In France, lock down measures introduced in March resulted in the closing of 75 000 restaurants, 3 000 clubs, and 40 000 cafes, affecting 1 million employees, who were temporarily laid off and placed on technical unemployment.

The following measures were taken in Türkiye to support tourism businesses during COVID-19 crisis²⁰⁶:

- Bank loans were provided for reimbursement of advance payments for early bookings.
- Social Security payments were postponed for 6 months.
- Ministry-certified travel agencies were allowed to work online without opening their workplaces, until the end of April.

²⁰⁵ OECD 2020-12-16.

²⁰⁶ <https://www.oecd.org>, 2020.

- The debts of tourism facilities located on public lands were delayed for 6 months.
- The activities of day-trip excursion boats, certified by the Ministry of Culture and Tourism, were stopped.
- The schedule to submit the relevant documents to obtain a Certificate from the Ministry of Culture and Tourism to open service and tourism establishments was frozen for tourism investments located on public lands with a due date of 1 April 2020.
- Swift bank loans offered for small scale tourism agencies without need of repayment for 6 months.
- The accommodation tax in hotels and tourism facilities was waived until November 2020.

Key policy priorities include²⁰⁷:

- Restoring traveller confidence
- Supporting tourism businesses to adapt and survive
- Promoting domestic tourism and supporting safe return of international tourism
- Providing clear information to travellers and businesses, and limiting uncertainty (to the extent possible)
- Evolving response measures to maintain capacity in the sector and address gaps in supports
- Strengthening co-operation within and between countries
- Building more resilient, sustainable tourism

While flexible policy solutions are needed to enable the tourism economy to live alongside the virus in the short to medium term, it is important to look beyond this and take steps to learn from the crisis, which has revealed gaps in government and industry preparedness and response capacity. Co-ordinated action across governments at all levels and the private sector is essential. The crisis is an opportunity to rethink tourism for the future. Tourism is at a crossroads and the measures put in place today will shape the tourism of tomorrow. Governments need to consider the longer-term implications of the crisis, while capitalising on digitalisation, supporting the low carbon

²⁰⁷ <https://www.oecd.org/coronavirus/policy-responses/rebuilding-tourism-for-the-future-covid-19-policy-responses-and-recovery-bced9859/>.

transition, and promoting the structural transformation needed to build a stronger, more sustainable and resilient tourism economy.

3.2. Impact of COVID-19 on Food and Beverage Industry

Food and beverage businesses constitute the most important elements of an important socio-economic sector that contributes greatly to the global economy. However, these sectors are vulnerable to natural hazards such as the COVID-19 pandemic and the resulting economic downturns. COVID-19 caused an unprecedented loss of jobs and income globally, resulting in millions of jobs and billions of dollars in potential revenue loss.²⁰⁸

During the COVID-19 pandemic, radical changes and rules were created in the service industry. With the implementation of new inspections and sanctions in this area, the food and beverage and the tourism industry were reshaped along with the pandemic.²⁰⁹ COVID-19 economically affected the food and beverage industry globally. Accordingly, various measures had been taken for food and beverage businesses all over the world. In America; although it varied by state region and community, nearly every state and local government implemented many resolutions to promote physical distancing by banning restaurants from serving dinner. According to the National Restaurant Association's survey of 6,500 restaurant owners in mid-April, about 60% of US restaurants had to close due to financial distress caused by the loss of diners.²¹⁰

It can be said that the COVID-19 pandemic, which has affected the whole world, basically affected food and beverage industry in three different ways. The first was the change in social life with the pandemic, and accordingly the change in customer expectations and behaviors, the second was the measures taken by both the states and professional organizations in this process, and the third was the problems experienced in the supply processes.

Data on eating out for 2020 indicated that COVID-19 negatively affected the restaurant industry in Türkiye as well as in the rest of the world. In Türkiye, the number of food

²⁰⁸ COVID-19 Cripples Global Restaurant and Hospitality Industry, *Journal of Current Issues in Tourism*, 24(11), 1487-1490.

²⁰⁹ Duru Ögün, Ş. (2021). COVID-19 salgınının yiyecek içecek işletmeleri üzerine etkisi: Ankara'da bulunan yiyecek içecek işletmeleri üzerine nitel bir araştırma (Master's thesis, Başkent Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü).

²¹⁰ COVID-19 and Restaurant Demand: Early Effects of Pandemic and Stay-at-Home Orders, *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 32(12), 3809-3834.

and beverage transactions and transaction amounts decreased by more than 25% between January and March 2020.²¹¹

Number of food and beverage transactions and transaction amounts in Türkiye decreased more than 25% between January - March 2020

Interbank Card Center provides sector-based transaction amount and transaction number data in credit and debit card breakdowns. The data shown in the chart includes the sum of transactions made with debit and credit cards.

The number of visits to the Yemeksepeti.com website in April decreased by 33% compared to the previous month.

The data includes the visits of Yemeksepeti.com from desktop and mobile devices. Since the banabi platform, which provides online grocery shopping service, can also be used through the website Yemeksepeti.com, it is estimated that the visits for food order may be lower than the numbers presented in the chart.

With the circular issued by the Ministry of Interior, restaurants could not host guests for a long time and operated only with takeaway service models. According to the data of the Interbank Card Center, while the amount of transactions in the food sector was 4.5 billion TL in January 2020, it was observed that expenditures decreased to 3.2 billion TL in March 2020. Looking at the number of visitors to the online food ordering site Yemeksepeti.com, which has been operating in Türkiye since 2001, in order to examine the demand for takeaway service during the period when the restaurants were closed, a 40% decrease is observed in the website traffic in the two-month period. TOBB President Rifat Hisarcıklıoğlu's statements that restaurant turnover decreased

²¹¹ Deloitte, COVID-19 Etkisinde Restoran Sektörünün Bugünü ve Geleceği, 2020, <https://www2.deloitte.com/content/dam/Deloitte/tr/Documents/consumer-business/COVID-19-etkisinde-restoran-sektorunun-bugunu-ve-gelecegi.pdf>

by 75% compared to the pre-epidemic supported the negative effects of COVID-19 on the restaurant industry.²¹²

Restrictions in Türkiye started on March 12 and were implemented gradually and periodically. Among these restrictions food and beverage businesses were sometimes only able to offer takeaway service and sometimes they were completely closed. While these response efforts minimized personal interaction and mitigated the spread of the virus, they threatened the survival of the restaurant industry. According to the data compiled from the statistics prepared by the Union of Chambers and Commodity Exchanges of Türkiye, 1,733 businesses operating in the field of "restaurants and mobile food service" stopped their activities in 2020. Of these enterprises, 1,170 were individuals, 495 were limited liability companies and 68 were joint stock companies. The global spread of COVID-19 with an ever-increasing momentum threatened the food supply chain. It also raised the concerns of consumers about food safety. In situations such as the COVID-19 pandemic or a natural disaster, food consumers changed their habits.²¹³ Due to the precautions and health concerns, many food and beverage businesses suspended their activities, and as a result of this situation, consumers turned to eating at home.

Food and beverage businesses, considering that it was a socializing environment for consumers in the pandemic process, it was seen that it had been particularly affected by the restrictions such as "stay at home" propaganda and "social distance" applied by governments.²¹⁴ Restricting the movement of employees in the food and beverage sector; while creating employment and income loss, poverty rates in the world gained momentum. Curfews and loss of income severely restricted access to the sector.²¹⁵ As a result of the negative effects of the process, some precautions were taken in Türkiye as well. The "Loss of Turnover" support program announced in the Official Gazette on February 17, 2021.²¹⁶

²¹² Deloitte, COVID-19 Etkisinde Restoran Sektörünün Bugünü ve Geleceği, 2020, <https://www2.deloitte.com/content/dam/Deloitte/tr/Documents/consumer-business/COVID-19-etkisinde-restoran-sektorunun-bugunu-ve-gelecegi.pdf>

²¹³ The Impact of COVID-19 Pandemic on Occupational Stress in Restaurant Work: A Qualitative Study, *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(19), 10378.

²¹⁴ Tüketicilerin COVID-19 Salgını Sürecinde Yiyecek-İçecek İşletmelerinden Bekledikleri Hizmetin Niteliğine İlişkin Bir Araştırma, *Journal of Tourism and Gastronomy Studies*, 8(4), 3362-3377.

²¹⁵ Pandemic&Food Security, *Journal of Agriculture, Food Systems& Community Development*, 9(3), 17-21.

²¹⁶ Resmi Gazete, 2020.

With the start of the pandemic, QR, web-based or disposable menu cards were offered. Contact-borne contamination of COVID-19 had led to the rapid introduction of such applications. Businesses tried to increase the variety by adding packaged foods, fast food products, healthy meals, long-lasting meals and group menus in their menus. The reasons for this can be listed as follows²¹⁷:

- 1- As a result of the decrease in demand, especially at the beginning of the pandemic, longer-lasting foods were added instead of perishable foods.
- 2- Foods suitable for takeaway, which became very important for the industry since the beginning of the pandemic were added, especially fast food products such as hamburgers and sandwiches.
- 3- Products that do not cause problems in packaging and takeaway were included in the menu.
- 4- With the health concern created by the pandemic, it was observed that consumers' preferences shifted to healthier products, and as a result, nutritious foods such as salads were added to the menu.
- 5- Due to the fact that all family members were in their homes especially during the closure periods, there was a large demand for the menus, especially for family members. Food and beverage businesses that were aware of this situation created new group menus.
- 6- While the takeaway caused many businesses to increase the variety of food on the menu in different ways, it also caused them to reduce the variety for some. The reason for this was that some foods did not comply with the package service, the demand for some foods, especially in the early stages of the pandemic, and the supply shortage in the products supplied from abroad.
- 7- The health crisis caused by COVID-19 brought the economic crisis with it. Food and beverage industry is also one of the most adversely affected sector due to various restrictions and closures. Accordingly, businesses have aimed to reduce their economic losses by making some changes in their menus. The most applied is the price hikes of the food and beverages on the menu. Consumers did not remain unresponsive to the aforementioned hikes. Contrary to the fact that the increase in the expenses of the enterprises reflects this on

²¹⁷ Bilgin, Y. K. & Tekeli, N. H. (2022). COVID-19'un Yiyecek İçecek İşletmelerine Olan Etkisi, *Doğuş Üniversitesi Dergisi*, 23, 281-301.

their menus, the businesses that think that increasing the sales will help in the solution of the situation in question have reduced the contents of their menus or they have chosen to organize campaigns such as buy one get one free.

9- The effects of COVID-19 had not only been on businesses but also on consumers. The most important effect on consumers was the transition from cash to credit card and the use of contactless feature of credit cards. One of the most important changes in customers' preferences had been sensitivity to cleanliness/distance. Compared to the pre-pandemic period, customers paid attention to the cleanliness of the business and the use of masks by the personnel, looking for a certain distance between other tables.

Customers' desire to consume healthy and safe food had brought into the fore the cleanliness and hygiene-seeking whereas the ambition to socialize and pleasure-seeking have remained more in the background. The changes in customers' motivations had also given rise to the differentiation in their behavior. Moreover, previous studies²¹⁸ also emphasized that consumers' motivations and behaviors were transformed.

²¹⁸ Deloitte, 2020; Jain, 2020; Seo & Jang, 2013; Tse et al., 2006.

4. HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY SEGMENTATION

4.1. Segmentation of Accommodation

4.1.1. Classification and Categorization of Hotels

The hotel industry is an incredibly diverse one. From small, family-run B&Bs to large, all-inclusive big-brand resorts, there are many different types of hotels located all around the world.

The number of different types of hotels is almost endless. From chain hotels to boutique hotels, motels to extended-stay, and economy to luxury, there are lots of different classifications of hotels and many ways to categorize them.

To help make sense of this hugely varied industry it's helpful to break the different hotel types into a few key classifications and categories that can be better understood. Different types of hotels can most commonly be classified in the following ways²¹⁹:

Star Rating

Possibly the most common classification of a hotel is its star rating. There's no one global standard or governing body, but the most well-known organizations are Quality Tourism Australia, American Automobile Association (AAA), Hotelstars Union (Europe), and AA Hotel and Hospitality Services (UK). Hotel ratings go from one-star at the most basic end to five-star hotels at the more luxury end of the scale.

Levels of Services

Although star ratings can help with marketing, hotels don't actually have to have one. They can also be classified and marketed by the level of service they provide. This ranges from basic, budget hotels to mid-range, more comfortable stays and luxury high-end accommodation.

²¹⁹ "From motels to luxury: what types of hotels are there?", <https://lesroches.edu/blog/types-hotel/>.

Ownership

Another way to classify types of hotels is by ownership or types of hotel management. The three main types are:

Proprietary ownership: where the hotel, of any size, is independently owned.

Management contract whereby other companies manage the hotel, usually on a long-term basis.

Franchises or hotel chains that are run by 'big name' hotel brands.

Target Market

Different types of hotels can also be grouped by their target market. These are hotels targeted to specific types of guests who need or want a hotel for a particular purpose. This might be for business, a longer-term residential stay, a casino or convenient for an airport.

Size

Hotels can also be classified by size. This isn't related to service quality or available facilities (although its size may affect what a hotel can offer) but is purely the number of rooms available. Size classifications can vary by region so you might see different definitions, but at a basic level:

- small hotels have up to 25 guest rooms,
- medium hotels have between 26 and 300 guest rooms,
- large hotels have 300-plus guest rooms.

Length of Stay

Another classification of hotels is the length of stay. Although not a direct commentary on the quality of service, it can have an impact. For example, short-stay hotels, like commercial or business traveler hotels, are likely to offer fewer or different services compared with long-stay, apartment-style accommodations.

Guest Demographic

Hotel businesses want to appeal to as broad a range of guests as possible; but understanding and catering to a key target demographic creates better quality, tailored services. Guests might be classed as tourists, business travelers, families, digital nomads, luxury travelers, or conference delegates.

People are highly varied individuals and so different types of accommodations are needed to meet the huge range of needs and preferences of different guests.

For example, airport hotels are designed for those flying out of or into the airport, particularly at anti-social times, whereas all-inclusive, adult-only resorts are designed for holidaymakers who want a relaxing, child-free vacation in one specific place.

Classification of Hotels

Star Rating System

As the most common classification of hotels, the star rating system was designed to measure hotel quality. Given it's the most commonly referred to classification, it's a good idea to familiarize yourself with what different hotel ratings mean so you know what you can expect²²⁰.

One-star Rating

A one-star rating doesn't mean a hotel is of poor quality, it's simply a reflection that it's a very basic, bare necessities-style accommodation. It's usually a small independent hotel offering a bed and a bathroom (sometimes shared bathroom facilities) with no additional amenities on site.

Two-star Rating

Two-star accommodation is generally similarly basic to one-star but is usually a slightly bigger hotel that's part of a larger franchise or chain. It's low budget but tends to offer some additional food and beverage services.

²²⁰ "From motels to luxury: what types of hotels are there?", <https://lesroches.edu/blog/types-hotel/>.

Three-star Rating

As a mid-range option, three-star hotels are slightly more comfortable and stylish than lower-rated hotels and tend to be part of larger hotel chains, such as Hilton or Marriott. Consumers can find different room types, benefit from room service and have access to on-site facilities like restaurants, business services, a pool, and a fitness center.

Four-star Rating

A four-star hotel, sometimes called a superior hotel, is normally a large, premium hotel. Consumers can find different room types and suite options, and a quality offering of in-house facilities such as fine dining, 24-hour room service, multiple pools, spa centers, secure parking, and limo services.

Five-star Rating

A five-star rating is the epitome of luxury. To be classed as a top-level hotel, the accommodation usually has to be spectacularly stylish and offer the highest quality service. Five-star hotels typically offer large, elegant rooms, high-spec entertainment systems, gourmet restaurants, state-of-the-art fitness, and spa centers, childcare services, luxury bedding, and bath products, and a 24-hour personal butler or concierge.

Categorization of Hotels

Similarly to classifications, hotels can be categorized in a variety of different ways. The main categories of hotels are presented below.

Hotel Types by Size

The size of a hotel doesn't refer to the size of the building as such, but the number of rooms or bed capacity it carries. There are varying definitions of hotel size, for example, "small" hotels can be anything from 20 to 200 rooms, but a more granular categorization of size is:

- hotels with less than 200 rooms are very small,
- hotels with up to 200 rooms are small,
- hotels with 200-399 rooms are medium,
- hotels with 400-700 rooms are large,

- hotels with more than 700 rooms are mega.

Hotel Types by Location

Hotels can be categorized by their location, by reference to their proximity to a city:

- Airport hotels are found next to an airport and used for guests in transit,
- City center hotels are typically located in commercial areas, right in the hub of the city,
- Motels – short for motor hotels – are found on highways and used by passing travelers,
- Suburb hotels are located near cities and tend to be more budget-friendly,
- Resorts are typically found in popular vacation spots around islands, beaches, and mountains.

Hotel Types by Target Market

The target market of a hotel can help to categorize what type of hotel it is, for example:

- Commercial or business hotels target business travelers,
- B&Bs cater to short-stay guests in transit or on a holiday tour,
- Casino hotels are aimed at guests who enjoy gambling,
- Self-catering hotels are for longer-stay guests who prefer to cook themselves and typically include families,
- Suite hotels target professionals by offering separate living and sleeping spaces so that they can conduct business and meetings in the hotel.

Hotel Types by Ownership

Hotels can also be categorized by their ownership, for example, B&Bs or self-catering hotels tend to be small family-owned businesses with their own way of running things. Whereas a corporate-owned chain of hotels will have strict policies and procedures in place that create a consistent service and experience across all its hotels.

Hotel Types by Star Rating

As already mentioned, hotels can also be categorized by their star rating from a basic one-star to luxury five-star accommodation.

4.1.2. Segmentation of Consumers

Hotels can segment their guests into groups/segments based on different parameters such as tastes and preferences, behavior, booking patterns, travel purpose, habits, etc.

Based on guest behavior, travel history and habits, and price sensitivity, hotels segmentalize guests to better organize and target their services and campaigns. Guests are usually segmented into the following categories²²¹:

Transients

These guests travel without any group or organization association, at non-negotiated rates. They usually book for shorter durations or stays, and their purpose of travel could be either leisure or business. Their booking style may be a booking in advance, a walk-in, or same-day online reservations.

Group

This is one of the biggest market segments of hotels including a group of people that are visiting the hotel together. Their rooms are typically reserved at discounted rates. These groups either book through a request for proposals (RFPs), through travel agents, or directly with the hotel.

Corporate travelers

This group includes all the travelers who have been sent through organizations or corporations on business to the city/state, for hotel accommodation. Hotels generally create subscription models and offer corporate discounts and other incentives to such travelers.

²²¹ "Hotel Market Segmentation - Importance, Types & Examples", <https://botshot.ai/resources/blog/hotel-market-segmentation>.

Wholesale

This segment consists of bulk bookings made through trip operators or booking agencies. These bookings are generally made at cheaper rates for tourists, tours, symphonies, travelling musicals, bands, and production crews.

SMERF

This is an umbrella term for a group market segment that includes Social, Military, Educational, Religious, and Fraternal travel groups.

Further guest segmentation can be done by categorizing guests based on geography, demography, psychographic traits, and behavioral patterns.

4.2. Segmentation of Food and Beverage

The food and beverage industry can be segmented in many different ways. Businesses can determine a segmentation strategy by considering; their products, geographic location or consumers (primary data).

- **Consumer profiles**

Certain aspects of the Turkish population that are worth bearing in mind when considering Turkish consumers. Most notably ²²²:

Ethnicity and Religion

While 99% of Türkiye's population identifies as Islamic, there are differences in the country concerning the levels of adherence to the religion in its strictest terms. The west of Türkiye is generally more liberal and relaxed about some of the taboo aspects of Islam such as alcohol consumption which is viewed as a much bigger taboo in the east of the country. Many larger urban centers are also more liberal on some aspects of Islamic teachings but within the rural areas of Türkiye, this is less likely to be the case.

²²² The Food and Beverage Market Entry Handbook: TÜRKİYE, European Commission.

Urban and Rural Divide

Around 75% of Türkiye's population lives in urban centers with 18% of the population living in Istanbul alone. The urban versus rural division becomes more apparent within the interior and eastern regions of the country, where the population is sparser with provinces likely to have only one major city of note within their borders. This division further impacts access to the internet, infrastructure and other utilities, making it particularly difficult to market EU products to citizens living in the rural interior of Türkiye. This further explains why the important market snapshot markets for EU products are all located in the west of Türkiye or along the Mediterranean coast, Ankara being the only exception.

Youth Population

Demographically, Türkiye is home to Europe's youngest population, which presents great opportunities for the country to be a key future market for EU food and beverages. Developing brand loyalty with the younger segments of the population, including the segment aged between 15-24 years old that represents 15.6% of the population, is key towards establishing a long-term business presence in Türkiye. This segment of the population is far more likely to be using the internet and actively engaging with social media platforms, which makes this a key channel for product marketing to this segment of the population.

Against the considerations set out above, notable overarching consumer types in Türkiye are set out below. It is important to note that, while these overarching types have relevance across the country to some extent, the various aforementioned nuances must be taken into account given that in such a diverse country, the relevance of universal consumer types is limited:

Independent and Proud Consumers

Turkish consumers are generally very proud of their country and any brand which acts against the interest of the state will struggle to appeal to consumers in Türkiye. Several brands have previously been banned or *de-facto* blacklisted for speaking in a non-favourable manner about Türkiye. Turkish consumers appreciate their domestic produce, such as raki, fruits and vegetables, which makes it additionally difficult for EU producers to compete in these product categories. It is important that any packaging

sent to Türkiye does not include anything which can be perceived as mocking the state or stating a historical standpoint counteractive to standard Turkish perspectives.

Appreciation for Fresh Foods

Türkiye is home to some of the most fertile soils in the world coupled with being within the proximity of the Mediterranean Sea, hence there is a deep appreciation for fresh produce in the country as is common in other Mediterranean countries such as Greece and Italy. Processed foods are less popular in Türkiye than in the EU market, even though consumption overall is growing. Turkish consumers will likely be drawn to products that can display their freshness either through a unique label of their origin or through incorporating additional added properties such as sugar-free variants.

Strivers

The depreciation of the Lira has resulted in many Turkish consumers having to seek out additional ways to make their money stretch. This is notable in the rise of bulk buying in Türkiye which has grown to become a common practice in the country. The fall in the value of the Lira acts as a barrier for consumers to purchase imported food and beverages as these products have become more expensive. A return in the strength of the Lira to the Euro would act as an incentive for consumers to purchase EU food and beverages, however, this is dependent on external factors.

5. HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY INSIGHTS

5.1. Accommodation

5.1.1. Global Trends of Industry

Keeping up-to-date with the latest accommodation trends is vital for those working in the industry for several different reasons, with the most important being the ability to meet customer expectations.

As new trends emerge and new technology, processes, and procedures become commonplace, hotel guests start to anticipate and expect these things, and they can find it jarring if those expectations are not met. At the same time, hotels that do not

keep pace with emerging trends can easily look out of touch or like they have been left behind.

- **CittaSlow (Slow Cities)**

Due to the impact of globalization, cities have transformed into living spaces that prioritize speed and consumption over self-sufficiency and sustainability. The fast-paced lifestyle has caused people to rush through activities such as eating, shopping, and transportation, leading to various health issues like depression, heart disease, and cancer. This lifestyle has also made cities unsustainable, as they consume resources from all over the world and destroy nature and communities. However, this consumption-based lifestyle has not brought happiness or satisfaction to people, leading to the emergence of the Cittaslow movement, which advocates for a slower pace of life. The goal of the Cittaslow movement is to promote self-sufficient, sustainable, and connected cities that prioritize communication, socialization, tradition, and technology while also protecting the environment and using renewable energy. These cities will provide a realistic alternative to the fast-paced, consumption-based lifestyle of modern cities.²²³

Cittaslow is an organization that was founded in Italy in 1999 and is inspired by the slow food movement. Among Cittaslow's goals is to improve the quality of life in towns by slowing down the general pace of life, especially in the use of space and the flow of life and traffic. The first Slow City in the world was Ludlow, England in 2003. The movement expanded beyond Italy, and national Slow City networks were formed in Germany, Norway, and the UK in 2006. In October 2020, İzmir, the 3rd largest city in Türkiye, became the world's first Cittaslow Metropolis. Each Cittaslow town has 50 targets and principles that it commits to working towards to improve the quality of life in the city. The main objectives of the movement are as follows:

- ✓ To improve the quality of life for everyone living in urban environments.
- ✓ To enhance the quality of life in cities.
- ✓ To resist the homogenization and globalization of cities worldwide.

²²³ <https://cittaslowturkiye.org/tr/uye-kentler/>

- ✓ To protect the environment.
- ✓ To promote cultural diversity and uniqueness in individual cities.
- ✓ To inspire a healthier lifestyle.

Sustainable tourism is tourism that takes into full account its current and future economic, social, and environmental impacts, addressing the needs of visitors, the industry, the environment, and host communities.^{224,225} Eco-tourism, eco-labeling, Cittaslow, Slow Food, and similar practices are among the factors that influence the demand for sustainable tourism.²²⁶ Therefore, slow cities can be considered one of the best examples of sustainable tourism.²²⁷ Regions that comply with the definition of slow cities attract both local and foreign tourists with their cultural texture. Preserving the natural and original texture also contributes to the mobility of tourism.

There are 21 members of Cittaslow in Türkiye, including Ahlat, Akyaka, Arapgir, Eğirdir, Foça, Gerze, Gökçeada, Göynük, Gündül, Halfeti, İznik, Köyceğiz, Mudurnu, Persembeye, Seferihisar, Savsat, Taraklı, Uzundere, Vize, Yalvaç, Yenipazar. Türkiye ranks fourth in the number of slow city members in the Cittaslow organization.

The slow city movement accelerates tourism as it attracts the attention of domestic and foreign tourists. Cittaslow formation supports the preservation of local tastes, local architecture and cultural values. This makes it a good option for tourists looking for alternative tourism instead of mass tourism.²²⁸

- **Slow Food**

The Slow Food Movement was initiated in 1986 in the city of Cuneo in the Langhe region of Italy. It was the first of the slow movements that were started. The Slow Food movement aims to ensure the sustainability of local cuisines, the continuity of cultures without distortion, and the preservation of food and agricultural biodiversity.²²⁹ Slow Food is an international movement aimed at embracing a sustainable gastronomic

²²⁴ <https://www.tursab.org.tr/assets/pdf/tursab-akademi/e-egitim/konu-ozetleri/unite-08.pdf>

²²⁵ World Tourism Organization, 2019

²²⁶ Çavuş Ş., Kaya B., Demirtaş B., (2019), Sürdürülebilir Turizm Açısından Slow Food Hareketine Bakış Ve Türkiye Uygulamaları, International Black Sea Coastline Countries Symposium, Batumi

²²⁷ Ünal, Ç. (2016), Turizm coğrafyasında yeni kavramlar "Yavaş Şehirler ve Yavaş Turizm". *Doğu Coğrafya Dergisi*, 36, 13-28.

²²⁸ Çıtak, Ş. Ö., & Özmen, Ş. Y. (2016). Sakin Şehirler Hızlı Turistler. *İnsan ve Toplum Bilimleri Araştırmaları Dergisi*, Cilt 5, Sayı 8, 2692-2706.

²²⁹ Çavuş Ş., Kaya B., Demirtaş B., (2019), Sürdürülebilir Turizm Açısından Slow Food Hareketine Bakış ve Türkiye Uygulamaları, International Black Sea Coastline Countries Symposium, Batumi

common culture. It promotes conscious consumption by consumers. The main objective of this movement is to prepare food with fresh and local ingredients without deviating from the original recipe and to enjoy the taste of the food. The use of local seeds, preservation of authenticity, and support for the development of local communities is promoted by this movement, which adopts the principle of "good, clean, and fair" food.²³⁰

The first village to join the Slow Food movement in Türkiye is **Germiyan village**, which is a Turkmen Village, located in Izmir Cesme. The people of the village, who bake their bread with pure natural sourdough, bring their vegetables from their own fields and make their meals with these vegetables. In the village, unseasonable early products are not used. Going to Germiyan Village, you can find sourdough breads produced by the Slow Food movement, kopanisti cheese, date olives, confectioner's delight, bazinara and rice ravioli.²³¹

There are 32 Convivia and communities in Türkiye: Adana for heritage food, Ankara, Antakya – Common Cuisine of Cultures, Balkon Bahçeleri, Kapadokya Sustainable Gastronomy and Tourism Alliance, Conservation Of Mut's Biodiversity and Ecology, Earth Market Foça, Earth Market Tarsus, Göbeklitepe, Halfeti, Heritage vines of TürkiyeT, Ibradi sustainable and ecological conservation, Ida, Izmir Bardacik, Karaburun Food, Biodiversity and Cultural Heritage, Kars, Mahal, Mugla – Food & Travel Sustainability, Ölmez Ağaç, Edremit Körfezi, Ortaca, from eldest to youngest, Preservation of food heritage of Tarsus, Preserving Food Biodiversity and the Ecosystem of Gökova, Preserving the culture of local food of Kastamonu, Preserving the local food heritage of Savastepe, Sile, Palamut, Slow Fish Mersin save the Mediterranean, Supporting small producers of Narlıdere, Sustainable Food Bursa, Teos, The Sustainability of Nigde's Agricultural Diversity, Trakya, Yagmur Boregi, Yavas Gari Bodrum, Youth Adana, Halet Çambel Urban Garden.²³²

²³⁰ <https://fabricatoday.org/turkiye-de-slow-food>

²³¹ <https://www.turizmgunlugu.com/2020/08/15/yavas-yemek-hareketi-slow-food/>

²³² <https://www.Slow-Food.com/nazioni-condotte/Türkiye/>

There are four presidia in our country: Divle Cave-Aged Cheese, Extra Virgin Olive Oil from Aegean Indigenous Landscapes and Siyez Wheat Bulgur.²³³ There are 79 types of products registered to Noah's Barn (Ark of Taste) in Türkiye.²³⁴

The Slow Food movement focuses on the promotion, preservation, and appreciation of local food, addressing issues such as surface dimensions. Through numerous internationally organized events and educational programs, it showcases regional cuisines and favorites. In this context, Slow Food attracts attention to regional kitchens and diversity, reflecting traditional culture and drawing interest to many lesser-known destinations in terms of gastronomic tourism. Promoting local cuisines, facilitated by the presence of local gastronomy enthusiasts, will contribute to the success of gastronomic tourism. Additionally, organized education, fairs, and events possess positive attractiveness features for tourism in destinations.²³⁵

Understanding the Factors Driving the Main Accommodation Trends

Trends can be defined as generalized changes in behavior or the emergence and growth of new methods, approaches, or ways of doing things. Within the accommodation industry, there are many different trends to be aware of, and these hotel trends are driven by several key factors, including the following²³⁶:

Emerging Technology

Technology is a key driver of trends in most industries, and hotel trends are influenced by technology in this way too. For instance, voice control and voice search are helping to revolutionize the customer experience, while artificial intelligence is helping to improve personalization and the quality of customer support.

Lifestyle Changes

Another major factor influencing hotel trends is the broad lifestyle changes that have been seen across the world. In general, people are more aware of climate change and

²³³ <https://www.fondazioneSlow Food.com/en/nazioni-presidi/Türkiye-en/>

²³⁴ <https://www.fondazioneSlow Food.com/en/nazioni-arca/Türkiye-en/>

²³⁵ Çavuş Ş., Kaya B., Demirtaş B., (2019), Sürdürülebilir Turizm Açısından Slow Food Hareketine Bakış ve Türkiye Uygulamaları, International Black Sea Coastline Countries Symposium, Batumi

²³⁶ "Hotel Trends: Discover The Latest Hotel Industry Trends for 2024!", <https://www.revfine.com/hotel-trends/>.

the role that human behavior has, which has led to greater demand for eco-friendly travel, sustainable food, and local rather than international tourism.

Coronavirus

The effects of the COVID-19 pandemic can still be felt worldwide. Associated restrictions are primarily in health, safety, and hygiene. On top of this, the pandemic accelerated the adoption of contactless payment methods, including mobile wallets.

Below, there is latest trends of accommodation industry²³⁷:

Sustainability

Sustainability has become a more popular hotel management trend in recent years, as today's environmentally conscious customers demand choices that align with their ethics more and more. At the minimum, modern consumers often require that their hotels be as energy-efficient as possible.

However, consumers are increasingly searching for hotels where eco-friendly planning is a core feature. From ecologically friendly construction materials to passive heating or cooling and renewable energy sources, the eco-hotel trend looks set to be with us for a long time. Fortunately, this trend is good for hotels, too — eco-friendly initiatives often mean lower running costs in the long term.

Renewable Energy

Today's travelers and diners are increasingly interested in ensuring their leisure doesn't come with a heavy environmental price tag. At the same time, businesses in the hospitality sector are seeing the benefits of reducing energy consumption and switching to renewables where possible.

Along with the reduction of waste, cutting down on energy consumption and embracing green energy can help hospitality businesses to become more efficient and attract environmentally conscious consumers. Hotels can utilize five renewable energy sources: solar, wind, combined heating and power, geothermal, and biofuels. Funding

²³⁷ "Hospitality Trends: The Latest Trends in The Hospitality Industry for 2024", <https://www.revfine.com/hospitality-trends/>.

and space constraints pose challenges, but the hospitality industry acknowledges the environmental responsibility and cost-saving potential amid energy market fluctuations.

Staff & Labor Shortages

Another of the major hotel trends that managers and recruiters need to be aware of in the years to come relates to staff and labor shortages. In particular, as technology continues to evolve and as customer expectations continue to grow, there is likely to be a limited supply of labor with the necessary skills to navigate this new reality.

For hoteliers, there are two main options here. The first is to invest in training and coaching so existing staff can up-skill to the required level. The alternative is to try to make their hotel more appealing for workers to attract talent from other hotels or those with the right skills from outside of the accommodation industry.

Personalization

Customers don't like to feel that they're just another anonymous statistic on a hotel's balance sheet. Greater personalization in a hotel's marketing makes consumers feel valued. It's also more effective, targeting individuals with the precise offers that are likely to be most interesting.

Personalized marketing can be directed towards specific users — for example, a guest who had previously spent their summer break at a hotel can be contacted the following year to suggest they book another stay — or it can be aimed at consumers who fit a certain profile and meet a particular set of conditions.

Artificial Intelligence (AI)

Artificial intelligence is one of the most important accommodation industry trends, transforming the sector in subtle but important ways. More and more businesses are using AI to handle some of their customer services, with simple but powerful chatbots providing support, fielding queries, and even taking care of the entire booking process. Combined with machine learning, these bots can effectively improve customer experience. Other AI applications include data analysis, making sense of customer information, and formulating marketing strategies. AI can deal effectively with large amounts of data that would overwhelm human analysts.

Wellness and Spas

A greater emphasis on guest wellbeing has been one of the most notable hotel trends of recent times. This can take many forms, from providing on-site spas where guests can relax and rejuvenate to offering yoga classes, gym or sports facilities, massage treatments, and more.

Even in hotels with a relative lack of space for these kinds of facilities, some options are relevant for wellness, such as healthy snacks in hotel rooms. Some hotels even function as wellness retreats, allowing guests to escape some of their everyday bad habits and focus on boosting their minds and bodies.

Unique Experiences

Another of the key hotel trends to be aware of is the growing demand among customers for unique experiences. Again, the options here are plentiful, from organizing local tours or activities to hosting special events in your property. These events could be classes taught by renowned experts or opportunities to experience innovative technology.

Quiet or silent hotels have also grown in popularity, and these kinds of offerings are primarily based around peace, quiet, high-quality sleep, and the ability to unwind from everyday stress. Any unique experiences your hotel can provide will help set it apart from rivals and make attracting guests easier.

Local Experience

Another trend that those in the hospitality industry are getting to grips with is the desire for tourists or travelers to enjoy local experiences. Many people do not simply want to experience a similar life but in a different location. Instead, they want to experience an authentic way of life in the location they visit.

Businesses in the hospitality industry are responding to this to cater to these demands. Hotels might provide local products, while other options like Airbnb and farmhouse accommodations can offer a more authentic guest experience. Moreover, travel agents and tour operators can help travelers participate in local activities.

Healthy and Organic Food & Drinks

In the past, a substantial section of the hospitality industry comprised fast-food restaurants and bars selling sugary alcoholic drinks. However, there has been a cultural shift, with people becoming more aware of what they put in their bodies, leading to healthy food and drink trends.

For restaurants, this has meant re-vamping menus with healthier options, including gluten-free, dairy-free, low-fat, vegetarian, vegan, and organic options. However, the trend for healthy food and drinks extends to hotels, catering services, and even holidays, with healthier room service options and healthier drinks sold behind bars.

Emphasis on Safety and Hygiene

Safety and hygiene measures are now one of the factors many customers will make their booking decisions because hotel guests are keen to minimize any unnecessary risks associated with travelling. While most businesses worldwide have gone back to normal operations regarding hygiene and safety, it remains a big part of the marketing and communications aspect for future guests.

Making sure the hotel shows cleanliness and its approach towards safety for guests is now an essential part of the marketing process, as customers are still very aware of the dangers of non-commitment to strict cleanliness protocols in hotels. These steps must be part of your hotel marketing strategies so that customers know about your efforts and guests feel safe during their stay.

Increased Adoption of Hotel Apps

Hotel apps offer a range of benefits, and increased adoption is among the most crucial technology-related hotel trends to learn about. With the right hotel app, you can potentially improve communication with your guests, provide contactless check-ins, improve your room service and housekeeping, and boost your revenue.

Smart Hotels

Smart hotels incorporate the Internet of Things (IoT) into their operation, using smart devices and systems to streamline the day-to-day running of the hotel, make things

more efficient and improve guests' experience. A smart hotel might use internet-enabled HVAC systems to fine-tune the temperature and ventilation in each room for maximum comfort and minimum energy waste.

Smart hotels may also allow guests to use technology such as phone apps or voice control to operate heating, cooling, lighting, and entertainment systems more easily. Smart hotel rooms will likely see higher demand as more people use smart technology in their homes.

Bleisure Travel

The under-40s tend to be a fairly frugal demographic with a work-hard, play-hard approach to life. These traits have driven one of the most talked-about accommodation industry trends to date: so-called bleisure (business/leisure) travel. Combining business and work with leisure travel, bleisure travel represents the best of both worlds.

Whether they're extending a work trip to take advantage of the possibilities offered by a destination or just squeezing in a little sightseeing before or after work, Millennials are finding savvy ways to explore the world without taking time off work. Online work makes bleisure travel even more popular.

5.1.2. Innovation and Technology in Industry

Hospitality technology describes a wide range of IT, e-commerce, and similar technology solutions within the hospitality industry. The use of this technology is typically intended to either make life easier for a business's employees or to improve the overall experience for hospitality customers.

Below, there is innovation and technology trends in accommodation industry²³⁸:

²³⁸ "The Latest Technology Trends in the Hospitality Industry of 2024", <https://www.revfine.com/technology-trends-hospitality-industry/>.

Predictive Ordering

Predictive ordering uses artificial intelligence (AI) to forecast customer demand and generate automated orders for hotels, restaurants, and other hospitality businesses. This can help businesses to reduce food waste and other waste perishables, improve inventory management, and boost profitability.

It can also help deliver a better customer experience by ensuring necessary supplies are always on hand. Predictive Ordering is among the newest technology trends in the hospitality industry, as it can help business owners keep up with the industry pace. A good way to start adapting predictive ordering is by using Order Management Systems.

Automated Waste Management

Each day, businesses in the hospitality industry discard tons of edible food. Not only is this a loss to the company in terms of money wasted on supplies, but it's also a social and environmental issue. To address the problem of food waste, many businesses are turning to automated waste management strategies.

These technologies encompass a range of solutions, such as the Internet of Things (IoT), advanced analytics, artificial intelligence (AI), robotics, chemical recycling, and more, making businesses more environmentally friendly. These technologies aid in revealing buying and usage patterns to business owners, which can cause long-term change.

Voice Search & Voice Control

Voice search is a growing technology trend within hospitality because many guests or customers are turning to voice search to find hotels, restaurants, and cafes. It is worth taking the time to capitalize on this properly. To do so, you must ensure your website and booking engine are structured so the voice search can be used properly.

In some settings, the demand for voice control is also growing. This could include everything from using smart speakers in hotel rooms, allowing for control of the various in-room devices, to automated order-taking in restaurants and cafes, meaning customers will no longer need to wait for waiting staff to take their orders.

Contactless Payments

Contactless payments offer several advantages for hotels, resorts, restaurants, bars, and cafes, which is why this has been among the main technology trends in the hospitality industry. Aside from speeding up payments and improving customer satisfaction, contactless tech is also easily compatible with loyalty programs.

Mobile contactless payments are possible even if customers do not have their wallets or their credit card has been misplaced. Additionally, with COVID still in the minds of hotel guests and other hospitality customers, contactless payments can also offer an excellent way to reduce human-to-human contact.

Increased Use of Hotel Robots

The growth in the use of robots ranks among the most fascinating hotel trends, with different companies using robotics for different purposes. Some hotels have deployed robots in concierge roles, where they welcome guests and provide important information or where they can serve as the first point of contact for customer service purposes.

Yet, other hotels have gone further, using robots to provide room service, carry luggage, or assist with cooking food. Robots can also be used to reduce customer-to-staff contact, which can greatly save costs, and for housekeeping purposes, helping to clean rooms and generally boost hygiene levels.

Robot Chefs

Many of the biggest technology trends in the hospitality industry right now involve robots. Robot concierges, robot servers, robot assistants, and housekeeping robots have all emerged onto the scene in recent years, and now robot chefs are set to make their presence felt in kitchens.

These are systems that can prepare dishes for a particular recipe with pinpoint accuracy. All measurements and cooking times are accurate, ensuring perfect results every time. A robot chef can improve efficiency and free your staff from engaging in work that needs a human touch.

The Deployment of Hotel Chatbots

Chatbots are another of the major accommodation industry trends to be aware of. They can be especially useful when the staff may be absent from other hotel operations and activities or during closed hotel office hours.

One of the best things about chatbots is their 24/7 availability. They can be used to increase direct bookings, provide automated support through the booking journey, and they will be able to interact with customers swiftly in multiple different languages. Chatbots can also assist with upselling, cross-selling, and follow-up efforts too.

Implementation of Virtual Reality (VR)

Regarding recent technology solutions, virtual reality must also be discussed. This allows users to experience a realistic digital version of a real-world location, which can be crucial for convincing customers to complete a booking.

Virtual reality tours can also be vital for booking weddings and business events because they allow customers to experience the facilities without needing to travel to see them in person. Tourists can also experience nearby tourist attractions, national parks, and hotel rooms. Modern VR tours can usually be carried out through a web browser, while the experience can be improved further if a VR headset is used.

Augmented Reality (AR)

Augmented reality (AR) is a close cousin to virtual reality. Where virtual reality replaces the real world with audio and visual input to create an immersive experience, augmented reality adds virtual elements to the real world.

This could mean, for example, a smartphone app that displays listings, opening times, and other information about the business or attraction that a visitor is looking at. Hotels can use AR to provide interactive maps and information about services such as spas, gyms, restaurants, etc. Hotels also use AR games to make their guests' visits more enjoyable and memorable.

Hotel Trends & the Metaverse

The rise of the metaverse is one of the most interesting and exciting hotel trends because it offers so much potential. Whether offering virtual spaces to guests, enhancing the real-world through augmented reality, selling NFT content, or promoting your hotel through virtual reality, there are many options to explore.

When guests are provided with opportunities to interact within virtual spaces offered by a hotel, it opens up the possibility of holding business meetings that are more engaging and personal, even if participants are physically located in different places. Offering metaverse options also allows hotels to promote themselves as metaverse hotels, likely appealing to the more technology-focused customer who wants to experience the latest innovations.

Using ChatGPT

ChatGPT is powering some of the most important technology trends in the hospitality industry today. It can help the hospitality industry in a variety of ways. It can be used to power chatbots that deliver 24/7 customer support, answering questions and resolving issues with no waiting. It can help analyze consumer data to help create personalized experiences.

ChatGPT can automate a range of functions and services, streamlining operations for hotels, restaurants, entertainment venues, and other businesses.

Mobile Check-In Technology

Mobile check-in technology allows guests to benefit from a keyless entry method, removing the need to wait around at reception and obtain a physical key or key card. Instead, contactless check-in is available using a mobile app, and hotels can send users a unique entry code, allowing them to access the property and even their room.

This can help to streamline the check-in process and allow for more seamless arrivals and departures. As the check-in technology requires guests to download the hotel app, this can also be used to deliver important customer information or even promotional messages, allowing your hotel to easily up-sell or cross-sell.

A further benefit of mobile check-in technology is the absence of physical keys, which avoids situations where they are lost, damaged, or stolen. Instead, everything related to room entry will be controlled via a smartphone.

WiFi 6

Of all the technology trends hospitality industry businesses should be aware of, WiFi 6 is among the most important for improving the guest experience and the experience of hospitality staff. WiFi 6 is the next generation of WiFi technology and is more than 30 percent faster while also boasting significantly improved throughput.

Such improvements to WiFi technology are especially important in an age where businesses are using a greater number of smart or IoT devices while customers are also increasingly connecting phones, laptops, tablets, and other devices to WiFi. Faster and more reliable WiFi can help hospitality companies to stand out from rivals.

NFT Marketing

NFT technology is still an emerging concept but shows great promise in marketing. It is most commonly used in hospitality to boost brand awareness through special offers or partnerships with local artists or business partners. NFTs are also increasingly being used for transactions taking place within the metaverse.

Some hospitality businesses have experimented with using NFT technology for membership cards or customer loyalty schemes. The uniqueness of each NFT makes the technology well-suited to these purposes and means this is one of the technology trends hospitality industry marketers need to keep track of in the years to come.

Recognition Technology

Recognition technology is one of the most important emerging tech trends, but its potential uses in the hospitality industry are especially interesting. In particular, biometrics is used to usher in a new age of seamless authentications, which could benefit hotel processes and customer purchases.

For example, imagine if a fingerprint or facial recognition technology could be used in your hotel to unlock rooms. Now consider the uses of the same technology for check-

in and check-out purposes. In the future, this technology is also likely to allow for completely seamless purchases, with payments being authenticated by touch.

Internet of Things (IoT)

Another technological trend within hospitality management is the 'Internet of Things', or IoT, which involves extending internet connectivity to everyday objects, devices, and appliances. These devices can then collect data and communicate or interact over the internet, turning previously unintelligent devices into 'smart' devices, which are often semi- or fully autonomous.

An example of this already being used in the hospitality sector is internet-enabled thermostats, which automatically adjust room temperatures at check-in and check-out times in response to temperature swings caused by the sun or opened windows. The same concept is also being deployed for lighting, improving energy efficiency by, for instance, reducing light intensity during daylight hours.

Big Data

Data collection has proliferated across almost all industries but can be used greatly by hospitality businesses to provide more personalized experiences. As an example, it could be used by travel agents to make intelligent destination recommendations based on age, gender, budget, previous locations visited, and so on.

Within the accommodation industry, big data allows businesses to identify trends, which can be used for revenue management purposes. This allows for more data-driven approaches to pricing strategies and enables business leaders to understand better current business performance and the outside influences that impact it.

Cybersecurity

Finally, the increased need for cybersecurity is among the most vital technology trends in the hospitality industry. Today, hotels and restaurants are more reliant on data than ever before and use IT systems more than ever before. However, this potentially leaves them in a much more vulnerable position.

Some of the biggest cybersecurity threats include ransomware attacks, phishing attacks, distributed denial-of-service (DDoS) attacks, and human error within the

company. For this reason, hotels need to invest adequately in cybersecurity awareness training, protect their IT systems, keep customer data secure, and ensure data is backed up and recoverable.

5.2. Food and Beverage

5.2.1. Global Trends of Industry

ADM, a global leader in human and animal nutrition, unveiled its third annual outlook on the global consumer trends that will shape the food, beverage and animal nutrition industries and drive market growth in the years ahead. Dissecting the intersection of health and well-being, sustainability and food security, ADM has identified eight spaces that detail consumers' evolving behaviors, attitudes and aspirations. The eight areas serve as anchor points to inspire innovation, ushering in a new wave of products and services for 2023. Below are the eight global consumer trends identified by ADM that are powering purposeful design and ingenuity for human, animal and pet nutrition and throughout supply chains.²³⁹

Expanded protein Choices

More than half (52%) of global consumers now consider themselves flexitarians, incorporating both animal-based and plantbased or other alternative proteins into their diet. Within that 52%, nearly two-thirds are defining their eating style as "trying to use more plant-based foods," leading to more demand for expanded protein options. Astechonology natives Gen Z and Gen Alpha grow up, acceptance of applying scientific advancements to make our food will continue to become more common place, and practices like cellular agriculture, precision fermentation, hybrid products, and those withinsect-based protein, are likely to flourish.

Balanced Wellness

Emotional, mental, physical, even spiritual health are increasingly seen by consumers as being intertwined, and as important as each other. Consumers are adopting a synergistic approach and making intentional and mindful choices about how they eat

²³⁹ ADM Announces Global Trends Set to Drive Nutrition Innovation for 2023, <https://www.adm.com/en-us/news/news-releases/2022/11/adm-announces-global-trends-set-to-drive-nutrition-innovation-for-2023/>, 28.04.2023.

and spend their time to address energy levels, disease prevention and overall mood and feeling. Globally, 79% of consumers believe that supporting their mental health has a positive effect on their overall health and wellness. Plus, 48% of global consumers plan to address their mental well-being over the next year, making the issue among their top concerns after immune function, digestive and heart health.

Proactive Personalization

What works for one person's wellness may not be ideal for another's. A "one size fits all" strategy for health and eating has fallen away in favor of tailored, "better for me" approaches. In fact, 63% of global consumers say they are interested in food and drink products that are customized to meet their individual nutritional needs. On top of that, 55% of global consumers say they are willing to spend more on functional foods that can support their health goals. Additionally, these personalized solutions would ideally integrate into one's lifestyle and take taste and culture preferences into consideration.

Trust and Traceability

From soil to table, consumers want to know where their food comes from, who made it and precisely what ingredients are included. They want to know how the product was produced and if the conditions of its production were humane. Some headway has been made in garnering consumer trust, with research showing that 42% of global consumers have become more trusting of environmental claims made by products and brands in the last two years. This need for transparency is born not only from food safety concerns but also from a desire for connection with the food and the communities that grow or make it. As such, consumers are looking to support companies they perceive as honest and authentic and that utilize technology like QR codes or blockchain to allow the traceability of products and ingredients to their origins.

Earth-friendly Production

Globally, 49% of consumers claim to have changed their diet in the last two years to lead a more environmentally friendly lifestyle. They're also demanding a higher standard from the companies they purchase from regarding their environmentally conscious practices. Consumers are greatly focusing on reducing their own food

waste, and they will expect the same from the brands they support. Consumers want proof of environmental rebuilding and restoration, as well.

Social Impact

Using their voices and their purchasing power, consumers are demanding that companies practice fair and humane treatment of the people and animals involved in every aspect of production. Almost 30% of global consumers have actively boycotted a product or brand because of its ethical credentials, and 40% seek out brands that guarantee farmers have been treated in an ethical manner. Ensuring workers' and farmers' livelihoods, employing inclusivity and diversity methods throughout the organization, and keeping products affordable and accessible to the end user are all important considerations to modern consumers when making purchasing decisions.

Modern Pet Parenting

For many, pets are part of the family, and their nutritional and emotional needs are being treated on par with their owners. In light of this, many pet parents require that their pets' food be made from the same ingredients as their own. Plus, as consumers pay increased attention to the well-being of their pets, branded health ingredients are highly sought after, with more than 60% of global cat and dog owners saying that branded health ingredients for their pets are important. This increasing personification of pets is leading to a holistic approach to pet care, with mental well-being, gut health, exercise and diet considerations all being made in conjunction with one another.

Experiential Eating

Increasingly, global consumers are getting more adventurous with their food, as 74% express a desire to try new flavors from around the world and 63% report they like to be experimental when cooking. While seeking out new and interesting flavor profiles, eaters also want to engage with fun and playful brands as part of the experience. If those brands can encourage participation through co-creation and virtual experiences, loyalty can be won with the sense of community it creates and the entertainment it provides. From health and wellness for both people and their pets, to environmental considerations and elevated consumption occasions, these eight trend spaces present opportunities for innovative forward-thinking companies to meet the evolving needs of consumers today. ADM is at the forefront of each of these areas, supporting brands in

creating novel offerings as a leading full-service supplier coupled with a deep pantry of ingredients and solutions, a global team of trend spotters, technical experts, scientists and more.²⁴⁰

5.2.2. Trends During the Coronavirus Pandemic

The impact of COVID-19 in Türkiye has been diverse, but overall mainly relates to the falling levels of tourism combined with the rise in online retailing. At the same time, Turks are increasingly concerned about their health and there has been a notable rise in demand for food and beverages which incorporate additional nutritional values. Turkish consumers have always been drawn to fresh foods such as fruit, vegetables and meats, but it became more difficult to procure these foods during the COVID-19 pandemic due to harvest shortages and with consumers less likely to visit on-site retailing outlets. On the other hand, the consumption of long shelf-life foods such as pasta, rice and canned vegetables grew during the pandemic, also driven by some stockpiling of these foods. It can be foreseen that many of these shopping and consumption habits will be retained in a post – COVID-19 economy¹¹.²⁴¹

Kotler (2020) takes attention that covid period of deprivation and anxiety will usher new consumer attitudes and behaviours that will change the nature of today's Capitalism. Ultimately, people will reevaluate what they consume, how much they consume, and how class concerns and inequality affect all of this. He mentioned that there are indications of a developing anti-consumerism movement nowadays and there are at least five different categories of anti-consumerists.²⁴²

Life Simplifiers

A growing number of customers are choosing to live simpler lives by eating less and making fewer purchases. They are responding to the 'stuff' mess. They wish to reduce the number of superfluous and unwanted items they own. Some people prefer renting versus buying and owning things; they are less interested in owning things like vehicles or even homes.

²⁴⁰Food&Ingredients International, January 2023.

²⁴¹The Food And Beverage Market Entry Handbook: Türkiye, 2022, pg.22

²⁴² Kotler, P. (2020). The consumer in the age of coronavirus. *Journal of Creating Value*, 6(1), 12-15.

Degrowth Activists

Degrowth activists, who believe that too much time and effort is being put into consuming, make up the second group. Degrowth proponents are concerned that consumption will exceed the earth's carrying capacity. The world's population was 3.7 billion people in 1970. The global population increased to 7.0 billion people in 2011. The world population is 7.7 billion as of the year 2020. By 2050, the UN projects that there will be 9.8 billion people on Earth. Being unable to feed so many people would be a nightmare. There is a finite amount of arable land, and the top soil quality is declining. Our oceans have dead zones where there is no marine life. Proponents of degrowth advocate for conservation and a reduction in our material wants.

Climate Activists

There is a separate set of people who are concerned about climate change and the risk that high-spending consumers pose to the environment by leaving behind so many carbon footprints that contaminate our air and water. Climate activists have sincere worries about the state of our planet and a deep respect for nature and science.

Sane Food Choosers

Fourth, there are people who have adopted the vegetarian and vegan lifestyles. They object to the way we slaughter animals for food. With a plant, vegetable, and fruit diet, everyone could eat healthfully and nutrient-densely. In an effort to increase income, livestock managers feed their cows and chickens so that they would grow quickly before killing them and selling the animal's components. Cows, on the other hand, are a significant source of the methane that heats our planet and causes greater temperatures, quicker glacial melting, and flooding in urban areas. Between 15,000 and 20,000 liters of water are needed, along with a lot of roughage to feed the animals, to produce one kilogram of beef.

Conservation Activists

Lastly, we learn about Conservationists who advocate for reusing, repairing, redecorating, or giving current products to those in need rather than destroying them. Conservationists want businesses to create more durable, better, and simpler products. They criticize businesses like Zara for releasing new women's clothing lines every two weeks that are only sold for that period of time. Conservationists are against any form of planned obsolescence. They are antagonistic to the market for luxury products. Several of them are anti-globalists and greens.

5.2.3. Turkish Food and Beverage Industry Trends

Due to global trends and Covid effect, The Turkish food and beverage industry is also shaped by constantly changing consumer demands and market trends. In terms of current trends, the followings stand out; (1) Rise in ethnical shopping habits, (2) Impulsive spending is common, (3) Increase in online shopping.²⁴³

Rise in Ethnical Shopping Habits

Turkish consumers are increasingly concerned about the ethnics behind their shopping habits. There has been a notable rise in demand for products deemed to be more ethnical, which includes GMO-free foods, organic foods and products alternative to meat. Turkish consumers are increasingly concerned about climate-related issues and are now more likely to be curious about the total CO2 footprint of the products they consume and the origin of the products. This can act as a driver for imported food and beverages from the EU, which are perceived within Türkiye as being both high quality and largely ethnical in production practices.

Impulses Spending is Common

Turkish consumers are particularly prone to impulse spending and keeping up with the latest trends and habits. Social media play a large role in this, as they advertise the latest trends to consumers and encourage impulse buying via targeted ads and promotions. Impulse buyers are further driven by lower prices when purchasing larger quantities, which has become more common as the value of the TRY has depreciated in recent years. This can act as a driver for imported food and beverages as EU

²⁴³ The Food and Beverage Market Entry Handbook: TÜRKİYE, European Commission.

producers can focus on marketing their products to encourage impulse buying from Turkish consumers.

Increase in Online Shopping

The outbreak of COVID-19 in Türkiye brought with it the increased need to purchase from online retailers. Although the levels of restrictions in Türkiye were not as severe as seen in many parts of the EU, consumers' concern about interacting and mixing too much in social bubbles encouraged online retailing over busier and higher-risk distribution channels such as bazaars and supermarkets. This can act as a driver for imported food and beverages from the EU, as producers now have a new marketing and distribution channel to reach Turkish consumers in a much more convenient and targeted way than previous channels allowed.

6. PRIMARY DATA COLLECTION BY MEANS OF CUSTOMER JOURNEY GRID

6.1. Scope of the Research

The research is conducted within the scope of the European Union project REMODEL being focused on the consumers' experience at **hotels** and **restaurants**. In this study, which focuses on the experiences of tourists in hotels and restaurants, the survey method was used to measure the experiences. Two questionnaires were prepared. The first questionnaire was developed to assess the last experience of tourists while staying in a hotel in Türkiye. The second questionnaire was developed to assess the last experience of tourists while having lunch/dinner in a restaurant in Türkiye.

6.2. Sample and Data

The research was conducted in İstanbul that is located in the the Nuts2 region in Türkiye. İstanbul is a city where many hotels and restaurants are located. The study collected data from four different samples using two questionnaires. First, tourists were divided into two groups, international and domestic. Then, hotel and restaurant

questionnaires were administered to international and domestic tourists. In the hotel survey, 300 international tourists and 300 domestic tourists were reached. The data collected were from 4-star and 5-star hotels. The survey conducted in restaurants reached 200 international tourists and 200 domestic tourists.

6.3. Descriptive Statistics of Hotel Customers

Descriptive statistics of 300 domestic and 300 international tourists are shown in the Table 129. Half of the domestic tourists in the study are women and half are men. Of the international tourists, 61.3% are female and 38.7% are male. The majority of domestic (61%) and international (76.3%) tourists are married. The economic status of the majority of the tourists was stated as medium-high and high. When the educational status is analysed, it is seen that the highest number of tourists are college or university graduates.

Table 129: Basic Statistics of the Sample (Hotel Customers)

	Domestic Tourists		International Tourists	
	N=300	%	N=300	%
Gender				
Female	150	50	116	38.7
Male	150	50	184	61.3
I would prefer not to ask this question	0	0	0	0
Marital Status				
Married	183	61.0	229	76.3
Living together	16	5.3	0	0
Single	75	25.0	71	23.7
Divorced	20	6.7	0	0
Widow	6	2.0	0	0
Socio-economic Status?				
Low	0	0	0	0
Medium-low	1	0.3	0	0
Medium	38	12.7	53	17.7
Medium-high	177	59.0	180	60.0
High	84	28.0	67	22.3
Level of Education				
Primary School	0	0	0	0
Secondary school up to 16 years	0	0	8	2.7

Higher or secondary or further education (A-levels, BTEC, etc.)	28	9.3	80	26.7
College or university	218	72.7	132	44.0
Post-graduate degree	54	18.0	80	26.7

In another question asked to domestic tourists, they were asked to indicate the which cities they came from within Türkiye. Graph 1 shows the distribution of the cities where domestic tourists come from. About 40% of the domestic tourist came from four provinces; Ankara, Antalya, Muğla and Bursa.

Graph 1: Provinces Where Domestic Tourists Come From

Similarly, international tourists were asked from which countries they came to Türkiye. The responses obtained in percentage terms are shown in Graph 2. About 40% of the participants came from three countries; England, Germany, and Qatar. At the same time, it is understood from the graph that there are many tourist visits to Türkiye from different countries.²⁴⁴

²⁴⁴ See Annex 1 to see detailed information which regions international tourists come from.

Graph 2: Countries Where International Tourists Come From

The number of stars of the hotels where domestic and foreign tourists stay in Türkiye are 4-star or 5-star hotels. Tourists were asked “Do you remember the name of the hotel? If the answer is Yes, which the hotel was?” The hotels names are shown in the Table 130 below.

Table 130: Name of the Hotels

	Domestic Tourists	
	N=300	%
Grand Beyazıt Hotel	73	24.3
DoubleTree by Hilton Hotel Istanbul	63	21.0
Sirkeci Mansion	60	20.0
Elite World Grand Istanbul Basın Ekspres	51	17.0
World Point Hotel	19	6.3
JW Marriott Hotel Istanbul Marmara Sea	17	5.7
Wyndham Istanbul Oldcity	17	5.7
International Tourists		
	N=300	%
Grand Beyazıt Hotel	71	23.7
Sirkeci Mansion	63	21.0
DoubleTree by Hilton Hotel Istanbul	57	19.0
Elite World Grand Istanbul Basın Ekspres	57	19.0
Wyndham Istanbul Oldcity	19	6.3
JW Marriott Hotel Istanbul Marmara Sea	17	5.7
World Point Hotel	16	5.3

The answers to the question about with whom domestic and international tourists stay in the hotel are summarised in the Table 131 and Graph 3.

Table 131: With Whom Did You Stay in the Hotel

	Domestic Tourists		International Tourists	
	N	%	N	%
Alone	39	13.0	18	6.0
With my friends	72	24.0	58	19.3
With my family	65	21.7	119	39.7
With my couple	52	17.3	64	21.3
With colleagues from work	62	20.7	18	6.0
With an organized tryp	10	3.3	23	7.7
Total	300	100%	300	100%

While domestic tourists mostly prefer to stay at the hotel with their *friends* (24%) and *families* (21.7%), international tourists prefer to stay at the hotel with their *families* (39.7%) and *couple* (21.3%).

Graph 3: With Whom Did You Stay in the Hotel

In another question, tourists were asked “*How long did you stay in the hotel?*”. The results obtained in terms of duration of stay are summarised in Table 132 and Graph 4. While the longest stay of domestic tourists is 2 and 3 days, the longest stay of international tourists is 3 days and between 3 and 5 days.

Table 132: Duration of Stay at the Hotel

	Domestic Tourists		International Tourists	
	N	%	N	%
1 day	13	4.3	0	0
2 days	98	32.7	45	15.0
3 days	104	34.7	141	47.0
Between 3 and 5 days	61	20.3	74	24.7
More than 5 days	24	8.0	40	13.3
Total	300	100%	300	100%

Graph 4: Duration of Stay at the Hotel

Inspiration & Search

The questions in this section are designed to find out how domestic and international tourists get inspired or get to know the hotels. The answers to the first question "Describe what you did to find inspiration or how you got in touch with information that caught your attention about the hotel" are summarised in the Table 133.

Table 133: Access to Information About the Hotel

	Domestic Tourists		International Tourists	
	N	%	N	%
A message in Instagram got my attention	4	1.3	5	1.7
My friends/family recommended it	50	16.7	67	22.3
My previous experience in the hotel	44	14.7	86	28.7
I knew because the reputation of the hotel	60	20.0	72	24.0

I was in the area, and I show the hotel	58	19.3	1	0.3
It was the closest option given the aim of the try	33	11.0	4	1.3
I was searching for a hotel in internet	51	17.0	65	21.7
Total	300	100%	300	100%

Among the answers given by international tourists to this question, the ones with the highest rate are “*My previous experience in the hotel*” and “*I knew because the reputation of the hotel*”. Among the answers given by domestic tourists to this question, the ones with the highest rate were “*I knew because the reputation of the hotel*” and “*I was in the area, and I show the hotel*”.

The answers to the question “*Where did you search for information about where to stay?*” are summarised in the Table 134 for domestic tourists. In this question, participants were allowed to choose three options.

Table 134: Search for Information (Domestic Tourists)

	First	Second	Third	Total
Google (or another search engine)	123	102	21	246
Recommendation at a hotel, travel agency or other face-to-face external source	47	35	31	113
TripAdvisor	39	36	56	131
Comments on social media about the hotel	21	1	19	41
Website (of the hotel)	20	34	49	103
Instagram or other social media	14	30	63	97
I asked my friends/family	8	34	33	75

According to the answers given, domestic tourists mostly prefer *search engines* and *TripAdvisor*. The third preference was *recommendation at a hotel, travel agency or other face-to-face external source*. It is also seen that there are quite a lot of people who choose the *website and Instagram* option. The answers given by international tourists to the same question are summarised in the Table 135.

Table 135: Search for Information (International Tourists)

	First	Second	Third	Total
Google (or another search engine)	50	49	34	133
Recommendation at a hotel, travel agency or other face-to-face external source	12	6	8	26
TripAdvisor	16	12	24	52

Comments on social media about the hotel	3	19	31	53
Website (of the hotel)	59	34	33	126
Instagram or other social media	1	12	5	18
I asked my friends/family	23	32	29	84

According to the answers given, it was seen that international tourists mostly prefer *search engines* and *websites*. The third preference was to *ask friends/family*.

The answers given to the question about how the tourist identifies himself/herself while searching for the hotel are given in Table 136.

Table 136: Identification of the Tourist During the Search

In this search you would say that we were:	Domestic Tourists		International Tourists	
	N	%	N	%
More Rational	103	34.3	152	50.7
More Emotional	197	65.7	131	43.7
None of Them	0	0	17	5.7
Total	300	100%	300	100%

International tourists found themselves *more rational* when searching than domestic tourists. On the contrary, it is seen that domestic tourists feel *more emotional*.

Another question asked to tourists was “Which was the level of commitment with the search, in a scale from 1 to 5 (being 1 not committed at all and 5 very committed)”. The answers given to the question about the level of commitment to the research were as shown in Table 137. While the majority of domestic tourists gave the commitment score as 4, the majority of international tourists gave the commitment score as 5.

Table 137: Level of Commitment with the Search

	Domestic Tourists		International Tourists	
	N	%	N	%
1 (not committed at all)	0	0	43	14.3
2	17	5.7	19	6.3
3	86	28.7	77	25.7
4	164	54.7	44	14.7
5 (very committed)	33	11.0	117	39.0
Total	300	100%	300	100%

The information in Table 138 are summary statistics about tourists' feelings while doing research. The question was “*How did you feel while searching for information? (multiple options can be chosen)*”. Tourists were allowed to choose more than one options. The most frequently selected options by international tourists are *happy* and *sure*. Domestic tourists, on the other hand, chose *pleased* and *joyful* the most.

Table 138: Feelings During the Search

	Domestic Tourists	International Tourists
Happy	7	189
Understood	13	2
Frustrated	0	0
Angry	0	0
Ashamed	0	0
Guilty	0	0
Fearful	2	0
Proud	27	20
Pleased	61	50
Loved	35	11
Joyful	51	14
Respected	33	35
Sure	36	115
Overwhelmed	6	5
Worried	18	42
Unsure	40	25
None of the previous ones	0	39

In another question, tourists were asked “*How much time did you spend in the search?*”. The responses to this question are summarised in Table 139.

Table 139: Time Spent in Search

	Domestic Tourists		International Tourists	
	N	%	N	%
Less than 10 minutes	278	92.7	129	43.0
Between 10 and 20 minutes	22	7.3	90	30.0
Between 20 and 30 minutes	0	0	33	11.0
Between 30 minutes and 1 hour	0	0	48	16.0
More than 1 hour	0	0	0	0
Total	300	100%	300	100%

According to the answers given, 43% of international tourists spend *less than 10 minutes* while searching. This rate was 92.7% for domestic tourists. The results obtained are also summarised in Graph 5.

Graph 5: Time Spent in Search

Moment of Decision

In this part of the study, tourists' decisions about the hotel were investigated. The first question asked to tourists was “*Which three factors were crucial to take the decision?*”. They were informed that they could choose three options for this question. Critical decision-making factors for domestic tourists are summarised in Table 140.

Table 140: Crucial factors to take the decision (Domestic Tourists)

	Domestic Tourists			
	First	Second	Third	Total
The location	10	69	32	201
The restaurant	9	4	53	66
The atmosphere (in terms of other clients)	28	15	27	70
The staff	0	2	7	9
The size of the room	0	1	2	3
The design of the room	2	2	6	10
The luminosity (in terms of windows) of the room	0	2	3	5
The photos of the reception and entrance hall	0	0	2	2

The option of a spa	0	0	0	0
The option of a gym	0	0	1	1
The price	2	4	20	26
The breakfast	0	3	5	8
The local character of the hotel	11	10	18	39
The design	4	7	10	21
The prestige of the hotel	40	45	32	117
The exclusive atmosphere	20	24	19	63
The comments (TripAdvisor or other social media)	41	62	17	120
The comments from family/friends	35	36	41	112
The Parking	0	2	0	2
The photos of the bathroom	0	0	0	0
Available offers	0	0	2	2
The international atmosphere	0	0	0	0
The originality	8	12	3	23

When the answers given by domestic tourists are analysed, it is understood that they consider the *location* of the hotel as the most critical factor when deciding about the hotel. The following answers were the *comments* and the *prestige* of the hotel. The answers of international tourists to the same question are given in Table 141.

Table 141: Crucial Factors to Take the Decision (International Tourists)

	International Tourists			
	First	Second	Third	Total
The location	67	6	2	75
The restaurant	79	17	25	121
The atmosphere (in terms of other clients)	27	11	16	54
The staff	20	21	13	54
The size of the room	1	11	6	18
The design of the room	13	38	43	94
The luminosity (in terms of windows) of the room	6	31	19	56
The photos of the reception and entrance hall	20	46	38	104

The option of a spa	4	6	6	16
The option of a gym	3	4	7	14
The price	33	51	57	141
The breakfast	9	28	20	57
The local character of the hotel	1	3	1	5
The design	3	8	16	27
The prestige of the hotel	1	1	2	4
The exclusive atmosphere	3	0	1	4
The comments (TripAdvisor or other social media)	6	3	1	10
The comments from family/friends	1	5	2	8
The Parking	0	0	0	0
The photos of the bathroom	4	11	17	32
Available offers	0	0	0	0
The international atmosphere	0	0	7	7
The originality	2	0	4	6

When these answers are analysed, it is understood that they consider the *price* as the most critical factor in deciding about the hotel. The following answers were *the restaurant* and *the photos of the reception and entrance hall*. The answers given to the question about how they define themselves during hotel selection are given in Table 142.

Table 142: Identification of the Tourist During the Selection

In your selection you would say that we were:	Domestic Tourists		International Tourists	
	N	%	N	%
More rational	92	30.7	139	46.3
More emotional	208	69.3	148	49.3
None of them	0	0	13	4.3
Total	300	100%	300	100%

While both rational and emotional decision making have similar percentages in the answers given by international tourists, the percentage of *more emotional* decision making is higher for domestic tourists.

The answers given to the question about the level of commitment to the selection were as shown in Table 143. The question was “*Which was the level of commitment with the selection, in a scale from 1 to 5 (being 1 not committed at all and 5 very committed)?*”. While the majority of domestic tourists gave the commitment score as 4, the majority of international tourists gave the commitment score as 5.

Table 143: Level of Commitment with the Selection

	Domestic Tourists		International Tourists	
	N	%	N	%
1 (not committed at all)	0	0	46	15.3
2	16	5.3	17	5.7
3	57	19.0	56	18.7
4	172	57.3	38	12.7
5 (very committed)	55	18.3	143	47.7
Total	300	100%	300	100%

The information in Table 144 are summary statistics about tourists' feelings while doing selection. The question was “*How did you feel while searching for information? (multiple options can be chosen)*”. Tourists were allowed to choose more than one options. The most frequently selected options by international tourists are *sure* and *happy*. Domestic tourists, on the other hand, chose *pleased* and *proud* the most.

Table 144: Feelings During the Selection

	Domestic Tourists	International Tourists
Sure	46	206
Worried	31	34
Unsure	24	21
Happy	28	100
Understood	24	2
Frustrated	0	0
Angry	1	0
Ashamed	1	0
Guilty	0	0
Fearful	1	0
Proud	54	19
Pleased	81	37
Loved	20	3
Joyful	17	5
Respected	4	5

Overwhelmed	8	1
None of the previous ones	0	32

In another question, tourists were asked “How much time did you spend in the taking the decision?”. The responses to this question are summarised in Table 145.

Table 145: Time Spent in Selection

	Domestic Tourists		International Tourists	
	N	%	N	%
Less than 10 minutes	280	93.3	142	47.3
Between 10 and 20 minutes	20	6.7	103	34.3
Between 20 and 30 minutes	0	0	18	6.0
Between 30 minutes and 1 hour	0	0	37	12.3
More than 1 hour	0	0	0	0
Total	300	100%	300	100%

According to the answers given, 47.3% of international tourists spend less than 10 minutes while searching. This rate was 93.3% for domestic tourists. The results obtained are also summarised in Graph 6.

Graph 6: Time Spent in Selection

Hotel Experience

In this part of the research, tourists were asked about their positive and negative experiences about the hotel. The first question was “*Please pick the 3 main positive issues of the experience*”. Table 146 shows the responses of domestic tourists regarding the positive aspects of the experience.

Table 146: Positive Issues of the Experience (Domestic Tourists)

	Domestic Tourists			
	First	Second	Third	Total
The location	53	40	43	136
The restaurant	3	10	20	33
The atmosphere (in terms of other clients)	15	15	14	44
The staff	3	1	10	14
The size of the room	3	3	14	20
The design of the room	12	14	40	66
The luminosity (in terms of windows) of the room	1	7	6	14
The reception and entrance hall	0	0	1	1
The spa	0	0	0	0
The gym	0	2	2	4
The price	4	10	19	33
The breakfast	0	1	5	6
The local character of the hotel	5	11	11	27
The design	4	21	22	47
The prestige of the hotel	68	43	22	133
The exclusive atmosphere	26	38	13	77
The Parking	1	6	8	15
The bathroom	0	0	2	2
Available offers	3	6	4	13
The international atmosphere	4	8	3	15
The originality	94	60	32	186
The crowdy atmosphere	1	4	9	14

According to the answers given by domestic tourists, the most positive issue is *originality*, *location* and *hotel prestige*. The same question was asked to international tourists and the answers in the Table 147 were obtained.

Table 147: Positive Issues of the Experience (International Tourists)

	International Tourists			
	First	Second	Third	Total
The location	68	11	8	87
The restaurant	82	28	15	125
The atmosphere (in terms of other clients)	43	13	13	231
The staff	20	35	13	68
The size of the room	5	10	9	24
The design of the room	13	43	45	101
The luminosity (in terms of windows) of the room	1	31	30	62
The reception and entrance hall	18	33	32	83
The spa	2	4	3	9
The gym	1	1	2	4
The price	31	50	73	154
The breakfast	3	22	18	43
The local character of the hotel	1	0	2	3
The design	2	8	10	20
The prestige of the hotel	1	1	0	2
The exclusive atmosphere	3	0	2	5
The Parking	0	0	0	0
The bathroom	2	5	17	24
Available offers	0	0	0	0
The international atmosphere	3	3	3	9
The originality	1	2	5	8
The crowded atmosphere	0	0	0	0

According to the answers given by domestic tourists, the most positive issue is *atmosphere, price and restaurant*.

After the positive issues asked “Please pick the 3 main negative issues of the experience” question asked. Table 148 shows the responses of domestic tourists regarding the negative issues of the experience

Table 148: Negative Issues of the Experience (Domestic Tourists)

	Domestic Tourists			
	First	Second	Third	Total
The location	4	4	5	13
The restaurant	20	29	23	72

The atmosphere (in terms of other clients)	3	2	4	9
The staff	1	0	1	2
The size of the room	35	19	23	77
The design of the room	31	18	26	75
The luminosity (in terms of windows) of the room	28	8	10	43
The reception and entrance hall	10	3	3	16
The spa	2	2	0	4
The gym	5	5	13	23
The price	23	11	13	47
The breakfast	19	26	21	66
The local character of the hotel	4	8	5	17
The design	10	7	5	22
The prestige of the hotel	6	2	7	15
The exclusive atmosphere	4	4	2	10
The Parking	21	17	39	77
The bathroom	11	34	23	68
Available offers	12	26	24	62
The international atmosphere	4	13	9	26
The originality	7	9	8	24
The crowdy atmosphere	43	53	36	132

According to the answers given by domestic tourists, the most negative issue is *crowdy atmosphere*, *parking* and *size of the room*. Lastly, Table 149 shows the responses of international tourists regarding the negative issues of the experience.

Table 149: Negative Issues of the Experience (International Tourists)

	Domestic Tourists			
	First	Second	Third	Total
The location	4	0	1	5
The restaurant	11	5	0	16
The atmosphere (in terms of other clients)	23	2	6	31
The staff	0	2	0	2
The size of the room	0	10	1	11
The design of the room	10	2	4	16
The luminosity (in terms of windows) of the room	5	17	9	31
The reception and entrance hall	5	7	1	13
The spa	1	6	17	24
The gym	19	5	11	35
The price	2	0	4	6
The breakfast	3	16	6	25

The local character of the hotel	23	11	41	75
The design	26	19	43	88
The prestige of the hotel	19	31	4	54
The exclusive atmosphere	7	35	14	56
The Parking	7	3	3	13
The bathroom	38	27	33	98
Available offers	9	13	31	53
The international atmosphere	9	8	13	30
The originality	38	24	22	84
The crowdy atmosphere	41	57	36	134

According to the answers given by international tourists, the most negative issue is *crowdy atmosphere, bathroom and design*.

Information on the feelings of domestic and international tourists about the hotel “*How did you feel?*” question was asked. The answers are shown in Table 150.

Table 150: Feelings

	Domestic Tourists	%	International Tourists	%
Sure	66	22.0	184	61.3
Worried	7	2.3	29	9.7
Unsure	20	6.7	27	9.0
Happy	68	22.7	41	13.7
Understood	33	11.0	0	0
Frustrated	12	4.0	0	0
Angry	3	1.0	0	0
Ashamed	2	0.7	0	0
Guilty	1	0.3	0	0
Fearful	3	1.0	0	0
Proud	19	6.3	1	0.3
Pleased	31	10.3	12	4.0
Loved	9	3.0	0	0
Joyful	15	5.0	1	0.3
Respected	2	0.7	3	1.0
Overwhelmed	9	3.0	0	0
None of the previous ones	0	0	2	0.7
Total	300	100%	300	100%

According to the responses in the table, the most common response of domestic tourists was *happy* with 22.7% and *sure* with 22%. The most common response of

international tourists was *sure* with 61.3%. The results obtained about the tourist during the experience are as in Table 151.

Table 151: The Tourist During the Experience

During the experience, you would say that you were	Domestic Tourists		International Tourists	
	N	%	N	%
More rational	117	39.0	119	39.7
More emotional	183	61.0	177	59.0
None of them	0	0	4	1.3
Total	300	100%	300	100%

61% of domestic tourists described themselves as *more emotional* during the experience. Same way, 59% of foreign tourists described themselves as *more emotional* during the experience. Tourists were asked another question in which they were asked to rate their experiences between 1 and 5 (being 1 very dissatisfied and 5 very satisfied) and the results in Table 152 were obtained.

Table 152: Evaluating the Satisfaction

	Domestic Tourists		International Tourists	
	N	%	N	%
1 (1very dissatisfied)	14	4.7	54	18.0
2	37	12.3	4	1.3
3	12	4.0	12	4.0
4	193	64.3	57	19.0
5 (very satisfied)	44	14.7	173	57.7
Total	300	100%	300	100%

The satisfaction levels of domestic and international tourists in terms of percentage are shown in Graph 7.

Graph 7: Evaluating the Satisfaction

When the satisfaction results are analysed, it is seen that the satisfaction scores of both domestic and international tourists are predominantly gathered at 4 and 5. This is an indication that satisfaction is high. In addition, tourists were asked a question about whether they share their experiences (“*Did you share the experience?*”) and the results are shown in Table 153.

Table 153: Sharing the Experience

	Domestic Tourists		International Tourists	
	N	%	N	%
Yes, online during the stay	221	73.7	98	32.7
Yes, online afterwards	14	4.7	86	28.7
Yes, online while and after the stay	8	2.7	52	17.3
Yes, talking with my family/friends	28	9.3	45	15.0
No	29	9.7	19	6.3
Total	300	100%	300	100%

It is seen that a high proportion of domestic tourists share their experiences *online during their stay* (73.7%). International tourists, on the other hand, share their experiences *online during the stay* (32.7%) and *afterwards* (28.7%) their stay.

The responses to the questions prepared as agree and disagree about the hotel and its various elements are shown in Table 154 for domestic tourists.

Table 154: The level of Agreement or Disagreement with some statements (Domestic Tourists)

	Totally Disagree	Disagree	Indifferent	Agree	Totally agree
The experience in the hotel was very pleasant	23	23	11	133	110
The staff seemed interested in helping me	10	8	18	90	174
They were really helpful and polite	6	14	19	114	147
Most services were very satisfying	25	29	7	125	114
They made me think that I was very important	39	34	28	145	54
I was treated like royalty	65	79	52	79	25
The service I received was much more than generally necessary	37	34	15	102	112
The experience at the hotel was full of wonderful surprises	29	38	21	119	93
The hotel was a pleasant surprise	34	39	20	109	98
The stay was very exciting	24	23	14	143	96
I felt stimulated during the stay	24	19	11	135	111
My day/s in the hotel is truly a special one	22	30	12	113	123
I felt that I was exceptionally lucky that day	25	33	13	120	109
I never thought that I could enjoy a stay at a hotel so much	32	64	32	103	69

When the answers given to the sentences are analysed, it is seen that domestic tourists mostly gave the answers of *agree* and *totally agree*. The results are also shown in Graph 8.

Graph 8: The Level of Agreement or Disagreement with Some Statements (Domestic Tourists)

The responses to the questions prepared as agree and disagree about the hotel and its various elements are shown in Table 155 for international tourists.

Table 155: The Level of Agreement or Disagreement with Some Statements (International Tourists)

	Totally Disagree	Disagree	Indifferent	Agree	Totally Agree
The experience in the hotel was very pleasant	37	23	81	98	61
The staff seemed interested in helping me	16	27	23	96	138
They were really helpful and polite	28	15	35	90	132
Most services were very satisfying	27	19	121	52	81
They made me think that I was very important	29	36	85	89	61
I was treated like royalty	49	88	84	44	35
The service I received was much more than generally necessary	23	21	66	93	97
The experience at the hotel was full of wonderful surprises	26	33	55	74	112
The hotel was a pleasant surprise	33	20	88	61	98
The stay was very exciting	27	24	55	93	101
I felt stimulated during the stay	29	23	70	75	103
My day/s in the hotel is truly a special one	29	29	77	79	86
I felt that I was exceptionally lucky that day	33	25	44	79	119
I never thought that I could enjoy a stay at a hotel so much	34	19	62	86	99

When the answers given to the sentences are analysed, it is seen that international tourists mostly gave the answers of *agree* and *totally agree*. The results are also shown in Graph 9.

Graph 9: The Level of Agreement or Disagreement with Some Statements (International Tourists)

Finally, the participants were asked whether they willing to go to this hotel again (“Are you willing to go to the hotel again?”). The answers obtained are as shown in Table 156.

Table 156: Willing to go to the Hotel Again

	Domestic Tourists		International Tourists	
	N	%	N	%
Yes	236	78.7	238	79.3
No	55	18.3	60	20.0
I don't know	9	3.0	2	0.7

The majority of both domestic (78.7%) and international (79.3%) tourists stated that they would like to come again. These results are summarised in percentage terms in Graph 10.

Graph 10: Willing to Go to the Hotel Again

6.4. Descriptive Statistics of Restaurant Customers

Descriptive statistics of 200 domestic and 200 international tourists participated in the research are shown in the Table 157.

Table 157: Basic Statistics of the Sample (Restaurant Customers)

	Domestic Tourists		International Tourists	
	N=200	%	N=200	%
Gender				
Female	117	58.5	76	38.0
Male	83	41.5	124	62.0
I would prefer not to ask this question	0	0	0	0
Marital Status				
Married	164	82.0	155	77.5
Living together	4	2.0	0	0
Single	25	12.5	45	22.5
Divorced	6	3.0	0	0
Widow	1	0.5	0	0
Which is your socio-economic status?				
Low	0	0	0	0
Medium-low	0	0	0	0
Medium	26	13.0	46	23.0
Medium-high	102	51.0	99	49.5
High	72	36.0	55	27.5

What is the highest level of education you have completed?				
Primary School	0	0	0	0
Secondary school up to 16 years	0	0	0	0
Higher or secondary or further education (A-levels, BTEC, etc.)	16	8.0	51	25.5
College or university	144	72.0	91	45.5
Post-graduate degree	40	20.0	58	29.0

In another question asked to domestic tourists, they were asked to indicate the which cities they came from within Türkiye. About 50% of the participants came from four provinces; İstanbul, Antalya, İzmir, and Bursa.

Graph 11: Provinces Where Domestic Tourists Come From

Similarly, international tourists were asked from which countries they came to Türkiye. The responses obtained are shown in the Graph 12. About 40% of the participants came from three countries; Germany, England and France. At the same time, it is understood from the graph that there are many tourist visits to Türkiye from different countries.²⁴⁵

²⁴⁵ See Annex 2 to see detailed information which regions international tourists come from

Graph 12: Countries Where International Tourists Come From

Tourists were asked whether they had *lunch* or *dinner* and 88% of domestic tourists and 80.5% of international tourists stated that they had dinner. The question “*Do you remember the name of the restaurant? If the answer is Yes, which the restaurant was?*” asked. The restaurant names are shown in the Table 158 below.

Table 158: Name of the Restaurants

	Domestic Tourists	
	N=200	%
Beso Restaurant Bistro	16	8.0
Deraliye Ottoman Cuisine Restaurant	52	26.0
Fine Dine Istanbul	16	8.0
Khorasani Restaurant	50	25.0
Kroren Restaurant	18	9.0
Resto Galata Terrace	44	22.0
No answer	4	2
	International Tourists	
	N=200	%
Beso Restaurant Bistro	17	8.5
Deraliye Ottoman Cuisine Restaurant	50	25.0
Fine Dine Istanbul	19	9.5
Khorasani Restaurant	49	24.5
Kroren Restaurant	15	7.5
Resto Galata Terrace	48	24.0
No answer	2	1.0

The answers to the question about “*With whom did you go to the restaurant?*” domestic and international tourists go to the restaurant are summarised in the Table 159 and Graph 13.

Table 159: With Whom Did You Go to the Restaurant

	Domestic Tourists		International Tourists	
	N	%	N	%
Alone	13	6.5	4	2.0
With my friends	39	19.5	54	27.0
With my family	51	25.5	88	44.0
With my couple	46	23.0	50	25.0
With colleagues from work	43	21.5	4	2.0
With an organized tryp	8	4.0	0	0
Total	200	100%	200	100%

While domestic tourists mostly prefer to go to the restaurant with their *families* and with their *couple*, international tourists prefer to go to the restaurant mostly with their *families*.

Graph 13: With Whom Did You Go to the Restaurant

In another question, tourists were asked “*How long did you stay in the restaurant?*”. The results obtained in terms of length of stay are summarised in Table 160 and Graph 14. While the longest stay of domestic tourists is less than 1 hour, the longest stay of international tourists is between 1 hour and 2 hours.

Table 160: Duration of Stay at the Restaurant

	Domestic Tourists		International Tourists	
	N	%	N	%
Less than 1 hour	154	77.0	14	7.0
Between 1 hour and 2 hours	34	17.0	130	65.0
Between 2 hours and 3 hours	8	4.0	56	28.0
More than 3 hours	4	2.0	0	0
Total	200	100%	200	100%

Graph 14: Duration of Stay at the Restaurant

Inspiration & Search

The questions in this section are designed to find out how domestic and international tourists get inspired or get to know the restaurants. The answers to the question "Describe what you did to find inspiration or how you got in touch with information that caught your attention about the restaurant" are summarised in the Table 161.

Table 161: Access to Information About the Restaurant

	Domestic Tourists		International Tourists	
	N	%	N	%
A message in Instagram got my attention	1	0.5	0	0
My friends/family recommended it	28	14.0	14	7.0
My previous experience in the restaurant	22	11.0	58	29.0
I knew because the reputation of the restaurant	37	18.5	47	23.5
I was in the area, and I show the restaurant	43	21.5	11	5.5
It was the closest option to have lunch/dinner	47	23.5	47	23.5
I was searching for a restaurant in internet	22	11.0	23	11.5
Total	200	100%	200	100%

Among the answers given by international tourists to this question, the ones with the highest rate are “*My previous experience in the restaurant*”, “*I knew because the reputation of the restaurant*”, and “*It was the closest option to have lunch/dinner*”. Among the answers given by domestic tourists to this question, the ones with the highest rate were “*It was the closest option to have lunch/dinner*” and “*I was in the area, and I show the restaurant*”.

The answers to the question “*Where did you search for information about where to have lunch/dinner?*” are summarised in the Table 162 for domestic tourists. In this question, participants were allowed to choose three options.

Table 162: Search for Information (Domestic Tourists)

	First	Second	Third	Total
Google (or another search engine)	49	73	32	154
Recommendation at a restaurant, travel agency or other face-to-face external source	8	6	5	19
TripAdvisor	5	7	28	40
Comments on social media about the restaurant	13	26	44	83
Website (of the restaurant)	3	21	27	51
Instagram or other social media	48	8	8	64
I asked my friends/family	41	26	23	90

According to the answers given, domestic tourists mostly prefer search *engines*, *ask their friends/family* and *comments on social media about the restaurant*. The answers given by international tourists to the same question are as in the Table 163.

Table 163: Search for Information (International Tourists)

	First	Second	Third	Total
Google (or another search engine)	16	19	20	55
Recommendation at a restaurant, travel agency or other face-to-face external source	67	5	12	84
TripAdvisor	8	6	16	30
Comments on social media about the restaurant	6	51	19	76
Website (of the restaurant)	0	2	11	13
Instagram or other social media	1	12	15	28
I asked my friends/family	3	6	8	17

According to the answers given, it was seen that international tourists mostly prefer *recommendation at a restaurant, travel agency or other face-to-face external source* and *comments on social media about the restaurant*.

The answers given to the question about how the tourist identifies himself/herself while searching for the restaurant are given in Table 164.

Table 164: Identification of the Tourist During the Search

In this search you would say that we were:	Domestic Tourists		International Tourists	
	N	%	N	%
More rational	50	25.0	131	65.5
More emotional	150	75.0	57	28.5
None of them	0	0	12	6.0
Total	200	100%	200	100%

International tourists found themselves *more rational* when searching than domestic tourists. On the contrary, it is seen that domestic tourists feel *more emotional*. This result is similar for hotels.

The answers given to the question about the level of commitment to the research were as shown in Table 165. While the majority of domestic tourists gave the commitment score as 4, the majority of international tourists gave the commitment score as 1.

Table 165: Level of Commitment with the Search

	Domestic Tourists		International Tourists	
	N	%	N	%
1 (not committed at all)	0	0	57	28.5
2	17	8.5	9	4.5
3	44	22.0	49	24.5
4	107	53.5	42	21.0
5 (very committed)	32	16.0	43	21.5
Total	200	100%	200	100%

The information in Table 166 are summary statistics about tourists' feelings while doing research. Tourists were allowed to choose more than one options. The most frequently selected options by international tourists are *happy* and *none of the previous ones*. Domestic tourists, on the other hand, chose *pleased* and *unsure* the most.

Table 166: Feelings During the Search

	Domestic Tourists	International Tourists
Happy	27	92
Understood	11	3
Frustrated	0	0
Angry	0	0
Ashamed	0	0
Guilty	0	0
Fearful	0	0
Proud	20	23
Pleased	45	47
Loved	19	8
Joyful	34	9
Respected	7	18
Sure	20	57
Overwhelmed	3	0
Worried	11	17
Unsure	36	7
None of the previous ones	1	69
Total	200	200

In another question, tourists were asked “*How much time did you spend in the search?*”. The responses to this question are summarised in Table 167.

Table 167: Time Spent in Search

	Domestic Tourists		International Tourists	
	N	%	N	%
Less than 10 minutes	195	97.5	73	36.5
Between 10 and 20 minutes	5	2.5	76	38.0
Between 20 and 30 minutes	0	0	34	17.0
More than 30 minutes	0	0	17	8.5
Total	200	100%	200	100%

According to the answers given, 74.5% of international tourists spend *less than 20 minutes* while searching. 97.5% domestic tourists spend *less than 10 minutes* while searching. The results obtained are also summarised in Graph 15.

Graph 15: Time Spent in Search

Moment of Decision

In this part of the study, tourists' decisions about the restaurant were investigated. The first question asked to tourists was “*Which three factors were crucial to take the decision?*”. They were informed that they could choose three options for this question.

Table 168: Crucial Factors to Take the Decision (Domestic Tourists)

	Domestic Tourists			
	First	Second	Third	Total
The location	48	36	18	102
The menu	60	41	23	124
The atmosphere (in terms of other clients)	22	10	22	54
The staff	0	3	3	6
The chef	0	4	3	7
The variety of options	25	29	21	75
The price	1	3	15	19
The quick service	3	3	7	13
The originality	9	16	17	42
The local character of the restaurant	2	4	7	13
The design	0	3	6	9
The prestige of the restaurant	6	11	10	27
The exclusive atmosphere	4	8	14	26
The comments (TripAdvisor or other social media)	6	20	12	38
The comments from family/friends	13	7	19	39
The Parking place	0	1	2	3
Available offers	1	1	1	3

When the answers given by domestic tourists are analysed, it is understood that they consider the *menu* and *location* of the restaurant as the most critical factor when deciding about the restaurant. The following answers were the *variety of options*. The answers of foreign tourists to the same question are given in Table 169.

Table 169: Crucial Factors to Take the Decision (International Tourists)

	International Tourists			
	First	Second	Third	Total
The location	44	8	3	55
The menu	56	10	29	95
The atmosphere (in terms of other clients)	41	16	13	70
The staff	10	15	13	38
The chef	6	17	6	29
The variety of options	10	29	55	94
The price	9	57	39	105
The quick service	8	19	18	45
The originality	3	24	15	42

The local character of the restaurant	1	0	3	4
The design	6	2	4	12
The prestige of the restaurant	1	2	0	3
The exclusive atmosphere	4	1	1	6
The comments (TripAdvisor or other social media)	0	0	0	0
The comments from family/friends	1	0	1	2
The Parking place	0	0	0	0
Available offers	0	0	0	0

When these answers are analysed, it is understood that they consider the *price*, *menu* and the *variety of options* as the most critical factor in deciding about the restaurant. The following answers were *the atmosphere (in terms of other clients)* and *location*. The answers given to the question about how they define themselves during restaurant selection are given in Table 170.

Table 170: Identification of the Tourist During the Selection

In your selection you would say that we were:	Domestic Tourists		International Tourists	
	N	%	N	%
More rational	47	23.5	129	64.5
More emotional	153	76.5	59	29.5
None of them	0	0	12	6.0
Total	200	100%	200	100%

The percentage of emotional decision making is higher for domestic tourists. Conversely, the percentage of rational decision making is higher for international tourists.

The answers given to the question about the level of commitment to the selection were as shown in Table 171. While the majority of domestic tourists gave the commitment score as 4, the majority of international tourists gave the commitment score as 1.

Table 171: Level of Commitment with the Selection

	Domestic Tourists		International Tourists	
	N	%	N	%
1 (not committed at all)	0	0	58	29.0
2	20	10.0	9	4.5
3	38	19.0	37	18.5
4	106	53.0	42	21.0
5 (very committed)	36	18.0	54	27.0
Total	200	100%	200	100%

The information in Table 172 are summary statistics about tourists' feelings while doing selection.

Table 172: Feelings During the Selection

	Domestic Tourists	International Tourists
Sure	40	109
Worried	36	26
Unsure	20	7
Happy	28	78
Understood	10	1
Frustrated	1	2
Angry	0	0
Ashamed	0	0
Guilty	0	0
Fearful	0	0
Proud	41	15
Pleased	40	19
Loved	12	3
Joyful	10	3
Respected	4	2
Overwhelmed	6	0
None of the previous ones	0	44
Total	200	200

Tourists were allowed to choose more than one options. The most frequently selected options by international tourists are *sure* and *happy*. Domestic tourists, on the other hand, chose *proud*, *pleased* and *sure* the most.

In another question, tourists were asked how much time they spent while selecting. The responses to this question are summarised in Table 173.

Table 173: Time Spent in Selection

	Domestic Tourists		International Tourists	
	N	%	N	%
Less than 10 minutes	200	100	85	42.5
Between 10 and 20 minutes	0	0	85	42.5
Between 20 and 30 minutes	0	0	24	12.0
More than 30 minutes	0	0	6	3.0
Total	200	100%	200	100%

According to the answers given, 85% of international tourists spend *less than 20 minutes* while searching. All of the domestic tourists spend *less than 10 minutes* while searching. The results obtained are also summarised in Graph 16.

Graph 16: Time Spent in Selection

Restaurant Experience

In this part of the research, tourists were asked about their positive and negative experiences about the restaurant. Tourists were asked to choose three options for this question. Table 174 shows the responses of domestic tourists regarding the positive aspects of the experience.

Table 174: Positive Issues of the Experience (Domestic Tourists)

	Domestic Tourists			
	First	Second	Third	Total
The location	16	22	30	68
The menu	36	39	22	97
The variety of options	8	31	23	62
The atmosphere (in terms of other clients)	17	8	8	33
The staff	2	2	2	6
The chef	1	6	2	9
The food	81	21	12	114
The price	0	1	1	2
The quick service	4	12	7	23
The originality	13	14	21	48
The local character of the restaurant	4	6	8	18
The design	0	3	11	14
The prestige of the restaurant	5	3	8	16
The exclusive atmosphere	4	8	12	24
Waiting time	7	13	22	42
Music at the restaurant	2	4	7	13
Crowdy atmosphere	0	5	4	9
The parking	0	2	0	2

According to the answers given by domestic tourists, the most positive issue is *food*, *menu*, and *location*. The same question was asked to international tourists and the answers in the Table 175 were obtained.

Table 175: Positive Issues of the Experience (International Tourists)

	International Tourists			
	First	Second	Third	Total
The location	28	16	5	49
The menu	64	28	14	106
The variety of options	33	42	28	103
The atmosphere (in terms of other clients)	30	29	17	76
The staff	13	8	25	46
The chef	5	16	6	27
The food	3	16	6	25
The price	12	24	63	99
The quick service	6	8	18	32
The originality	3	7	15	25
The local character of the restaurant	0	2	0	2
The design	0	3	1	4
The prestige of the restaurant	0	0	1	1
The exclusive atmosphere	3	1	1	5
Waiting time	0	0	0	0
Music at the restaurant	0	0	0	0
Crowdy atmosphere	0	0	0	0
The parking	0	0	0	0

According to the answers given by domestic tourists, the most positive issue is *menu*, *variety of options*, and *price*. Table 176 shows the responses of domestic tourists regarding the negative issues of the experience.

Table 176: Negative Issues of the Experience (Domestic Tourists)

	Domestic Tourists			
	First	Second	Third	Total
The location	10	13	9	32
The menu	2	1	6	9
The variety of options	9	11	12	32
The atmosphere (in terms of other clients)	3	3	5	11
The staff	0	2	1	3
The chef	0	0	0	0
The food	14	4	0	18
The price	36	11	31	78
The quick service	10	17	14	41
The originality	3	6	7	16
The local character of the restaurant	2	3	4	9
The design	16	9	14	39

The prestige of the restaurant	4	2	1	7
The exclusive atmosphere	5	2	3	10
Waiting time	10	19	22	51
Music at the restaurant	5	11	12	28
Crowdy atmosphere	36	35	22	93
The parking	35	51	37	123

According to the answers given by domestic tourists, the most negative issue is *parking*, *crowdy atmosphere*, and *price*. Lastly, Table 177 shows the responses of international tourists regarding the negative issues of the experience.

Table 177: Negative Issues of the Experience (International Tourists)

	International Tourists			
	First	Second	Third	Total
The location	1	0	1	2
The menu	0	0	2	2
The variety of options	3	2	0	5
The atmosphere (in terms of other clients)	4	5	1	10
The staff	4	4	1	9
The chef	0	3	0	3
The food	18	0	6	24
The price	0	3	1	4
The quick service	9	23	9	41
The originality	5	35	9	49
The local character of the restaurant	10	16	2	28
The design	20	34	20	74
The prestige of the restaurant	8	3	19	30
The exclusive atmosphere	12	3	27	42
Waiting time	28	9	50	87
Music at the restaurant	43	14	21	78
Crowdy atmosphere	35	43	31	109
The parking	0	3	0	3

According to the answers given by international tourists, the most negative issue is *crowdy atmosphere*, *waiting time* and *music at the restaurant*. Information on the feelings of domestic and international tourists about the restaurant is shown in Table 178.

Table 178: Feelings

	Domestic Tourists	%	International Tourists	%
Sure	31	15.5	70	35.0
Worried	7	3.5	41	20.5
Unsure	18	9.0	18	9.0
Happy	62	31.0	48	24.0
Understood	9	4.5	0	0
Frustrated	30	15.0	1	0.5
Angry	0	0	0	0
Ashamed	0	0	0	0
Guilty	0	0	0	0
Fearful	0	0	0	0
Proud	2	1.0	1	0.5
Pleased	10	5.0	12	6.0
Loved	15	7.5	1	0.5
Joyful	2	1.0	2	1.0
Respected	5	2.5	2	1.0
Overwhelmed	3	1.5	0	0
None of the previous ones	6	3.0	4	2.0
Total	200	100%	200	100%

According to the responses in the table, the most common response of domestic tourists was *happy* with 31% and the most common response of international tourists was *sure* with 35%. The results obtained about the tourist during the experience are as in Table 179.

Table 179: The Tourist During the Experience

During the experience, you would say that you were	Domestic Tourists		International Tourists	
	N	%	N	%
More rational	71	35.5	119	59.5
More emotional	129	64.5	75	37.5
None of them	0	0	6	3.0
Total	200	100%	200	100%

65.5% of domestic tourists described themselves as more emotional during the experience. Opposite way, 59.5% of international tourists described themselves as more rational during the experience.

Tourists were asked another question in which they were asked to rate their experiences between 1 and 5 (being 1 very dissatisfied and 5 very satisfied) and the results in Table 180 were obtained.

Table 180: Evaluating the Satisfaction

	Domestic Tourists		International Tourists	
	N	%	N	%
1 (very dissatisfied)	9	4.5	57	28.5
2	44	22.0	6	3.0
3	13	6.5	17	8.5
4	101	50.5	56	28.0
5 (very satisfied)	33	16.5	64	32.0
Total	200	100%	200	100%

The satisfaction levels of domestic and international tourists in terms of percentage are shown in Graph 17.

Graph 17: Evaluating the Satisfaction

When the satisfaction results are analysed, it is seen that the satisfaction scores of both local and international tourists are predominantly gathered at 4 and 5. This is an indication that satisfaction is high. However, unlike domestic tourists, it is also seen that international tourists are very dissatisfied at a high rate (28.5%). In addition, tourists were asked a question about whether they share their experiences and the results are shown in Table 181.

Table 181: Sharing the Experience

	Domestic Tourists		International Tourists	
	N	%	N	%
Yes, online during having lunch/dinner	164	82.0	23	11.5
Yes, online afterwards	6	3.0	46	23.0
Yes, online while and after lunch/dinner	1	0.5	70	35.0
Yes, talking with my family/friends	11	5.5	41	20.5
No	18	9.0	20	10.0
Total	200	100%	200	100%

It is seen that a high proportion of domestic tourists share their experiences *online during their lunch/dinner* (82%). International tourists, on the other hand, share their experiences *online while and after lunch/dinner* (35%) and *online afterwards* (23%). In addition, the rate of international tourists who chose the option of *talking with my family/friends* (20%) is also high.

The responses to the questions prepared as agree and disagree about the restaurant and its various elements are shown in Table 182 for domestic tourists.

Table 182: The Level of Agreement or Disagreement with Some Statements (Domestic Tourists)

	Totally Disagree	Disagree	Indifferent	Agree	Totally Agree
The experience in the restaurant was very pleasant	16	33	12	73	66
The staff seemed interested in helping me	10	16	7	78	89
They were really helpful and polite	7	18	9	77	89
Most services were very satisfying	29	26	10	59	76
They made me think that I was very important	38	33	16	81	32
I was treated like royalty	60	50	35	43	12
The service I received was much more than generally necessary	51	26	13	55	55
The dining/lunch experience was full of wonderful surprises	38	32	10	60	60
The restaurant was a pleasant surprise	41	26	8	64	61

The meal was very exciting	29	17	12	73	69
I felt stimulated during the dining/lunch process	38	18	8	68	68
My day in the restaurant is truly a special one	30	28	7	74	61
I felt that I was exceptionally lucky that day	35	28	3	79	55
I never thought that I could enjoy a meal so much	42	30	8	76	44

When the answers given to the sentences are analysed, it is seen that domestic tourists mostly gave the answers of *agree* and *totally agree*. The results are also shown in Graph 18.

Graph 18: The Level of Agreement or Disagreement with Some Statements (Domestic Tourists)

The responses to the questions prepared as agree and disagree about the restaurant and its various elements are shown in Table 183 for international tourists.

Table 183: The Level of Agreement or Disagreement with Some Statements (International Tourists)

	Totally Disagree	Disagree	Indifferent	Agree	Totally agree
The experience in the restaurant was very pleasant	26	33	46	57	38
The staff seemed interested in helping me	20	18	25	50	87
They were really helpful and polite	22	24	25	35	94
Most services were very satisfying	21	17	94	39	29
They made me think that I was very important	28	31	41	62	38
I was treated like royalty	46	71	42	19	22
The service I received was much more than generally necessary	25	18	52	49	56
The dining/lunch experience was full of wonderful surprises	23	27	43	45	62
The restaurant was a pleasant surprise	28	32	42	40	58
The meal was very exciting	23	25	47	43	62
I felt stimulated during the dining/lunch process	32	15	45	52	56
My day in the restaurant is truly a special one	25	30	48	37	60
I felt that I was exceptionally lucky that day	30	27	34	48	61
I never thought that I could enjoy a meal so much	31	30	38	41	60

When the answers given to the sentences are analysed, it is seen that international tourists mostly gave the answers of *agree*, *totally agree* and *indifferent*. The results are also shown in Graph 19.

Graph 19: The Level of Agreement or Disagreement with Some Statements (International Tourists)

It can be seen that the distribution of responses is different for international tourists compared to domestic tourists and that there are tourists in each satisfaction level.

Finally, the participants were asked whether they willing to go to this restaurant again. The answers obtained are as shown in Table 184.

Table 184: Willing to go to the Restaurant Again

	Domestic Tourists		International Tourists	
	N	%	N	%
Yes	132	66.0	134	67.0
No	59	29.5	60	30.0
I don't know	9	4.5	6	3.0
Total	200	100%	200	100%

The majority of both domestic (66%) and international (67%) tourists stated that they would like to come again. These results are summarised in percentage terms in Graph 20.

Graph 20: Willing to Go to the Restaurant Again

7. CONCLUSION

Analysis of the Hospitality Sector in Türkiye is one of the deliverables of the REMODEL project funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101079203. It is the first task of Work Package 4 Research on Innovative Business Models Leveraging the BMI Lab. This document is based on the conditions set out in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement. This document is a guiding reference for other deliverables to be produced during the REMODEL project under the Work Package of 4.

This report includes the analysis of the Turkish hospitality sector by means of secondary and primary data. As mentioned in the report, hospitality is a sector that focuses on providing accommodations to visitors at hospitality-related industries, such as hotels, motels, restaurants, cruise ships, country clubs, casinos, and convention centers. It can be said that accommodation and food and beverage sectors are two important parts of the hospitality industry.

Türkiye reached the highest number of arrivals in 2019 with 51.7 million. According to the latest published data, the number of arrivals was 51.4 million in 2022. Of the arrivals

in 2022, 50.5 million were overnight visitors and 1 million were same-day visitors. Tourism expenditure, which was \$26.4 billion in 2008, reached its historical peak with \$57.8 billion in 2022. Tourism expenditures, which fell to \$13.5 billion in 2020 due to the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, increased to \$57.8 billion in 2022.

As mentioned, accommodation industry is the most important part of hospitality industry. Accommodation can be classified into different categories such as five star, four star, three star and etc. There are three important cities which are Antalya, İstanbul and Muğla respectively in terms of accommodation. 44 % of the five star hotels of Türkiye is located in Antalya. 17 % of the five star hotels of Türkiye is located in İstanbul and lastly 8 % of the five star hotels of Türkiye is located in Muğla. 20,2% of the four star hotels of Türkiye is located in Antalya. 18,3 % of the four star hotels of Türkiye is located in İstanbul and lastly 9,2 % of the four star hotels of Türkiye is located in Muğla. There are totally 1189 three star hotels in Türkiye according to the data of Culture and Tourism Ministry 2022. İstanbul has the biggest number of three star hotels. Antalya, Muğla, Ankara and İzmir follow İstanbul respectively.

Accommodation industry is largely dominated by domestic brands, whereas the international brands have addressed most of the supply. The region has been attracting a great number of investors and has more diversified profiles of such companies. The franchising model is dominating the market. Accor SA, InterContinental Hotels Group, Marriott International, Inc, Wyndham Hotels & Resorts Inc. are the major companies in Türkiye.

The Turkish food service sector is large, highly fragmented, and can be divided into two categories: commercial and institutional food service. Commercial food service consists of full-service, self-service restaurants (mostly restaurants called esnaf lokantasi serving Turkish home-style restaurants), limited-service restaurants (e.g., fast food), as well as cafes/bars, home-delivery/takeaway outlets, street stalls/kiosks; serving approximately at 140,000 locations throughout the country in 2017 according to EMI. In 2021, there were about 123,000 commercial food service restaurants in Türkiye with sales of more than 120 billion TL.

When examining the distribution of Food and Beverage Establishments by regions, it is observed that these facilities are concentrated in the Marmara and Aegean regions. Food and beverage operations include various types of restaurants (bistros, brasseries, coffee shops, first class/ fine dining, ethnic, themed), cafes, cafeterias, takeaways, canteens, function rooms, tray service operations, lounge service operations, home delivery operations and room service operations for hotel guests. Leading companies of food and beverage industry can be classified into four categories. These categories are full-service restaurants, limited-service restaurants, fast-food chains and Michelin awarded restaurants. According to the 2023 evaluation results of Michelin Guide Istanbul, one of the most respected restaurant evaluation systems in the world, 5 restaurants in Istanbul have been awarded with Michelin star and 10 restaurants received a Bib Gourmand (award for great food at reasonable prices).

In the report, primary data was also collected from the customers of the hospitality sector in order to include customers and their perspective into the analysis. The primary research focused on the consumers' experience at hotels and restaurants. The survey method was used to measure the experiences. Two questionnaires were prepared. The first questionnaire was developed to assess the last experience of tourists while staying in a hotel in Türkiye. The second questionnaire was developed to assess the last experience of tourists while having lunch/dinner in a restaurant in Türkiye. The research was conducted in İstanbul that is located in the the Nuts2 region in Türkiye. İstanbul is a city where many hotels and restaurants are located. Data was collected from four different samples using two questionnaires. First, tourists were divided into two groups, international and domestic. Then, hotel and restaurant questionnaires were administered to international and domestic tourists. In the hotel survey, 300 international tourists and 300 domestic tourists were reached. The survey conducted in restaurants reached 200 international tourists and 200 domestic tourists. Thus, customer journey was analysed from the perspective of customers and made an important contribution to the secondary data for understanding the hospitality sector in Türkiye.

Annex 1: Distribution of International Tourists (Hotel)

	N	%		N	%		N	%		N	%
BONN	16	5.3	CANTERBURY	2	0.7	BUSAN	1	0.3	MONTEVIDEO	1	0.3
LONDRA	15	5.0	DNIPRO	2	0.7	CALGARYA	1	0.3	MONTREAL	1	0.3
BERLIN	11	3.7	ER REYYAN	2	0.7	CALI	1	0.3	MUSAYID	1	0.3
MANCHESTER	7	2.3	GIRNE	2	0.7	CAMBRIDGE	1	0.3	MÜSAYID	1	0.3
TOKYO	6	2.0	HALEP	2	0.7	CAMIRI	1	0.3	NATAL	1	0.3
DOHA	5	1.7	HERSON	2	0.7	CHESTER	1	0.3	NECEF	1	0.3
EL VAKRA	5	1.7	JABRİYA	2	0.7	ÇENGDU	1	0.3	NICE	1	0.3
EXETER	5	1.7	KİEV	2	0.7	DAMISTAN	1	0.3	NİMES	1	0.3
HAMBURG	5	1.7	LEİCESTER	2	0.7	DUHAN	1	0.3	OSAKA	1	0.3
TRURO	5	1.7	LİMA	2	0.7	ECATEPEC	1	0.3	PADANG	1	0.3
VUHAN	5	1.7	MARSILYA	2	0.7	EDMONTON	1	0.3	PARIS	1	0.3
BİRMİNGHAM	4	1.3	MEDAN	2	0.7	ER RÜVEYS	1	0.3	PATTAYA	1	0.3
MÜNİH	4	1.3	MERIDA	2	0.7	FARDAWS	1	0.3	PERM	1	0.3
OTTOVA	4	1.3	MOSKOVA	2	0.7	FORTALEZA	1	0.3	PYONGYANG	1	0.3
WINCHESTER	4	1.3	MUSUL	2	0.7	GAZIMAĞUSA	1	0.3	RAMADI	1	0.3
AMMAN	3	1.0	NANKİN	2	0.7	GOLFİTO	1	0.3	RELDEER	1	0.3
BAMBERG	3	1.0	PORTO ALEGRE	2	0.7	HADIYA	1	0.3	RİBE	1	0.3
BOCHUM	3	1.0	PRESTON	2	0.7	HARBİN	1	0.3	RİO DE JANEİRO	1	0.3
BÖHLEN	3	1.0	RİVNE	2	0.7	HARKOV	1	0.3	RİYAD	1	0.3
BREMEN	3	1.0	ROSARIO	2	0.7	HAVALLI	1	0.3	SABAH AL SALEM	1	0.3
BRİTOL	3	1.0	SALMIYA	2	0.7	HAVANA	1	0.3	SALVADOR	1	0.3
BRÜKSEL	3	1.0	SANTIAGO	2	0.7	İRBİD	1	0.3	SAN HOSE	1	0.3
CALGARY	3	1.0	TAHRAN	2	0.7	İSFAHAN	1	0.3	SANTA FE	1	0.3
DERBY	3	1.0	TİENTSİN	2	0.7	KHAİTAN	1	0.3	SAU PAULA	1	0.3
KAZAN	3	1.0	TIJUANA	2	0.7	KOBE	1	0.3	SOUTHAMPTON	1	0.3
MANAUS	3	1.0	TORONTO	2	0.7	KYOTO	1	0.3	ŞAM	1	0.3
MENDOZA	3	1.0	ULSAN	2	0.7	LA PAZ	1	0.3	ŞANGHAY	1	0.3
PEKİN	3	1.0	VERACRUZ	2	0.7	LACHORRERA	1	0.3	ŞEHREKÜRD	1	0.3

SAMARA	3	1.0	ABU HALİFA	1	0.3	LANCASTER	1	0.3	ŞIRAZ	1	0.3
SEUL	3	1.0	AHMEDİ	1	0.3	LIVERPOOL	1	0.3	TERESINA	1	0.3
TOMSK	3	1.0	AL KIRANAH	1	0.3	LONDRINA	1	0.3	TIWANAKU	1	0.3
AKAPULKO	2	0.7	AMSTERDAM	1	0.3	LUSAIL	1	0.3	TUMBES	1	0.3
AL KHOR	2	0.7	ASTRAHAN	1	0.3	LYON	1	0.3	TUNJA	1	0.3
BAGDAT	2	0.7	BAKU	1	0.3	MAKARYEV	1	0.3	VANCOUVER	1	0.3
BATH	2	0.7	BECKUM	1	0.3	MANAMA	1	0.3	YORK	1	0.3
BEYRUT	2	0.7	BENSE	1	0.3	MEKSIKO	1	0.3	ZEKREET	1	0.3
BOGOTA	2	0.7	BURYATYA	1	0.3	MIKOLOYİV	1	0.3	ZERKA	1	0.3

Annex 2: Distribution of International Tourists (Restaurant)

	N	%		N	%
ABU HALIFA	1	0.5	LONDRA	7	3.5
AHMEDI	2	1.0	LOZAN	1	0.5
AL VAKRA	1	0.5	LYON	3	1.5
ALCEVKS	1	0.5	MAHAUT	1	0.5
AMMAN	1	0.5	MANCHESTER	7	3.5
AMSTERDAM	1	0.5	MARSILYA	6	3.0
BAKSAN	1	0.5	MEDAN	1	0.5
BAMBERG	4	2.0	MENDOZA	2	1.0
BELGOROD	1	0.5	MERIDA	5	2.5
BERLIN	23	11.5	MOSKOVA	2	1.0
BIRMINGHAM	4	2.0	MUNICH	1	0.5
BOCHUM	3	1.5	MUSAYID	1	0.5
BOGOTA	1	0.5	NAMUR	1	0.5
BÖHLEN	3	1.5	NANTES	1	0.5
BONN	18	9.0	NOVOSIBIRSK	1	0.5
BRANDIS	1	0.5	OSAKA	2	1.0
BREMEN	2	1.0	OTTOVA	2	1.0

BRISTOL	1	0.5	OXFORD	3	1.5
BUSAN	1	0.5	PARIS	2	1.0
CALGARY	1	0.5	PATTAYA	1	0.5
CAMIRI	1	0.5	PEKIN	2	1.0
CANTERBURY	3	1.5	PUNO	1	0.5
CIDDE	1	0.5	RASON	1	0.5
DAVID	1	0.5	RIBE	1	0.5
DAVOS	1	0.5	RIVNE	1	0.5
DERBY	4	2.0	ROCHA	1	0.5
DNIPRO	2	1.0	SALMIYA	1	0.5
DOHA	3	1.5	SAMARA	1	0.5
DUHAN	3	1.5	SAN HOSE	1	0.5
EDMONTON	1	0.5	ŞANGHAY	1	0.5
EL VAKRA	1	0.5	SAYDA	1	0.5
EXETER	2	1.0	STRAZBURG	5	2.5
FORTALEZA	2	1.0	TAIF	1	0.5
GIRNE	1	0.5	TEBUK	1	0.5
HALEP	1	0.5	TIENTSIN	1	0.5
HALEPCE	1	0.5	TIJUANA	3	1.5
HAMBURG	6	3.0	TOKYO	2	1.0
HARKOV	3	1.5	TOMSK	1	0.5
HAVALLI	1	0.5	TORONTO	3	1.5
JABRIYA	1	0.5	TRURO	2	1.0
JEJU	1	0.5	ULSAN	1	0.5
KAZAN	1	0.5	ULUKISLA	1	0.5
KOBE	1	0.5	VERACRUZ	2	1.0
LAHEY	1	0.5	WINCHESTER	1	0.5

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